

IsaGeoCoq: Partial porting of GeoCoq 2.4.0. Case studies: Tarski's postulate of parallels implies the 5th postulate of Euclid, the postulate of Playfair and the original postulate of Euclid.

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Abstract

The GeoCoq library contains a formalization of geometry using the Coq proof assistant. It contains both proofs about the foundations of geometry [20, 15, 6, 16] and high-level proofs in the same style as in high-school. [1](Code Repository <https://github.com/GeoCoq/GeoCoq>).

Some theorems also inspired by [20] are also formalized with others ITP(Metamath, Mizar) or ATP [24, 25, 3, 23, 4, 2, 17, 5, 11, 19, 8, 9, 10].

We port a part of the GeoCoq 2.4.0 library within the Isabelle/Hol proof assistant: more precisely, the files Chap02.v to Chap13_3.v, suma.v as well as the associated definitions and some useful files for the demonstration of certain parallel postulates.

While the demonstrations in Coq are written in procedural language [26], the transcript is done in declarative language Isar[18].

The synthetic approach of the demonstrations are directly inspired by those contained in GeoCoq. Some demonstrations are credited to G.E Martin («lemma bet_le_lt:» in Ch11_angles.thy, proved by Martin as Theorem 18.17 in [14]) or Gupta H.N (Krippen Lemma, proved by Gupta in its PhD in 1965 as Theorem 3.45). (See [12]).

In this work, the proofs are not constructive. The sledeghammer tool being used to find some demonstrations.

The names of the lemmas and theorems used are kept as far as possible as well as the definitions. A different translation has been proposed when the name was already used in Isabel/Hol ("Len" is translated as "TarskiLen") or that characters were not allowed in Isabel/Hol ("anga" in Ch13_angles.v is translated as "angaP"). For some definitions the highlighting of a variable has changed the order or the position of the variables (Midpoint, Out, Inter,...).

All the lemmas are valid in absolute/neutral space defined with Tarski's axioms.

It should be noted that T.J.M. Makarios [13] has begun some demonstrations of certain proposals mainly those corresponding to SST chapters 2 and 3. It uses a definition that does not quite coincide with the definition used in Geocoq and here. As an example, Makarios introduces the axiom A11 (Axiom of continuity) in the definition of the locale "Tarski_absolute_space".

Furthermore, the definition of the locale "TarskiAbsolute" [22, 21] is not not identical to the one defined in the "Tarski_neutral_dimensionless" class of GeoCoq. Indeed this one does not contain the axiom "upper_dimension". In some cases particular, it is nevertheless to use the axiom "upper_dimension". The addition of the word "_2D" in the file indicates its presence.

In the last part, it is formalized that, in the neutral/absolute space, the axiom of the parallels of the system of Tarski implies the Playfair axiom, the 5th postulate of euclide and the postulate original from Euclid. These proofs, which are not constructive, are directly inspired by [12, 7].

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theory *Tarski-Neutral*

imports

Main

begin

1 Neutral geometry dimensionless

1.1 Tarski's axiom system for neutral geometry: dimensionless

locale *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless* =

fixes *Bet* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool ((- - - -))

and *Cong* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

and *TPA TPB TPC* :: 'p

assumes *cong-pseudo-reflexivity*: ∀ a b.

Cong a b b a

and *cong-inner-transitivity*: ∀ a b p q r s.

Cong a b p q ∧

Cong a b r s

→

Cong p q r s

and *cong-identity*: ∀ a b c.

Cong a b c c

→

a = b

and *segment-construction*: ∀ a b c q.

∃ x. (*Bet q a x* ∧ *Cong a x b c*)

and *five-segment*: ∀ a b c d a' b' c' d'.

a ≠ b ∧

Bet a b c ∧

Bet a' b' c' ∧

Cong a b a' b' ∧

Cong b c b' c' ∧

Cong a d a' d' ∧

Cong b d b' d'

→

Cong c d c' d'

and *between-identity*: ∀ a b.

Bet a b a

→

a = b

and *inner-pasch*: ∀ a b c p q.

Bet a p c ∧

Bet b q c

→

(∃ x. *Bet p x b* ∧ *Bet q x a*)

and *lower-dim*: ¬ *Bet TPA TPB TPC* ∧ ¬ *Bet TPB TPC TPA* ∧ ¬ *Bet TPC TPA TPB*

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

1.2 Definitions

definition *OFSC* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(----- *OFSC* ----- [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B C D \text{ OFSC } A' B' C' D'$

\equiv

$\text{Bet } A B C \wedge$

$\text{Bet } A' B' C' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } A B A' B' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } B C B' C' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } A D A' D' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } B D B' D'$

definition *Cong3* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(--- *Cong3* --- [99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B C \text{ Cong3 } A' B' C'$

\equiv

$\text{Cong } A B A' B' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } A C A' C' \wedge$

$\text{Cong } B C B' C'$

definition *Col* ::

$[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(Col --- [99,99,99] 50)

where

$\text{Col } A B C$

\equiv

$\text{Bet } A B C \vee \text{Bet } B C A \vee \text{Bet } C A B$

definition *Bet4* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Bet4* --- [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$\text{Bet4 } A1 A2 A3 A4$

\equiv

$\text{Bet } A1 A2 A3 \wedge$

$\text{Bet } A2 A3 A4 \wedge$

$\text{Bet } A1 A3 A4 \wedge$

$\text{Bet } A1 A2 A4$

definition *BetS* ::

$[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$ (*BetS* --- [99,99,99] 50)

where

$\text{BetS } A B C$

\equiv

$\text{Bet } A B C \wedge$

$A \neq B \wedge$

$B \neq C$

definition *SumS* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(--- *SumS* --- [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$

\equiv

$\exists P Q R. \text{Bet } P Q R \wedge \text{Cong } P Q A B \wedge \text{Cong } Q R C D \wedge \text{Cong } P R E F$

definition *FSC* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{----- } FSC \text{ ----- } [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ C \ D \ FSC \ A' \ B' \ C' \ D'$
 \equiv
 $Col \ A \ B \ C \ \wedge$
 $A \ B \ C \ Cong3 \ A' \ B' \ C' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ A \ D \ A' \ D' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ B \ D \ B' \ D'$

definition *IFSC* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{----- } IFSC \text{ ----- } [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ C \ D \ IFSC \ A' \ B' \ C' \ D'$
 \equiv
 $Bet \ A \ B \ C \ \wedge$
 $Bet \ A' \ B' \ C' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ A \ C \ A' \ C' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ B \ C \ B' \ C' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ A \ D \ A' \ D' \ \wedge$
 $Cong \ C \ D \ C' \ D'$

definition *Le* ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{-- } Le \text{ -- } [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ Le \ C \ D$
 \equiv
 $\exists \ E. (Bet \ C \ E \ D \ \wedge \ Cong \ A \ B \ C \ E)$

definition *Lt* ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{-- } Lt \text{ -- } [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ Lt \ C \ D$
 \equiv
 $A \ B \ Le \ C \ D \ \wedge \ \neg \ Cong \ A \ B \ C \ D$

definition *Ge* ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{-- } Ge \text{ -- } [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ Ge \ C \ D$
 \equiv
 $C \ D \ Le \ A \ B$

definition *Gt* ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{-- } Gt \text{ -- } [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $A \ B \ Gt \ C \ D$
 \equiv
 $C \ D \ Lt \ A \ B$

definition *Out* ::
 $[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{-- } Out \text{ -- } [99,99,99] \ 50)$
where
 $P \ Out \ A \ B$
 \equiv
 $A \neq P \ \wedge$
 $B \neq P \ \wedge$
 $(Bet \ P \ A \ B \ \vee \ Bet \ P \ B \ A)$

definition *Midpoint* ::

$[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- *Midpoint* - - [99,99,99] 50)

where

$M \text{ Midpoint } A B$

\equiv

$B \text{ et } A M B \wedge$

$C \text{ ong } A M M B$

definition *Per* ::

$[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Per* - - - [99,99,99] 50)

where

$P \text{ er } A B C$

\equiv

$\exists C'. (B \text{ Midpoint } C C' \wedge C \text{ ong } A C A C')$

definition *PerpAt* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- *PerpAt* - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$X \text{ PerpAt } A B C D$

\equiv

$A \neq B \wedge$

$C \neq D \wedge$

$C \text{ ol } X A B \wedge$

$C \text{ ol } X C D \wedge$

$(\forall U V. ((C \text{ ol } U A B \wedge C \text{ ol } V C D) \longrightarrow P \text{ er } U X V))$

definition *Perp* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *Perp* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B \text{ Perp } C D$

\equiv

$\exists X::'p. X \text{ PerpAt } A B C D$

definition *Coplanar* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Coplanar* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$C \text{ oplanar } A B C D$

\equiv

$\exists X. (C \text{ ol } A B X \wedge C \text{ ol } C D X) \vee$

$(C \text{ ol } A C X \wedge C \text{ ol } B D X) \vee$

$(C \text{ ol } A D X \wedge C \text{ ol } B C X)$

definition *TS* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *TS* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B \text{ TS } P Q$

\equiv

$\neg C \text{ ol } P A B \wedge \neg C \text{ ol } Q A B \wedge (\exists T::'p. C \text{ ol } T A B \wedge B \text{ et } P T Q)$

definition *ReflectL* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *ReflectL* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B$

\equiv

$(\exists X. X \text{ Midpoint } P P' \wedge C \text{ ol } A B X) \wedge (A B \text{ Perp } P P' \vee P = P')$

definition *Reflect* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *Reflect* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where
 $P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$
 \equiv
 $(A \neq B \wedge P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B) \vee (A = B \wedge A \text{ Midpoint } P P')$

definition InAngle ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- \text{ InAngle } - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 \equiv
 $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge P \neq B \wedge$
 $(\exists X. \text{ Bet } A X C \wedge (X = B \vee B \text{ Out } X P))$

definition ParStrict::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- - \text{ ParStrict } - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
 \equiv
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D \wedge$
 $\neg (\exists X. \text{ Col } X A B \wedge \text{ Col } X C D)$

definition Par::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- - \text{ Par } - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$
 \equiv
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D \vee (A \neq B \wedge C \neq D \wedge \text{ Col } A C D \wedge \text{ Col } B C D)$

definition Plg::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{Plg } - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $\text{Plg } A B C D$
 \equiv
 $(A \neq C \vee B \neq D) \wedge (\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A C \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B D)$

definition ParallelogramStrict::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{ParallelogramStrict } - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $\text{ParallelogramStrict } A B A' B'$
 \equiv
 $A A' \text{ TS } B B' \wedge$
 $A B \text{ Par } A' B' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A B A' B'$

definition ParallelogramFlat::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{ParallelogramFlat } - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $\text{ParallelogramFlat } A B A' B'$
 \equiv
 $\text{Col } A B A' \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A B B' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A B A' B' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A B' A' B \wedge$
 $(A \neq A' \vee B \neq B')$

definition Parallelogram::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{Parallelogram } - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $\text{Parallelogram } A B A' B'$

≡
ParallelogramStrict $A B A' B' \vee$ *ParallelogramFlat* $A B A' B'$

definition Rhombus::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (*Rhombus* - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Rhombus $A B C D$

≡
Plg $A B C D \wedge$ *Cong* $A B B C$

definition Rectangle::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (*Rectangle* - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Rectangle $A B C D$

≡
Plg $A B C D \wedge$ *Cong* $A C B D$

definition Square::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (*Square* - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Square $A B C D$

≡
Rectangle $A B C D \wedge$ *Cong* $A B B C$

definition Kite::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (*Kite* - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Kite $A B C D$

≡
Cong $B C C D \wedge$ *Cong* $D A A B$

definition Lambert::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (*Lambert* - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Lambert $A B C D$

≡
 $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge C \neq D \wedge A \neq D \wedge$
Per $B A D \wedge$
Per $A D C \wedge$
Per $A B C \wedge$
Coplanar $A B C D$

definition OS ::
 $[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (- - *OS* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
 $A B OS P Q$

≡
 $\exists R::p. A B TS P R \wedge A B TS Q R$

definition TSP ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 (- - - *TSP* - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
 $A B C TSP P Q$

≡
 $(\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C P) \wedge (\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C Q) \wedge$
 $(\exists T. \text{Coplanar } A B C T \wedge \text{Bet } P T Q)$

definition OSP ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

(- - - OSP - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
A B C OSP P Q
 \equiv
 $\exists R. ((A B C TSP P R) \wedge (A B C TSP Q R))$

definition Saccheri::
 $['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(Saccheri - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Saccheri A B C D
 \equiv
Per B A D \wedge
Per A D C \wedge
Cong A B C D \wedge *A D OS B C*

definition ReflectLAt ::
 $['p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- ReflectLAt - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
M ReflectLAt P' P A B
 \equiv
 $(M \text{Midpoint } P P' \wedge \text{Col } A B M) \wedge (A B \text{Perp } P P' \vee P = P')$

definition ReflectAt ::
 $['p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- ReflectAt - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
M ReflectAt P' P A B
 \equiv
 $(A \neq B \wedge M \text{ReflectLAt } P' P A B) \vee (A = B \wedge A = M \wedge M \text{Midpoint } P P')$

definition upper-dim-axiom ::
bool
(UpperDimAxiom [] 50)
where
upper-dim-axiom
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C P Q.$
 $P \neq Q \wedge$
Cong A P A Q \wedge
Cong B P B Q \wedge
Cong C P C Q
 \longrightarrow
 $(\text{Bet } A B C \vee \text{Bet } B C A \vee \text{Bet } C A B)$

definition all-coplanar-axiom ::
bool
(AllCoplanarAxiom [] 50)
where
AllCoplanarAxiom
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C P Q.$
 $P \neq Q \wedge$
Cong A P A Q \wedge
Cong B P B Q \wedge
Cong C P C Q
 \longrightarrow
 $(\text{Bet } A B C \vee \text{Bet } B C A \vee \text{Bet } C A B)$

definition upper-dim-3-axiom ::
bool
where
upper-dim-3-axiom

\equiv
 $\forall A B C P Q R. P \neq Q \wedge Q \neq R \wedge P \neq R \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A P A Q \wedge \text{Cong } B P B Q \wedge \text{Cong } C P C Q \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A P A R \wedge \text{Cong } B P B R \wedge \text{Cong } C P C R \longrightarrow$
 $(\text{Bet } A B C \vee \text{Bet } B C A \vee \text{Bet } C A B)$

definition *median-planes-axiom* ::

bool

where

median-planes-axiom

\equiv
 $\forall A B C D P Q. P \neq Q \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A P A Q \wedge \text{Cong } B P B Q \wedge \text{Cong } C P C Q \wedge \text{Cong } D P D Q \longrightarrow$
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$

definition *plane-intersection-axiom* ::

bool

where

plane-intersection-axiom

\equiv
 $\forall A B C D E F P.$
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C P \wedge \text{Coplanar } D E F P \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists Q. \text{Coplanar } A B C Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } D E F Q \wedge P \neq Q)$

definition *space-separation-axiom* ::

bool

where

space-separation-axiom

\equiv
 $\forall A B C P Q.$
 $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C P \wedge \neg \text{Coplanar } A B C Q \longrightarrow$
 $(A B C \text{ TSP } P Q \vee A B C \text{ OSP } P Q)$

definition *orthonormal-family-axiom* ::

bool

where

orthonormal-family-axiom

\equiv
 $\forall S U1' U1 U2 U3 U4.$
 $\neg (S \neq U1' \wedge \text{Bet } U1 S U1' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } S U1 S U1' \wedge \text{Cong } S U2 S U1' \wedge \text{Cong } S U3 S U1' \wedge \text{Cong } S U4 S U1' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } U1 U2 U1' U2 \wedge \text{Cong } U1 U3 U1' U2 \wedge \text{Cong } U1 U4 U1' U2 \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } U2 U3 U1' U2 \wedge \text{Cong } U2 U4 U1' U2 \wedge \text{Cong } U3 U4 U1' U2)$

definition *CongA* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

(- - - *CongA* - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$A B C \text{ CongA } D E F$

\equiv
 $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E \wedge$
 $(\exists A' C' D' F'. \text{Bet } B A A' \wedge \text{Cong } A A' E D \wedge \text{Bet } B C C' \wedge \text{Cong } C C' E F \wedge$
 $\text{Bet } E D D' \wedge \text{Cong } D D' B A \wedge \text{Bet } E F F' \wedge \text{Cong } F F' B C \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A' C' D' F')$

definition *LeA* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

(- - - *LeA* - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where
 $A B C LeA D E F$
 \equiv
 $\exists P. (P InAngle D E F \wedge A B C CongA D E P)$

definition LtA ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - LtA - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B C LtA D E F$
 \equiv
 $A B C LeA D E F \wedge \neg A B C CongA D E F$

definition GtA ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - GtA - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B C GtA D E F$
 \equiv
 $D E F LtA A B C$

definition Acute ::
 $[p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(Acute - - - [99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $Acute A B C$
 \equiv
 $\exists A' B' C'. (Per A' B' C' \wedge A B C LtA A' B' C')$

definition Obtuse ::
 $[p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(Obtuse - - - [99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $Obtuse A B C$
 \equiv
 $\exists A' B' C'. (Per A' B' C' \wedge A' B' C' LtA A B C)$

definition OrthAt ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- OrthAt - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $X OrthAt A B C U V$
 \equiv
 $\neg Col A B C \wedge U \neq V \wedge Coplanar A B C X \wedge Col U V X \wedge$
 $(\forall P Q. (Coplanar A B C P \wedge Col U V Q) \longrightarrow Per P X Q)$

definition Orth ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - Orth - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B C Orth U V$
 \equiv
 $\exists X. X OrthAt A B C U V$

definition SuppA ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - SuppA - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A B C SuppA D E F$
 \equiv
 $A \neq B \wedge (\exists A'. Bet A B A' \wedge D E F CongA C B A')$

definition SumA ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - - - SumA - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)$
where

$A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A G H I$
 \equiv
 $\exists J. (C B J \text{ Cong} A D E F \wedge \neg B C \text{ OS} A J \wedge \text{ Coplanar} A B C J \wedge A B J \text{ Cong} A G H I)$

definition *TriSumA* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- - - \text{TriSumA} - - - [99, 99, 99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $A B C \text{ TriSumA} D E F$
 \equiv
 $\exists G H I. (A B C B C A \text{ Sum} A G H I \wedge G H I C A B \text{ Sum} A D E F)$

definition *SAMS* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(\text{SAMS} - - - - - [99, 99, 99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $\text{SAMS} A B C D E F$
 \equiv
 $(A \neq B \wedge (E \text{ Out} D F \vee \neg \text{Bet} A B C)) \wedge (\exists J. (C B J \text{ Cong} A D E F \wedge \neg (B C \text{ OS} A J) \wedge \neg (A B \text{ TS} C J) \wedge \text{ Coplanar} A B C J))$

definition *Inter* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- \text{Inter} - - - - [99, 99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $X \text{ Inter} A1 A2 B1 B2$
 \equiv
 $B1 \neq B2 \wedge (\exists P::'p. (\text{Col} P B1 B2 \wedge \neg \text{Col} P A1 A2)) \wedge \text{Col} A1 A2 X \wedge \text{Col} B1 B2 X$

definition *Perp2* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- \text{Perp2} - - - - [99, 99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $P \text{ Perp2} A B C D$
 \equiv
 $\exists X Y. (\text{Col} P X Y \wedge X Y \text{ Perp} A B \wedge X Y \text{ Perp} C D)$

definition *Perp-bisect* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- - \text{PerpBisect} - - [99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $P Q \text{ PerpBisect} A B$
 \equiv
 $A B \text{ ReflectL} P Q \wedge A \neq B$

definition *Perp-bisect-bis* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- - \text{PerpBisectBis} - - [99, 99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $P Q \text{ PerpBisectBis} A B$
 \equiv
 $\exists I. I \text{ PerpAt} P Q A B \wedge I \text{ Midpoint} A B$

definition *Is-on-perp-bisect* ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 $(- \text{IsOnPerpBisect} - - [99, 99, 99] 50)$
where
 $P \text{ IsOnPerpBisect} A B$
 \equiv
 $\text{Cong} A P P B$

definition *isosceles*::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

(- - - *isosceles* [99,99,99] 50)
where
A B C isosceles
 \equiv
Cong A B B C

definition *equilateral*::
 $['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(- - - *equilateral* [99,99,99] 50)
where
A B C equilateral
 \equiv
Cong A B B C \wedge *Cong B C C A*

definition *equilateralStrict*::
 $['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(- - - *equilateralStrict* [99,99,99] 50)
where
A B C equilateralStrict
 \equiv
A B C equilateral \wedge *A \neq B*

definition *QCong*::
 $(['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
(*QCong* - [99] 50)
where
QCong l
 \equiv
 $\exists A B. (\forall X Y. (Cong A B X Y \longleftrightarrow l X Y))$

definition *TarskiLen*::
 $['p, 'p, (['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool)] \Rightarrow bool$
(*TarskiLen* - - - [99,99,99] 50)
where
TarskiLen A B l
 \equiv
QCong l \wedge *l A B*

definition *QCongNull* ::
 $(['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
(*QCongNull* - [99] 50)
where
QCongNull l
 \equiv
QCong l \wedge $(\exists A. l A A)$

definition *QCongA* ::
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
(*QCongA* - [99] 50)
where
QCongA a
 \equiv
 $\exists A B C. (A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge (\forall X Y Z. A B C CongA X Y Z \longleftrightarrow a X Y Z))$

definition *Ang* ::
 $['p, 'p, 'p, (['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool)] \Rightarrow bool$
(- - - *Ang* - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
A B C Ang a
 \equiv
QCongA a \wedge
a A B C

definition *QCongAAcute* ::
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
(*QCongAAcute* - [99] 50)

where
 $QCongAAcute\ a$
 \equiv
 $\exists\ A\ B\ C. (Acute\ A\ B\ C \wedge (\forall\ X\ Y\ Z. (A\ B\ C\ CongA\ X\ Y\ Z \longleftrightarrow a\ X\ Y\ Z)))$

definition $AngAcute\ ::$
 $[\prime p, \prime p, \prime p, ([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool)] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- - - AngAcute - [99,99,99,99] 50)$
where
 $A\ B\ C\ AngAcute\ a$
 \equiv
 $((QCongAAcute\ a) \wedge (a\ A\ B\ C))$

definition $QCongANullAcute\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(QCongANullAcute - [99] 50)$
where
 $QCongANullAcute\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongAAcute\ a \wedge$
 $(\forall\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow B\ Out\ A\ C))$

definition $QCongAnNull\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(QCongAnNull - [99] 50)$
where
 $QCongAnNull\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongA\ a \wedge$
 $(\forall\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow \neg\ B\ Out\ A\ C))$

definition $QCongAnFlat\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(QCongAnFlat - [99] 50)$
where
 $QCongAnFlat\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongA\ a \wedge$
 $(\forall\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow \neg\ Bet\ A\ B\ C))$

definition $IsNullAngaP\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(IsNullAngaP - [99] 50)$
where
 $IsNullAngaP\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongAAcute\ a \wedge$
 $(\exists\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \wedge B\ Out\ A\ C))$

definition $QCongANull\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(QCongANull - [99] 50)$
where
 $QCongANull\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongA\ a \wedge$
 $(\forall\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow B\ Out\ A\ C))$

definition $AngFlat\ ::$
 $([\prime p, \prime p, \prime p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
 $(AngFlat - [99] 50)$
where
 $AngFlat\ a$
 \equiv
 $QCongA\ a \wedge$
 $(\forall\ A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow Bet\ A\ B\ C))$

definition *EqLTarski* ::
 ($[p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$) \Rightarrow ($[p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$) \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*EqLTarski* - [99,99] 50)
where
 l1 *EqLTarski* l2
 \equiv
 $\forall A B. l1 A B \longleftrightarrow l2 A B$

definition *EqA* ::
 ($[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$) \Rightarrow ($[p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$) \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*EqA* - [99,99] 50)
where
 a1 *EqA* a2
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C. a1 A B C \longleftrightarrow a2 A B C$

definition *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals* ::
bool
 (*HypothesisRightSaccheriQuadrilaterals*)
where
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C D. \text{Saccheri } A B C D \longrightarrow \text{Per } A B C$

definition *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals* ::
bool
 (*HypothesisAcuteSaccheriQuadrilaterals*)
where
hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C D. \text{Saccheri } A B C D \longrightarrow \text{Acute } A B C$

definition *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals* ::
bool
 (*HypothesisObtuseSaccheriQuadrilaterals*)
where
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
 \equiv
 $\forall A B C D. \text{Saccheri } A B C D \longrightarrow \text{Obtuse } A B C$

definition *Defect* ::
 ($[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$)
 (*Defect* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Defect *A B C D E F*
 \equiv
 $(\exists G H I. (A B C \text{TriSum} A G H I \wedge G H I \text{Supp} A D E F))$

definition *Ar1* ::
 ($[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$)
 (*Ar1* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Ar1 *PO E A B C*
 \equiv
 $PO \neq E \wedge \text{Col } PO E A \wedge \text{Col } PO E B \wedge \text{Col } PO E C$

definition *Ar2* ::
 ($[p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$)
 (*Ar2* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Ar2 *PO E E' A B C*
 \equiv
 $\neg \text{Col } PO E E' \wedge \text{Col } PO E A \wedge \text{Col } PO E B \wedge \text{Col } PO E C$

definition *Pj* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *Pj* - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

A B Pj C D

\equiv

A B Par C D \vee *C = D*

definition *Sum* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Sum* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

Sum PO E E' A B C

\equiv

Ar2 PO E E' A B C \wedge

$(\exists A' C'. E E' Pj A A' \wedge \text{Col } PO E' A' \wedge PO E Pj A' C' \wedge$
PO E' Pj B C' \wedge E' E Pj C' C)

definition *Proj* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(- - *Proj* - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

P Q Proj A B X Y

\equiv

A \neq *B* \wedge *X* \neq *Y* $\wedge \neg A B Par X Y \wedge \text{Col } A B Q \wedge (P Q Par X Y \vee P = Q)$

definition *Sump* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Sump* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

Sump PO E E' A B C

\equiv

Col PO E A \wedge *Col PO E B* \wedge

$(\exists A' C' P'. A A' Proj PO E' E E' \wedge PO E Par A' P' \wedge$
B C' Proj A' P' PO E' \wedge C' C Proj PO E E E')

definition *Prod* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Prod* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

Prod PO E E' A B C

\equiv

Ar2 PO E E' A B C \wedge

$(\exists B'. E E' Pj B B' \wedge \text{Col } PO E' B' \wedge E' A Pj B' C)$

definition *Prodp* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Prodp* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

Prodp PO E E' A B C

\equiv

Col PO E A \wedge *Col PO E B* \wedge

$(\exists B'. B B' Proj PO E' E E' \wedge B' C Proj PO E A E')$

definition *Opp* ::

$[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
(*Opp* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where
Opp PO E E' A B
 \equiv
Sum PO E E' B A PO

definition Diff ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Diff* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Diff PO E E' A B C
 \equiv
 $\exists B'. Opp PO E E' B B' \wedge Sum PO E E' A B' C$

definition sum3 ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*sum3* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
sum3 PO E E' A B C S
 \equiv
 $\exists AB. Sum PO E E' A B AB \wedge Sum PO E E' AB C S$

definition sum4 ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Sum4* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Sum4 PO E E' A B C D S
 \equiv
 $\exists ABC. sum3 PO E E' A B C ABC \wedge Sum PO E E' ABC D S$

definition sum22 ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*sum22* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
sum22 PO E E' A B C D S
 \equiv
 $\exists AB CD. Sum PO E E' A B AB \wedge Sum PO E E' C D CD \wedge Sum PO E E' AB CD S$

definition Ar2p4 ::
 $[p, p, p, p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Ar2p4* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)
where
Ar2p4 PO E E' A B C D
 \equiv
 $\neg Col PO E E' \wedge Col PO E A \wedge Col PO E B \wedge Col PO E C \wedge Col PO E D$

definition Ps ::
 $[p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Ps* - - - [99,99,99] 50)
where
Ps X E A
 \equiv
X Out A E

definition Ng ::
 $[p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Ng* - - - [99,99,99] 50)
where
Ng X E A
 \equiv
 $A \neq X \wedge E \neq X \wedge Bet A X E$

definition *LtP* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*LtP* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
LtP *X E E' A B*
 \equiv
 $\exists D. \text{Diff } X E E' B A D \wedge \text{Ps } X E D$

definition *LeP* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*LeP* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
LeP *X E E' A B*
 \equiv
LtP *X E E' A B* \vee *A = B*

definition *Length* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*Length* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
Length *X E E' A B L*
 \equiv
 $X \neq E \wedge \text{Col } X E L \wedge \text{LeP } X E E' X L \wedge \text{Cong } X L A B$

definition *IsLength* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*IsLength* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
IsLength *X E E' A B L*
 \equiv
Length *X E E' A B L* \vee (*X = E* \wedge *X = L*)

definition *Sumg* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*Sumg* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
Sumg *X E E' A B C*
 \equiv
Sum *X E E' A B C* \vee ($\neg \text{Ar2 } X E E' A B B \wedge C = X$)

definition *Prodg* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*Prodg* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
Prodg *X E E' A B C*
 \equiv
Prod *X E E' A B C* \vee ($\neg \text{Ar2 } X E E' A B B \wedge C = X$)

definition *PythRel* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*PythRel* - - - - - [*99,99,99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
PythRel *X E E' A B C*
 \equiv
 $\text{Ar2 } X E E' A B C \wedge$
 $((X = B \wedge (A = C \vee \text{Opp } X E E' A C)) \vee (\exists B'. X B' \text{Perp } X B \wedge \text{Cong } X B' X B \wedge \text{Cong } X C A B'))$

definition *SignEq* ::
 [*'p, 'p, 'p, 'p*] \Rightarrow *bool*
 (*SignEq* - - - - [*99,99,99,99*] 50)
where
SignEq *X E A B*
 \equiv

$P_s X E A \wedge P_s X E B \vee N_g X E A \wedge N_g X E B$

definition $LtPs ::$

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(LtPs - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$

where

$LtPs X E E' A B$

\equiv

$\exists D. P_s X E D \wedge Sum X E E' A D B$

definition $IsOrthocenter ::$

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- IsOrthocenter - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$

where

$H IsOrthocenter A B C \equiv \neg Col A B C \wedge$
 $A H Perp B C \wedge$
 $B H Perp A C \wedge$
 $C H Perp A B$

definition $IsCircumcenter ::$

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- IsCircumcenter - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$

where

$G IsCircumcenter A B C \equiv$
 $Cong A G B G \wedge$
 $Cong B G C G \wedge$
 $Coplanar G A B C$

definition $IsGravityCenter ::$

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(- IsGravityCenter - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)$

where

$G IsGravityCenter A B C \equiv \neg Col A B C \wedge$
 $(\exists I J. I Midpoint B C \wedge$
 $J Midpoint A C \wedge$
 $Col G A I \wedge$
 $Col G B J)$

definition $Lcos :: (['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$

$(['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $bool$

where

$Lcos lb lc a \equiv$
 $QCong lb \wedge QCong lc \wedge QCongAAcute a \wedge$
 $(\exists A B C. (Per C B A \wedge lb A B \wedge lc A C \wedge a B A C))$

definition $EqLcos :: (['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$

$(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $(['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $bool$

where

$EqLcos la a lb b \equiv (\exists lp. Lcos lp la a \wedge Lcos lp lb b)$

definition $Lcos2 :: (['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$

$(['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $(['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$
 $bool$

where

$Lcos2 lp l a b \equiv \exists la. Lcos la l a \wedge Lcos lp la b$

definition $EqLcos2 :: (['p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow$

$([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 bool

where

$\text{EqLcos2 } l1 \ a \ b \ l2 \ c \ d \equiv (\exists \ lp. \text{Lcos2 } lp \ l1 \ a \ b \wedge \text{Lcos2 } lp \ l2 \ c \ d)$

definition $\text{Lcos3} :: ([p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$

$([p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 bool

where

$\text{Lcos3 } lp \ l \ a \ b \ c \equiv \exists \ la \ lab. \text{Lcos } la \ l \ a \wedge$
 $\text{Lcos } lab \ la \ b \wedge \text{Lcos } lp \ lab \ c$

definition $\text{EqLcos3} :: ([p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$

$([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 $([p, p, p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}) \Rightarrow$
 bool

where

$\text{EqLcos3 } l1 \ a \ b \ c \ l2 \ d \ e \ f \equiv (\exists \ lp. \text{Lcos3 } lp \ l1 \ a \ b \ c \wedge \text{Lcos3 } lp \ l2 \ d \ e \ f)$

definition $\text{EqV} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- \text{EqV} - - [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ \text{EqV} \ C \ D \equiv \text{Parallelogram } A \ B \ D \ C \vee (A = B \wedge C = D)$

definition $\text{SumV} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- - - \text{SumV} - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ C \ D \ \text{SumV} \ E \ F \equiv \forall \ D'. \ C \ D \ \text{EqV} \ B \ D' \longrightarrow A \ D' \ \text{EqV} \ E \ F$

definition $\text{SumVExists} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- - - \text{SumVExists} - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ C \ D \ \text{SumVExists} \ E \ F \equiv (\exists \ D'. \ B \ D' \ \text{EqV} \ C \ D \wedge A \ D' \ \text{EqV} \ E \ F)$

definition $\text{SameDir} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- \text{SameDir} - - [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ \text{SameDir} \ C \ D \equiv$
 $(A = B \wedge C = D) \vee (\exists \ D'. \ C \ \text{Out} \ D \ D' \wedge A \ B \ \text{EqV} \ C \ D')$

definition $\text{OppDir} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- \text{OppDir} - - [99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ \text{OppDir} \ C \ D \equiv A \ B \ \text{SameDir} \ D \ C$

definition $\text{CongA3} :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

$(- - \text{CongA3} - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] \ 50)$

where

$A \ B \ C \ \text{CongA3} \ A' \ B' \ C' \equiv$
 $A \ B \ C \ \text{CongA} \ A' \ B' \ C' \wedge B \ C \ A \ \text{CongA} \ B' \ C' \ A' \wedge C \ A \ B \ \text{CongA} \ C' \ A' \ B'$

definition *Projp* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool
 (- - Projp - - [99,99,99,99] 50)
where
 P Q Projp A B ≡
 A ≠ B ∧ ((Col A B Q ∧ A B Perp P Q) ∨ (Col A B P ∧ P = Q))

1.3 Propositions

lemma *cong-reflexivity*:
shows Cong A B A B
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-symmetry*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong C D A B
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-transitivity*:
assumes Cong A B C D **and** Cong C D E F
shows Cong A B E F
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-left-commutativity*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong B A C D
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-right-commutativity*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong A B D C
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-3421*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong C D B A
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-4312*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong D C A B
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-4321*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong D C B A
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-trivial-identity*:
shows Cong A A B B
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-reverse-identity*:
assumes Cong A A C D
shows C = D
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-commutativity*:
assumes Cong A B C D
shows Cong B A D C
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *not-cong-2134*:
assumes ¬ Cong A B C D
shows ¬ Cong B A C D

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-1243*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ D\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-2143*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ B\ A\ D\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-3412*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ C\ D\ A\ B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-4312*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ D\ C\ A\ B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-3421*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ C\ D\ B\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-4321*:

assumes $\neg Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $\neg Cong\ D\ C\ B\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *five-segment-with-def*:

assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ OFSC\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'$ **and** $A \neq B$

shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-diff*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and** $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $C \neq D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-diff-2*:

assumes $B \neq A$ **and** $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $C \neq D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-diff-3*:

assumes $C \neq D$ **and** $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $A \neq B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-diff-4*:

assumes $D \neq C$ **and** $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $A \neq B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-3-sym*:

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

shows $A'\ B'\ C'\ Cong3\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-3-swap*:

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

shows $B\ A\ C\ Cong3\ B'\ A'\ C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-3-swap-2*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong3 } A' B' C'$
shows $A C B \text{ Cong3 } A' C' B'$
(proof)

lemma *cong3-transitivity*:

assumes $A0 B0 C0 \text{ Cong3 } A1 B1 C1$ **and**
 $A1 B1 C1 \text{ Cong3 } A2 B2 C2$
shows $A0 B0 C0 \text{ Cong3 } A2 B2 C2$
(proof)

lemma *eq-dec-points*:

shows $A = B \vee \neg A = B$
(proof)

lemma *distinct*:

assumes $P \neq Q$
shows $R \neq P \vee R \neq Q$
(proof)

lemma *l2-11*:

assumes $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $Bet A' B' C'$ **and**
 $Cong A B A' B'$ **and**
 $Cong B C B' C'$
shows $Cong A C A' C'$
(proof)

lemma *bet-cong3*:

assumes $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $Cong A B A' B'$
shows $\exists C'. A B C \text{ Cong3 } A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *construction-uniqueness*:

assumes $Q \neq A$ **and**
 $Bet Q A X$ **and**
 $Cong A X B C$ **and**
 $Bet Q A Y$ **and**
 $Cong A Y B C$
shows $X = Y$
(proof)

lemma *Cong-cases*:

assumes $Cong A B C D \vee Cong A B D C \vee Cong B A C D \vee Cong B A D C \vee Cong C D A B \vee$
 $Cong C D B A \vee Cong D C A B \vee Cong D C B A$
shows $Cong A B C D$
(proof)

lemma *Cong-perm* :

assumes $Cong A B C D$
shows $Cong A B C D \wedge Cong A B D C \wedge Cong B A C D \wedge Cong B A D C \wedge Cong C D A B \wedge$
 $Cong C D B A \wedge Cong D C A B \wedge Cong D C B A$
(proof)

lemma *bet-col*:

assumes $Bet A B C$
shows $Col A B C$
(proof)

lemma *between-trivial*:

shows $Bet A B B$
(proof)

lemma *between-symmetry*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Bet-cases*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C \vee Bet\ C\ B\ A$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Bet-perm*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Bet\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-trivial2*:
shows $Bet\ A\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-equality*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and** $Bet\ B\ A\ C$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-equality-2*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ B$
shows $B = C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-exchange3*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ D$
shows $Bet\ B\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-neq12--neq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $A \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-neq21--neq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B \neq A$
shows $A \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-neq23--neq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $A \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-neq32--neq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $A \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-bet-distincts*:
assumes $\neg Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-inner-transitivity*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**

Bet B C D
shows *Bet A B C*
{proof}

lemma *outer-transitivity-between2:*
assumes *Bet A B C* **and**
Bet B C D **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows *Bet A C D*
{proof}

lemma *between-exchange2:*
assumes *Bet A B D* **and**
Bet B C D
shows *Bet A C D*
{proof}

lemma *outer-transitivity-between:*
assumes *Bet A B C* **and**
Bet B C D **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows *Bet A B D*
{proof}

lemma *between-exchange4:*
assumes *Bet A B C* **and**
Bet A C D
shows *Bet A B D*
{proof}

lemma *l3-9-4:*
assumes *Bet4 A1 A2 A3 A4*
shows *Bet4 A4 A3 A2 A1*
{proof}

lemma *l3-17:*
assumes *Bet A B C* **and**
Bet A' B' C **and**
Bet A P A'
shows $\exists Q. \text{Bet } P \ Q \ C \wedge \text{Bet } B \ Q \ B'$
{proof}

lemma *lower-dim-ex:*
 $\exists A \ B \ C. \neg (\text{Bet } A \ B \ C \vee \text{Bet } B \ C \ A \vee \text{Bet } C \ A \ B)$
{proof}

lemma *two-distinct-points:*
 $\exists X::'p. \exists Y::'p. X \neq Y$
{proof}

lemma *point-construction-different:*
 $\exists C. \text{Bet } A \ B \ C \wedge B \neq C$
{proof}

lemma *another-point:*
 $\exists B::'p. A \neq B$
{proof}

lemma *Cong-stability:*
assumes $\neg \neg \text{Cong } A \ B \ C \ D$
shows *Cong A B C D*
{proof}

lemma *l2-11-b:*
assumes *Bet A B C* **and**
Bet A' B' C' **and**

Cong $A B A' B'$ and
Cong $B C B' C'$
shows *Cong* $A C A' C'$
<proof>

lemma *cong-dec-eq-dec-b*:
assumes $\neg A \neq B$
shows $A = B$
<proof>

lemma *BetSEq*:
assumes *BetS* $A B C$
shows *Bet* $A B C \wedge A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *l4-2*:
assumes $A B C D$ *IFSC* $A' B' C' D'$
shows *Cong* $B D B' D'$
<proof>

lemma *l4-3*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ and
Bet $A' B' C'$ and
Cong $A C A' C'$
and *Cong* $B C B' C'$
shows *Cong* $A B A' B'$
<proof>

lemma *l4-3-1*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ and
Bet $A' B' C'$ and
Cong $A B A' B'$ and
Cong $A C A' C'$
shows *Cong* $B C B' C'$
<proof>

lemma *l4-5*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ and
Cong $A C A' C'$
shows $\exists B'. (Bet A' B' C' \wedge A B C Cong3 A' B' C')$
<proof>

lemma *l4-6*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ and
 $A B C Cong3 A' B' C'$
shows *Bet* $A' B' C'$
<proof>

lemma *cong3-bet-eq*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ and
 $A B C Cong3 A X C$
shows $X = B$
<proof>

lemma *col-permutation-1*:
assumes *Col* $A B C$
shows *Col* $B C A$
<proof>

lemma *col-permutation-2*:
assumes *Col* $A B C$
shows *Col* $C A B$
<proof>

lemma *col-permutation-3*:

assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-permutation-4*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ B\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-permutation-5*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ A\ C\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-permutation-1*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ B\ C\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-permutation-2*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ C\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-permutation-3*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-permutation-4*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ B\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-permutation-5*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ C\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Col-cases*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C \vee Col\ A\ C\ B \vee Col\ B\ A\ C \vee Col\ B\ C\ A \vee Col\ C\ A\ B \vee Col\ C\ B\ A$
shows $Col\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Col-perm*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge Col\ A\ C\ B \wedge Col\ B\ A\ C \wedge Col\ B\ C\ A \wedge Col\ C\ A\ B \wedge Col\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-trivial-1*:
 $Col\ A\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-trivial-2*:
 $Col\ A\ B\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-trivial-3*:
 $Col\ A\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l4-13*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $Col\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-14R1 :

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $\exists\ C'.\ A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-14R2 :

assumes $Bet\ B\ C\ A$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $\exists\ C'.\ A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-14R3 :

assumes $Bet\ C\ A\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $\exists\ C'.\ A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-14 :

assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $\exists\ C'.\ A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-16R1 :

assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ FSC\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$

shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-16R2 :

assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ FSC\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'$

and $Bet\ B\ C\ A$

shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-16R3 :

assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ FSC\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$Bet\ C\ A\ B$

shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-16 :

assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ FSC\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'$ **and**

$A \neq B$

shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-17 :

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ P\ A\ Q$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ P\ B\ Q$

shows $Cong\ C\ P\ C\ Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma l_4-18 :

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ C\ A\ C'$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ B\ C'$

shows $C = C'$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l4-19*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ B\ C'$
shows $C = C'$
<proof>

lemma *not-col-distincts*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *NCol-cases*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ C\ B \vee \neg\ Col\ B\ A\ C \vee \neg\ Col\ B\ C\ A \vee \neg\ Col\ C\ A\ B \vee \neg\ Col\ C\ B\ A$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
<proof>

lemma *NCol-perm*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge \neg\ Col\ A\ C\ B \wedge \neg\ Col\ B\ A\ C \wedge \neg\ Col\ B\ C\ A \wedge \neg\ Col\ C\ A\ B \wedge \neg\ Col\ C\ B\ A$
<proof>

lemma *col-cong-3-cong-3-eq*:

assumes $A \neq B$
 and $Col\ A\ B\ C$
 and $A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C1$
 and $A\ B\ C\ Cong3\ A'\ B'\ C2$
shows $C1 = C2$
<proof>

lemma *l5-1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ D$
shows $Bet\ A\ C\ D \vee Bet\ A\ D\ C$
<proof>

lemma *l5-2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ D$
shows $Bet\ B\ C\ D \vee Bet\ B\ D\ C$
<proof>

lemma *segment-construction-2*:

assumes $A \neq Q$
shows $\exists\ X. ((Bet\ Q\ A\ X \vee Bet\ Q\ X\ A) \wedge Cong\ Q\ X\ B\ C)$
<proof>

lemma *l5-3*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ D$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C \vee Bet\ A\ C\ B$
<proof>

lemma *bet3--bet*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ E$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Bet\ A\ C\ E$
<proof>

lemma *le-bet*:

assumes $C\ D\ Le\ A\ B$
shows $\exists\ X. (Bet\ A\ X\ B \wedge Cong\ A\ X\ C\ D)$

<proof>

lemma *l5-5-1:*

assumes $A B Le C D$

shows $\exists X. (Bet A B X \wedge Cong A X C D)$

<proof>

lemma *l5-5-2:*

assumes $\exists X. (Bet A B X \wedge Cong A X C D)$

shows $A B Le C D$

<proof>

lemma *l5-6:*

assumes $A B Le C D$ **and**

$Cong A B A' B'$ **and**

$Cong C D C' D'$

shows $A' B' Le C' D'$

<proof>

lemma *le-reflexivity:*

shows $A B Le A B$

<proof>

lemma *le-transitivity:*

assumes $A B Le C D$ **and**

$C D Le E F$

shows $A B Le E F$

<proof>

lemma *between-cong:*

assumes $Bet A C B$ **and**

$Cong A C A B$

shows $C = B$

<proof>

lemma *cong3-symmetry:*

assumes $A B C Cong3 A' B' C'$

shows $A' B' C' Cong3 A B C$

<proof>

lemma *between-cong-2:*

assumes $Bet A D B$ **and**

$Bet A E B$ **and**

$Cong A D A E$

shows $D = E$

<proof>

lemma *between-cong-3:*

assumes $A \neq B$

and $Bet A B D$

and $Bet A B E$

and $Cong B D B E$

shows $D = E$

<proof>

lemma *le-anti-symmetry:*

assumes $A B Le C D$ **and**

$C D Le A B$

shows $Cong A B C D$

<proof>

lemma *cong-dec:*

shows $Cong A B C D \vee \neg Cong A B C D$

<proof>

lemma *bet-dec:*

shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg\ Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-dec*:
shows $Col\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-trivial*:
shows $A\ A\ Le\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-cases*:
shows $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D \vee C\ D\ Le\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-zero*:
assumes $A\ B\ Le\ C\ C$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-diff*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and** $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
shows $C \neq D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt-diff*:
assumes $A\ B\ Lt\ C\ D$
shows $C \neq D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-cong-eq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ A\ D$
shows $C = D \wedge A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong--le*:
assumes $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong--le3412*:
assumes $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $C\ D\ Le\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le1221*:
shows $A\ B\ Le\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-left-comm*:
assumes $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
shows $B\ A\ Le\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-right-comm*:
assumes $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ D\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-comm*:
assumes $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
shows $B\ A\ Le\ D\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ge-left-comm*:
 assumes $A B Ge C D$
 shows $B A Ge C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ge-right-comm*:
 assumes $A B Ge C D$
 shows $A B Ge D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ge-comm0*:
 assumes $A B Ge C D$
 shows $B A Ge D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt-right-comm*:
 assumes $A B Lt C D$
 shows $A B Lt D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt-left-comm*:
 assumes $A B Lt C D$
 shows $B A Lt C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt-comm*:
 assumes $A B Lt C D$
 shows $B A Lt D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gt-left-comm0*:
 assumes $A B Gt C D$
 shows $B A Gt C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gt-right-comm*:
 assumes $A B Gt C D$
 shows $A B Gt D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gt-comm*:
 assumes $A B Gt C D$
 shows $B A Gt D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong2-lt--lt*:
 assumes $A B Lt C D$ **and**
 $Cong A B A' B'$ **and**
 $Cong C D C' D'$
 shows $A' B' Lt C' D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *fourth-point*:
 assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Col A B P$ **and**
 $Bet A B C$
 shows $Bet P A B \vee Bet A P B \vee Bet B P C \vee Bet B C P$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *third-point*:
 assumes $Col A B P$
 shows $Bet P A B \vee Bet A P B \vee Bet A B P$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l5-12-a*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ A\ C \wedge B\ C\ Le\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--le1213*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--le2313*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $B\ C\ Le\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--lt1213*:
assumes $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A\ B\ Lt\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--lt2313*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $B\ C\ Lt\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l5-12-b*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Le\ A\ C$ **and**
 $B\ C\ Le\ A\ C$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-le-eq*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
and $A\ C\ Le\ B\ C$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *or-lt-cong-gt*:
 $A\ B\ Lt\ C\ D \vee A\ B\ Gt\ C\ D \vee Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt--le*:
assumes $A\ B\ Lt\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le1234-lt--lt*:
assumes $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Lt\ E\ F$
shows $A\ B\ Lt\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le3456-lt--lt*:
assumes $A\ B\ Lt\ C\ D$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Le\ E\ F$
shows $A\ B\ Lt\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt-transitivity*:
assumes $A\ B\ Lt\ C\ D$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Lt\ E\ F$
shows $A\ B\ Lt\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma not-and-lt:
 $\neg (A B Lt C D \wedge C D Lt A B)$
<proof>

lemma nlt:
 $\neg A B Lt A B$
<proof>

lemma le--nlt:
assumes $A B Le C D$
shows $\neg C D Lt A B$
<proof>

lemma cong--nlt:
assumes $Cong A B C D$
shows $\neg A B Lt C D$
<proof>

lemma nlt--le:
assumes $\neg A B Lt C D$
shows $C D Le A B$
<proof>

lemma lt--nle:
assumes $A B Lt C D$
shows $\neg C D Le A B$
<proof>

lemma nle--lt:
assumes $\neg A B Le C D$
shows $C D Lt A B$
<proof>

lemma lt1123:
assumes $B \neq C$
shows $A A Lt B C$
<proof>

lemma bet2-le2--le-R1:
assumes $Bet a P b$ and
 $Bet A Q B$ and
 $P a Le Q A$ and
 $P b Le Q B$ and
 $B = Q$
shows $a b Le A B$
<proof>

lemma bet2-le2--le-R2:
assumes $Bet a P b$ and
 $Bet A P O B$ and
 $P o a Le P O A$ and
 $P o b Le P O B$ and
 $A \neq P O$ and
 $B \neq P O$
shows $a b Le A B$
<proof>

lemma bet2-le2--le:
assumes $Bet a P b$ and
 $Bet A Q B$ and
 $P a Le Q A$ and
 $P b Le Q B$
shows $a b Le A B$
<proof>

lemma Le-cases:

assumes $A B Le C D \vee B A Le C D \vee A B Le D C \vee B A Le D C$
shows $A B Le C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Lt-cases*:
assumes $A B Lt C D \vee B A Lt C D \vee A B Lt D C \vee B A Lt D C$
shows $A B Lt C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-out*:
assumes $B \neq A$ and
 $Bet A B C$
shows $A Out B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-out-1*:
assumes $B \neq A$ and
 $Bet C B A$
shows $A Out B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-dec*:
shows $P Out A B \vee \neg P Out A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-diff1*:
assumes $A Out B C$
shows $B \neq A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-diff2*:
assumes $A Out B C$
shows $C \neq A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-distinct*:
assumes $A Out B C$
shows $B \neq A \wedge C \neq A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-col*:
assumes $A Out B C$
shows $Col A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l6-2*:
assumes $A \neq P$ and
 $B \neq P$ and
 $C \neq P$ and
 $Bet A P C$
shows $Bet B P C \longleftrightarrow P Out A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-out--bet*:
assumes $Bet A P C$ and
 $P Out A B$
shows $Bet B P C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l6-3-1*:
assumes $P Out A B$
shows $A \neq P \wedge B \neq P \wedge (\exists C. (C \neq P \wedge Bet A P C \wedge Bet B P C))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l6-3-2*:
assumes $A \neq P$ and

$B \neq P$ and
 $\exists C. (C \neq P \wedge \text{Bet } A P C \wedge \text{Bet } B P C)$
shows $P \text{ Out } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-4-1*:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A B$ and
 $\text{Col } A P B$
shows $\neg \text{Bet } A P B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-4-2*:
assumes $\text{Col } A P B$
and $\neg \text{Bet } A P B$
shows $P \text{ Out } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-trivial*:
assumes $A \neq P$
shows $P \text{ Out } A A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-6*:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A B$
shows $P \text{ Out } B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-7*:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A B$ and
 $P \text{ Out } B C$
shows $P \text{ Out } A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-out-out-bet*:
assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$ and
 $B \text{ Out } A A'$ and
 $B \text{ Out } C C'$
shows $\text{Bet } A' B C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out2-bet-out*:
assumes $B \text{ Out } A C$ and
 $B \text{ Out } X P$ and
 $\text{Bet } A X C$
shows $B \text{ Out } A P \wedge B \text{ Out } C P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-11-uniqueness*:
assumes $A \text{ Out } X R$ and
 $\text{Cong } A X B C$ and
 $A \text{ Out } Y R$ and
 $\text{Cong } A Y B C$
shows $X = Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l6-11-existence*:
assumes $R \neq A$ and
 $B \neq C$
shows $\exists X. (A \text{ Out } X R \wedge \text{Cong } A X B C)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *segment-construction-3*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $X \neq Y$
shows $\exists C. (A \text{ Out } B C \wedge \text{Cong } A C X Y)$

<proof>

lemma l6-13-1:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A \ B$ **and**
 $P \ A \ Le \ P \ B$
shows $Bet \ P \ A \ B$
<proof>

lemma l6-13-2:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A \ B$ **and**
 $Bet \ P \ A \ B$
shows $P \ A \ Le \ P \ B$
<proof>

lemma l6-16-1:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $Col \ S \ P \ Q$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ P \ Q$
shows $Col \ X \ P \ S$
<proof>

lemma col-transitivity-1:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $Col \ P \ Q \ A$ **and**
 $Col \ P \ Q \ B$
shows $Col \ P \ A \ B$
<proof>

lemma col-transitivity-2:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $Col \ P \ Q \ A$ **and**
 $Col \ P \ Q \ B$
shows $Col \ Q \ A \ B$
<proof>

lemma l6-21:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col \ A \ B \ P$ **and**
 $Col \ A \ B \ Q$ **and**
 $Col \ C \ D \ P$ **and**
 $Col \ C \ D \ Q$
shows $P = Q$
<proof>

lemma col2--eq:
assumes $Col \ A \ X \ Y$ **and**
 $Col \ B \ X \ Y$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A \ X \ B$
shows $X = Y$
<proof>

lemma not-col-exists:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists \ C. \neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma col3:
assumes $X \neq Y$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ Y \ A$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ Y \ B$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ Y \ C$
shows $Col \ A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma colx:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Col\ X\ Y\ A$ **and**
 $Col\ X\ Y\ B$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ X\ Y\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out2--bet*:
assumes $A\ Out\ B\ C$ **and**
 $C\ Out\ A\ B$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-le2--le1346*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Le\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $B\ C\ Le\ B'\ C'$
shows $A\ C\ Le\ A'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-le2--le2356-R1*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ A\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $A\ A\ Le\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $A'\ C'\ Le\ A\ C$
shows $B'\ C'\ Le\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-le2--le2356-R2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Le\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $A'\ C'\ Le\ A\ C$
shows $B'\ C'\ Le\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-le2--le2356*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Le\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $A'\ C'\ Le\ A\ C$
shows $B'\ C'\ Le\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-le2--le1245*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $B\ C\ Le\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $A'\ C'\ Le\ A\ C$
shows $A'\ B'\ Le\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-preserves-bet*:
assumes $Bet\ B\ A'\ A0$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ A'\ E\ D'$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ A0\ E\ D0$ **and**
 $E\ Out\ D'\ D0$
shows $Bet\ E\ D'\ D0$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-cong-cong*:
assumes $B\ Out\ A\ A0$ **and**
 $E\ Out\ D\ D0$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ A\ E\ D$ **and**

Cong B A0 E D0
shows *Cong A A0 D D0*
<proof>

lemma *not-out-bet:*
assumes *Col A B C* **and**
 $\neg B \text{ Out } A C$
shows *Bet A B C*
<proof>

lemma *or-bet-out:*
shows $Bet A B C \vee B \text{ Out } A C \vee \neg Col A B C$
<proof>

lemma *not-bet-out:*
assumes *Col A B C* **and**
 $\neg Bet A B C$
shows *B Out A C*
<proof>

lemma *not-bet-and-out:*
shows $\neg (Bet A B C \wedge B \text{ Out } A C)$
<proof>

lemma *out-to-bet:*
assumes *Col A' B' C'* **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A C \longleftrightarrow B' \text{ Out } A' C'$ **and**
Bet A B C
shows *Bet A' B' C'*
<proof>

lemma *col-out2-col:*
assumes *Col A B C* **and**
B Out A AA **and**
B Out C CC
shows *Col AA B CC*
<proof>

lemma *bet2-out-out:*
assumes $B \neq A$ **and**
 $B' \neq A$ **and**
A Out C C' **and**
Bet A B C **and**
Bet A B' C'
shows *A Out B B'*
<proof>

lemma *bet2--out:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq B'$ **and**
Bet A B C
and *Bet A B' C*
shows *A Out B B'*
<proof>

lemma *out-bet-out-1:*
assumes *P Out A C* **and**
Bet A B C
shows *P Out A B*
<proof>

lemma *out-bet-out-2:*
assumes *P Out A C* **and**
Bet A B C
shows *P Out B C*
<proof>

lemma *out-bet--out*:
assumes $Bet\ P\ Q\ A$ **and**
 $Q\ Out\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Out\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *segment-reverse*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists\ B'.\ Bet\ A\ B'\ C \wedge Cong\ C\ B'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-col-ex*:
shows $\exists\ C.\ A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge Col\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-bet-ex3*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists\ D.\ A \neq D \wedge B \neq D \wedge C \neq D \wedge Col\ A\ B\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-col-ex3*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists\ D.\ A \neq D \wedge B \neq D \wedge C \neq D \wedge Col\ A\ B\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Out-cases*:
assumes $A\ Out\ B\ C \vee A\ Out\ C\ B$
shows $A\ Out\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ex-sums*:
shows $\exists\ E\ F.\ A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sums-sym*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$
shows $C\ D\ A\ B\ SumS\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sums2--cong56*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E'\ F'$
shows $Cong\ E\ F\ E'\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sums2--cong12*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$
and $A'\ B'\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$
shows $Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sums2--cong34*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ D\ SumS\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C'\ D'\ SumS\ E\ F$
shows $Cong\ C\ D\ C'\ D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong3-sums--sums*:
assumes *Cong A B A' B' and*
 Cong C D C' D' and
 Cong E F E' F' and
 A B C D SumS E F
shows *A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'*
<proof>

lemma *sums123312*:
shows *A B C C SumS A B*
<proof>

lemma *sums--cong1245*:
assumes *A B C C SumS D E*
shows *Cong A B D E*
<proof>

lemma *sums--eq34*:
assumes *A B C D SumS A B*
shows *C = D*
<proof>

lemma *sums112323*:
shows *A A B C SumS B C*
<proof>

lemma *sums--cong2345*:
assumes *A A B C SumS D E*
shows *Cong B C D E*
<proof>

lemma *sums--eq12*:
assumes *A B C D SumS C D*
shows *A = B*
<proof>

lemma *sums-left-comm*:
assumes *A B C D SumS E F*
shows *B A C D SumS E F*
<proof>

lemma *sums-middle-comm*:
assumes *A B C D SumS E F*
shows *A B D C SumS E F*
<proof>

lemma *sums-right-comm*:
assumes *A B C D SumS E F*
shows *A B C D SumS F E*
<proof>

lemma *sums-comm*:
assumes *A B C D SumS E F*
shows *B A D C SumS F E*
<proof>

lemma *bet--sums*:
assumes *Bet A B C*

shows $A B B C \text{ SumS } A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums-assoc-1*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } G H$ **and**
 $C D E F \text{ SumS } I J$ **and**
 $G H E F \text{ SumS } K L$
shows $A B I J \text{ SumS } K L$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums-assoc-2*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } G H$ **and**
 $C D E F \text{ SumS } I J$ **and**
 $A B I J \text{ SumS } K L$
shows $G H E F \text{ SumS } K L$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums-assoc*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } G H$ **and**
 $C D E F \text{ SumS } I J$
shows $G H E F \text{ SumS } K L \longleftrightarrow A B I J \text{ SumS } K L$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums--le1256*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$
shows $A B \text{ Le } E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums--le3456*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$
shows $C D \text{ Le } E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eq-sums--eq*:
assumes $A B C D \text{ SumS } E E$
shows $A = B \wedge C = D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums-diff-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$
shows $E \neq F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sums-diff-2*:
assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 $A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$
shows $E \neq F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le2-sums2--le*:
assumes $A B \text{ Le } A' B'$ **and**
 $C D \text{ Le } C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D \text{ SumS } E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' \text{ SumS } E' F'$
shows $E F \text{ Le } E' F'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le2-sums2--cong12*:
assumes $A B Le A' B'$ **and**
 $C D Le C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E F$
shows $Cong A B A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le2-sums2--cong34*:
assumes $A B Le A' B'$ **and**
 $C D Le C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E F$
shows $Cong C D C' D'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le-lt12-sums2--lt*:
assumes $A B Lt A' B'$ **and**
 $C D Le C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $E F Lt E' F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le-lt34-sums2--lt*:
assumes $A B Le A' B'$ **and**
 $C D Lt C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $E F Lt E' F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lt2-sums2--lt*:
assumes $A B Lt A' B'$ **and**
 $C D Lt C' D'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $E F Lt E' F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le2-sums2--le12*:
assumes $C' D' Le C D$ **and**
 $E F Le E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $A B Le A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le2-sums2--le34*:
assumes $A' B' Le A B$ **and**
 $E F Le E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $C D Le C' D'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *le-lt34-sums2--lt12*:
assumes $C' D' Lt C D$ **and**
 $E F Le E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $A B Lt A' B'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-lt12-sums2--lt34*:
assumes $A' B' Lt A B$ **and**
 $E F Le E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $C D Lt C' D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-lt56-sums2--lt12*:
assumes $C' D' Le C D$ **and**
 $E F Lt E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $A B Lt A' B'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *le-lt56-sums2--lt34*:
assumes $A' B' Le A B$ **and**
 $E F Lt E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $C D Lt C' D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt2-sums2--lt12*:
assumes $C' D' Lt C D$ **and**
 $E F Lt E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $A B Lt A' B'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lt2-sums2--lt34*:
assumes $A' B' Lt A B$ **and**
 $E F Lt E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D SumS E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' SumS E' F'$
shows $C D Lt C' D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-dec*:
 $I Midpoint A B \vee \neg I Midpoint A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *is-midpoint-id*:
assumes $A Midpoint A B$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *is-midpoint-id-2*:
assumes $A Midpoint B A$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l7-2*:
assumes $M Midpoint A B$

shows M Midpoint $B A$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-3*:
assumes M Midpoint $A A$
shows $M = A$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-3-2*:
 A Midpoint $A A$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *symmetric-point-construction*:
 $\exists P'. A$ Midpoint $P P'$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *symmetric-point-uniqueness*:
assumes P Midpoint $A P1$ and
 P Midpoint $A P2$
shows $P1 = P2$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-9*:
assumes A Midpoint $P X$ and
 A Midpoint $Q X$
shows $P = Q$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-9-bis*:
assumes A Midpoint $P X$ and
 A Midpoint $X Q$
shows $P = Q$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-13-R1*:
assumes $A \neq P$ and
 A Midpoint $P' P$ and
 A Midpoint $Q' Q$
shows $Cong P Q P' Q'$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-13*:
assumes A Midpoint $P' P$ and
 A Midpoint $Q' Q$
shows $Cong P Q P' Q'$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-15*:
assumes A Midpoint $P P'$ and
 A Midpoint $Q Q'$ and
 A Midpoint $R R'$ and
 $Bet P Q R$
shows $Bet P' Q' R'$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *l7-16*:
assumes A Midpoint $P P'$ and
 A Midpoint $Q Q'$ and
 A Midpoint $R R'$ and
 A Midpoint $S S'$ and
 $Cong P Q R S$
shows $Cong P' Q' R' S'$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *symmetry-preserves-midpoint*:
assumes Z Midpoint $A D$ and

Z Midpoint B E **and**
Z Midpoint C F **and**
B Midpoint A C
shows *E Midpoint D F*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Mid-cases*:
assumes *A Midpoint B C* \vee *A Midpoint C B*
shows *A Midpoint B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Mid-perm*:
assumes *A Midpoint B C*
shows *A Midpoint B C* \wedge *A Midpoint C B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-17*:
assumes *A Midpoint P P'* **and**
B Midpoint P P'
shows $A = B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-17-bis*:
assumes *A Midpoint P P'* **and**
B Midpoint P' P
shows $A = B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-20*:
assumes *Col A M B* **and**
Cong M A M B
shows $A = B \vee M \text{ Midpoint } A B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-20-bis*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Col A M B **and**
Cong M A M B
shows *M Midpoint A B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *cong-col-mid*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
Col A B C **and**
Cong A B B C
shows *B Midpoint A C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-21-R1*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
Cong A B C D **and**
Cong B C D A **and**
Col A P C **and**
Col B P D
shows *P Midpoint A C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l7-21*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
Cong A B C D **and**
Cong B C D A **and**
Col A P C **and**
Col B P D
shows $P \text{ Midpoint } A C \wedge P \text{ Midpoint } B D$

<proof>

lemma l7-22-aux-R1:

assumes $Bet\ A1\ C\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ B1\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A1\ C\ B1$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ C\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $M1\ Midpoint\ A1\ B1$ **and**
 $M2\ Midpoint\ A2\ B2$ **and**
 $C\ A1\ Le\ C\ C$
shows $Bet\ M1\ C\ M2$
<proof>

lemma l7-22-aux-R2:

assumes $A2 \neq C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A1\ C\ A2$ **and**
 $Bet\ B1\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A1\ C\ B1$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A2\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $M1\ Midpoint\ A1\ B1$ **and**
 $M2\ Midpoint\ A2\ B2$ **and**
 $C\ A1\ Le\ C\ A2$
shows $Bet\ M1\ C\ M2$
<proof>

lemma l7-22-aux:

assumes $Bet\ A1\ C\ A2$ **and**
 $Bet\ B1\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A1\ C\ B1$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A2\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $M1\ Midpoint\ A1\ B1$ **and**
 $M2\ Midpoint\ A2\ B2$ **and**
 $C\ A1\ Le\ C\ A2$
shows $Bet\ M1\ C\ M2$
<proof>

lemma l7-22:

assumes $Bet\ A1\ C\ A2$ **and**
 $Bet\ B1\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A1\ C\ B1$ **and**
 $Cong\ C\ A2\ C\ B2$ **and**
 $M1\ Midpoint\ A1\ B1$ **and**
 $M2\ Midpoint\ A2\ B2$
shows $Bet\ M1\ C\ M2$
<proof>

lemma bet-col1:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ D$
shows $Col\ A\ B\ C$
<proof>

lemma l7-25-R1:

assumes $Cong\ C\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists X. X\ Midpoint\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma l7-25-R2:

assumes $Cong\ C\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $\neg Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists X. X\ Midpoint\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma l7-25:

assumes $Cong\ C\ A\ C\ B$

shows $\exists X. X \text{ Midpoint } A B$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-distinct-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $I \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $I \neq A \wedge I \neq B$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-distinct-2*:
assumes $I \neq A$ **and**
 $I \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $A \neq B \wedge I \neq B$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-distinct-3*:
assumes $I \neq B$ **and**
 $I \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $A \neq B \wedge I \neq A$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-def*:
assumes $B \text{ et } A B C$ **and**
 $C \text{ong } A B B C$
shows $B \text{ Midpoint } A C$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-bet*:
assumes $B \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $B \text{ et } A B C$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-col*:
assumes $M \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $Col M A B$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-cong*:
assumes $B \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $C \text{ong } A B B C$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-out*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $A \text{ Out } B C$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-out-1*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $C \text{ Out } A B$
<proof>

lemma *midpoint-not-midpoint*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $I \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $\neg B \text{ Midpoint } A I$
<proof>

lemma *swap-diff*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $B \neq A$
<proof>

lemma *cong-cong-half-1*:

assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 $Cong$ A B A' B'
shows $Cong$ A M A' M'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *cong-cong-half-2*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 $Cong$ A B A' B'
shows $Cong$ B M B' M'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *cong-mid2--cong*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 $Cong$ A M A' M'
shows $Cong$ A B A' B'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *mid--lt*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* A B
shows A M *Lt* A B
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *le-mid2--le13*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 A M *Le* A' M'
shows A B *Le* A' B'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *le-mid2--le12*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B'
and A B *Le* A' B'
shows A M *Le* A' M'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-mid2--lt13*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 A M *Lt* A' M'
shows A B *Lt* A' B'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-mid2--lt12*:
assumes M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 M' *Midpoint* A' B' **and**
 A B *Lt* A' B'
shows A M *Lt* A' M'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *midpoint-preserves-out*:
assumes A *Out* B C **and**
 M *Midpoint* A A' **and**
 M *Midpoint* B B' **and**
 M *Midpoint* C C'
shows A' *Out* B' C'
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *col-cong-bet*:
assumes Col A B D **and**
 $Cong$ A B C D **and**
 Bet A C B

shows $Bet\ C\ A\ D \vee Bet\ C\ B\ D$
(proof)

lemma *col-cong2-bet1*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ B\ D$
shows $Bet\ C\ B\ D$
(proof)

lemma *col-cong2-bet2*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ D\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ C\ A\ D$
(proof)

lemma *col-cong2-bet3*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ B\ D$
shows $Bet\ B\ C\ D$
(proof)

lemma *col-cong2-bet4*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ D\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ B\ D\ C$
(proof)

lemma *col-bet2-cong1*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ C\ B\ D$
shows $Cong\ A\ C\ D\ B$
(proof)

lemma *col-bet2-cong2*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ C\ A\ D$
shows $Cong\ D\ A\ B\ C$
(proof)

lemma *bet2-lt2--lt*:
assumes $Bet\ a\ Po\ b$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ PO\ B$ **and**
 $Po\ a\ Lt\ PO\ A$ **and**
 $Po\ b\ Lt\ PO\ B$
shows $a\ b\ Lt\ A\ B$
(proof)

lemma *bet2-lt-le--lt*:
assumes $Bet\ a\ Po\ b$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ PO\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ Po\ a\ PO\ A$ **and**
 $Po\ b\ Lt\ PO\ B$
shows $a\ b\ Lt\ A\ B$
(proof)

lemma *per-dec*:
Per $A B C \vee \neg$ Per $A B C$
(proof)

lemma *l8-2*:
assumes Per $A B C$
shows Per $C B A$
(proof)

lemma *Per-cases*:
assumes Per $A B C \vee$ Per $C B A$
shows Per $A B C$
(proof)

lemma *Per-perm* :
assumes Per $A B C$
shows Per $A B C \wedge$ Per $C B A$
(proof)

lemma *l8-3* :
assumes Per $A B C$ and
A \neq B and
Col $B A A'$
shows Per $A' B C$
(proof)

lemma *l8-4*:
assumes Per $A B C$ and
B Midpoint $C C'$
shows Per $A B C'$
(proof)

lemma *l8-5*:
shows Per $A B B$
(proof)

lemma *l8-6*:
assumes Per $A B C$ and
Per $A' B C$ and
Bet $A C A'$
shows $B = C$
(proof)

lemma *l8-7*:
assumes Per $A B C$ and
Per $A C B$
shows $B = C$
(proof)

lemma *l8-8*:
assumes Per $A B A$
shows $A = B$
(proof)

lemma *per-distinct*:
assumes Per $A B C$ and
A \neq B
shows $A \neq C$
(proof)

lemma *per-distinct-1*:
assumes Per $A B C$ and
B \neq C
shows $A \neq C$
(proof)

lemma l8-9:

assumes $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A = B \vee C = B$
(proof)

lemma l8-10:

assumes $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ Cong^3\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $Per\ A'\ B'\ C'$
(proof)

lemma col-col-per-per:

assumes $A \neq X$ **and**
 $C \neq X$ **and**
 $Col\ U\ A\ X$ **and**
 $Col\ V\ C\ X$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ X\ C$
shows $Per\ U\ X\ V$
(proof)

lemma perp-in-dec:

$X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D \vee \neg X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
(proof)

lemma perp-distinct:

assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq D$
(proof)

lemma l8-12:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $X\ PerpAt\ C\ D\ A\ B$
(proof)

lemma per-col:

assumes $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Col\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Per\ A\ B\ D$
(proof)

lemma l8-13-2:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col\ X\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Col\ X\ C\ D$ **and**
 $\exists U. \exists V. Col\ U\ A\ B \wedge Col\ V\ C\ D \wedge U \neq X \wedge V \neq X \wedge Per\ U\ X\ V$
shows $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
(proof)

lemma l8-14-1:

$\neg A\ B\ Perp\ A\ B$
(proof)

lemma l8-14-2-1a:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$
(proof)

lemma perp-in-distinct:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq D$
(proof)

lemma *l8-14-2-1b*:

assumes $X \text{ PerpAt } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**
 $Col \ Y \ A \ B$ **and**
 $Col \ Y \ C \ D$
shows $X = Y$
<proof>

lemma *l8-14-2-1b-bis*:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ C \ D$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ A \ B$ **and**
 $Col \ X \ C \ D$
shows $X \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ D$
<proof>

lemma *l8-14-2-2*:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ C \ D$ **and**
 $\forall \ Y. (Col \ Y \ A \ B \ \wedge \ Col \ Y \ C \ D) \longrightarrow X = Y$
shows $X \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ D$
<proof>

lemma *l8-14-3*:

assumes $X \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**
 $Y \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ D$
shows $X = Y$
<proof>

lemma *l8-15-1*:

assumes $Col \ A \ B \ X$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ C \ X$
shows $X \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ X$
<proof>

lemma *l8-15-2*:

assumes $Col \ A \ B \ X$ **and**
 $X \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ C \ X$
shows $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ C \ X$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-per*:

assumes $B \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ B \ C$
shows $Per \ A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *perp-sym*:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ A \ B$
shows $C \ D \ \text{Perp} \ C \ D$
<proof>

lemma *perp-col0*:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{Perp} \ C \ D$ **and**
 $X \neq Y$ **and**
 $Col \ A \ B \ X$ **and**
 $Col \ A \ B \ Y$
shows $C \ D \ \text{Perp} \ X \ Y$
<proof>

lemma *per-perp-in*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Per \ A \ B \ C$
shows $B \ \text{PerpAt} \ A \ B \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *per-perp*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**

Per A B C
shows $A B \text{Perp} B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-left-comm:*
assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$
shows $B A \text{Perp} C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-right-comm:*
assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$
shows $A B \text{Perp} D C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-comm:*
assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$
shows $B A \text{Perp} D C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-in-sym:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} C D A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-in-left-comm:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} B A C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-in-right-comm:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} A B D C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-in-comm:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} B A D C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Perp-cases:*
assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D \vee B A \text{Perp} C D \vee A B \text{Perp} D C \vee B A \text{Perp} D C \vee C D \text{Perp} A B \vee$
 $C D \text{Perp} B A \vee D C \text{Perp} A B \vee D C \text{Perp} B A$
shows $A B \text{Perp} C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Perp-perm :*
assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$
shows $A B \text{Perp} C D \wedge B A \text{Perp} C D \wedge A B \text{Perp} D C \wedge B A \text{Perp} D C \wedge C D \text{Perp} A B \wedge$
 $C D \text{Perp} B A \wedge D C \text{Perp} A B \wedge D C \text{Perp} B A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Perp-in-cases:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D \vee X \text{PerpAt} B A C D \vee X \text{PerpAt} A B D C \vee X \text{PerpAt} B A D C \vee$
 $X \text{PerpAt} C D A B \vee X \text{PerpAt} C D B A \vee X \text{PerpAt} D C A B \vee X \text{PerpAt} D C B A$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Perp-in-perm:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D \wedge X \text{PerpAt} B A C D \wedge X \text{PerpAt} A B D C \wedge X \text{PerpAt} B A D C \wedge$
 $X \text{PerpAt} C D A B \wedge X \text{PerpAt} C D B A \wedge X \text{PerpAt} D C A B \wedge X \text{PerpAt} D C B A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-in-col:*
assumes $X \text{PerpAt} A B C D$
shows $\text{Col} A B X \wedge \text{Col} C D X$

<proof>

lemma *perp-perp-in:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} C A$

shows $A \text{PerpAt} A B C A$

<proof>

lemma *perp-per-1:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} C A$

shows $\text{Per} B A C$

<proof>

lemma *perp-per-2:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} A C$

shows $\text{Per} B A C$

<proof>

lemma *perp-col:*

assumes $A \neq E$ **and**

$A B \text{Perp} C D$ **and**

$\text{Col} A B E$

shows $A E \text{Perp} C D$

<proof>

lemma *perp-col2:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} X Y$ **and**

$C \neq D$ **and**

$\text{Col} A B C$ **and**

$\text{Col} A B D$

shows $C D \text{Perp} X Y$

<proof>

lemma *perp-col4:*

assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**

$R \neq S$ **and**

$\text{Col} A B P$ **and**

$\text{Col} A B Q$ **and**

$\text{Col} C D R$ **and**

$\text{Col} C D S$ **and**

$A B \text{Perp} C D$

shows $P Q \text{Perp} R S$

<proof>

lemma *perp-not-eq-1:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$

shows $A \neq B$

<proof>

lemma *perp-not-eq-2:*

assumes $A B \text{Perp} C D$

shows $C \neq D$

<proof>

lemma *diff-per-diff:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Cong} A P B R$ **and**

$\text{Per} B A P$

and $\text{Per} A B R$

shows $P \neq R$

<proof>

lemma *per-not-colp:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq P$ **and**

$B \neq R$ **and**

$\text{Per} B A P$

and $Per\ A\ B\ R$
shows $\neg\ Col\ P\ A\ R$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *per-not-col*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-not-col2*:
assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-not-col*:
assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ A$
shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-in-col-perp-in*:
assumes $C \neq E$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ E$ **and**
 $P\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $P\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-col2-bis*:
assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ P$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ Q$ **and**
 $P \neq Q$
shows $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-in-perp-bis-R1*:
assumes $X \neq A$ **and**
 $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $X\ B\ Perp\ C\ D \vee A\ X\ Perp\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-in-perp-bis*:
assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $X\ B\ Perp\ C\ D \vee A\ X\ Perp\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-per-perp*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**

 $D \neq C$ **and**
 $Col\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$
shows $C\ D\ Perp\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *per-cong-mid-R1*:
assumes $B = H$ **and**

 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ H\ C\ H$ **and**
 $Per\ H\ B\ C$
shows $B\ Midpoint\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *per-cong-mid-R2*:

assumes

$B \neq C$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ H\ C\ H$ **and**

$Per\ H\ B\ C$

shows $B\ Midpoint\ A\ C$

<proof>

lemma *per-cong-mid*:

assumes $B \neq C$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ H\ C\ H$ **and**

$Per\ H\ B\ C$

shows $B\ Midpoint\ A\ C$

<proof>

lemma *per-double-cong*:

assumes $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$B\ Midpoint\ C\ C'$

shows $Cong\ A\ C\ A\ C'$

<proof>

lemma *cong-perp-or-mid-R1*:

assumes $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$M\ Midpoint\ A\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ X\ B\ X$

shows $X = M \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ X \wedge M\ PerpAt\ X\ M\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *cong-perp-or-mid-R2*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$M\ Midpoint\ A\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ X\ B\ X$

shows $X = M \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ X \wedge M\ PerpAt\ X\ M\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *cong-perp-or-mid*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$M\ Midpoint\ A\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ X\ B\ X$

shows $X = M \vee \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ X \wedge M\ PerpAt\ X\ M\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *col-per2-cases*:

assumes $B \neq C$ **and**

$B' \neq C$ **and**

$C \neq D$ **and**

$Col\ B\ C\ D$ **and**

$Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Per\ A\ B'\ C$

shows $B = B' \vee \neg\ Col\ B'\ C\ D$

<proof>

lemma *l8-16-1*:

assumes $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ U$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ C\ X$

shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge Per\ C\ X\ U$

<proof>

lemma *l8-16-2*:

assumes $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ U$ **and**

$U \neq X$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Per } C X U$
shows $A B \text{ Perp } C X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-18-uniqueness*:

assumes
 $\text{Col } A B X$ and
 $A B \text{ Perp } C X$ and
 $\text{Col } A B Y$ and
 $A B \text{ Perp } C Y$
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-distinct*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Col } A B X$ and
 $X \text{ Midpoint } C C'$
shows $C \neq C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-20-1-R1*:

assumes $A = B$
shows $\text{Per } B A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-20-1-R2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $\text{Per } A B C$ and
 $P \text{ Midpoint } C' D$ and
 $A \text{ Midpoint } C' C$ and
 $B \text{ Midpoint } D C$
shows $\text{Per } B A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-20-1*:

assumes $\text{Per } A B C$ and
 $P \text{ Midpoint } C' D$ and
 $A \text{ Midpoint } C' C$ and
 $B \text{ Midpoint } D C$
shows $\text{Per } B A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-20-2*:

assumes $P \text{ Midpoint } C' D$ and
 $A \text{ Midpoint } C' C$ and
 $B \text{ Midpoint } D C$ and
 $B \neq C$
shows $A \neq P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-col1*:

assumes $C \neq X$ and
 $A B \text{ Perp } C D$ and
 $\text{Col } C D X$
shows $A B \text{ Perp } C X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-18-existence*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$
shows $\exists X. \text{Col } A B X \wedge A B \text{ Perp } C X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-21-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

shows $\exists P. \exists T. (A B \text{ Perp } P A \wedge \text{Col } A B T \wedge \text{Bet } C T P)$
(proof)

lemma *l8-21*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\exists P T. A B \text{ Perp } P A \wedge \text{Col } A B T \wedge \text{Bet } C T P$

(proof)

lemma *per-cong*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq P$ **and**

$\text{Per } B A P$ **and**

$\text{Per } A B R$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A P B R$ **and**

$\text{Col } A B X$ **and**

$\text{Bet } P X R$

shows $\text{Cong } A R P B$

(proof)

lemma *perp-cong*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq P$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } P A$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } R B$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A P B R$ **and**

$\text{Col } A B X$ **and**

$\text{Bet } P X R$

shows $\text{Cong } A R P B$

(proof)

lemma *perp-exists*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\exists X. \text{PO } X \text{ Perp } A B$

(proof)

lemma *perp-vector*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\exists X Y. A B \text{ Perp } X Y$

(proof)

lemma *midpoint-existence-aux*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } Q B$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } P A$ **and**

$\text{Col } A B T$ **and**

$\text{Bet } Q T P$ **and**

$A P \text{ Le } B Q$

shows $\exists X. X \text{ Midpoint } A B$

(proof)

lemma *midpoint-existence*:

$\exists X. X \text{ Midpoint } A B$

(proof)

lemma *MidR-uniq-aux*:

shows $\exists!x. x \text{ Midpoint } A B$

(proof)

lemma *SymR-uniq-aux*:

assumes $B \text{ Midpoint } A x$ **and**

$B \text{ Midpoint } A y$

shows $x = y$

(proof)

lemma *perp-in-id*:

assumes $X \text{ PerpAt } A B C A$

shows $X = A$
<proof>

lemma *l8-22*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq P$ **and**
 $Per\ B\ A\ P$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ R$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ P\ B\ R$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**
 $Bet\ P\ X\ R$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ R\ P\ B$

shows $X\ Midpoint\ A\ B \wedge X\ Midpoint\ P\ R$
<proof>

lemma *l8-22-bis*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq P$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ A$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Perp\ R\ B$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ P\ B\ R$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**
 $Bet\ P\ X\ R$

shows $Cong\ A\ R\ P\ B \wedge X\ Midpoint\ A\ B \wedge X\ Midpoint\ P\ R$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-perp*:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$
<proof>

lemma *perp-proj*:

assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ C\ D$
shows $\exists\ X.\ Col\ A\ B\ X \wedge A\ X\ Perp\ C\ D$
<proof>

lemma *l8-24* :

assumes $P\ A\ Perp\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Q\ B\ Perp\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ T$ **and**
 $Bet\ P\ T\ Q$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ R\ Q$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ P\ B\ R$

shows $\exists\ X.\ X\ Midpoint\ A\ B \wedge X\ Midpoint\ P\ R$
<proof>

lemma *col-per2--per*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ X\ P$ **and**
 $Per\ B\ X\ P$
shows $Per\ C\ X\ P$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-per-1*:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Per\ A\ X\ C$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-per-2*:

assumes $X\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Per\ A\ X\ D$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-per-3*:

assumes $X \text{ PerpAt } A B C D$
shows $\text{Per } B X C$
<proof>

lemma *perp-in-per-4*:
assumes $X \text{ PerpAt } A B C D$
shows $\text{Per } B X D$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-1*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A B D C$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-2*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A C B D$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-3*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A C D B$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-4*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A D B C$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-5*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A D C B$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-6*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B A C D$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-7*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B A D C$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-8*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B C A D$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-9*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B C D A$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-10*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B D A C$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-11*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } B D C A$
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-12*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows *Coplanar C A B D*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-13*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar C A D B*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-14*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar C B A D*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-15*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar C B D A*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-16*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar C D A B*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-17*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar C D B A*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-18*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D A B C*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-19*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D A C B*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-20*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D B A C*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-21*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D B C A*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-22*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D C A B*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-perm-23*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows *Coplanar D C B A*
<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-1*:
assumes \neg *Coplanar A B C D*
shows \neg *Coplanar A B D C*
<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-2*:
assumes \neg *Coplanar A B C D*
shows \neg *Coplanar A C B D*

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-3:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A C D B$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-4:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A D B C$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-5:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A D C B$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-6:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B A C D$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-7:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B A D C$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-8:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B C A D$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-9:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B C D A$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-10:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B D A C$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-11:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } B D C A$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-12:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C A B D$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-13:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C A D B$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-14:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C B A D$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-15:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$

shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C B D A$

<proof>

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-16*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C D A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-17*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } C D B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-18*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-19*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D A C B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-20*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D B A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-21*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D B C A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-22*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D C A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncoplanar-perm-23*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } D C B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *coplanar-trivial*:
 shows $\text{Coplanar } A A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col--coplanar*:
 assumes $\text{Col } A B C$
 shows $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncop--ncol*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncop--ncols*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge \neg \text{Col } A B D \wedge \neg \text{Col } A C D \wedge \neg \text{Col } B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet--coplanar*:
 assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$
 shows $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out--coplanar*:

assumes A *Out* B C
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *midpoint--coplanar*:
assumes A *Midpoint* B C
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *perp--coplanar*:
assumes A B *Perp* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *ts--coplanar*:
assumes A B *TS* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *reflectl--coplanar*:
assumes A B *ReflectL* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *reflect--coplanar*:
assumes A B *Reflect* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *inangle--coplanar*:
assumes A *InAngle* B C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *pars--coplanar*:
assumes A B *ParStrict* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *par--coplanar*:
assumes A B *Par* C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg--coplanar*:
assumes *Plg* A B C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgs--coplanar*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgf--coplanar*:
assumes *ParallelogramFlat* A B C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *parallelogram--coplanar*:
assumes *Parallelogram* A B C D
shows *Coplanar* A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rhombus--coplanar*:
assumes *Rhombus* A B C D

shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *rectangle--coplanar*:
assumes *Rectangle A B C D*
shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *square--coplanar*:
assumes *Square A B C D*
shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *lambert--coplanar*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D*
shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *ts-distincts*:
assumes *A B TS P Q*
shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq P \wedge A \neq Q \wedge B \neq P \wedge B \neq Q \wedge P \neq Q$
<proof>

lemma *l9-2*:
assumes *A B TS P Q*
shows *A B TS Q P*
<proof>

lemma *invert-two-sides*:
assumes *A B TS P Q*
shows *B A TS P Q*
<proof>

lemma *l9-3*:
assumes *P Q TS A C and*
Col M P Q and
M Midpoint A C and
Col R P Q and
R Out A B
shows *P Q TS B C*
<proof>

lemma *mid-preserves-col*:
assumes *Col A B C and*
M Midpoint A A' and
M Midpoint B B' and
M Midpoint C C'
shows *Col A' B' C'*
<proof>

lemma *per-mid-per*:
assumes
Per X A B and
M Midpoint A B and
M Midpoint X Y
shows $Cong A X B Y \wedge Per Y B A$
<proof>

lemma *sym-preserve-diff*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
M Midpoint A A' and
M Midpoint B B'
shows $A' \neq B'$
<proof>

lemma *l9-4-1-aux-R1*:

assumes $R = S$ **and**
 $S C Le R A$ **and**
 $P Q TS A C$ **and**
 $Col R P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp A R$ **and**
 $Col S P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp C S$ **and**
 $M Midpoint R S$
shows $\forall U C'. M Midpoint U C' \longrightarrow (R Out U A \longleftrightarrow S Out C C')$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l9-4-1-aux-R21*:
assumes $R \neq S$ **and**
 $S C Le R A$ **and**
 $P Q TS A C$ **and**
 $Col R P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp A R$ **and**
 $Col S P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp C S$ **and**
 $M Midpoint R S$
shows $\forall U C'. M Midpoint U C' \longrightarrow (R Out U A \longleftrightarrow S Out C C')$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l9-4-1-aux*:
assumes $S C Le R A$ **and**
 $P Q TS A C$ **and**
 $Col R P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp A R$ **and**
 $Col S P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp C S$ **and**
 $M Midpoint R S$
shows $\forall U C'. (M Midpoint U C' \longrightarrow (R Out U A \longleftrightarrow S Out C C'))$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *per-col-eq*:
assumes $Per A B C$ **and**
 $Col A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $A = B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l9-4-1*:
assumes $P Q TS A C$ **and**
 $Col R P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp A R$ **and**
 $Col S P Q$ **and**
 $P Q Perp C S$ **and**
 $M Midpoint R S$
shows $\forall U C'. M Midpoint U C' \longrightarrow (R Out U A \longleftrightarrow S Out C C')$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *mid-two-sides*:
assumes $M Midpoint A B$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B X$ **and**
 $M Midpoint X Y$
shows $A B TS X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-preserves-two-sides*:
assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col A B C$ **and**
 $Col A B D$ **and**
 $A B TS X Y$
shows $C D TS X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *out-out-two-sides*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A B TS X Y$ **and**

$Col I A B$ **and**

$Col I X Y$ **and**

$I Out X U$ **and**

$I Out Y V$

shows $A B TS U V$

<proof>

lemma *l9-4-2-aux-R1*:

assumes $R = S$ **and**

$S C Le R A$ **and**

$P Q TS A C$ **and**

$Col R P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp A R$ **and**

$Col S P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp C S$ **and**

$R Out U A$ **and**

$S Out V C$

shows $P Q TS U V$

<proof>

lemma *l9-4-2-aux-R2*:

assumes $R \neq S$ **and**

$S C Le R A$ **and**

$P Q TS A C$ **and**

$Col R P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp A R$ **and**

$Col S P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp C S$ **and**

$R Out U A$ **and**

$S Out V C$

shows $P Q TS U V$

<proof>

lemma *l9-4-2-aux*:

assumes $S C Le R A$ **and**

$P Q TS A C$ **and**

$Col R P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp A R$ **and**

$Col S P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp C S$ **and**

$R Out U A$ **and**

$S Out V C$

shows $P Q TS U V$

<proof>

lemma *l9-4-2*:

assumes $P Q TS A C$ **and**

$Col R P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp A R$ **and**

$Col S P Q$ **and**

$P Q Perp C S$ **and**

$R Out U A$ **and**

$S Out V C$

shows $P Q TS U V$

<proof>

lemma *l9-5*:

assumes $P Q TS A C$ **and**

$Col R P Q$ **and**

$R Out A B$

shows $P Q TS B C$

<proof>

lemma *outer-pasch-R1*:
assumes $Col\ P\ Q\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ P$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ Q\ C$
shows $\exists\ X.\ Bet\ A\ X\ B \wedge Bet\ P\ Q\ X$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *outer-pasch-R2*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ P\ Q\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ P$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ Q\ C$
shows $\exists\ X.\ Bet\ A\ X\ B \wedge Bet\ P\ Q\ X$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *outer-pasch*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ C\ P$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ Q\ C$
shows $\exists\ X.\ Bet\ A\ X\ B \wedge Bet\ P\ Q\ X$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *os-distincts*:
assumes $A\ B\ OS\ X\ Y$
shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq X \wedge A \neq Y \wedge B \neq X \wedge B \neq Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *invert-one-side*:
assumes $A\ B\ OS\ P\ Q$
shows $B\ A\ OS\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-8-1*:
assumes $P\ Q\ TS\ A\ C$ **and**
 $P\ Q\ TS\ B\ C$
shows $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-two-sides-id*:
shows $\neg\ P\ Q\ TS\ A\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-8-2*:
assumes $P\ Q\ TS\ A\ C$ **and**
 $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Q\ TS\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-9*:
assumes $P\ Q\ TS\ A\ B$
shows $\neg\ P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-9-bis*:
assumes $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
shows $\neg\ P\ Q\ TS\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *one-side-chara*:
assumes $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
shows $\forall\ X.\ Col\ X\ P\ Q \longrightarrow \neg\ Bet\ A\ X\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-10*:

assumes $\neg Col A P Q$
shows $\exists C. P Q TS A C$
<proof>

lemma one-side-reflexivity:
assumes $\neg Col A P Q$
shows $P Q OS A A$
<proof>

lemma one-side-symmetry:
assumes $P Q OS A B$
shows $P Q OS B A$
<proof>

lemma one-side-transitivity:
assumes $P Q OS A B$ **and**
 $P Q OS B C$
shows $P Q OS A C$
<proof>

lemma l9-17:
assumes $P Q OS A C$ **and**
 $Bet A B C$
shows $P Q OS A B$
<proof>

lemma l9-18-R1:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**
 $Col A B P$
and $X Y TS A B$
shows $Bet A P B \wedge \neg Col X Y A \wedge \neg Col X Y B$
<proof>

lemma l9-18-R2:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**
 $Col A B P$ **and**
 $Bet A P B$ **and**
 $\neg Col X Y A$ **and**
 $\neg Col X Y B$
shows $X Y TS A B$
<proof>

lemma l9-18:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**
 $Col A B P$
shows $X Y TS A B \longleftrightarrow (Bet A P B \wedge \neg Col X Y A \wedge \neg Col X Y B)$
<proof>

lemma l9-19-R1:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**
 $Col A B P$ **and**
 $X Y OS A B$
shows $P Out A B \wedge \neg Col X Y A$
<proof>

lemma l9-19-R2:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**

 $P Out A B$ **and**
 $\neg Col X Y A$
shows $X Y OS A B$
<proof>

lemma l9-19:
assumes $Col X Y P$ **and**
 $Col A B P$

shows $X Y OS A B \leftrightarrow (P Out A B \wedge \neg Col X Y A)$
<proof>

lemma *one-side-not-col123*:
assumes $A B OS X Y$
shows $\neg Col A B X$
<proof>

lemma *one-side-not-col124*:
assumes $A B OS X Y$
shows $\neg Col A B Y$
<proof>

lemma *col-two-sides*:
assumes $Col A B C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $A B TS P Q$
shows $A C TS P Q$
<proof>

lemma *col-one-side*:
assumes $Col A B C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $A B OS P Q$
shows $A C OS P Q$
<proof>

lemma *out-out-one-side*:
assumes $A B OS X Y$ **and**
 $A Out Y Z$
shows $A B OS X Z$
<proof>

lemma *out-one-side*:
assumes $\neg Col A B X \vee \neg Col A B Y$ **and**
 $A Out X Y$
shows $A B OS X Y$
<proof>

lemma *bet--ts*:
assumes $A \neq Y$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B X$ **and**
 $Bet X A Y$
shows $A B TS X Y$
<proof>

lemma *bet-ts--ts*:
assumes $A B TS X Y$ **and**
 $Bet X Y Z$
shows $A B TS X Z$
<proof>

lemma *bet-ts--os*:
assumes $A B TS X Y$ **and**
 $Bet X Y Z$
shows $A B OS Y Z$
<proof>

lemma *l9-31* :
assumes $A X OS Y Z$ **and**
 $A Z OS Y X$
shows $A Y TS X Z$
<proof>

lemma *col123--nos*:
assumes $Col P Q A$

shows $\neg P Q OS A B$
<proof>

lemma *col124--nos*:
assumes *Col P Q B*
shows $\neg P Q OS A B$
<proof>

lemma *col2-os--os*:
assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 Col A B C and
 Col A B D and
 A B OS X Y
shows $C D OS X Y$
<proof>

lemma *os-out-os*:
assumes *Col A B P and*
 A B OS C D and
 P Out C C'
shows $A B OS C' D$
<proof>

lemma *ts-ts-os*:
assumes $A B TS C D$ **and**
 C D TS A B
shows $A C OS B D$
<proof>

lemma *col-one-side-out*:
assumes $Col A X Y$ **and**
 A B OS X Y
shows $A Out X Y$
<proof>

lemma *col-two-sides-bet*:
assumes $Col A X Y$ **and**
 A B TS X Y
shows $Bet X A Y$
<proof>

lemma *os-ts1324--os*:
assumes $A X OS Y Z$ **and**
 A Y TS X Z
shows $A Z OS X Y$
<proof>

lemma *ts2--ex-bet2*:
assumes $A C TS B D$ **and**
 B D TS A C
shows $\exists X. Bet A X C \wedge Bet B X D$
<proof>

lemma *out-one-side-1*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 Col A B X and
 X Out C D
shows $A B OS C D$
<proof>

lemma *out-two-sides-two-sides*:
assumes
 Col A B PX and
 PX Out X P and
 A B TS P Y
shows $A B TS X Y$

<proof>

lemma l8-21-bis:

assumes $X \neq Y$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } C \ A \ B$

shows $\exists P. \text{Cong } A \ P \ X \ Y \wedge A \ B \ \text{Perp } P \ A \wedge A \ B \ \text{TS } C \ P$

<proof>

lemma ts--ncol:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{TS } X \ Y$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A \ X \ Y \vee \neg \text{Col } B \ X \ Y$

<proof>

lemma one-or-two-sides-aux:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } C \ A \ B$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } D \ A \ B$ **and**

$\text{Col } A \ C \ X$

and $\text{Col } B \ D \ X$

shows $A \ B \ \text{TS } C \ D \vee A \ B \ \text{OS } C \ D$

<proof>

lemma cop--one-or-two-sides:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } C \ A \ B$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } D \ A \ B$

shows $A \ B \ \text{TS } C \ D \vee A \ B \ \text{OS } C \ D$

<proof>

lemma os--coplanar:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{OS } C \ D$

shows $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$

<proof>

lemma coplanar-trans-1:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } P \ Q \ R$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } P \ Q \ R \ A$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } P \ Q \ R \ B$

shows $\text{Coplanar } Q \ R \ A \ B$

<proof>

lemma col-cop--cop:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**

$C \neq D$ **and**

$\text{Col } C \ D \ E$

shows $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ E$

<proof>

lemma bet-cop--cop:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ E$ **and**

$\text{Bet } C \ D \ E$

shows $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$

<proof>

lemma col2-cop--cop:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**

$C \neq D$ **and**

$\text{Col } C \ D \ E$ **and**

$\text{Col } C \ D \ F$

shows $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ E \ F$

<proof>

lemma col-cop2--cop:

assumes $U \neq V$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ U$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ V$ **and**

$\text{Col } U \ V \ P$

shows *Coplanar A B C P*
<proof>

lemma *bet-cop2--cop*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C U and*
Coplanar A B C W and
Bet U V W
shows *Coplanar A B C V*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-pseudo-trans-lem1*:
assumes \neg *Col P Q R and*
Coplanar P Q R A and
Coplanar P Q R B and
Coplanar P Q R C
shows *Coplanar A B C R*
<proof>

lemma *coplanar-pseudo-trans*:
assumes \neg *Col P Q R and*
Coplanar P Q R A and
Coplanar P Q R B and
Coplanar P Q R C and
Coplanar P Q R D
shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *l9-30*:
assumes \neg *Coplanar A B C P and*
 \neg *Col D E F and*
Coplanar D E F P and
Coplanar A B C X and
Coplanar A B C Y and
Coplanar A B C Z and
Coplanar D E F X and
Coplanar D E F Y and
Coplanar D E F Z
shows *Col X Y Z*
<proof>

lemma *cop-per2--col*:
assumes *Coplanar A X Y Z and*
A \neq Z and
Per X Z A and
Per Y Z A
shows *Col X Y Z*
<proof>

lemma *cop-perp2--col*:
assumes *Coplanar A B Y Z and*
X Y Perp A B and
X Z Perp A B
shows *Col X Y Z*
<proof>

lemma *two-sides-dec*:
shows *A B TS C D \vee \neg A B TS C D*
<proof>

lemma *cop-nts--os*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D and*
 \neg *Col C A B and*
 \neg *Col D A B and*
 \neg *A B TS C D*
shows *A B OS C D*
<proof>

lemma *cop-nos--ts*:

assumes *Coplanar A B C D* **and**

\neg *Col C A B* **and**

\neg *Col D A B* **and**

\neg *A B OS C D*

shows *A B TS C D*

<proof>

lemma *one-side-dec*:

A B OS C D \vee \neg *A B OS C D*

<proof>

lemma *cop-dec*:

Coplanar A B C D \vee \neg *Coplanar A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *ex-diff-cop*:

$\exists E$. *Coplanar A B C E* \wedge $D \neq E$

<proof>

lemma *ex-ncol-cop*:

assumes $D \neq E$

shows $\exists F$. *Coplanar A B C F* \wedge \neg *Col D E F*

<proof>

lemma *ex-ncol-cop2*:

$\exists E F$. (*Coplanar A B C E* \wedge *Coplanar A B C F* \wedge \neg *Col D E F*)

<proof>

lemma *col2-cop2--eq*:

assumes \neg *Coplanar A B C U* **and**

$U \neq V$ **and**

Coplanar A B C P **and**

Coplanar A B C Q **and**

Col U V P **and**

Col U V Q

shows $P = Q$

<proof>

lemma *cong3-cop2--col*:

assumes *Coplanar A B C P* **and**

Coplanar A B C Q **and**

$P \neq Q$ **and**

Cong A P A Q **and**

Cong B P B Q **and**

Cong C P C Q

shows *Col A B C*

<proof>

lemma *l9-38*:

assumes *A B C TSP P Q*

shows *A B C TSP Q P*

<proof>

lemma *l9-39*:

assumes *A B C TSP P R* **and**

Coplanar A B C D **and**

D Out P Q

shows *A B C TSP Q R*

<proof>

lemma *l9-41-1*:

assumes *A B C TSP P R* **and**

A B C TSP Q R

shows *A B C OSP P Q*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l9-41-2*:

assumes $A B C TSP P R$ and
 $A B C OSP P Q$

shows $A B C TSP Q R$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *tsp-exists*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C P$

shows $\exists Q. A B C TSP P Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *osp-reflexivity*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C P$

shows $A B C OSP P P$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *osp-symmetry*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$

shows $A B C OSP Q P$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *osp-transitivity*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$ and

$A B C OSP Q R$

shows $A B C OSP P R$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cop3-tsp--tsp*:

assumes $\neg Col D E F$ and

$Coplanar A B C D$ and

$Coplanar A B C E$ and

$Coplanar A B C F$ and

$A B C TSP P Q$

shows $D E F TSP P Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cop3-osp--osp*:

assumes $\neg Col D E F$ and

$Coplanar A B C D$ and

$Coplanar A B C E$ and

$Coplanar A B C F$ and

$A B C OSP P Q$

shows $D E F OSP P Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ncop-distincts*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C D$

shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge A \neq D \wedge B \neq C \wedge B \neq D \wedge C \neq D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *tsp-distincts*:

assumes $A B C TSP P Q$

shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq P \wedge B \neq P \wedge C \neq P \wedge A \neq Q \wedge B \neq Q \wedge C \neq Q \wedge P \neq Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *osp-distincts*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$

shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq P \wedge B \neq P \wedge C \neq P \wedge A \neq Q \wedge B \neq Q \wedge C \neq Q$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *tsp--ncop1*:

assumes $A B C TSP P Q$

shows $\neg Coplanar A B C P$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *tsp--ncop2*:

assumes $A B C TSP P Q$
shows $\neg Coplanar A B C Q$
<proof>

lemma *osp--ncop1*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$
shows $\neg Coplanar A B C P$
<proof>

lemma *osp--ncop2*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$
shows $\neg Coplanar A B C Q$
<proof>

lemma *tsp--nosp*:

assumes $A B C TSP P Q$
shows $\neg A B C OSP P Q$
<proof>

lemma *osp--ntsp*:

assumes $A B C OSP P Q$
shows $\neg A B C TSP P Q$
<proof>

lemma *osp-bet--osp*:

assumes $A B C OSP P R$ **and**
 $Bet P Q R$
shows $A B C OSP P Q$
<proof>

lemma *l9-18-3*:

assumes $Coplanar A B C P$ **and**
 $Col X Y P$
shows $A B C TSP X Y \longleftrightarrow (Bet X P Y \wedge \neg Coplanar A B C X \wedge \neg Coplanar A B C Y)$
<proof>

lemma *bet-cop--tsp*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C X$ **and**
 $P \neq Y$ **and**
 $Coplanar A B C P$ **and**
 $Bet X P Y$
shows $A B C TSP X Y$
<proof>

lemma *cop-out--osp*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C X$ **and**
 $Coplanar A B C P$ **and**
 $P Out X Y$
shows $A B C OSP X Y$
<proof>

lemma *l9-19-3*:

assumes $Coplanar A B C P$ **and**
 $Col X Y P$
shows $A B C OSP X Y \longleftrightarrow (P Out X Y \wedge \neg Coplanar A B C X)$
<proof>

lemma *cop2-ts--tsp*:

assumes $\neg Coplanar A B C X$ **and** $Coplanar A B C D$ **and**
 $Coplanar A B C E$ **and** $D E TS X Y$
shows $A B C TSP X Y$
<proof>

lemma *cop2-os--osp*:

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C X$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C E$ **and**
 $D E \text{ OS } X Y$
shows $A B C \text{ OSP } X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop3-tsp--ts*:
assumes $D \neq E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } D E X Y$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ TSP } X Y$
shows $D E \text{ TS } X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop3-osp--os*:
assumes $D \neq E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } D E X Y$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ OSP } X Y$
shows $D E \text{ OS } X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-tsp--ex-cop2*:
assumes
 $A B C \text{ TSP } D E$
shows $\exists Q. (\text{Coplanar } A B C Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } D E P Q \wedge P \neq Q)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-osp--ex-cop2*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C P$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ OSP } D E$
shows $\exists Q. \text{Coplanar } A B C Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } D E P Q \wedge P \neq Q$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sac--coplanar*:
assumes $\text{Saccheri } A B C D$
shows $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-sym*:
 $\exists Y. (A B \text{ Perp } X Y \vee X = Y) \wedge (\exists M. \text{Col } A B M \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } X Y)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-image-is-image-spec*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $P' P \text{ Reflect } A B \longleftrightarrow P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-sym1*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists Y. (A B \text{ Perp } X Y \vee X = Y) \wedge (\exists M. \text{Col } A B M \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } X Y \wedge X Y \text{ Reflect } A B)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-2-uniqueness*:
assumes $P1 P \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**
 $P2 P \text{ Reflect } A B$
shows $P1 = P2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-2-uniqueness-spec*:
assumes $P1 P \text{ ReflectL } A B$ **and**
 $P2 P \text{ ReflectL } A B$
shows $P1 = P2$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-2-existence-spec*:

$\exists P'. P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-2-existence*:

$\exists P'. P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-4-spec*:

assumes $P P' \text{ ReflectL } A B$

shows $P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-4*:

assumes $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$

shows $P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-5*:

assumes $P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**

$P'' P' \text{ Reflect } A B$

shows $P = P''$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-6-uniqueness*:

assumes $P P1 \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**

$P P2 \text{ Reflect } A B$

shows $P1 = P2$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-6-uniqueness-spec*:

assumes $P P1 \text{ ReflectL } A B$ **and**

$P P2 \text{ ReflectL } A B$

shows $P1 = P2$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-6-existence-spec*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\exists P. P' P \text{ ReflectL } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-6-existence*:

$\exists P. P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-7*:

assumes $P' P \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**

$Q' Q \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**

$P' = Q'$

shows $P = Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l10-8*:

assumes $P P \text{ Reflect } A B$

shows $\text{Col } P A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col--refl*:

assumes $\text{Col } P A B$

shows $P P \text{ ReflectL } A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-image-col-cong*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B X$
shows $\text{Cong } P X P' X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *is-image-spec-col-cong*:
assumes $P P' \text{ ReflectL } A B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B X$
shows $\text{Cong } P X P' X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *image-id*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B T$ and
 $T T' \text{ Reflect } A B$
shows $T = T'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *osym-not-col*:
assumes $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A B P$
shows $\neg \text{Col } A B P'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-preserves-image*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B M$ and
 $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$ and
 $M \text{ Midpoint } P Q$ and
 $M \text{ Midpoint } P' Q'$
shows $Q Q' \text{ Reflect } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *image-in-is-image-spec*:
assumes $M \text{ ReflectLAt } P P' A B$
shows $P P' \text{ ReflectL } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *image-in-gen-is-image*:
assumes $M \text{ ReflectAt } P P' A B$
shows $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *image-image-in*:
assumes $P \neq P'$ and
 $P P' \text{ ReflectL } A B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B M$ and
 $\text{Col } P M P'$
shows $M \text{ ReflectLAt } P P' A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *image-in-col*:
assumes $Y \text{ ReflectLAt } P P' A B$
shows $\text{Col } P P' Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *is-image-spec-rev*:
assumes $P P' \text{ ReflectL } A B$
shows $P P' \text{ ReflectL } B A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *is-image-rev*:
assumes $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$
shows $P P' \text{ Reflect } B A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-preserves-per*:
assumes $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $M\ Midpoint\ A\ A1$ **and**
 $M\ Midpoint\ B\ B1$ **and**
 $M\ Midpoint\ C\ C1$
shows $Per\ A1\ B1\ C1$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col--image-spec*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ X$
shows $X\ X\ ReflectL\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-triv*:
 $A\ A\ Reflect\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-midpoint--image*:
assumes $Cong\ A\ X\ A\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ Midpoint\ X\ Y$
shows $Y\ X\ Reflect\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-image-spec--eq*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ P$ **and**
 $P\ P'\ ReflectL\ A\ B$
shows $P = P'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-spec-triv*:
 $A\ A\ ReflectL\ B\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-spec--eq*:
assumes $P\ P'\ ReflectL\ A\ A$
shows $P = P'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image--midpoint*:
assumes $P\ P'\ Reflect\ A\ A$
shows $A\ Midpoint\ P'\ P$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *is-image-spec-dec*:
 $A\ B\ ReflectL\ C\ D \vee \neg A\ B\ ReflectL\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l10-14*:
assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $P\ P'\ Reflect\ A\ B$
shows $A\ B\ TS\ P\ P'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l10-15*:
assumes $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $\neg Col\ A\ B\ P$
shows $\exists Q. A\ B\ Perp\ Q\ C \wedge A\ B\ OS\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ex-per-cong*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $X \neq Y$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $\neg Col\ A\ B\ D$

shows $\exists P. \text{Per } P C A \wedge \text{Cong } P C X Y \wedge A B \text{ OS } P D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *exists-cong-per*:
 $\exists C. \text{Per } A B C \wedge \text{Cong } B C X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-per2--col*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C X. (\text{Per } A X C \wedge X \neq C \wedge \text{Per } B X C) \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-col-perp2--col*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X Y P. (\text{Col } A B P \wedge A B \text{ Perp } X P \wedge P A \text{ Perp } Y P) \longrightarrow \text{Col } Y X P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-perp2--col*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall X Y Z A B. (X Y \text{ Perp } A B \wedge X Z \text{ Perp } A B) \longrightarrow \text{Col } X Y Z$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-not-two-sides-one-side-aux*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X Y P X. (A \neq B \wedge P X \neq A \wedge A B \text{ Perp } X P X \wedge \text{Col } A B P X \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Col } X A B \wedge \neg \text{Col } Y A B \wedge \neg A B \text{ TS } X Y) \longrightarrow A B \text{ OS } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-not-two-sides-one-side*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X Y. (\neg \text{Col } X A B \wedge \neg \text{Col } Y A B \wedge \neg A B \text{ TS } X Y) \longrightarrow A B \text{ OS } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-not-one-side-two-sides*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X Y. (\neg \text{Col } X A B \wedge \neg \text{Col } Y A B \wedge \neg A B \text{ OS } X Y) \longrightarrow A B \text{ TS } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-one-or-two-sides*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X Y. (\neg \text{Col } X A B \wedge \neg \text{Col } Y A B) \longrightarrow (A B \text{ TS } X Y \vee A B \text{ OS } X Y)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-all-coplanar*:
assumes *upper-dim-axiom*
shows *all-coplanar-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *all-coplanar-implies-upper-dim*:
assumes *all-coplanar-axiom*
shows *upper-dim-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *all-coplanar-upper-dim*:
shows *all-coplanar-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *upper-dim-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-stab*:
shows $\neg \neg$ *upper-dim-axiom* \longrightarrow *upper-dim-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop--cong-on-bisect*:
assumes *Coplanar* $A B X P$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $A B$ **and**
 M *PerpAt* $A B P M$ **and**
Cong $X A X B$

shows $Col\ M\ P\ X$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-cop-mid-perp--col:*
assumes $Coplanar\ A\ B\ X\ P$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ X\ B\ X$ **and**
 $M\ Midpoint\ A\ B$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ M$
shows $Col\ M\ P\ X$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cop-image-in2--col:*
assumes $Coplanar\ A\ B\ P\ Q$ **and**
 $M\ ReflectLAt\ P\ P'\ A\ B$ **and**
 $M\ ReflectLAt\ Q\ Q'\ A\ B$
shows $Col\ M\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l10-10-spec:*
assumes $P'\ P\ ReflectL\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Q'\ Q\ ReflectL\ A\ B$
shows $Cong\ P\ Q\ P'\ Q'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l10-10:*
assumes $P'\ P\ Reflect\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Q'\ Q\ Reflect\ A\ B$
shows $Cong\ P\ Q\ P'\ Q'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-preserves-bet:*
assumes $A\ A'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ B'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $C\ C'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-gen-preserves-bet:*
assumes $A\ A'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ B'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $C\ C'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-preserves-col:*
assumes $A\ A'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ B'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $C\ C'\ ReflectL\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ A'\ B'\ C'$ $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-gen-preserves-col:*
assumes $A\ A'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ B'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $C\ C'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *image-gen-preserves-ncol:*
assumes $A\ A'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $B\ B'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $C\ C'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $\neg Col\ A\ B\ C$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *image-gen-preserves-inter*:
assumes $A A' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $C C' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $D D' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B I$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D I$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A' B' I'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C' D' I'$
shows $I I' \text{ Reflect } X Y$
(proof)

lemma *intersection-with-image-gen*:
assumes $A A' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A B A'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A' B' C$
shows $\text{Col } C X Y$
(proof)

lemma *image-preserves-midpoint* :
assumes $A A' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $C C' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $A \text{ Midpoint } B C$
shows $A' \text{ Midpoint } B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *image-spec-preserves-per*:
assumes $A A' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $C C' \text{ ReflectL } X Y$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B C$
shows $\text{Per } A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *image-preserves-per*:
assumes $A A' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $C C' \text{ Reflect } X Y$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B C$
shows $\text{Per } A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *l10-12*:
assumes $\text{Per } A B C$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B A' B'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B C B' C'$
shows $\text{Cong } A C A' C'$
(proof)

lemma *l10-16*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A' B' P$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B A' B'$
shows $\exists C'. A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C' \wedge A' B' \text{ OS } P C'$
(proof)

lemma *cong-cop-image--col*:

assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $P P' \text{ Reflect } A B$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } P X P' X$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B P X$
shows $\text{Col } A B X$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-cop-per2-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B X$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B X B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B X Y$
shows $X = Y \vee B \text{ Midpoint } X Y$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-cop-per2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B X$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B X B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B X Y$
shows $X = Y \vee X Y \text{ ReflectL } A B$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-cop-per2-gen*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B X$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B X B Y$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B X Y$
shows $X = Y \vee X Y \text{ Reflect } A B$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *ex-perp-cop*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists Q. A B \text{ Perp } Q C \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B P Q$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *hilbert-s-version-of-pasch-aux*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A I P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } B C P$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } B I C$ **and**
 $B \neq I$ **and**
 $I \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $\exists X. \text{Col } I P X \wedge$
 $((\text{Bet } A X B \wedge A \neq X \wedge X \neq B \wedge A \neq B) \vee (\text{Bet } A X C \wedge A \neq X \wedge X \neq C \wedge A \neq C))$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *hilbert-s-version-of-pasch*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } C Q P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A B P$ **and**
 $\text{BetS } A Q B$
shows $\exists X. \text{Col } P Q X \wedge (\text{BetS } A X C \vee \text{BetS } B X C)$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *two-sides-cases*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } P O A B$ **and**
 $P O P O S A B$
shows $P O A T S P B \vee P O B T S P A$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *not-par-two-sides*:

assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ I$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ I$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists\ X\ Y. Col\ C\ D\ X \wedge Col\ C\ D\ Y \wedge A\ B\ TS\ X\ Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cop-not-par-other-side*:
assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ I$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ I$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$ **and**
 $Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ P$
shows $\exists\ Q. Col\ C\ D\ Q \wedge A\ B\ TS\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cop-not-par-same-side*:
assumes $C \neq D$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ I$ **and**
 $Col\ C\ D\ I$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$ **and**
 $Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ P$
shows $\exists\ Q. Col\ C\ D\ Q \wedge A\ B\ OS\ P\ Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-equiv-defA*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Q\ PerpBisectBis\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-equiv-defB*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisectBis\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-equiv-def*:
shows $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B \longleftrightarrow P\ Q\ PerpBisectBis\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-sym-1*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
shows $Q\ P\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-sym-2*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-sym-3*:
assumes $A\ B\ PerpBisect\ C\ D$
shows $B\ A\ PerpBisect\ D\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-perp*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
shows $P\ Q\ Perp\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-cong-1*:
assumes $P\ Q\ PerpBisect\ A\ B$
shows $Cong\ A\ P\ B\ P$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-cong-2*:
assumes $P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
shows $\text{Cong } A Q B Q$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-cong2*:
assumes $P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
shows $\text{Cong } A P B P \wedge \text{Cong } A Q B Q$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-cong*:
assumes
 $\text{Cong } A pO B pO$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B pO C pO$
shows $\text{Cong } A pO C pO$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-cop-perp-bisect*:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } P Q A B$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A P B P$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A Q B Q$
shows $P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-mid-perp-bisect*:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A P B P$ **and**
 $Q \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-is-on-perp-bisect*:
assumes $P \text{ IsOnPerpBisect } A B$ **and**
 $P \text{ IsOnPerpBisect } B C$
shows $P \text{ IsOnPerpBisect } A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-mid-perp-bisect*:
assumes $C \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $C D \text{ Perp } A B$
shows $C D \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-cop2-perp-bisect-col*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A C D E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } B C D E$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } C D C E$ **and**
 $A B \text{ PerpBisect } D E$
shows $\text{Col } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-cop2-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists P Q. P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C Q$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists P Q. P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bisect-existence-cop*:
assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\exists P Q. P Q \text{ PerpBisect } A B \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C Q$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-3*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$
shows $\exists A' C' D' F'. B \text{ Out } A' A \wedge B \text{ Out } C' C' \wedge$
 $E \text{ Out } D' D \wedge E \text{ Out } F' F' \wedge$
 $A' B C' \text{ Cong } D' E F'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-aux*:

assumes $B \text{ Out } A A'$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } D D'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B A' E D'$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } B A A0$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } E D D0$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A A0 E D$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } D D0 B A$
shows $\text{Cong } B A0 E D0 \wedge \text{Cong } A' A0 D' D0$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-3-bis*:

assumes $\exists A' C' D' F'.$
 $(B \text{ Out } A' A \wedge B \text{ Out } C' C \wedge E \text{ Out } D' D \wedge E \text{ Out } F' F \wedge A' B C' \text{ Cong } D' E F')$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-4-1*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A' A$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C' C$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } D' D$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } F' F$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B A' E D'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B C' E F'$
shows $\text{Cong } A' C' D' F'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-4-2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $F \neq E$ **and**
 $\forall A' C' D' F'. (B \text{ Out } A' A \wedge B \text{ Out } C' C \wedge E \text{ Out } D' D \wedge E \text{ Out } F' F \wedge \text{Cong } B A' E D' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } B C' E F' \rightarrow \text{Cong } A' C' D' F')$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga-refl*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga-sym*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong } A A' B' C'$
shows $A' B' C' \text{ Cong } A A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-10*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A' A$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C' C$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } D' D$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } F' F$

shows $A' B C' \text{ Cong} A D' E F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out2--conga*:
assumes $B \text{ Out } A' A$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C' C$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong3-diff*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$
shows $A' \neq B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong3-diff2*:
assumes $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$
shows $B' \neq C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong3-conga*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong3-conga2*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A'' B'' C''$
shows $A' B' C' \text{ Cong} A'' B'' C''$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-diff1*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
shows $A \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-diff2*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
shows $C \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-diff45*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
shows $A' \neq B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-diff56*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
shows $C' \neq B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-trans*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A' B' C' \text{ Cong} A'' B'' C''$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A'' B'' C''$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-pseudo-refl*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A C B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma conga-trivial-1:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$
shows $A B A \text{ Cong} A C D C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-13:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet D E D'$ **and**
 $D' \neq E$
shows $A' B C \text{ Cong} A D' E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma conga-right-comm:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A F E D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma conga-left-comm:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$
shows $C B A \text{ Cong} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma conga-comm:
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$
shows $C B A \text{ Cong} A F E D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma conga-line:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A' \neq B'$ **and**
 $B' \neq C'$
and $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $Bet A' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-14:
assumes $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet C B C'$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-16:
assumes $Per A B C$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $Per A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A' \neq B'$ **and**
 $C' \neq B'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-17:
assumes $Per A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
shows $Per A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-18-1*:

assumes *Bet C B D* **and**

B ≠ C **and**

B ≠ D **and**

A ≠ B **and**

Per A B C

shows *A B C CongA A B D*

<proof>

lemma *l11-18-2*:

assumes *Bet C B D* **and**

A B C CongA A B D

shows *Per A B C*

<proof>

lemma *cong3-preserves-out*:

assumes *A Out B C* **and**

A B C Cong3 A' B' C'

shows *A' Out B' C'*

<proof>

lemma *l11-21-a*:

assumes *B Out A C* **and**

A B C CongA A' B' C'

shows *B' Out A' C'*

<proof>

lemma *l11-21-b*:

assumes *B Out A C* **and**

B' Out A' C'

shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*

<proof>

lemma *conga-cop--or-out-ts*:

assumes *Coplanar A B C C'* **and**

A B C CongA A B C'

shows *B Out C C' ∨ A B TS C C'*

<proof>

lemma *conga-os--out*:

assumes *A B C CongA A B C'* **and**

A B OS C C'

shows *B Out C C'*

<proof>

lemma *cong2-conga-cong*:

assumes *A B C CongA A' B' C'* **and**

Cong A B A' B' **and**

Cong B C B' C'

shows *Cong A C A' C'*

<proof>

lemma *angle-construction-1*:

assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**

\neg *Col A' B' P*

shows $\exists C'. (A B C CongA A' B' C' \wedge A' B' OS C' P)$

<proof>

lemma *angle-construction-2*:

assumes *A ≠ B* **and**

B ≠ C **and**

\neg *Col A' B' P*

shows $\exists C'. (A B C CongA A' B' C' \wedge (A' B' OS C' P \vee Col A' B' C'))$

<proof>

lemma *ex-conga-ts*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } A' B' P$
shows $\exists C'. A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C' \wedge A' B' \text{ TS } C' P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-15:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } D E P$
shows
 $\exists F. (A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F \wedge E D \text{ OS } F P) \wedge$
 $(\forall F1 F2. ((A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F1 \wedge E D \text{ OS } F1 P) \wedge$
 $(A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F2 \wedge E D \text{ OS } F2 P))$
 $\longrightarrow E \text{ Out } F1 F2)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-19:
assumes $\text{Per } A B P1$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B P2$ **and**
 $A B \text{ OS } P1 P2$
shows $B \text{ Out } P1 P2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-22-bet:
assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $P' B' \text{ TS } A' C'$ **and**
 $A B P \text{ Cong } A' B' P'$ **and**
 $P B C \text{ Cong } A' P' B' C'$
shows $\text{Bet } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-22a:
assumes $B P \text{ TS } A C$ **and**
 $B' P' \text{ TS } A' C'$ **and**
 $A B P \text{ Cong } A' B' P'$ **and**
 $P B C \text{ Cong } A' P' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-22b:
assumes $B P \text{ OS } A C$ **and**
 $B' P' \text{ OS } A' C'$ **and**
 $A B P \text{ Cong } A' B' P'$ **and**
 $P B C \text{ Cong } A' P' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-22:
assumes $((B P \text{ TS } A C \wedge B' P' \text{ TS } A' C') \vee (B P \text{ OS } A C \wedge B' P' \text{ OS } A' C'))$ **and**
 $A B P \text{ Cong } A' B' P'$ **and**
 $P B C \text{ Cong } A' P' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma l11-24:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } C B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma col-in-angle:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $P \neq B$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A P \vee B \text{ Out } C P$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out321--inangle*:
assumes $C \neq B$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A P$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inangle1123*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $A \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out341--inangle*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C P$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inangle3123*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $C \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *in-angle-two-sides*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } B A P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } B C P$ **and**
 $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $P B \text{ TS } A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *in-angle-out*:
assumes $B \text{ Out } A C$ **and**
 $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $B \text{ Out } A P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-in-angle-out*:
assumes $\text{Col } B A P$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $B \text{ Out } A P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-25-aux*:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A' A$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A' B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-25*:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A' A$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C' C$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } P' P$
shows $P' \text{ InAngle } A' B C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inangle-distincts*:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge P \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *segment-construction-0*:
shows $\exists B'. \text{Cong } A' B' A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *angle-construction-3:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$C \neq B$ **and**

$A' \neq B'$

shows $\exists C'. A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-28:*

assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**

$\text{Col } A C D$

shows $\exists D'. (\text{Cong } A D A' D' \wedge \text{Cong } B D B' D' \wedge \text{Cong } C D C' D')$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-conga--bet:*

assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**

$A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$

shows $\text{Bet } A' B' C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *in-angle-one-side:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } B A P$ **and**

$P \text{ InAngle } A B C$

shows $A B \text{ OS } P C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inangle-one-side:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B P$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B Q$ **and**

$P \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and**

$Q \text{ InAngle } A B C$

shows $A B \text{ OS } P Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inangle-one-side2:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B P$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B Q$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } C B P$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } C B Q$ **and**

$P \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and**

$Q \text{ InAngle } A B C$

shows $A B \text{ OS } P Q \wedge C B \text{ OS } P Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-conga-col:*

assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$

shows $\text{Col } D E F$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncol-conga-ncol:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$

shows $\neg \text{Col } D E F$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *angle-construction-4:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$C \neq B$ **and**

$A' \neq B'$

shows $\exists C'. (A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C' \wedge \text{Coplanar } A' B' C' P)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lea-distincts*:

assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } D E F$

shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *l11-29-a*:

assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } D E F$

shows $\exists Q. (C \text{ InAngle } A B Q \wedge A B Q \text{ CongA } D E F)$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *in-angle-line*:

assumes $P \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$C \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A B C$

shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *l11-29-b*:

assumes $\exists Q. (C \text{ InAngle } A B Q \wedge A B Q \text{ CongA } D E F)$

shows $A B C \text{ LeA } D E F$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *bet-in-angle-bet*:

assumes $\text{Bet } A B P$ **and**

$P \text{ InAngle } A B C$

shows $\text{Bet } A B C$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lea-line*:

assumes $\text{Bet } A B P$ **and**

$A B P \text{ LeA } A B C$

shows $\text{Bet } A B C$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *eq-conga-out*:

assumes $A B A \text{ CongA } D E F$

shows $E \text{ Out } D F$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *out-conga-out*:

assumes $B \text{ Out } A C$ **and**

$A B C \text{ CongA } D E F$

shows $E \text{ Out } D F$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *conga-ex-cong3*:

assumes $A B C \text{ CongA } A' B' C'$

shows $\exists AA CC. ((B \text{ Out } A AA \wedge B \text{ Out } C CC) \longrightarrow AA B CC \text{ Cong3 } A' B' C')$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *conga-preserves-in-angle*:

assumes $A B C \text{ CongA } A' B' C'$ **and**

$A B I \text{ CongA } A' B' I'$ **and**

$I \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and** $A' B' \text{ OS } I' C'$

shows $I' \text{ InAngle } A' B' C'$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *l11-30*:

assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } D E F$ **and**

$A B C \text{ CongA } A' B' C'$ **and**

$D E F \text{ CongA } D' E' F'$

shows $A' B' C' \text{ LeA } D' E' F'$

\langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *l11-31-1*:

assumes $B \text{ Out } A \ C$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $F \neq E$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *l11-31-2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $F \neq E$ **and**
 $B \text{ et } D \ E \ F$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *lea-refl*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *conga--lea*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ CongA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *conga--lea456123*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ CongA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $D \ E \ F \ LeA \ A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *lea-left-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $C \ B \ A \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *lea-right-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ F \ E \ D$
<proof>

lemma *lea-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $C \ B \ A \ LeA \ F \ E \ D$
<proof>

lemma *lta-left-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LtA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $C \ B \ A \ LtA \ D \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *lta-right-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LtA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $A \ B \ C \ LtA \ F \ E \ D$
<proof>

lemma *lta-comm*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LtA \ D \ E \ F$
shows $C \ B \ A \ LtA \ F \ E \ D$
<proof>

lemma *lea-out4--lea*:

assumes $A \ B \ C \ LeA \ D \ E \ F$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } A \ A'$ **and**
 $B \text{ Out } C \ C'$ **and**

$E \text{ Out } D D'$ and
 $E \text{ Out } F F'$
shows $A' B C' \text{ LeA } D' E F'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lea121345*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $C \neq D$ and
 $D \neq E$
shows $A B A \text{ LeA } C D E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *inangle--lea*:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $A B P \text{ LeA } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *inangle--lea-1*:
assumes $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $P B C \text{ LeA } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *inangle--lta*:
assumes $\neg \text{ Col } P B C$ and
 $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
shows $A B P \text{ LtA } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *in-angle-trans*:
assumes $C \text{ InAngle } A B D$ and
 $D \text{ InAngle } A B E$
shows $C \text{ InAngle } A B E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lea-trans*:
assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } A1 B1 C1$ and
 $A1 B1 C1 \text{ LeA } A2 B2 C2$
shows $A B C \text{ LeA } A2 B2 C2$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *in-angle-asy*:
assumes $D \text{ InAngle } A B C$ and
 $C \text{ InAngle } A B D$
shows $A B C \text{ CongA } A B D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lea-asy*:
assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } D E F$ and
 $D E F \text{ LeA } A B C$
shows $A B C \text{ CongA } D E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-lta--bet*:
assumes $\text{ Col } X Y Z$ and
 $A B C \text{ LtA } X Y Z$
shows $\text{ Bet } X Y Z$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-lta--out*:
assumes $\text{ Col } A B C$ and
 $A B C \text{ LtA } X Y Z$
shows $B \text{ Out } A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lta-distincts*:

assumes $A B C LtA D E F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E \wedge D \neq F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *gta-distincts*:
assumes $A B C GtA D E F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E \wedge A \neq C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-distincts*:
assumes $Acute A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *obtuse-distincts*:
assumes $Obtuse A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge A \neq C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *two-sides-in-angle*:
assumes $B \neq P'$ **and**
 $B P TS A C$ **and**
 $Bet P B P'$
shows $P InAngle A B C \vee P' InAngle A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *in-angle-reverse*:
assumes $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $C InAngle A B D$
shows $D InAngle A' B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *in-angle-trans2*:
assumes $C InAngle A B D$ **and**
 $D InAngle A B E$
shows $D InAngle C B E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-36-aux1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $D' \neq E$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $Bet D E D'$ **and**
 $A B C LeA D E F$
shows $D' E F LeA A' B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-36-aux2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $D' \neq E$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $Bet D E D'$ **and**
 $D' E F LeA A' B C$
shows $A B C LeA D E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-36*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $D' \neq E$ **and**

Bet A B A' and
Bet D E D'
shows $A B C \text{ Le} A D E F \longleftrightarrow D' E F \text{ Le} A A' B C$
 <proof>

lemma *l11-41-aux:*
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
Bet B A D and
A ≠ D
shows $A C B \text{ Lt} A C A D$
 <proof>

lemma *l11-41:*
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
Bet B A D and
A ≠ D
shows $A C B \text{ Lt} A C A D \wedge A B C \text{ Lt} A C A D$
 <proof>

lemma *not-conga:*
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $\neg A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$
shows $\neg A' B' C' \text{ Cong} A D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *not-conga-sym:*
assumes $\neg A B C \text{ Cong} A D E F$
shows $\neg D E F \text{ Cong} A A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *not-and-lta:*
shows $\neg (A B C \text{ Lt} A D E F \wedge D E F \text{ Lt} A A B C)$
 <proof>

lemma *conga-preserves-lta:*
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Lt} A D E F$
shows $A' B' C' \text{ Lt} A D' E' F'$
 <proof>

lemma *lta-trans:*
assumes $A B C \text{ Lt} A A_1 B_1 C_1$ **and**
 $A_1 B_1 C_1 \text{ Lt} A_2 B_2 C_2$
shows $A B C \text{ Lt} A_2 B_2 C_2$
 <proof>

lemma *obtuse-sym:*
assumes *Obtuse A B C*
shows *Obtuse C B A*
 <proof>

lemma *acute-sym:*
assumes *Acute A B C*
shows *Acute C B A*
 <proof>

lemma *acute-col--out:*
assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
Acute A B C
shows $B \text{ Out } A C$
 <proof>

lemma *col-obtuse--bet:*
assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
Obtuse A B C

shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out--acute*:
assumes $B\ Out\ A\ C$
shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--obtuse*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and** $B \neq C$
shows $Obtuse\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-43-aux*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $Per\ B\ A\ C \vee Obtuse\ B\ A\ C$
shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-43*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $Per\ B\ A\ C \vee Obtuse\ B\ A\ C$
shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C \wedge Acute\ A\ C\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-lea-acute*:
assumes $Acute\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ LeA\ D\ E\ F$
shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lea-obtuse-obtuse*:
assumes $Obtuse\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ LeA\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Obtuse\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-1-a*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ A\ B\ C$
shows $B\ A\ C\ CongA\ B\ C\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-2-a*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B\ A\ Lt\ B\ C$
shows $B\ C\ A\ LtA\ B\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-lta-and-conga*:
 $\neg (A\ B\ C\ LtA\ D\ E\ F \wedge A\ B\ C\ CongA\ D\ E\ F)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *conga-sym-equiv*:
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C' \longleftrightarrow A'\ B'\ C'\ CongA\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *conga-dec*:
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ D\ E\ F \vee \neg\ A\ B\ C\ CongA\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lta-not-conga*:

assumes $A B C LtA D E F$
shows $\neg A B C CongA D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lta--lea*:
assumes $A B C LtA D E F$
shows $A B C LeA D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *nlta*:
 $\neg A B C LtA A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lea--nlta*:
assumes $A B C LeA D E F$
shows $\neg D E F LtA A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lta--nlea*:
assumes $A B C LtA D E F$
shows $\neg D E F LeA A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-1-b*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $B A C CongA B C A$
shows $Cong B A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-2-b*:
assumes $B A C LtA B C A$
shows $B C Lt B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-1*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$
shows $B A C CongA B C A \longleftrightarrow Cong B A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-2*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$
shows $B A C LtA B C A \longleftrightarrow B C Lt B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-44-2bis*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$
shows $B A C LeA B C A \longleftrightarrow B C Le B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-46*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Per A B C \vee Obtuse A B C$
shows $B A Lt A C \wedge B C Lt A C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-47*:
assumes $Per A C B$ **and**
 $H PerpAt C H A B$
shows $Bet A H B \wedge A \neq H \wedge B \neq H$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l11-49*:
assumes $A B C CongA A' B' C'$ **and**
 $Cong B A B' A'$ **and**
 $Cong B C B' C'$

shows $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C' \wedge (A \neq C \longrightarrow (B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ B'\ A'\ C' \wedge B\ C\ A\ Cong\ A\ B'\ C'\ A'))$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-50-1*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ B'\ A'\ C'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C' \wedge Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C' \wedge A\ C\ B\ Cong\ A\ A'\ C'\ B'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-50-2*:

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B\ C\ A\ Cong\ A\ B'\ C'\ A'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$

shows $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C' \wedge Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C' \wedge C\ A\ B\ Cong\ A\ C'\ A'\ B'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-51*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$

shows
 $B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ B'\ A'\ C' \wedge A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ A'\ B'\ C' \wedge B\ C\ A\ Cong\ A\ B'\ C'\ A'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga-distinct*:

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ D\ E\ F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-52*:

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $B\ C\ Le\ A\ C$

shows $Cong\ B\ A\ B'\ A' \wedge B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ B'\ A'\ C' \wedge B\ C\ A\ Cong\ A\ B'\ C'\ A'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-53*:

assumes $Per\ D\ C\ B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ B\ C$

shows $C\ A\ D\ Lt\ A\ C\ B\ D \wedge B\ D\ Lt\ A\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-conga-obtuse--cong-conga2*:

assumes $Obtuse\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ Cong\ A\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$

shows $Cong\ B\ A\ B'\ A' \wedge B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ B'\ A'\ C' \wedge B\ C\ A\ Cong\ A\ B'\ C'\ A'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-per2--cong-conga2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Per\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$ **and**

Cong B C B' C'
shows *Cong B A B' A' \wedge B A C Cong A B' A' C' \wedge B C A Cong A B' C' A'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-per2--cong*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
Cong A C A' C' **and**
Cong B C B' C'
shows *Cong B A B' A'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-per2--cong-3*:
assumes *Per A B C*
Per A' B' C' **and**
Cong A C A' C' **and**
Cong B C B' C'
shows *A B C Cong3 A' B' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-lt-per2--lt*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
Cong A B A' B' **and**
B C Lt B' C'
shows *A C Lt A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-le-per2--le*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
Cong A B A' B' **and**
B C Le B' C'
shows *A C Le A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lt2-per2--lt*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
A B Lt A' B' **and**
B C Lt B' C'
shows *A C Lt A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *le-lt-per2--lt*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
A B Le A' B' **and**
B C Lt B' C'
shows *A C Lt A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *le2-per2--le*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
A B Le A' B' **and**
B C Le B' C'
shows *A C Le A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-lt-per2--lt-1*:
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
Per A' B' C' **and**
A B Lt A' B' **and**
Cong A C A' C'
shows *B' C' Lt B C*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *symmetry-preserves-conga*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and** $C \neq B$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } C C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-57*:
assumes $A A' OS B B'$ **and**
 $Per B A A'$ **and**
 $Per B' A' A$ **and**
 $A A' OS C C'$ **and**
 $Per C A A'$ **and**
 $Per C' A' A$
shows $B A C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop3-orth-at--orth-at*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } D E F$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C F$ **and**
 $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
shows $X \text{ OrthAt } D E F U V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col2-orth-at--orth-at*:
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $\text{Col } P Q U$ **and**
 $\text{Col } P Q V$ **and**
 $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C P Q$
shows $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-orth-at--orth-at*:
assumes $U \neq W$ **and**
 $\text{Col } U V W$ **and**
 $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
shows $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U W$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *orth-at-symmetry*:
assumes $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
shows $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C V U$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *orth-at-distincts*:
assumes $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C \wedge U \neq V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *orth-at-chara*:
 $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C X P \longleftrightarrow$
 $(\neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge X \neq P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C X \wedge (\forall D. (\text{Coplanar } A B C D \longrightarrow \text{Per } D X P)))$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop3-orth--orth*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } D E F$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C E$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C F$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Orth } U V$
shows $D E F \text{ Orth } U V$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col2-orth--orth:*

assumes $U \neq V$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ U$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ V$ **and**

$A\ B\ C\ Orth\ P\ Q$

shows $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ V$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-orth--orth:*

assumes $U \neq W$ **and**

$Col\ U\ V\ W$ **and**

$A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ V$

shows $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ W$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *orth-symmetry:*

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ V$

shows $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ V\ U$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *orth-distincts:*

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ V$

shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C \wedge U \neq V$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-cop-orth--orth-at:*

assumes $A\ B\ C\ Orth\ U\ V$ **and**

$Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ X$ **and**

$Col\ U\ V\ X$

shows $X\ OrthAt\ A\ B\ C\ U\ V$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-60-aux:*

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ P\ A\ Q$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ P\ B\ Q$ **and**

$Cong\ C\ P\ C\ Q$ **and**

$Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $Cong\ D\ P\ D\ Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-60:*

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Per\ A\ D\ P$ **and**

$Per\ B\ D\ P$ **and**

$Per\ C\ D\ P$ **and**

$Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ E$

shows $Per\ E\ D\ P$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-60-bis:*

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$D \neq P$ **and**

$Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**

$Per\ A\ D\ P$ **and**

$Per\ B\ D\ P$ **and**

$Per\ C\ D\ P$

shows $D\ OrthAt\ A\ B\ C\ D\ P$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l11-61:*

assumes $A \neq A'$ **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

Coplanar A A' B B' and
Per B A A' and
Per B' A' A and
Coplanar A A' C C' and
Per C A A' and
Per B A C
shows *Per B' A' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-61-bis:*
assumes *D OrthAt A B C D P and*
D E Perp E Q and
Coplanar A B C E and
Coplanar D E P Q
shows *E OrthAt A B C E Q*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-62-unicity:*
assumes *Coplanar A B C D and*
Coplanar A B C D' and
 $\forall E. \text{Coplanar } A B C E \longrightarrow \text{Per } E D P$ **and**
 $\forall E. \text{Coplanar } A B C E \longrightarrow \text{Per } E D' P$
shows $D = D'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-62-unicity-bis:*
assumes *X OrthAt A B C X U and*
Y OrthAt A B C Y U
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at2--eq:*
assumes *X OrthAt A B C U V and*
Y OrthAt A B C U V
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-cop-orth-at--eq:*
assumes *X OrthAt A B C U V and*
Coplanar A B C Y and
Col U V Y
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at--ncop1:*
assumes $U \neq X$ **and**
X OrthAt A B C U V
shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C U$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at--ncop2:*
assumes $V \neq X$ **and**
X OrthAt A B C U V
shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C V$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at--ncop:*
assumes *X OrthAt A B C X P*
shows $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-62-existence:*
 $\exists D. (\text{Coplanar } A B C D \wedge (\forall E. (\text{Coplanar } A B C E \longrightarrow \text{Per } E D P)))$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-62-existence-bis:*

assumes $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C P$
shows $\exists X. X \text{ OrthAt } A B C X P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-63-aux*:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \text{ OrthAt } A B C E P$
shows $\exists Q. (D E \text{ OS } P Q \wedge A B C \text{ Orth } D Q)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l11-63-existence*:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C P$
shows $\exists Q. A B C \text{ Orth } D Q$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l8-21-3*:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A B C D$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Coplanar } A B C X$
shows
 $\exists P T. (A B C \text{ Orth } D P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C T \wedge \text{Bet } X T P)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *mid2-orth-at2--cong*:

assumes $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C X P$ **and**
 $Y \text{ OrthAt } A B C Y Q$ **and**
 $X \text{ Midpoint } P P'$ **and**
 $Y \text{ Midpoint } Q Q'$
shows $\text{Cong } P Q P' Q'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at2-tsp--ts*:

assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $P \text{ OrthAt } A B C P X$ **and**
 $Q \text{ OrthAt } A B C Q Y$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ TSP } X Y$
shows $P Q \text{ TS } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-dec*:

shows $A B C \text{ Orth } U V \vee \neg A B C \text{ Orth } U V$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orth-at-dec*:

shows $X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V \vee \neg X \text{ OrthAt } A B C U V$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tsp-dec*:

shows $A B C \text{ TSP } X Y \vee \neg A B C \text{ TSP } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *osp-dec*:

shows $A B C \text{ OSP } X Y \vee \neg A B C \text{ OSP } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *ts2--inangle*:

assumes $A C \text{ TS } B P$ **and**
 $B P \text{ TS } A C$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *os-ts--inangle*:

assumes $B P \text{ TS } A C$ **and**
 $B A \text{ OS } C P$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *os2--inangle*:
assumes $B A OS C P$ **and**
 $B C OS A P$
shows $P InAngle A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-conga--acute*:
assumes $Acute A B C$ **and**
 $A B C CongA D E F$
shows $Acute D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-out2--acute*:
assumes $B Out A' A$ **and**
 $B Out C' C$ **and**
 $Acute A B C$
shows $Acute A' B C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *conga-obtuse--obtuse*:
assumes $Obtuse A B C$ **and**
 $A B C CongA D E F$
shows $Obtuse D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *obtuse-out2--obtuse*:
assumes $B Out A' A$ **and**
 $B Out C' C$ **and**
 $Obtuse A B C$
shows $Obtuse A' B C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-lea--bet*:
assumes $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $A B C LeA D E F$
shows $Bet D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-lea--out*:
assumes $E Out D F$ **and**
 $A B C LeA D E F$
shows $B Out A C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet2-lta--lta*:
assumes $A B C LtA D E F$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet D E D'$ **and**
 $D' \neq E$
shows $D' E F LtA A' B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lea123456-lta--lta*:
assumes $A B C LeA D E F$ **and**
 $D E F LtA G H I$
shows $A B C LtA G H I$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lea456789-lta--lta*:
assumes $A B C LtA D E F$ **and**
 $D E F LeA G H I$
shows $A B C LtA G H I$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-per--lta*:

assumes *Acute A B C* **and**

D ≠ E **and**

E ≠ F **and**

Per D E F

shows *A B C LtA D E F*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *obtuse-per--lta*:

assumes *Obtuse A B C* **and**

D ≠ E **and**

E ≠ F **and**

Per D E F

shows *D E F LtA A B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *acute-obtuse--lta*:

assumes *Acute A B C* **and**

Obtuse D E F

shows *A B C LtA D E F*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lea-in-angle*:

assumes *A B P LeA A B C* **and**

A B OS C P

shows *P InAngle A B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *acute-bet--obtuse*:

assumes *Bet A B A'* **and**

A' ≠ B **and**

Acute A B C

shows *Obtuse A' B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-obtuse--acute*:

assumes *Bet A B A'* **and**

A' ≠ B **and**

Obtuse A B C

shows *Acute A' B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *inangle-dec*:

P InAngle A B C $\vee \neg P$ *InAngle A B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lea-dec*:

A B C LeA D E F $\vee \neg A B C$ *LeA D E F*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lta-dec*:

A B C LtA D E F $\vee \neg A B C$ *LtA D E F*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lea-total*:

assumes *A ≠ B* **and**

B ≠ C **and**

D ≠ E **and**

E ≠ F

shows *A B C LeA D E F* $\vee D E F$ *LeA A B C*

⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *or-lta2-conga*:

assumes *A ≠ B* **and**

C ≠ B **and**

$D \neq E$ and
 $F \neq E$
shows $A B C Lt A D E F \vee D E F Lt A A B C \vee A B C Cong A D E F$
 <proof>

lemma angle-partition:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $B \neq C$
shows $Acute A B C \vee Per A B C \vee Obtuse A B C$
 <proof>

lemma acute-chara-1:
assumes $Bet A B A'$ and
 $B \neq A'$ and
 $Acute A B C$
shows $A B C Lt A' B C$
 <proof>

lemma acute-chara-2:
assumes $Bet A B A'$ and
 $A B C Lt A' B C$
shows $Acute A B C$
 <proof>

lemma acute-chara:
assumes $Bet A B A'$ and
 $B \neq A'$
shows $Acute A B C \longleftrightarrow A B C Lt A' B C$
 <proof>

lemma obtuse-chara:
assumes $Bet A B A'$ and
 $B \neq A'$
shows $Obtuse A B C \longleftrightarrow A' B C Lt A A B C$
 <proof>

lemma conga--acute:
assumes $A B C Cong A A C B$
shows $Acute A B C$
 <proof>

lemma cong--acute:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $Cong A B A C$
shows $Acute A B C$
 <proof>

lemma nltA--lea:
assumes $\neg A B C Lt A D E F$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $D \neq E$ and
 $E \neq F$
shows $D E F Le A A B C$
 <proof>

lemma nlea--lta:
assumes $\neg A B C Le A D E F$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $D \neq E$ and
 $E \neq F$
shows $D E F Lt A A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *triangle-strict-inequality*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ B\ D$ **and**

$\neg\ Bet\ A\ B\ C$

shows $A\ C\ Lt\ A\ D$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-inequality*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ D$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ B\ D$

shows $A\ C\ Le\ A\ D$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-strict-inequality-2*:

assumes $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$ **and**

$\neg\ Bet\ A\ B\ C$

shows $A\ C\ Lt\ A'\ C'$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-inequality-2*:

assumes $Bet\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$

shows $A\ C\ Le\ A'\ C'$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-strict-reverse-inequality*:

assumes $A\ Out\ B\ D$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ C\ A\ D$ **and**

$\neg\ A\ Out\ B\ C$

shows $B\ D\ Lt\ B\ C$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-reverse-inequality*:

assumes $A\ Out\ B\ D$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ C\ A\ D$

shows $B\ D\ Le\ B\ C$

<proof>

lemma *os3--lta*:

assumes $A\ B\ OS\ C\ D$ **and**

$B\ C\ OS\ A\ D$ **and**

$A\ C\ OS\ B\ D$

shows $B\ A\ C\ Lt\ A\ B\ D\ C$

<proof>

lemma *bet-le--lt*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ D\ B$ **and**

$A\ \neq\ D$ **and**

$D\ \neq\ B$ **and**

$A\ C\ Le\ B\ C$

shows $D\ C\ Lt\ B\ C$

<proof>

lemma *cong2--ncol*:

assumes $A\ \neq\ B$ **and**

$B\ \neq\ C$ **and**

$A\ \neq\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ P\ B\ P$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ P\ C\ P$

shows $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong4-cop2--eq*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

Cong $A P B P$ **and**

Cong $A P C P$ **and**

Coplanar $A B C P$ **and**

Cong $A Q B Q$ **and**

Cong $A Q C Q$ **and**

Coplanar $A B C Q$

shows $P = Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t18-18-aux*:

assumes *Cong* $A B D E$ **and**

Cong $A C D F$ **and**

$F D E$ *LtA* $C A B$ **and**

\neg *Col* $A B C$ **and**

\neg *Col* $D E F$ **and**

$D F$ *Le* $D E$

shows $E F$ *Lt* $B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t18-18*:

assumes *Cong* $A B D E$ **and**

Cong $A C D F$ **and**

$F D E$ *LtA* $C A B$

shows $E F$ *Lt* $B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t18-19*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

Cong $A B D E$ **and**

Cong $A C D F$ **and**

$E F$ *Lt* $B C$

shows $F D E$ *LtA* $C A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *acute-trivial*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *Acute* $A B A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *acute-not-per*:

assumes *Acute* $A B C$

shows \neg *Per* $A B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *angle-bisector*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$C \neq B$

shows $\exists P. (P$ *InAngle* $A B C \wedge P B A$ *CongA* $P B C)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *reflectl--conga*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq P$ **and**

$P P'$ *ReflectL* $A B$

shows $A B P$ *CongA* $A B P'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-cop-out-reflectl--out*:

assumes $\neg B$ *Out* $A C$ **and**

Coplanar A B C P and
P B A CongA P B C and
B Out A T and
T T' ReflectL B P
shows *B Out C T'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-conga-cop-reflectl--col:*
assumes \neg *B Out A C and*
Coplanar A B C P and
P B A CongA P B C and
Col B A T and
T T' ReflectL B P
shows *Col B C T'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga2-cop2--col:*
assumes \neg *B Out A C and*
P B A CongA P B C and
P' B A CongA P' B C and
Coplanar A B P P' and
Coplanar B C P P'
shows *Col B P P'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga2-cop2--col-1:*
assumes \neg *Col A B C and*
P B A CongA P B C and
P' B A CongA P' B C and
Coplanar A B C P and
Coplanar A B C P'
shows *Col B P P'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-conga--conga:*
assumes *P B A CongA P B C and*
Col B P P' and
B \neq P'
shows *P' B A CongA P' B C*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-inangle--ex-col-inangle:*
assumes \neg *B Out A C and*
P InAngle A B C and
Coplanar A B C Q
shows $\exists R. (R \text{ InAngle } A B C \wedge P \neq R \wedge \text{Col } P Q R)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-inangle2--out:*
assumes \neg *Bet A B C and*
P InAngle A B C and
Q InAngle A B C and
Col B P Q
shows *B Out P Q*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *inangle2--lea:*
assumes *P InAngle A B C and*
Q InAngle A B C
shows *P B Q LeA A B C*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conga-inangle-per--acute:*
assumes *Per A B C and*
P InAngle A B C and
P B A CongA P B C

shows *Acute A B P*
<proof>

lemma *conga-inangle2-per--acute:*
assumes *Per A B C* **and**
P InAngle A B C **and**
P B A CongA P B C **and**
Q InAngle A B C
shows *Acute P B Q*
<proof>

lemma *lta-os--ts:*
assumes
A O1 P LtA A O1 B **and**
O1 A OS B P
shows *O1 P TS A B*
<proof>

lemma *bet--suppa:*
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
B ≠ C **and**
B ≠ A' **and**
Bet A B A'
shows *A B C SuppA C B A'*
<proof>

lemma *ex-suppa:*
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
B ≠ C
shows $\exists D E F. A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
<proof>

lemma *suppa-distincts:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F*
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge D \neq E \wedge E \neq F$
<proof>

lemma *suppa-right-comm:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F*
shows *A B C SuppA F E D*
<proof>

lemma *suppa-left-comm:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F*
shows *C B A SuppA D E F*
<proof>

lemma *suppa-comm:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F*
shows *C B A SuppA F E D*
<proof>

lemma *suppa-sym:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F*
shows *D E F SuppA A B C*
<proof>

lemma *conga2-suppa--suppa:*
assumes *A B C CongA A' B' C'* **and**
D E F CongA D' E' F' **and**
A B C SuppA D E F
shows *A' B' C' SuppA D' E' F'*
<proof>

lemma *suppa2--conga456:*
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F* **and**

$A B C \text{ Supp} A D' E' F'$
shows $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
(proof)

lemma *suppa2--conga123*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$ **and**
 $A' B' C' \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *bet-out--suppa*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } D F$
shows $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
(proof)

lemma *bet-suppa--out*:
assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $E \text{ Out } D F$
(proof)

lemma *out-suppa--bet*:
assumes $B \text{ Out } A C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $\text{Bet } D E F$
(proof)

lemma *per-suppa--per*:
assumes $\text{Per } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $\text{Per } D E F$
(proof)

lemma *per2--suppa*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \neq F$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B C$ **and**
 $\text{Per } D E F$
shows $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
(proof)

lemma *suppa--per*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Supp} A A B C$
shows $\text{Per } A B C$
(proof)

lemma *acute-suppa--obtuse*:
assumes $\text{Acute } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $\text{Obtuse } D E F$
(proof)

lemma *obtuse-suppa--acute*:
assumes $\text{Obtuse } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Supp} A D E F$
shows $\text{Acute } D E F$
(proof)

lemma *lea-suppa2--lea*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Supp} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Supp} A D' E' F'$

$A B C \text{ Le}A D E F$
shows $D' E' F' \text{ Le}A A' B' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lta-suppa2--lta*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Supp}A A' B' C'$
and $D E F \text{ Supp}A D' E' F'$
and $A B C \text{ Lt}A D E F$
shows $D' E' F' \text{ Lt}A A' B' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *suppa-dec*:
 $A B C \text{ Supp}A D E F \vee \neg A B C \text{ Supp}A D E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-one-side-aux*:
assumes $C A \text{ OS} P B$ **and**
 $\text{Acute } A C P$ **and**
 $C A \text{ Perp} B C$
shows $C B \text{ OS} A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-one-side-aux0*:
assumes $\text{Col } A C P$ **and**
 $\text{Acute } A C P$ **and**
 $C A \text{ Perp} B C$
shows $C B \text{ OS} A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-cop-perp--one-side*:
assumes $\text{Acute } A C P$ **and**
 $C A \text{ Perp} B C$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C P$
shows $C B \text{ OS} A P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute--not-obtuse*:
assumes $\text{Acute } A B C$
shows $\neg \text{Obtuse } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *suma-distincts*:
assumes $A B C D E F \text{ Sum}A G H I$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge D \neq E \wedge E \neq F \wedge G \neq H \wedge H \neq I$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *trisuma-distincts*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum}A D E F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C \wedge D \neq E \wedge E \neq F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *ex-suma*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \neq F$
shows $\exists G H I. A B C D E F \text{ Sum}A G H I$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *suma2--conga*:
assumes $A B C D E F \text{ Sum}A G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum}A G' H' I'$
shows $G H I \text{ Cong}A G' H' I'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *suma-sym*:

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$
shows $D E F A B C SumA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *conga3-suma--suma:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $A B C CongA A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F CongA D' E' F'$ **and**
 $G H I CongA G' H' I'$
shows $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
(proof)

lemma *out6-suma--suma:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $B Out A A'$ **and**
 $B Out C C'$ **and**
 $E Out D D'$ **and**
 $E Out F F'$ **and**
 $H Out G G'$ **and**
 $H Out I I'$
shows $A' B C' D' E F' SumA G' H I'$
(proof)

lemma *out546-suma--conga:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $E Out D F$
shows $A B C CongA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *out546--suma:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $E Out D F$
shows $A B C D E F SumA A B C$
(proof)

lemma *out213-suma--conga:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $B Out A C$
shows $D E F CongA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *out213--suma:*

assumes $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \neq F$ **and**
 $B Out A C$
shows $A B C D E F SumA D E F$
(proof)

lemma *suma-left-comm:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$
shows $C B A D E F SumA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *suma-middle-comm:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$
shows $A B C F E D SumA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *suma-right-comm:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$
shows $A B C D E F SumA I H G$
(proof)

lemma *suma-comm:*

assumes $A B C D E F SumA G H I$

shows $C B A F E D \text{ Sum} A I H G$
<proof>

lemma *ts--suma:*
assumes $A B TS C D$
shows $C B A A B D \text{ Sum} A C B D$
<proof>

lemma *ts--suma-1:*
assumes $A B TS C D$
shows $C A B B A D \text{ Sum} A C A D$
<proof>

lemma *inangle--suma:*
assumes $P \text{ InAngle} A B C$
shows $A B P P B C \text{ Sum} A A B C$
<proof>

lemma *bet--suma:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $P \neq B$ **and** $Bet A B C$
shows $A B P P B C \text{ Sum} A A B C$
<proof>

lemma *sams-chara:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B$ **and**
 $Bet A B A'$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F \longleftrightarrow D E F LeA C B A'$
<proof>

lemma *sams-distincts:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge D \neq E \wedge E \neq F$
<proof>

lemma *sams-sym:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $SAMS D E F A B C$
<proof>

lemma *sams-right-comm:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $SAMS A B C F E D$
<proof>

lemma *sams-left-comm:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $SAMS C B A D E F$
<proof>

lemma *sams-comm:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $SAMS C B A F E D$
<proof>

lemma *conga2-sams--sams:*
assumes $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$
<proof>

lemma *out546--sams:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ and
 E Out $D F$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F$
(proof)

lemma *out213--sams*:
assumes $D \neq E$ and
 $E \neq F$ and
 B Out $A C$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F$
(proof)

lemma *bet-suma--sams*:
assumes $A B C D E F$ $SumA G H I$ and
 $Bet G H I$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F$
(proof)

lemma *bet--sams*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $P \neq B$ and
 $Bet A B C$
shows $SAMS A B P P B C$
(proof)

lemma *suppa--sams*:
assumes $A B C$ $SuppA D E F$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F$
(proof)

lemma *os-ts--sams*:
assumes $B P TS A C$ and
 $A B OS P C$
shows $SAMS A B P P B C$
(proof)

lemma *os2--sams*:
assumes $A B OS P C$ and
 $C B OS P A$
shows $SAMS A B P P B C$
(proof)

lemma *inangle--sams*:
assumes P $InAngle A B C$
shows $SAMS A B P P B C$
(proof)

lemma *sams-suma--lea123789*:
assumes $A B C D E F$ $SumA G H I$ and
 $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $A B C LeA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *sams-suma--lea456789*:
assumes $A B C D E F$ $SumA G H I$ and
 $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $D E F LeA G H I$
(proof)

lemma *sams-lea2--sams*:
assumes $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ and
 $A B C LeA A' B' C'$ and
 $D E F LeA D' E' F'$
shows $SAMS A B C D E F$
(proof)

lemma *sams-lea456-suma2--lea:*
assumes $D E F \text{ LeA } D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D' E' F' \text{ SumA } G' H' I'$
shows $G H I \text{ LeA } G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea123-suma2--lea:*
assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D E F \text{ SumA } G' H' I'$
shows $G H I \text{ LeA } G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea2-suma2--lea:*
assumes $A B C \text{ LeA } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ LeA } D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' \text{ SumA } G' H' I'$
shows $G H I \text{ LeA } G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams2-suma2--conga456:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D' E' F' \text{ SumA } G H I$
shows $D E F \text{ CongA } D' E' F'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams2-suma2--conga123:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D E F \text{ SumA } G H I$
shows $A B C \text{ CongA } A' B' C'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma-assoc-1:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ SumA } D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A' B' C' G H I \text{ SumA } K L M$
shows $A B C D' E' F' \text{ SumA } K L M$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma-assoc-2:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ SumA } D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D' E' F' \text{ SumA } K L M$
shows $A' B' C' G H I \text{ SumA } K L M$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma-assoc:*
assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ SumA } A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ SumA } D' E' F'$
shows

$A' B' C' G H I \text{ Sum} A K L M \longleftrightarrow A B C D' E' F' \text{ Sum} A K L M$
(proof)

lemma *sams-assoc-1*:

assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ Sum} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' G H I$
shows $SAMS A B C D' E' F'$
(proof)

lemma *sams-assoc-2*:

assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ Sum} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D' E' F'$
shows $SAMS A' B' C' G H I$
(proof)

lemma *sams-assoc*:

assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS D E F G H I$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F G H I \text{ Sum} A D' E' F'$
shows $(SAMS A' B' C' G H I) \longleftrightarrow (SAMS A B C D' E' F')$
(proof)

lemma *sams-nos--nts*:

assumes $SAMS A B C C B J$ **and**
 $\neg B C OS A J$
shows $\neg A B TS C J$
(proof)

lemma *conga-sams-nos--nts*:

assumes $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $C B J \text{ Cong} A D E F$ **and**
 $\neg B C OS A J$
shows $\neg A B TS C J$
(proof)

lemma *sams-lea2-suma2--conga123*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Le} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Le} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' \text{ Sum} A G H I$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *sams-lea2-suma2--conga456*:

assumes $A B C \text{ Le} A A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Le} A D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' \text{ Sum} A G H I$
shows $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
(proof)

lemma *sams-suma--out213*:

assumes $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A D E F$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $B \text{ Out} A C$
(proof)

lemma *sams-suma--out546*:
assumes $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $A B C$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$
shows $E Out D F$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea-lta123-suma2--lta*:
assumes $A B C$ *LtA* $A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F$ *LeA* $D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $G H I$ *LtA* $G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea-lta456-suma2--lta*:
assumes $A B C$ *LeA* $A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F$ *LtA* $D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $G H I$ *LtA* $G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lta2-suma2--lta*:
assumes $A B C$ *LtA* $A' B' C'$ **and**
 $D E F$ *LtA* $D' E' F'$ **and**
 $SAMS A' B' C' D' E' F'$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $G H I$ *LtA* $G' H' I'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea2-suma2--lea123*:
assumes $D' E' F' LeA D E F$ **and**
 $G H I$ *LeA* $G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $A B C$ *LeA* $A' B' C'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea2-suma2--lea456*:
assumes $A' B' C' LeA A B C$ **and**
 $G H I$ *LeA* $G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $D E F$ *LeA* $D' E' F'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea-lta456-suma2--lta123*:
assumes $D' E' F' LtA D E F$ **and**
 $G H I$ *LeA* $G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $A B C$ *LtA* $A' B' C'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sams-lea-lta123-suma2--lta456*:
assumes $A' B' C' LtA A B C$ **and**
 $G H I$ *LeA* $G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F$ *SumA* $G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$

shows $D E F LtA D' E' F'$
<proof>

lemma *sams-lea-lta789-suma2--lta123*:
assumes $D' E' F' LeA D E F$ **and**
 $G H I LtA G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $A B C LtA A' B' C'$
<proof>

lemma *sams-lea-lta789-suma2--lta456*:
assumes $A' B' C' LeA A B C$ **and**
 $G H I LtA G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $D E F LtA D' E' F'$
<proof>

lemma *sams-lta2-suma2--lta123*:
assumes $D' E' F' LtA D E F$ **and**
 $G H I LtA G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $A B C LtA A' B' C'$
<proof>

lemma *sams-lta2-suma2--lta456*:
assumes $A' B' C' LtA A B C$ **and**
 $G H I LtA G' H' I'$ **and**
 $SAMS A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F SumA G H I$ **and**
 $A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G' H' I'$
shows $D E F LtA D' E' F'$
<proof>

lemma *sams123231*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $SAMS A B C B C A$
<proof>

lemma *col-suma--col*:
assumes $Col D E F$ **and**
 $A B C B C A SumA D E F$
shows $Col A B C$
<proof>

lemma *ncol-suma--ncol*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $A B C B C A SumA D E F$
shows $\neg Col D E F$
<proof>

lemma *per2-suma--bet*:
assumes $Per A B C$ **and**
 $Per D E F$ **and**
 $A B C D E F SumA G H I$
shows $Bet G H I$
<proof>

lemma *bet-per2--suma*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \neq F$ **and**
 $G \neq H$ **and**
 $H \neq I$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Per\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Bet\ G\ H\ I$
shows $A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F\ SumA\ G\ H\ I$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *per2--sams*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $E \neq F$ **and**
 $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Per\ D\ E\ F$
shows $SAMS\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-per-suma--per456*:
assumes $Per\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F\ SumA\ G\ H\ I$
shows $Per\ D\ E\ F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-per-suma--per123*:
assumes $Per\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Bet\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F\ SumA\ G\ H\ I$
shows $Per\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-suma--per*:
assumes $Bet\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ A\ B\ C\ SumA\ D\ E\ F$
shows $Per\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute--sams*:
assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$
shows $SAMS\ A\ B\ C\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-suma--nbet*:
assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ A\ B\ C\ SumA\ D\ E\ F$
shows $\neg\ Bet\ D\ E\ F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute2--sams*:
assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Acute\ D\ E\ F$
shows $SAMS\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute2-suma--nbet-a*:
assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ LeA\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F\ SumA\ G\ H\ I$
shows $\neg\ Bet\ G\ H\ I$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute2-suma--nbt:*
assumes *Acute A B C and*
Acute D E F and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows \neg *Bet G H I*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-per--sams:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per A B C and
Acute D E F
shows *SAMS A B C D E F*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-per-suma--nbt:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per A B C and
Acute D E F and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows \neg *Bet G H I*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *obtuse--nsams:*
assumes *Obtuse A B C*
shows \neg *SAMS A B C A B C*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *nbt-sams-suma--acute:*
assumes \neg *Bet D E F and*
SAMS A B C A B C and
A B C A B C SumA D E F
shows *Acute A B C*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *nsams--obtuse:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 \neg *SAMS A B C A B C*
shows *Obtuse A B C*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sams2-suma2--conga:*
assumes *SAMS A B C A B C and*
A B C A B C SumA D E F and
SAMS A' B' C' A' B' C' and
A' B' C' A' B' C' SumA D E F
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute2-suma2--conga:*
assumes *Acute A B C and*
A B C A B C SumA D E F and
Acute A' B' C' and
A' B' C' A' B' C' SumA D E F
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet2-suma--out:*
assumes *Bet A B C and*
Bet D E F and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows *H Out G I*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *col2-suma--col*:
assumes *Col A B C and*
Col D E F and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows *Col G H I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma-suppa--bet*:
assumes *A B C SuppA D E F and*
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows *Bet G H I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-suppa--suma*:
assumes *G ≠ H and*
H ≠ I and
A B C SuppA D E F and
Bet G H I
shows *A B C D E F SumA G H I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-suma--suppa*:
assumes *A B C D E F SumA G H I and*
Bet G H I
shows *A B C SuppA D E F*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet2-suma--suma*:
assumes *A' ≠ B and*
D' ≠ E and
Bet A B A' and
Bet D E D' and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows *A' B C D' E F SumA G H I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma-suppa2--suma*:
assumes *A B C SuppA A' B' C' and*
D E F SuppA D' E' F' and
A B C D E F SumA G H I
shows *A' B' C' D' E' F' SumA G H I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma2-obtuse2--conga*:
assumes *Obtuse A B C and*
A B C A B C SumA D E F and
Obtuse A' B' C' and
A' B' C' A' B' C' SumA D E F
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-suma2--or-conga*:
assumes *A0 ≠ B and*
Bet A B A0 and
A B C A B C SumA D E F and
A' B' C' A' B' C' SumA D E F
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C' ∨ A0 B C CongA A' B' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *suma2--or-conga-suppa*:
assumes *A B C A B C SumA D E F and*
A' B' C' A' B' C' SumA D E F
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C' ∨ A B C SuppA A' B' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *ex-trisuma*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$
shows $\exists D E F. A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-perm-231*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
shows $B C A \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-perm-312*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
shows $C A B \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-perm-321*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
shows $C B A \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-perm-213*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
shows $B A C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-perm-132*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
shows $A C B \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-trisuma--trisuma*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
shows $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D' E' F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma2--conga*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D' E' F'$
shows $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga3-trisuma--trisuma*:
assumes $A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**
 $B C A \text{ Cong} A' B' C' A'$ **and**
 $C A B \text{ Cong} A' C' A' B'$
shows $A' B' C' \text{ TriSum} A D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-trisuma--bet*:
assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ TriSum} A P Q R$
shows $\text{Bet } P Q R$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *suma-dec*:
 $A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A G H I \vee \neg A B C D E F \text{ Sum} A G H I$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sams-dec*:
 $\text{SAMS } A B C D E F \vee \neg \text{SAMS } A B C D E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *trisuma-dec*:

$A B C \text{ TriSum} A P Q R \vee \neg A B C \text{ TriSum} A P Q R$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *acute-not-bet*:
assumes *Acute A B C*
shows $\neg \text{Bet } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-3-stab*:
assumes $\neg \neg \text{upper-dim-3-axiom}$
shows *upper-dim-3-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *median-planes-implies-upper-dim*:
assumes *median-planes-axiom*
shows *upper-dim-3-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *median-planes-aux*:
assumes $\forall A B C P Q M. P \neq Q \wedge \text{Cong } A P A Q \wedge \text{Cong } B P B Q \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } C P C Q \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } P Q \longrightarrow \text{Coplanar } M A B C$
shows *median-planes-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-aux-1*:
assumes *orthonormal-family-axiom*
shows $\forall A B X P Q. \neg \text{Col } P Q X \wedge \text{Per } A X P \wedge \text{Per } A X Q \wedge \text{Per } B X P \wedge \text{Per } B X Q \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-aux-2*:
assumes $\forall A B X P Q. \neg \text{Col } P Q X \wedge \text{Per } A X P \wedge \text{Per } A X Q \wedge$
 $\text{Per } B X P \wedge \text{Per } B X Q \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B X$
shows *orthonormal-family-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-aux*:
shows *orthonormal-family-axiom* \longleftrightarrow
 $(\forall A B X P Q. \neg \text{Col } P Q X \wedge \text{Per } A X P \wedge \text{Per } A X Q \wedge \text{Per } B X P \wedge \text{Per } B X Q \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B X)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim-implies-orthonormal-family-axiom*:
assumes *upper-dim-3-axiom*
shows *orthonormal-family-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-axiom-implies-orth-at2--col*:
assumes *orthonormal-family-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C P Q X. X \text{ OrthAt } A B C X P \wedge X \text{ OrthAt } A B C X Q \longrightarrow \text{Col } P Q X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-axiom-implies-not-two-sides-one-side*:
assumes *orthonormal-family-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C X Y. \neg \text{Coplanar } A B C X \wedge \neg \text{Coplanar } A B C Y \wedge$
 $\neg A B C \text{ TSP } X Y \longrightarrow A B C \text{ OSP } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *orthonormal-family-axiom-implies-space-separation*:
assumes *orthonormal-family-axiom*
shows *space-separation-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *space-separation-implies-plane-intersection*:
assumes *space-separation-axiom*
shows *plane-intersection-axiom*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *plane-intersection-implies-space-separation:*

assumes *plane-intersection-axiom*

shows *space-separation-axiom*

<proof>

lemma *space-separation-implies-median-planes:*

assumes *space-separation-axiom*

shows *median-planes-axiom*

<proof>

theorem *upper-dim-3-equivalent-axioms:*

shows (*upper-dim-3-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *orthonormal-family-axiom*) \wedge

(*orthonormal-family-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *space-separation-axiom*) \wedge

(*space-separation-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *plane-intersection-axiom*) \wedge

(*plane-intersection-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *median-planes-axiom*)

<proof>

lemma *par-reflexivity:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $A B \text{ Par } A B$

<proof>

lemma *par-strict-irreflexivity:*

$\neg A B \text{ ParStrict } A B$

<proof>

lemma *not-par-strict-id:*

$\neg A B \text{ ParStrict } A C$

<proof>

lemma *par-id:*

assumes $A B \text{ Par } A C$

shows $\text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *par-strict-not-col-1:*

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *par-strict-not-col-2:*

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$

shows $\neg \text{Col } B C D$

<proof>

lemma *par-strict-not-col-3:*

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$

shows $\neg \text{Col } C D A$

<proof>

lemma *par-strict-not-col-4:*

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A B D$

<proof>

lemma *par-id-1:*

assumes $A B \text{ Par } A C$

shows $\text{Col } B A C$

<proof>

lemma *par-id-2:*

assumes $A B \text{ Par } A C$

shows $\text{Col } B C A$

<proof>

lemma *par-id-3:*

assumes $A B Par A C$
shows $Col A C B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-id-4*:
assumes $A B Par A C$
shows $Col C B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-id-5*:
assumes $A B Par A C$
shows $Col C A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-symmetry*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $C D ParStrict A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-symmetry*:
assumes $A B Par C D$
shows $C D Par A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-left-comm*:
assumes $A B Par C D$
shows $B A Par C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-right-comm*:
assumes $A B Par C D$
shows $A B Par D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-comm*:
assumes $A B Par C D$
shows $B A Par D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-left-comm*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $B A ParStrict C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-right-comm*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $A B ParStrict D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-comm*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $B A ParStrict D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-neq1*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $A \neq B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-neq2*:
assumes $A B ParStrict C D$
shows $C \neq D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-neq1*:
assumes $A B Par C D$

shows $A \neq B$
<proof>

lemma *par-neg2*:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $C \neq D$
<proof>

lemma *Par-cases*:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D \vee B A \text{ Par } C D \vee A B \text{ Par } D C \vee B A \text{ Par } D C \vee$
 $C D \text{ Par } A B \vee C D \text{ Par } B A \vee D C \text{ Par } A B \vee D C \text{ Par } B A$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
<proof>

lemma *Par-perm*:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge B A \text{ Par } C D \wedge A B \text{ Par } D C \wedge B A \text{ Par } D C \wedge$
 $C D \text{ Par } A B \wedge C D \text{ Par } B A \wedge D C \text{ Par } A B \wedge D C \text{ Par } B A$
<proof>

lemma *Par-strict-cases*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D \vee B A \text{ ParStrict } C D \vee A B \text{ ParStrict } D C \vee$
 $B A \text{ ParStrict } D C \vee C D \text{ ParStrict } A B \vee C D \text{ ParStrict } B A \vee$
 $D C \text{ ParStrict } A B \vee D C \text{ ParStrict } B A$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
<proof>

lemma *Par-strict-perm*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D \wedge B A \text{ ParStrict } C D \wedge A B \text{ ParStrict } D C \wedge$
 $B A \text{ ParStrict } D C \wedge C D \text{ ParStrict } A B \wedge C D \text{ ParStrict } B A \wedge$
 $D C \text{ ParStrict } A B \wedge D C \text{ ParStrict } B A$
<proof>

lemma *l12-6*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
shows $A B \text{ OS } C D$
<proof>

lemma *pars--os3412*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
shows $C D \text{ OS } A B$
<proof>

lemma *perp-dec*:
 $A B \text{ Perp } C D \vee \neg A B \text{ Perp } C D$
<proof>

lemma *col-cop2-perp2--col*:
assumes $X1 X2 \text{ Perp } A B$ **and**
 $Y1 Y2 \text{ Perp } A B$ **and**
 $\text{Col } X1 Y1 Y2$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B X2 Y1$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B X2 Y2$
shows $\text{Col } X2 Y1 Y2$
<proof>

lemma *col-perp2-ncol-col*:
assumes $X1 X2 \text{ Perp } A B$ **and**
 $Y1 Y2 \text{ Perp } A B$ **and**
 $\text{Col } X1 Y1 Y2$ **and**
 $\neg \text{Col } X1 A B$
shows $\text{Col } X2 Y1 Y2$
<proof>

lemma *l12-9*:

assumes

Coplanar C1 C2 A1 B1 and

Coplanar C1 C2 A1 B2 and

Coplanar C1 C2 A2 B1 and

Coplanar C1 C2 A2 B2 and

A1 A2 Perp C1 C2 and

B1 B2 Perp C1 C2

shows *A1 A2 Par B1 B2*

<proof>

lemma *parallel-existence:*

assumes *A ≠ B*

shows $\exists C D. C \neq D \wedge A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge \text{Col } P C D$

<proof>

lemma *par-col-par:*

assumes *C ≠ D' and*

A B Par C D and

Col C D D'

shows *A B Par C D'*

<proof>

lemma *parallel-existence1:*

assumes *A ≠ B*

shows $\exists Q. A B \text{ Par } P Q$

<proof>

lemma *par-not-col:*

assumes *A B ParStrict C D and*

Col X A B

shows $\neg \text{Col } X C D$

<proof>

lemma *not-strict-par1:*

assumes *A B Par C D and*

Col A B X and

Col C D X

shows *Col A B C*

<proof>

lemma *not-strict-par2:*

assumes *A B Par C D and*

Col A B X and

Col C D X

shows *Col A B D*

<proof>

lemma *not-strict-par:*

assumes *A B Par C D and*

Col A B X and

Col C D X

shows $\text{Col } A B C \wedge \text{Col } A B D$

<proof>

lemma *not-par-not-col:*

assumes *A ≠ B and*

A ≠ C and

$\neg A B \text{ Par } A C$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *not-par-inter-uniqueness:*

assumes *A ≠ B and*

C ≠ D and

$\neg A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

Col A B X and

$Col\ C\ D\ X$ and
 $Col\ A\ B\ Y$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ Y$
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *inter-uniqueness-not-par*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ and
 $Col\ A\ B\ P$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ P$
shows $\neg\ A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-not-col-not-par*:
assumes $\exists\ P.\ Col\ A\ B\ P \wedge Col\ C\ D\ P$ and
 $\exists\ Q.\ Col\ C\ D\ Q \wedge \neg\ Col\ A\ B\ Q$
shows $\neg\ A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *par-distincts*:
assumes $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$
shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D \wedge A \neq B \wedge C \neq D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *par-not-col-strict*:
assumes $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ P$ and
 $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$
shows $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-cop-perp2--pars*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ P$ and
 $Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ D$ and
 $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ Q$ and
 $C\ D\ Perp\ P\ Q$
shows $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *all-one-side-par-strict*:
assumes $C \neq D$ and
 $\forall\ P.\ Col\ C\ D\ P \longrightarrow A\ B\ OS\ C\ P$
shows $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *par-col-par-2*:
assumes $A \neq P$ and
 $Col\ A\ B\ P$ and
 $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$
shows $A\ P\ Par\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *par-col2-par*:
assumes $E \neq F$ and
 $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ E$ and
 $Col\ C\ D\ F$
shows $A\ B\ Par\ E\ F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *par-col2-par-bis*:
assumes $E \neq F$ and
 $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$ and
 $Col\ E\ F\ C$ and
 $Col\ E\ F\ D$

shows $A B \text{ Par } E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-col-par-strict*:
assumes $C \neq E$ **and**
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D E$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } C E$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-col2-par-strict*:
assumes $E \neq F$ **and**
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D E$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D F$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } E F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *line-dec*:
 $(\text{Col } C1 B1 B2 \wedge \text{Col } C2 B1 B2) \vee \neg (\text{Col } C1 B1 B2 \wedge \text{Col } C2 B1 B2)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-distinct*:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-col4--par*:
assumes $E \neq F$ **and**
 $G \neq H$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B E$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B F$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D G$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D H$
shows $E F \text{ Par } G H$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-col4--par-strict*:
assumes $E \neq F$ **and**
 $G \neq H$ **and**
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B E$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B F$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D G$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D H$
shows $E F \text{ ParStrict } G H$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-one-side*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Col } C D P$
shows $A B \text{ OS } C P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-all-one-side*:
assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
shows $\forall P. \text{Col } C D P \longrightarrow A B \text{ OS } C P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-trivial*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B X$
shows $X \text{ Inter } A X B X$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-sym*:

assumes $X \text{ Inter } A B C D$
shows $X \text{ Inter } C D A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-left-comm*:
assumes $X \text{ Inter } A B C D$
shows $X \text{ Inter } B A C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-right-comm*:
assumes $X \text{ Inter } A B C D$
shows $X \text{ Inter } A B D C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-comm*:
assumes $X \text{ Inter } A B C D$
shows $X \text{ Inter } B A D C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l12-17*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $P \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $P \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l12-18-a*:
assumes $Cong A B C D$ **and**
 $Cong B C D A$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $Col A P C$ **and**
 $Col B P D$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l12-18-b*:
assumes $Cong A B C D$ **and**
 $Cong B C D A$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $Col A P C$ **and**
 $Col B P D$
shows $B C \text{ Par } D A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l12-18-c*:
assumes $Cong A B C D$ **and**
 $Cong B C D A$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $Col A P C$ **and**
 $Col B P D$
shows $B D \text{ TS } A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l12-18-d*:
assumes $Cong A B C D$ **and**
 $Cong B C D A$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $Col A P C$ **and**
 $Col B P D$
shows $A C \text{ TS } B D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l12-18:*

assumes $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**

$Cong\ B\ C\ D\ A$ **and**

$\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$B \neq D$ **and**

$Col\ A\ P\ C$ **and**

$Col\ B\ P\ D$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D \wedge B\ C\ Par\ D\ A \wedge B\ D\ TS\ A\ C \wedge A\ C\ TS\ B\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-two-sides-two-sides:*

assumes $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$ **and**

$B\ D\ TS\ A\ C$

shows $A\ C\ TS\ B\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-one-or-two-sides:*

assumes $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$

shows $(A\ C\ TS\ B\ D \wedge B\ D\ TS\ A\ C) \vee (A\ C\ OS\ B\ D \wedge B\ D\ OS\ A\ C)$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l12-21-b:*

assumes $A\ C\ TS\ B\ D$ **and**

$B\ A\ C\ CongA\ D\ C\ A$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l12-22-aux:*

assumes $P \neq A$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

$Bet\ P\ A\ C$ **and**

$P\ A\ OS\ B\ D$ **and**

$B\ A\ P\ CongA\ D\ C\ P$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l12-22-b:*

assumes $P\ Out\ A\ C$ **and**

$P\ A\ OS\ B\ D$ **and**

$B\ A\ P\ CongA\ D\ C\ P$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-par:*

assumes $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-distinct:*

assumes $A\ B\ ParStrict\ C\ D$

shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-par:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ C$

shows $A\ B\ Par\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-col-perp--out:*

assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Col\ B\ C\ A'$ **and**

$B\ C\ Perp\ A\ A'$

shows $B \text{ Out } A' C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *acute-col-perp--out-1*:
assumes $\text{Acute } A B C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B C A'$ **and**
 $B A \text{ Perp } A A'$
shows $B \text{ Out } A' C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-inangle-per2--inangle*:
assumes $\text{Per } A B C$ **and**
 $T \text{ InAngle } A B C$ **and**
 $P B A \text{ CongA } P B C$ **and**
 $\text{Per } B P T$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C P$
shows $P \text{ InAngle } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-not-par*:
assumes $A B \text{ Perp } X Y$
shows $\neg A B \text{ Par } X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-conga-perp*:
assumes $B P \text{ TS } A C$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B C B$ **and**
 $A B P \text{ CongA } C B P$
shows $A C \text{ Perp } B P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-inter-exists*:
assumes $A B \text{ Perp } C D$
shows $\exists P. \text{Col } A B P \wedge \text{Col } C D P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-inter-perp-in*:
assumes $A B \text{ Perp } C D$
shows $\exists P. \text{Col } A B P \wedge \text{Col } C D P \wedge P \text{ PerpAt } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-npars--inter-exists*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A1 B1 A2 B2$ **and**
 $\neg A1 B1 \text{ ParStrict } A2 B2$
shows $\exists X. \text{Col } X A1 B1 \wedge \text{Col } X A2 B2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-npar--inter-exists*:
assumes $\text{Coplanar } A1 B1 A2 B2$ **and**
 $\neg A1 B1 \text{ Par } A2 B2$
shows $\exists X. \text{Col } X A1 B1 \wedge \text{Col } X A2 B2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-npar--inter*:
assumes $A1 \neq B1$ **and**
 $A2 \neq B2$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A1 B1 A2 B2$ **and**
 $\neg A1 B1 \text{ Par } A2 B2$
shows $\exists X. X \text{ Inter } A1 B1 A2 B2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter--npar*:
assumes $X \text{ Inter } A1 A2 B1 B2$
shows $\neg A1 A2 \text{ Par } B1 B2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-identity-inv*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\neg \text{Cong } A B C C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-midpoint-col*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B B'$
shows $A' \neq B' \wedge \text{Col } A A' B' \wedge \text{Col } B A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-par-strict*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B B'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet3-cong3-bet*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $A \neq D$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } D A C$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A C B$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } D C D'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A D B C$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } D C C D'$
shows $\text{Bet } C B D'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-double-bet*:
assumes $B' \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $C' \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A B' C'$
shows $\text{Bet } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-half-bet*:
assumes $\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**
 $B' \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $C' \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $\text{Bet } A B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-preserves-bet*:
assumes $B' \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $C' \text{ Midpoint } A C$
shows $\text{Bet } A B C \longleftrightarrow \text{Bet } A B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *symmetry-preseves-bet1*:
assumes $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } M A B$
shows $\text{Bet } M A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *symmetry-preseves-bet2*:
assumes $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } M A' B'$
shows $\text{Bet } M A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *symmetry-preserves-bet*:

assumes $M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$

shows $\text{Bet } M A' B' \longleftrightarrow \text{Bet } M A B$

<proof>

lemma *bet-cong-bet*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A B D$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A C B D$

shows $\text{Bet } B C D$

<proof>

lemma *col-cong-mid* :

assumes $A B \text{ Par } A' B'$ **and**

$\neg A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$

shows $\exists M. ((M \text{ Midpoint } A A' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B B') \vee$
 $(M \text{ Midpoint } A B' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B A'))$

<proof>

lemma *mid-par-cong1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$

shows $\text{Cong } A B A' B' \wedge A B \text{ Par } A' B'$

<proof>

lemma *mid-par-cong2*:

assumes $A \neq B'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$

shows $\text{Cong } A B' A' B \wedge A B' \text{ Par } A' B$

<proof>

lemma *mid-par-cong*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq B'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } A A'$ **and**

$M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$

shows $\text{Cong } A B A' B' \wedge \text{Cong } A B' A' B \wedge A B \text{ Par } A' B' \wedge A B' \text{ Par } A' B$

<proof>

lemma *Parallelogram-strict-Parallelogram*:

assumes $\text{ParallelogramStrict } A B C D$

shows $\text{Parallelogram } A B C D$

<proof>

lemma *plgf-permut*:

assumes $\text{ParallelogramFlat } A B C D$

shows $\text{ParallelogramFlat } B C D A$

<proof>

lemma *plgf-sym*:

assumes $\text{ParallelogramFlat } A B C D$

shows $\text{ParallelogramFlat } C D A B$

<proof>

lemma *plgf-irreflexive*:

shows $\neg \text{ParallelogramFlat } A B A B$

<proof>

lemma *plgs-irreflexive*:

shows $\neg \text{ParallelogramStrict } A B A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-irreflexive*:

shows $\neg \text{Parallelogram } A B A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgf-mid*:

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
shows $\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A C \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plgs*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plgf-aux*:

assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plgf-1*:

assumes $A \neq C$

 $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plgf-2*:

assumes $B \neq D$
 $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plgf*:

assumes $A \neq C \vee B \neq D$
 $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *mid-plg*:

assumes $A \neq C \vee B \neq D$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-cong-uniqueness*:

assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } C D$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B C D$
shows $A = C \wedge B = D \vee A = D \wedge B = C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgf-not-comm1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramFlat* $A B D C$
<proof>

lemma *plgf-not-comm2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramFlat* $B A C D$
<proof>

lemma *plgf-not-comm*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramFlat* $A B D C \wedge \neg$ *ParallelogramFlat* $B A C D$
<proof>

lemma *plgf-cong*:
assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$
shows *Cong* $A B C D \wedge$ *Cong* $A D B C$
<proof>

lemma *plg-to-parallelogram*:
assumes *Plg* $A B C D$
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-one-side*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows $A B OS C D \wedge C D OS A B$
<proof>

lemma *parallelogram-strict-not-col*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *Col* $A B C$
<proof>

lemma *parallelogram-strict-not-col-2*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *Col* $B C D$
<proof>

lemma *parallelogram-strict-not-col-3*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *Col* $C D A$
<proof>

lemma *parallelogram-strict-not-col-4*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *Col* $A B D$
<proof>

lemma *plgs--pars*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows $A B$ *ParStrict* $C D$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-sym*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows *ParallelogramStrict* $C D A B$
<proof>

lemma *plg-sym*:
assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
shows *Parallelogram* $C D A B$

<proof>

lemma *Rhombus-Plg:*

assumes *Rhombus A B C D*

shows *Plg A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *Rectangle-Plg:*

assumes *Rectangle A B C D*

shows *Plg A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *Rectangle-Parallelogram:*

assumes *Rectangle A B C D*

shows *Parallelogram A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *plg-cong-rectangle:*

assumes *Plg A B C D and*

Cong A C B D

shows *Rectangle A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *plg-trivial:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *Parallelogram A B B A*

<proof>

lemma *plg-trivial1:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *Parallelogram A A B B*

<proof>

lemma *col-not-plgs:*

assumes *Col A B C*

shows \neg *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *plg-col-plgf:*

assumes *Col A B C and*

Parallelogram A B C D

shows *ParallelogramFlat A B C D*

<proof>

lemma *plg-bet1:*

assumes *Parallelogram A B C D and*

Bet A C B

shows *Bet D A C*

<proof>

lemma *plgf-trivial1:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *ParallelogramFlat A B B A*

<proof>

lemma *plgf-trivial2:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *ParallelogramFlat A A B B*

<proof>

lemma *plgf-not-point:*

assumes *ParallelogramFlat A A B B*

shows $A \neq B$

<proof>

lemma *plgf-trivial-neq:*

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A A C D$
shows $C = D \wedge A \neq C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgf-trivial-trans*:
assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A A B B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat $B B C C$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A A C C \vee A = C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgf-trivial*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B B A$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgf3-mid*:
assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B A C$
shows *A Midpoint* $B C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cong3-id*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Col $A B C$ **and**
Col $A B D$ **and**
Cong $A B C D$ **and**
Cong $A D B C$ **and**
Cong $A C B D$
shows $A = D \wedge B = C \vee A = C \wedge B = D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *col-cong-mid1*:
assumes $A \neq D$ **and**
Col $A B C$ **and**
Col $A B D$ **and**
Cong $A B C D$ **and**
Cong $A C B D$
shows $\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A D \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *col-cong-mid2*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
Col $A B C$ **and**
Col $A B D$ **and**
Cong $A B C D$ **and**
Cong $A D B C$
shows $\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A C \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgs-not-col*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge \neg \text{Col } B C D \wedge \neg \text{Col } C D A \wedge \neg \text{Col } A B D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *not-col-sym-not-col*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
A Midpoint $B B'$
shows $\neg \text{Col } A B' C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plg-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists D. \text{Parallelogram } A B C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgs-diff*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$

shows *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D \wedge A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge C \neq D \wedge D \neq A \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq D$
<proof>

lemma *sym-par*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $A A'$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $B B'$
shows $A B$ *Par* $A' B'$
<proof>

lemma *symmetry-preserves-two-sides*:
assumes Col $X Y M$ **and**
 $X Y$ *TS* $A B$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $A A'$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $B B'$
shows $X Y$ *TS* $A' B'$
<proof>

lemma *symmetry-preserves-one-side*:
assumes Col $X Y M$ **and**
 $X Y$ *OS* $A B$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $A A'$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $B B'$
shows $X Y$ *OS* $A' B'$
<proof>

lemma *plgf-bet*:
assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B B' A'$
shows Bet $A' B' A \wedge Bet$ $B' A B$
 $\vee Bet$ $A' A B' \wedge Bet$ $A B' B$
 $\vee Bet$ $A A' B \wedge Bet$ $A' B B'$
 $\vee Bet$ $A B A' \wedge Bet$ $B A' B'$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. \exists D. ParallelogramStrict$ $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *Rectangle-not-triv*:
shows $\neg Rectangle$ $A A A A$
<proof>

lemma *Plg-triv*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows *Plg* $A A B B$
<proof>

lemma *Rectangle-triv*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows *Rectangle* $A A B B$
<proof>

lemma *Rectangle-not-triv-2*:
shows $\neg Rectangle$ $A B A B$
<proof>

lemma *Square-not-triv*:
shows $\neg Square$ $A A A A$
<proof>

lemma *Square-not-triv-2*:
shows $\neg Square$ $A A B B$
<proof>

lemma *Square-not-triv-3*:

shows \neg *Square* $A B A B$
(*proof*)

lemma *Square-Rectangle*:
assumes *Square* $A B C D$
shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
(*proof*)

lemma *Square-Parallelogram*:
assumes *Square* $A B C D$
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
(*proof*)

lemma *Rhombus-Rectangle-Square*:
assumes *Rhombus* $A B C D$ **and**
Rectangle $A B C D$
shows *Square* $A B C D$
(*proof*)

lemma *rhombus-cong-square*:
assumes *Rhombus* $A B C D$ **and**
Cong $A C B D$
shows *Square* $A B C D$
(*proof*)

lemma *Kite-comm*:
assumes *Kite* $A B C D$
shows *Kite* $C D A B$
(*proof*)

lemma *per2-col-eq*:
assumes $A \neq P$ **and**
 $A \neq P'$ **and**
Per $A P B$ **and**
Per $A P' B$ **and**
Col $P A P'$
shows $P = P'$
(*proof*)

lemma *per2-preserves-diff*:
assumes $PO \neq A'$ **and**
 $PO \neq B'$ **and**
Col $PO A' B'$ **and**
Per $PO A' A$ **and**
Per $PO B' B$ **and**
 $A' \neq B'$
shows $A \neq B$
(*proof*)

lemma *per23-preserves-bet*:
assumes *Bet* $A B C$ **and**
 $A \neq B'$ **and** $A \neq C'$ **and**
Col $A B' C'$ **and**
Per $A B' B$ **and**
Per $A C' C$
shows *Bet* $A B' C'$
(*proof*)

lemma *per23-preserves-bet-inv*:
assumes *Bet* $A B' C'$ **and**
 $A \neq B'$ **and**
Col $A B C$ **and**
Per $A B' B$ **and**
Per $A C' C$
shows *Bet* $A B C$
(*proof*)

lemma *per13-preserves-bet:*

assumes *Bet A B C and*

B ≠ A' and

B ≠ C' and

Col A' B C' and

Per B A' A and

Per B C' C

shows *Bet A' B C'*

<proof>

lemma *per13-preserves-bet-inv:*

assumes *Bet A' B C' and*

B ≠ A' and

B ≠ C' and

Col A B C and

Per B A' A and

Per B C' C

shows *Bet A B C*

<proof>

lemma *per3-preserves-bet1:*

assumes *Col PO A B and*

Bet A B C and

PO ≠ A' and

PO ≠ B' and

PO ≠ C' and

Per PO A' A and

Per PO B' B and

Per PO C' C and

Col A' B' C' and

Col PO A' B'

shows *Bet A' B' C'*

<proof>

lemma *per3-preserves-bet2-aux:*

assumes *Col PO A C and*

A ≠ C' and

Bet A B' C' and

PO ≠ A and

PO ≠ B' and

PO ≠ C' and

Per PO B' B and

Per PO C' C and

Col A B C and

Col PO A C'

shows *Bet A B C*

<proof>

lemma *per3-preserves-bet2:*

assumes *Col PO A C and*

A' ≠ C' and

Bet A' B' C' and

PO ≠ A' and

PO ≠ B' and

PO ≠ C' and

Per PO A' A and

Per PO B' B and

Per PO C' C and

Col A B C and

Col PO A' C'

shows *Bet A B C*

<proof>

lemma *symmetry-preserves-per:*

assumes *Per B P A and*

B Midpoint A A' and
B Midpoint P P'
shows *Per B P' A'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-1-aux:*

assumes \neg *Col A B C and*
P Midpoint B C and
Q Midpoint A C and
R Midpoint A B
shows
 $\exists X Y. (R \text{ PerpAt } X Y A B \wedge X Y \text{ Perp } P Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C X \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C Y)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-1:*

assumes \neg *Col A B C and*
P Midpoint B C and
Q Midpoint A C and
R Midpoint A B
shows
 $\exists X Y. (R \text{ PerpAt } X Y A B \wedge X Y \text{ Perp } P Q)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *per-lt:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
Per A B C
shows $A B \text{ Lt } A C \wedge C B \text{ Lt } A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-perp-conga:*

assumes *Cong A B C B and*
A C Perp B P
shows $A B P \text{ Cong } A C B P \wedge B P \text{ TS } A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *perp-per-bet:*

assumes \neg *Col A B C and*

Per A B C and
P PerpAt P B A C
shows *Bet A P C*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *ts-per-per-ts:*

assumes $A B \text{ TS } C D$ **and**
Per B C A and
Per B D A
shows $C D \text{ TS } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-2-1:*

assumes $A B \text{ TS } C D$ **and**
Per B C A and
Per B D A and
Col C D E and
A E Perp C D and
C A B Cong A D A B
shows $B A C \text{ Cong } A D A E \wedge B A D \text{ Cong } C A E \wedge \text{Bet } C E D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle-mid-par-lem:*

assumes \neg *Col A B C and*
P Midpoint B C and
Q Midpoint A C
shows $A B \text{ Par } P Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *triangle-mid-par*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \ \text{Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \ \text{Midpoint } A \ C$

shows $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } Q \ P$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop4-perp-in2--col*:

assumes $\text{Coplanar } X \ Y \ A \ A'$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } X \ Y \ A \ B'$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } X \ Y \ B \ A'$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } X \ Y \ B \ B'$ **and**

$P \ \text{PerpAt } A \ B \ X \ Y$ **and**

$P \ \text{PerpAt } A' \ B' \ X \ Y$

shows $\text{Col } A \ B \ A'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-2*:

assumes $A \ B \ \text{TS } C \ D$ **and**

$\text{Per } B \ C \ A$ **and**

$\text{Per } B \ D \ A$ **and**

$\text{Col } C \ D \ E$ **and**

$A \ E \ \text{Perp } C \ D$

shows $B \ A \ C \ \text{CongA } D \ A \ E \wedge B \ A \ D \ \text{CongA } C \ A \ E \wedge \text{Bet } C \ E \ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-refl*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ A \ B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-sym*:

assumes $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } C \ D \ A \ B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-left-comm*:

assumes $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } B \ A \ C \ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-right-comm*:

assumes $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ D \ C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-comm*:

assumes $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } B \ A \ D \ C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-pseudo-trans*:

assumes $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**

$P \ \text{Perp2 } C \ D \ E \ F$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } C \ D \ P$

shows $P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ E \ F$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-cop-perp2--pars-bis*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ P$ **and**

$\text{Col } C \ D \ P$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**

$P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } C \ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-preserves-bet23*:

assumes $Bet\ PO\ A\ B$ **and**

$Col\ PO\ A'\ B'$ **and**

$\neg\ Col\ PO\ A\ A'$ **and**

$PO\ Perp2\ A\ A'\ B\ B'$

shows $Bet\ PO\ A'\ B'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-preserves-bet13*:

assumes $Bet\ B\ PO\ C$ **and**

$Col\ PO\ B'\ C'$ **and**

$\neg\ Col\ PO\ B\ B'$ **and**

$PO\ Perp2\ B\ C'\ C\ B'$

shows $Bet\ B'\ PO\ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-image-perp-in*:

assumes $A \neq A'$ **and**

$X \neq Y$ **and**

$A\ A'\ Reflect\ X\ Y$

shows $\exists\ P.\ P\ PerpAt\ A\ A'\ X\ Y$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-inter-perp-in-n*:

assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ D$

shows $\exists\ P.\ Col\ A\ B\ P \wedge Col\ C\ D\ P \wedge P\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp2-perp-in*:

assumes $PO\ Perp2\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**

$\neg\ Col\ PO\ A\ B$ **and**

$\neg\ Col\ PO\ C\ D$

shows $\exists\ P\ Q.\ Col\ A\ B\ P \wedge Col\ C\ D\ Q \wedge Col\ PO\ P\ Q \wedge P\ PerpAt\ PO\ P\ A\ B \wedge Q\ PerpAt\ PO\ Q\ C\ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-8*:

assumes $U \neq PO$ **and**

$V \neq PO$ **and**

$Col\ PO\ P\ Q$ **and**

$Col\ PO\ U\ V$ **and**

$Per\ P\ U\ PO$ **and**

$Per\ Q\ V\ PO$

shows $PO\ Out\ P\ Q \longleftrightarrow PO\ Out\ U\ V$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-in-rewrite*:

assumes $P\ PerpAt\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $P\ PerpAt\ A\ P\ P\ C \vee P\ PerpAt\ A\ P\ P\ D \vee P\ PerpAt\ B\ P\ P\ C \vee P\ PerpAt\ B\ P\ P\ D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-out-acute*:

assumes $B\ Out\ A\ C'$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ C\ C'$

shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-bet-obtuse*:

assumes $B \neq C'$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ C\ C'$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C'$

shows $Obtuse\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sac-perm*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D*

shows *Saccheri D C B A*

<proof>

lemma *sac-distincts*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D*

shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge C \neq D \wedge A \neq D \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq D$

<proof>

lemma *lam-perm*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *Lambert A D C B*

<proof>

lemma *sac--cong*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D*

shows *Cong A C B D*

<proof>

lemma *sac--conga*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D*

shows *A B C CongA B C D*

<proof>

lemma *lam--pars1234*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *A B ParStrict C D*

<proof>

lemma *lam--pars1423*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *A D ParStrict B C*

<proof>

lemma *lam--par1234*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *A B Par C D*

<proof>

lemma *lam--par1423*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *A D Par B C*

<proof>

lemma *lam--os*:

assumes *Lambert A B C D*

shows *A B OS C D*

<proof>

lemma *per2-os--pars*:

assumes *Per B A D and*

Per A D C and

A D OS B C

shows *A B ParStrict C D*

<proof>

lemma *per2-os--ncol123*:

assumes *Per B A D and*

Per A D C and

A D OS B C

shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *per2-os--ncol234*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C
shows \neg *Col B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sac--pars1234*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A B ParStrict C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sac--par1234*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A B Par C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-os-per2--lta*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C **and**
A B Lt C D
shows *B C D LtA A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt4321-os-per2--lta*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C **and**
D C Lt B A
shows *A B C LtA B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lta-os-per2--lt*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C **and**
B C D LtA A B C
shows *A B Lt C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lta123234-os-per2--lt*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C **and**
A B C LtA B C D
shows *D C Lt B A*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *conga-per2-os--cong*:
assumes *Per B A D* **and**
Per A D C **and**
A D OS B C **and**
B C D CongA A B C
shows *Cong A B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *mid2-sac--perp-lower*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
M Midpoint B C **and**

N Midpoint A D
shows *A D Perp M N*
<proof>

lemma *mid2-sac--perp-upper-R1:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *Cong N B N C*
<proof>

lemma *mid2-sac--perp-upper:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *B C Perp M N*
<proof>

lemma *sac--pars1423:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A D ParStrict B C*
<proof>

lemma *sac--par1423:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A D Par B C*
<proof>

lemma *mid2-sac--lam6521:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *Lambert N M B A*
<proof>

lemma *mid2-sac--lam6534:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *Lambert N M C D*
<proof>

lemma *lam6521-mid2--sac:*
assumes *Lambert N M B A and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *Saccheri A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *lam6534-mid2--sac:*
assumes *Lambert N M C D and*
M Midpoint B C and
N Midpoint A D
shows *Saccheri A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *cong-lam--per:*
assumes *Lambert A B C D and*
Cong A D B C
shows *Per B C D*
<proof>

lemma *lam-lt--acute*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D* **and**
A D Lt B C
shows *Acute B C D*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lam-lt--obtuse*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D* **and**
B C Lt A D
shows *Obtuse B C D*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *ngta*:
shows $\neg A B C \text{ Gt} A A B C$ \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lam-per--cong*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D* **and**
Per B C D
shows *Cong A D B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *acute-lam--lt*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D* **and**
Acute B C D
shows *A D Lt B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lam-obtuse--lt*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D* **and**
Obtuse B C D
shows *B C Lt A D*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *sac--ex2-mid-mid-lam-conga*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows $\exists M N. M \text{ Midpoint } B C \wedge N \text{ Midpoint } A D \wedge \text{Lambert } N M B A \wedge A B C \text{ Cong} A M B A$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cong-sac--per-aux1*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
Cong A D B C
shows *Per A B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cong-sac--per-aux2*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
Per A B C
shows *Cong A D B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cong-sac--per*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *Cong A D B C* \longleftrightarrow *Per A B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lt-sac--acute-aux1*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
A D Lt B C
shows *Acute A B C*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *lt-sac--acute-aux2*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Acute A B C
shows *A D Lt B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-sac--acute*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A D Lt B C* \longleftrightarrow *Acute A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-sac--obtuse-aux1*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
B C Lt A D
shows *Obtuse A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-sac--obtuse-aux2*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Obtuse A B C
shows *B C Lt A D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lt-sac--obtuse*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *B C Lt A D* \longleftrightarrow *Obtuse A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-7--per*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Bet B P C and
Bet A Q D and
A \neq Q and
Q \neq D and
Per P Q A and
Cong P Q A B
shows *Per A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-7--acute*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Bet B P C and
Bet A Q D and
A \neq Q and
Per P Q A and
P Q Lt A B
shows *Acute A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-7--obtuse*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Bet B P C and
Bet A Q D and
A \neq Q and
Per P Q A and
A B Lt P Q
shows *Obtuse A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-7--cong*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* and
Bet B P C and
Bet A Q D and
A \neq Q and
Per P Q A and
Per A B C
shows *Cong P Q A B*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-7--lt5612*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet B P C and

Bet A Q D and

A \neq Q and

Q \neq D and

Per P Q A and

Acute A B C

shows *P Q Lt A B*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-7--lt1256*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet B P C and

Bet A Q D and

A \neq Q and

Q \neq D and

Per P Q A and

Obtuse A B C

shows *A B Lt P Q*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-8-aux-1*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet A D S and

D \neq S and

Per A S R

shows *C \neq R*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-8-aux-2*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet B C R and

Bet A D S and

Per A S R and

S Out R J and

Cong S J A B

shows *Saccheri A B J S*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-8-aux-3*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet B C R and

Bet A D S and

D \neq S and

Per A S R and

S Out R J and

Cong S J A B

shows *Saccheri D C J S*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-8-aux-4*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*

Bet B C R and

Bet A D S and

D \neq S and

Per A S R and

S Out R J and

Cong S J A B

shows *S J OS C B*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-8-aux-5*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

Per A S R **and**

S Out R J **and**

Cong S J A B

shows *Coplanar A B C J*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8-aux*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

D ≠ S **and**

Per A S R **and**

S Out R J **and**

Cong S J A B

shows *C ≠ R ∧ Saccheri A B J S ∧ Saccheri D C J S ∧ S J OS C B ∧ Coplanar A B C J*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8--per*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

D ≠ S **and**

Per A S R **and**

Cong R S A B

shows *Per A B C*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8--acute*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

D ≠ S **and**

Per A S R **and**

A B Lt R S

shows *Acute A B C*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8--obtuse*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

D ≠ S **and**

Per A S R **and**

R S Lt A B

shows *Obtuse A B C*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8--cong*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

D ≠ S **and**

Per A S R **and**

Per A B C

shows *Cong R S A B*

<proof>

lemma *t22-8--lt1256*:

assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**

Bet B C R **and**

Bet A D S **and**

$D \neq S$ and
 Per $A S R$ and
 Acute $A B C$
shows $A B Lt R S$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-8--lt5612*:
assumes Saccheri $A B C D$ and
 Bet $B C R$ and
 Bet $A D S$ and
 $D \neq S$ and
 Per $A S R$ and
 Obtuse $A B C$
shows $R S Lt A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9-aux-1*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$ and
 Per $S R M$
shows Per $Q P M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9-aux-2*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$ and
 Per $Q P M$
shows Per $S R M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9-aux-3*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$ and
 Acute $S R M$
shows Acute $Q P M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9-aux-4*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$ and
 Acute $Q P M$
shows
 Acute $S R M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9-aux*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$
shows $(Per S R M \longleftrightarrow Per Q P M) \wedge (Acute S R M \longleftrightarrow Acute Q P M)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-9--per-1*:
assumes Lambert $N M P Q$ and
 Lambert $N M R S$ and
 Bet $M P R$ and
 Bet $N Q S$ and

Per S R M
shows *Per Q P M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--per-2:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S and
Per Q P M
shows *Per S R M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--per:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S
shows *Per S R M* \longleftrightarrow *Per Q P M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--acute-1:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S and
Acute S R M
shows *Acute Q P M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--acute-2:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S and
Acute Q P M
shows *Acute S R M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--acute:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S
shows *Acute S R M* \longleftrightarrow *Acute Q P M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--obtuse-1:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S and
Obtuse S R M
shows *Obtuse Q P M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--obtuse-2:*
assumes *Lambert N M P Q and*
Lambert N M R S and
Bet M P R and
Bet N Q S and
Obtuse Q P M
shows *Obtuse S R M*
<proof>

lemma *t22-9--obtuse:*

assumes *Lambert N M P Q* **and**
Lambert N M R S **and**
Bet M P R **and**
Bet N Q S
shows *Obtuse S R M* \longleftrightarrow *Obtuse Q P M*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-lam2--cong-conga-1*:
assumes *Lambert N M P Q* **and**
Lambert N' M' P' Q' **and**
Cong N Q N' Q' **and**
Cong P Q P' Q'
shows *Cong N M N' M'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-lam2--cong-conga-2*:
assumes *Lambert N M P Q* **and**
Lambert N' M' P' Q' **and**
Cong N Q N' Q' **and**
Cong P Q P' Q'
shows *M P Q CongA M' P' Q'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-lam2--cong-conga*:
assumes *Lambert N M P Q* **and**
Lambert N' M' P' Q' **and**
Cong N Q N' Q' **and**
Cong P Q P' Q'
shows *Cong N M N' M' \wedge M P Q CongA M' P' Q'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-sac2--cong*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
Saccheri A' B' C' D' **and**
Cong A B A' B' **and**
Cong A D A' D'
shows *Cong B C B' C'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *sac--perp1214*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A B Perp A D*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *sac--perp3414*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *C D Perp A D*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-sac2--sac*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
Saccheri A B E F **and**
D \neq F **and**
Coplanar A B D F
shows *Saccheri D C E F*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *three-hypotheses-aux*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D* **and**
Saccheri A' B' C' D' **and**
M Midpoint B C **and**

M' Midpoint $B' C'$ and
 N Midpoint $A D$ and
 N' Midpoint $A' D'$ and
 $M N \text{ Le } M' N'$
shows $(\text{Per } A B C \longleftrightarrow \text{Per } A' B' C') \wedge (\text{Acute } A B C \longleftrightarrow \text{Acute } A' B' C')$
 <proof>

lemma *three-hypotheses-aux-1*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and
Saccheri $A' B' C' D'$ and
 M Midpoint $B C$ and
 M' Midpoint $B' C'$ and
 N Midpoint $A D$ and
 N' Midpoint $A' D'$ and
 $M N \text{ Le } M' N'$ and
 $\text{Per } A B C$
shows $\text{Per } A' B' C'$
 <proof>

lemma *three-hypotheses-aux-2*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and
Saccheri $A' B' C' D'$ and
 M Midpoint $B C$ and
 M' Midpoint $B' C'$ and
 N Midpoint $A D$ and
 N' Midpoint $A' D'$ and
 $M N \text{ Le } M' N'$ and
 $\text{Per } A' B' C'$
shows $\text{Per } A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *three-hypotheses-aux-3*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and
Saccheri $A' B' C' D'$ and
 M Midpoint $B C$ and
 M' Midpoint $B' C'$ and
 N Midpoint $A D$ and
 N' Midpoint $A' D'$ and
 $M N \text{ Le } M' N'$ and
 $\text{Acute } A B C$
shows $\text{Acute } A' B' C'$
 <proof>

lemma *three-hypotheses-aux-4*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and
Saccheri $A' B' C' D'$ and
 M Midpoint $B C$ and
 M' Midpoint $B' C'$ and
 N Midpoint $A D$ and
 N' Midpoint $A' D'$ and
 $M N \text{ Le } M' N'$ and
 $\text{Acute } A' B' C'$
shows $\text{Acute } A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *per-sac--rah*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and
 $\text{Per } A B C$
shows *HypothesisRightSaccheriQuadrilaterals*
 <proof>

lemma *acute-sac--aah*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ and

Acute A B C
shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
<proof>

lemma *obtuse-sac--oah:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and*
Obtuse A B C
shows *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
<proof>

lemma *per--ex-saccheri:*
assumes *Per B A D and*
A ≠ B and
A ≠ D
shows $\exists C. \textit{Saccheri A B C D}$
<proof>

lemma *ex-saccheri:*
 $\exists A B C D. \textit{Saccheri A B C D}$
<proof>

lemma *ex-lambert:*
 $\exists A B C D. \textit{Lambert A B C D}$
<proof>

lemma *saccheri-s-three-hypotheses:*
hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals \vee
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals \vee
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
<proof>

lemma *not-aah:*
assumes *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals* \vee
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows $\neg \textit{hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
<proof>

lemma *not-rah:*
assumes *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals* \vee
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows $\neg \textit{hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
<proof>

lemma *not-oah:*
assumes *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals* \vee
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows $\neg \textit{hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
<proof>

lemma *lam-per--rah-1:*
assumes *Lambert A B C D and*
Per B C D
shows *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
<proof>

lemma *lam-per--rah-2:*
assumes *Lambert A B C D and*
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows *Per B C D*
<proof>

lemma *lam-per--rah:*
assumes *Lambert A B C D*
shows $\textit{Per B C D} \longleftrightarrow \textit{hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
<proof>

lemma *lam-acute--aah-1*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D and Acute B C D*
shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lam-acute--aah-2*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D and hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *Acute B C D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lam-acute--aah*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D*
shows *Acute B C D \longleftrightarrow hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lam-obtuse--oah-1*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D and Obtuse B C D*
shows *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lam-obtuse--oah-2*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D and hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *Obtuse B C D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lam-obtuse--oah*:
assumes *Lambert A B C D*
shows *Obtuse B C D \longleftrightarrow hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--per-1*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and A B D Cong A B D C*
shows *Per A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--per-2*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and Per A B C*
shows *A B D Cong A B D C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--per*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *A B D Cong A B D C \longleftrightarrow Per A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--acute-1*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and A B D Lt A B D C*
shows *Acute A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--acute-2*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D and Acute A B C*
shows *A B D Lt A B D C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *t22-11--acute*:
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*

shows $A B D \text{ Lt} A B D C \longleftrightarrow \text{Acute } A B C$
(proof)

lemma *t22-11--obtuse-1*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ **and**
 $B D C \text{ Lt} A A B D$
shows *Obtuse* $A B C$
(proof)

lemma *t22-11--obtuse-2*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$ **and**
Obtuse $A B C$
shows $B D C \text{ Lt} A A B D$
(proof)

lemma *t22-11--obtuse*:
assumes *Saccheri* $A B C D$
shows $B D C \text{ Lt} A A B D \longleftrightarrow \text{Obtuse } A B C$
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--rah-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per $A B C$ **and**
 $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A A B C$
shows *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--rah-2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per $A B C$ **and**
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A A B C$
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--rah*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per $A B C$
shows $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A A B C \longleftrightarrow \text{hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--aah-1*:
assumes *Per* $A B C$ **and**
 $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A P Q R$ **and**
Acute $P Q R$
shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--aah-2*:
assumes *Per* $A B C$ **and**
 $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A P Q R$ **and**
hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows *Acute* $P Q R$
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--aah*:
assumes *Per* $A B C$ **and**
 $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A P Q R$
shows *Acute* $P Q R \longleftrightarrow \text{hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
(proof)

lemma *t22-12--oah-1*:
assumes *Per* $A B C$ **and**
 $B C A C A B \text{ Sum} A P Q R$ **and**

Obtuse P Q R
shows *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-12--oah-2*:
assumes *Per A B C and*
B C A C A B SumA P Q R and
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows *Obtuse P Q R*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-12--oah*:
assumes *Per A B C and*
B C A C A B SumA P Q R
shows *Obtuse P Q R* \longleftrightarrow *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--aux*:
assumes \neg *Col A B C and*
Acute A B C and
Acute A C B
shows \exists *A'*. *Bet B A' C* \wedge *Per B A' A* \wedge *Per C A' A* \wedge
B A' A CongA C A' A \wedge *A B C CongA A B A' A* \wedge
B C A CongA A' C A \wedge *A A' TS B C*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--bet-aux*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals and*
 \neg *Col A B C and*
A B C TriSumA P Q R and
Acute A B C and
Acute A C B
shows *Bet P Q R*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--bet*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals and*
A B C TriSumA P Q R
shows *Bet P Q R*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--sams-nbet-aux*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals and*
 \neg *Col A B C and*
C A B A B C SumA D E F and
D E F B C A SumA P Q R and
Acute A B C and
Acute A C B
shows *SAMS D E F B C A* \wedge \neg *Bet P Q R*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--sams-nbet*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals and*
 \neg *Col A B C and*
C A B A B C SumA D E F and
D E F B C A SumA P Q R
shows *SAMS D E F B C A* \wedge \neg *Bet P Q R*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--nsams-aux*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals and*

\neg Col A B C and
 C A B A B C SumA D E F and
 Acute A B C and
 Acute A C B
shows \neg SAMS D E F B C A
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--nsams*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals* and
 \neg Col A B C and
 C A B A B C SumA D E F
shows \neg SAMS D E F B C A
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--rah*:
assumes \neg Col A B C and
 A B C TriSumA P Q R and
 Bet P Q R
shows *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--aah*:
assumes C A B A B C SumA D E F and
 D E F B C A SumA P Q R and
 SAMS D E F B C A and
 \neg Bet P Q R
shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-14--oah*:
assumes C A B A B C SumA D E F and
 \neg SAMS D E F B C A
shows *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-mid--suma*:
assumes \neg Col A B C and
 M Midpoint A B and
 Cong M A M C
shows C A B A B C SumA A C B
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-17--rah-1*:
assumes \neg Col A B C and
 M Midpoint A B and
 Cong M A M C and
 Per A C B
shows *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-17--rah-2*:
assumes \neg Col A B C and
 M Midpoint A B and
 Cong M A M C and

hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows $Per\ A\ C\ B$
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--rah*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C
shows $Per\ A\ C\ B \longleftrightarrow hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals$
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--oah-1*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C and
Obtuse A C B
shows *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--oah-2*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C and
hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows *Obtuse A C B*
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--oah*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C
shows $Obtuse\ A\ C\ B \longleftrightarrow hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--aah-1*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C and
Acute A C B
shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--aah-2*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C and
hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals
shows *Acute A C B*
(proof)

lemma *t22-17--aah*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
M Midpoint A B and
Cong M A M C
shows $Acute\ A\ C\ B \longleftrightarrow hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals$
(proof)

lemma *t22-20*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
A B C B C A Sum A D E F
shows *SAMS D E F C A B*
(proof)

lemma *absolute-exterior-angle-theorem*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**

Bet $B A B'$ **and**
 $A \neq B'$ **and**
 $A B C B C A \text{ Sum} A D E F$
shows $D E F \text{ Le} A C A B'$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-distincts*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C \wedge D \neq E \wedge E \neq F$
 <proof>

lemma *ex-defect*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$
shows $\exists D E F. \text{Defect } A B C D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *conga-defect--defect*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$ **and**
 $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
shows $\text{Defect } A B C D' E' F'$
 <proof>

lemma *defect2--conga*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$ **and**
 $\text{Defect } A B C D' E' F'$
shows $D E F \text{ Cong} A D' E' F'$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-perm-231*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{Defect } B C A D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-perm-312*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{Defect } C A B D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-perm-321*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{Defect } C B A D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-perm-213*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{Defect } B A C D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *defect-perm-132*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{Defect } A C B D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *conga3-defect--defect*:
assumes $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**
 $B C A \text{ Cong} A' B' C' A'$ **and**
 $C A B \text{ Cong} A' C' A' B'$
shows $\text{Defect } A' B' C' D E F$
 <proof>

lemma *col-defect--out*:
assumes $\text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $\text{Defect } A B C D E F$

shows $E \text{ Out } D F$
(proof)

lemma *rah-defect--out*:
assumes *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals* **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $E \text{ Out } D F$
(proof)

lemma *defect-ncol-out--rah*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $E \text{ Out } D F$
shows *hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(proof)

lemma *t22-16-1*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C1\ C$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C1\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Defect\ B\ C1\ C\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I\ SumA\ K\ L\ M$
shows $SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I \wedge Defect\ A\ B\ C\ K\ L\ M$
(proof)

lemma *t22-16-1bis*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C1\ C$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C1\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Defect\ B\ C1\ C\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C\ K\ L\ M$
shows $SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I \wedge D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I\ SumA\ K\ L\ M$
(proof)

lemma *t22-16-2aux*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C\ D1\ D2\ D3$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ D\ C1\ C2\ C3$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ D\ C\ B1\ B2\ B3$ **and**
 $Defect\ C\ B\ D\ A1\ A2\ A3$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ PO\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ PO\ D$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $D1\ D2\ D3\ B1\ B2\ B3\ SumA\ P\ Q\ R$
shows $SAMS\ C1\ C2\ C3\ A1\ A2\ A3 \wedge C1\ C2\ C3\ A1\ A2\ A3\ SumA\ P\ Q\ R$
(proof)

lemma *t22-16-2aux1*:
assumes $\neg\ hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ C\ D1\ D2\ D3$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ B\ D\ C1\ C2\ C3$ **and**
 $Defect\ A\ D\ C\ B1\ B2\ B3$ **and**
 $Defect\ C\ B\ D\ A1\ A2\ A3$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ PO\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ PO\ D$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ D$ **and**
 $D1\ D2\ D3\ B1\ B2\ B3\ SumA\ P\ Q\ R$
shows $SAMS\ C1\ C2\ C3\ A1\ A2\ A3 \wedge C1\ C2\ C3\ A1\ A2\ A3\ SumA\ P\ Q\ R$
(proof)

lemma *t22-16-2*:

assumes \neg *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals* **and**

Defect A B C D1 D2 D3 **and**

Defect A B D C1 C2 C3 **and**

Defect A D C B1 B2 B3 **and**

Defect C B D A1 A2 A3 **and**

Bet A P O C **and**

Bet B P O D **and**

SAMS D1 D2 D3 B1 B2 B3 **and**

D1 D2 D3 B1 B2 B3 SumA P Q R

shows *SAMS C1 C2 C3 A1 A2 A3* \wedge *C1 C2 C3 A1 A2 A3 SumA P Q R*

<proof>

lemma *isosceles-sym* :

assumes *A B C isosceles*

shows *C B A isosceles*

<proof>

lemma *isosceles-conga*:

assumes *A \neq C* **and**

A \neq B **and**

A B C isosceles

shows *C A B CongA A C B*

<proof>

lemma *conga-isosceles*:

assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**

C A B CongA A C B

shows *A B C isosceles*

<proof>

lemma *isosceles-foot--midpoint-conga*:

assumes *A B C isosceles* **and**

Col H A C **and**

H B Perp A C

shows \neg *Col A B C* \wedge *A \neq H* \wedge *C \neq H* \wedge *H Midpoint A C* \wedge *H B A CongA H B C*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-strict-equilateral*:

assumes *A B C equilateralStrict*

shows *A B C equilateral*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-cong*:

assumes *A B C equilateral*

shows *Cong A B B C* \wedge *Cong B C C A* \wedge *Cong C A A B*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-rot*:

assumes *A B C equilateral*

shows *B C A equilateral*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-swap*:

assumes *A B C equilateral*

shows *B A C equilateral*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-rot-2*:

assumes *A B C equilateral*

shows *C B A equilateral*

<proof>

lemma *equilateral-swap-2*:

assumes $A B C$ equilateral
shows $A C B$ equilateral
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-swap-rot:
assumes $A B C$ equilateral
shows $C A B$ equilateral
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-isosceles-1:
assumes $A B C$ equilateral
shows $A B C$ isosceles
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-isosceles-2:
assumes $A B C$ equilateral
shows $B C A$ isosceles
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-isosceles-3:
assumes $A B C$ equilateral
shows $C A B$ isosceles
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-neq:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-swap-1:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $A C B$ equilateralStrict
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-swap-2:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $B A C$ equilateralStrict
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-swap-3:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $B C A$ equilateralStrict
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-swap-4:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $C A B$ equilateralStrict
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-swap-5:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $C B A$ equilateralStrict
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict--not-col:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows \neg Col $A B C$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-conga-1:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict
shows $C A B$ Cong $A A C B$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma equilateral-strict-conga-2:
assumes $A B C$ equilateralStrict

shows $B A C \text{ Cong} A A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *equilateral-strict-conga-3*:
assumes $A B C \text{ equilateralStrict}$
shows $C B A \text{ Cong} A B C A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga3-equilateral*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $B A C \text{ Cong} A A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A B C A$
shows $A B C \text{ equilateral}$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lg-exists*:
 $\exists l. (Q\text{Cong } l \wedge l A B)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lg-cong*:
assumes $Q\text{Cong } l$ **and**
 $l A B$ **and**
 $l C D$
shows $\text{Cong } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lg-cong-lg*:
assumes $Q\text{Cong } l$ **and**
 $l A B$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B C D$
shows $l C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lg-sym*:
assumes $Q\text{Cong } l$
and $l A B$
shows $l B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-points-lg*:
assumes $Q\text{Cong } l$
shows $\exists A B. l A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-len-cong*:
assumes $\text{TarskiLen } A B l$ **and**
 $\text{TarskiLen } C D l$
shows $\text{Cong } A B C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-len-cong-is-len*:
assumes $\text{TarskiLen } A B l$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B C D$
shows $\text{TarskiLen } C D l$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-is-len*:
assumes $\neg \text{Cong } A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{TarskiLen } A B l$
shows $\neg l C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-is-len1*:
assumes $\neg \text{Cong } A B C D$
and $\text{TarskiLen } A B l$
shows $\neg \text{TarskiLen } C D l$

<proof>

lemma *lg-null-instance:*
assumes *QCongNull l*
shows $l A A$
<proof>

lemma *lg-null-trivial:*
assumes *QCong l*
and $l A A$
shows *QCongNull l*
<proof>

lemma *lg-null-dec:*

shows $QCongNull l \vee \neg QCongNull l$
<proof>

lemma *ex-point-lg:*
assumes *QCong l*
shows $\exists B. l A B$
<proof>

lemma *ex-point-lg-out:*
assumes $A \neq P$ **and**
QCong l **and**
 $\neg QCongNull l$
shows $\exists B. (l A B \wedge A Out B P)$
<proof>

lemma *ex-point-lg-bet:*
assumes *QCong l*
shows $\exists B. (l M B \wedge Bet A M B)$
<proof>

lemma *ex-points-lg-not-col:*
assumes *QCong l*
and $\neg QCongNull l$
shows $\exists A B. (l A B \wedge \neg Col A B P)$
<proof>

lemma *ex-eql:*
assumes $\exists A B. (TarskiLen A B l1 \wedge TarskiLen A B l2)$
shows $l1 = l2$
<proof>

lemma *all-eql:*
assumes *TarskiLen A B l1* **and**
TarskiLen A B l2
shows $l1 EqLTarski l2$
<proof>

lemma *null-len:*
assumes *TarskiLen A A la* **and**
TarskiLen B B lb
shows $la EqLTarski lb$
<proof>

lemma *eql-equivalence:*
assumes *QCong la* **and**
QCong lb **and**
QCong lc
shows $la = lb \wedge (la = lb \longrightarrow lb = la) \wedge (la = lb \wedge lb = lc \longrightarrow la = lc)$
<proof>

lemma *ex-lg:*

$\exists l. (QCong\ l \wedge l\ A\ B)$
(proof)

lemma *lg-eql-lg*:
assumes *QCong l1* and
 l1 EqLTarski l2
shows *QCong l2*
(proof)

lemma *ex-eqL*:
assumes *QCong l1* and
 QCong l2 and
 $\exists A\ B. (l1\ A\ B \wedge l2\ A\ B)$
shows *l1 EqLTarski l2*
(proof)

lemma *ang-exists*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $C \neq B$
shows $\exists a. (QCongA\ a \wedge a\ A\ B\ C)$
(proof)

lemma *ex-points-eng*:
assumes *QCongA a*
shows $\exists A\ B\ C. (a\ A\ B\ C)$
(proof)

lemma *ang-conga*:
assumes *QCongA a* and
 $a\ A\ B\ C$ and
 $a\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$
(proof)

lemma *is-ang-conga*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ Ang\ a$ and
 $A'\ B'\ C'\ Ang\ a$
shows $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$
(proof)

lemma *is-ang-conga-is-ang*:
assumes $A\ B\ C\ Ang\ a$ and
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $A'\ B'\ C'\ Ang\ a$
(proof)

lemma *not-conga-not-ang*:
assumes *QCongA a* and
 $\neg A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$ and
 $a\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg a\ A'\ B'\ C'$
(proof)

lemma *not-conga-is-ang*:
assumes $\neg A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$ and
 $A\ B\ C\ Ang\ a$
shows $\neg a\ A'\ B'\ C'$
(proof)

lemma *not-cong-is-ang1*:
assumes $\neg A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$ and
 $A\ B\ C\ Ang\ a$
shows $\neg A'\ B'\ C'\ Ang\ a$
(proof)

lemma *ex-eqa*:

assumes $\exists A B C.(A B C \text{ Ang } a1 \wedge A B C \text{ Ang } a2)$
shows $a1 = a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *all-ega*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Ang } a1$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Ang } a2$
shows $a1 = a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-ang-distinct*:
assumes $A B C \text{ Ang } a$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *null-ang*:
assumes $A B A \text{ Ang } a1$ **and**
 $C D C \text{ Ang } a2$
shows $a1 = a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *flat-ang*:
assumes $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $Bet A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Ang } a1$ **and**
 $A' B' C' \text{ Ang } a2$
shows $a1 = a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ang-distinct*:
assumes $QCongA a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-ang*:
assumes $B \neq A$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $\exists a. (QCongA a \wedge a A B C)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-exists*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq B$ **and**
 $Acute A B C$
shows $\exists a. (QCongAAcute a \wedge a A B C)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-is-ang*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$
shows $QCongA a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-points-anga*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$
shows $\exists A B C. a A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-conga*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$ **and**
 $a A B C$ **and**
 $a A' B' C'$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong } A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-anga-to-is-ang*:

assumes $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$
shows $A B C \text{ Ang } a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-anga-conga*:
assumes $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$ **and**
 $A' B' C' \text{ AngAcute } a$
shows $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-anga-conga-is-anga*:
assumes $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$
shows $A' B' C' \text{ AngAcute } a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-conga-is-anga*:
assumes $\neg A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$
shows $\neg a A' B' C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-cong-is-anga1*:
assumes $\neg A B C \text{ Cong} A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$
shows $\neg A' B' C' \text{ AngAcute } a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ex-eqaa*:
assumes $\exists A B C. (A B C \text{ AngAcute } a1 \wedge A B C \text{ AngAcute } a2)$
shows $a1 \text{ Eq} A a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *all-eqaa*:
assumes $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a1$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a2$
shows $a1 \text{ Eq} A a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-anga-distinct*:
assumes $A B C \text{ AngAcute } a$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *null-anga*:
assumes $A B A \text{ AngAcute } a1$ **and**
 $C D C \text{ AngAcute } a2$
shows $a1 \text{ Eq} A a2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-distinct*:
assumes $Q \text{ Cong} A \text{ Acute } a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-is-len-eq*:
assumes $A \text{ Out } B C$ **and**
 $\text{TarskiLen } A B l$ **and**
 $\text{TarskiLen } A C l$
shows $B = C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-len-eq*:
assumes $Q \text{ Cong } l$ **and**
 $A \text{ Out } B C$ **and**

$l A B$ **and**
 $l A C$
shows $B = C$ $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ex-anga*:
assumes $Acute A B C$
shows $\exists a. (QCongA Acute a \wedge a A B C)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-null-ang-ang*:
assumes $QCongAnNull a$
shows $QCongA a$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-null-ang-def-equiv*:
 $QCongAnNull a \longleftrightarrow (QCongA a \wedge (\exists A B C. (a A B C \wedge \neg B Out A C)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-flat-ang-def-equiv*:
 $QCongAnFlat a \longleftrightarrow (QCongA a \wedge (\exists A B C. (a A B C \wedge \neg Bet A B C)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ang-const*:
assumes $QCongA a$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ang-sym*:
assumes $QCongA a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $a C B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ang-not-null-lg*:
assumes $QCongA a$ **and**
 $QCong l$ **and**
 $a A B C$ **and**
 $l A B$
shows $\neg QCongNull l$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ang-distincts*:
assumes $QCongA a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *anga-sym*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $a C B A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *anga-not-null-lg*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$ **and**
 $QCong l$ **and**
 $a A B C$ **and**
 $l A B$
shows $\neg QCongNull l$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *anga-distincts*:
assumes $QCongAAcute a$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ang-const-o:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ P$ **and**
 $Q\text{Cong}A \ a$ **and**
 $Q\text{CongAnNull } a$ **and**
 $Q\text{CongAnFlat } a$
shows $\exists C. a \ A \ B \ C \wedge A \ B \ OS \ C \ P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-const:*

assumes $Q\text{CongAAcute } a$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. a \ A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *null-anga-null-angaP:*

$Q\text{CongANullAcute } a \longleftrightarrow \text{IsNullAngaP } a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-null-anga-out:*

assumes
 $a \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $Q\text{CongANullAcute } a$
shows $B \ \text{Out } A \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-acute:*

assumes $Q\text{CongAAcute } a$ **and**
 $a \ A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Acute } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-null-not-col:*

assumes $Q\text{CongAAcute } a$ **and**
 $\neg Q\text{CongANullAcute } a$ **and**
 $a \ A \ B \ C$
shows $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ang-cong-ang:*

assumes $Q\text{Cong}A \ a$ **and**
 $a \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ C \ \text{Cong}A \ A' \ B' \ C'$
shows $a \ A' \ B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-null-ang-out:*

assumes
 $a \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $Q\text{CongANull } a$
shows $B \ \text{Out } A \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-null-ang:*

assumes $Q\text{Cong}A \ a$ **and**
 $a \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $B \ \text{Out } A \ C$
shows $Q\text{CongANull } a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-flat-ang:*

assumes $Q\text{Cong}A \ a$ **and**
 $a \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{AngFlat } a$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-null-anga:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B\ Out\ A\ C$
shows $QCongANullAcute\ a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-not-flat:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$
shows $QCongAnFlat\ a$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-const-o:*

assumes $\neg\ Col\ A\ B\ P$ **and**
 $\neg\ QCongANullAcute\ a$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ a$
shows $\exists\ C.\ (a\ A\ B\ C \wedge A\ B\ OS\ C\ P)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-conga-anga:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $a\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-out-anga:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $B\ Out\ A\ A'$ **and**
 $B\ Out\ C\ C'$
shows $a\ A'\ B\ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *out-out-anga:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $B\ Out\ A\ C$ **and**
 $B'\ Out\ A'\ C'$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$
shows $a\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-null-all:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $QCongANullAcute\ a$
shows $a\ A\ B\ A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-col-out:*

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ C$
shows $B\ Out\ A\ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ang-not-lg-null:*

assumes $QCong\ la$ **and**
 $QCong\ lc$ **and**
 $QCongA\ a$ **and**
 $la\ A\ B$ **and**
 $lc\ C\ B$ **and**
 $a\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg\ QCongNull\ la \wedge \neg\ QCongNull\ lc$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *anga-not-lg-null*:

assumes

$QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**

$la\ A\ B$ **and**

$lc\ C\ B$ **and**

$a\ A\ B\ C$

shows $\neg\ QCongNull\ la \wedge \neg\ QCongNull\ lc$

<proof>

lemma *anga-col-null*:

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**

$a\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ C$

shows $B\ Out\ A\ C \wedge QCongANullAcute\ a$

<proof>

lemma *eqA-preserves-ang*:

assumes $QCongA\ a$ **and**

$a\ EqA\ b$

shows $QCongA\ b$

<proof>

lemma *eqA-preserves-anga*:

assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**

$a\ EqA\ b$

shows $QCongAAcute\ b$

<proof>

lemma *l13-6*:

assumes $Lcos\ lc\ l\ a$ **and**

$Lcos\ ld\ l\ a$

shows $lc\ EqLTarski\ ld$

<proof>

lemma *null-lcos-eql*:

assumes $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$ **and**

$QCongANullAcute\ a$

shows $l\ EqLTarski\ lp$

<proof>

lemma *eql-lcos-null*:

assumes $Lcos\ l\ lp\ a$ **and**

$l\ EqLTarski\ lp$

shows $QCongANullAcute\ a$

<proof>

lemma *lcos-lg-not-null*:

assumes $Lcos\ l\ lp\ a$

shows $\neg\ QCongNull\ l \wedge \neg\ QCongNull\ lp$

<proof>

lemma *perp-acute-out*:

assumes $Acute\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ C\ C'$ **and**

$Col\ A\ B\ C'$

shows $B\ Out\ A\ C'$

<proof>

lemma *perp-col-out--acute-aux*:

assumes $A\ B\ Perp\ C\ C'$ **and**

$B\ Out\ A\ C'$

shows $Acute\ A\ B\ C$

<proof>

lemma *perp-out--acute*:
assumes $A B \text{ Perp } C C'$ **and**
 $Col A B C'$
shows $Acute A B C \longleftrightarrow B \text{ Out } A C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *obtuse-not-acute*:
assumes $Obtuse A B C$
shows $\neg Acute A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-not-obtuse*:
assumes $Acute A B C$
shows $\neg Obtuse A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *perp-obtuse-bet*:
assumes $A B \text{ Perp } C C'$ **and**
 $Col A B C'$ **and**
 $Obtuse A B C$
shows $Bet A B C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const0*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$ **and**
 $QCongANullAcute a$
shows $\exists A B C. l A B \wedge lp B C \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const1*:
fixes $P::'p$
assumes $Lcos lp l a$ **and**
 $\neg QCongANullAcute a$
shows $\exists A B C. \neg Col A B P \wedge A B OS C P \wedge l A B \wedge lp B C \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$
shows $\exists A B C. lp A B \wedge l B C \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-lq-distincts*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$ **and**
 $l A B$ **and**
 $a A B C$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const-a*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$
shows $\forall B. \exists A C. l A B \wedge lp B C \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const-ab*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$ **and**
 $l A B$
shows $\exists C. lp B C \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const-cb*:
assumes $Lcos lp l a$ **and**
 $lp B C$
shows $\exists A. l A B \wedge a A B C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-lg-anga*:
assumes $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$
shows $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a \wedge QCong\ l \wedge QCong\ lp \wedge QCongAAcute\ a$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-eql-lcos*:
assumes $lp1\ EqLTarski\ lp2$ **and**
 $l1\ EqLTarski\ l2$ **and**
 $Lcos\ lp1\ l1\ a$
shows $Lcos\ lp2\ l2\ a$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-not-lg-null*:
assumes $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$
shows $\neg QCongNull\ lp$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-const-o*:
assumes $\neg Col\ A\ B\ P$ **and**
 $\neg QCongANullAcute\ a$ **and**
 $QCong\ l$ **and**
 $QCong\ lp$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $l\ A\ B$ **and**
 $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$
shows $\exists C. A\ B\ OS\ C\ P \wedge a\ A\ B\ C \wedge lp\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *flat-not-acute*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg Acute\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-comp-not-acute*:
assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Acute\ A\ B\ D$
shows $\neg Acute\ C\ B\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-per*:
assumes $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $QCong\ l$ **and**
 $QCong\ lp$ **and**
 $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$ **and**
 $l\ A\ C$ **and**
 $lp\ A\ B$ **and**
 $a\ B\ A\ C$
shows $Per\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *is-null-anga-dec*:
shows $QCongANullAcute\ a \vee \neg QCongANullAcute\ a$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lcos-lg*:
assumes $Lcos\ lp\ l\ a$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Perp\ B\ C$ **and**
 $a\ B\ A\ C$ **and**
 $l\ A\ C$
shows $lp\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l13-7*:
assumes $Lcos\ la\ l\ a$ **and**

Lcos lb l b **and**
Lcos lab la b **and**
Lcos lba lb a
shows *lab EqLTarski lba*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *out-acute*:
assumes *B Out A C*
shows *Acute A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *perp-acute*:
assumes *Col A C P* **and**
P PerpAt B P A C
shows *Acute A B P*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *null-lcos*:
assumes *QCong l* **and**
 \neg *QCongNull l* **and**
QCongANullAcute a
shows *Lcos l l a*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-exists*:
assumes *QCongAAcute a* **and**
QCong l **and**
 \neg *QCongNull l*
shows \exists *lp. Lcos lp l a*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-uniqueness*:
assumes *Lcos l1 l a* **and**
Lcos l2 l a
shows *l1 EqLTarski l2*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eqa-lcos*:
assumes *Lcos lp l a* **and**
a EqA b
shows *Lcos lp l b*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eq-refl*:
assumes *QCong la* **and**
 \neg *QCongNull la* **and**
QCongAAcute a
shows *EqLcos la a la a*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eq-sym*:
assumes *EqLcos la a lb b*
shows *EqLcos lb b la a*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eq-trans*:
assumes *EqLcos la a lb b* **and**
EqLcos lb b lc c
shows *EqLcos la a lc c*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-comm*:
assumes *Lcos2 lp l a b*
shows *Lcos2 lp l b a*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-exists*:
assumes *QCong l* **and**
 \neg *QCongNull l* **and**
QCongAAcute a **and**
QCongAAcute b
shows \exists *lp*. *Lcos2 lp l a b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-exists'*:
assumes *QCong l* **and**
 \neg *QCongNull l* **and**
QCongAAcute a **and**
QCongAAcute b
shows \exists *la lab*. *Lcos la l a* \wedge *Lcos lab la b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-eq-refl*:
assumes *QCong l* **and**
 \neg *QCongNull l* **and**
QCongAAcute a **and**
QCongAAcute b
shows *EqLcos2 l a b l a b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-eq-sym*:
assumes *EqLcos2 l1 a b l2 c d*
shows *EqLcos2 l2 c d l1 a b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-uniqueness*:
assumes *Lcos2 l1 l a b* **and**
Lcos2 l2 l a b
shows *l1 EqLTarski l2*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-eql-lcos2*:
assumes *Lcos2 la lla a b* **and**
lla EqLTarski llb **and**
la EqLTarski lb
shows *Lcos2 lb llb a b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-lg-anga*:
assumes *Lcos2 lp l a b*
shows *Lcos2 lp l a b* \wedge *QCong lp* \wedge *QCong l* \wedge *QCongAAcute a* \wedge *QCongAAcute b*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-eq-trans*:
assumes *EqLcos2 l1 a b l2 c d* **and**
EqLcos2 l2 c d l3 e f
shows *EqLcos2 l1 a b l3 e f*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eq-lcos2-eq*:
assumes *QCongAAcute c* **and**
EqLcos la a lb b
shows *EqLcos2 la a c lb b c*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-lg-not-null*:
assumes *Lcos2 lp l a b*
shows \neg *QCongNull l* \wedge \neg *QCongNull lp*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos3-lcos-1-2-a*:
assumes *Lcos3 lp l a b c*

shows $\exists la. Lcos\ la\ l\ a \wedge Lcos2\ lp\ la\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos-1-2-b*:
assumes $\exists la. Lcos\ la\ l\ a \wedge Lcos2\ lp\ la\ b\ c$
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos-1-2*:
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c \longleftrightarrow (\exists la. Lcos\ la\ l\ a \wedge Lcos2\ lp\ la\ b\ c)$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos-2-1-a*:
assumes $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
shows $\exists lab. Lcos2\ lab\ l\ a\ b \wedge Lcos\ lp\ lab\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos-2-1-b*:
assumes $\exists lab. Lcos2\ lab\ l\ a\ b \wedge Lcos\ lp\ lab\ c$
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos-2-1*:
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c \longleftrightarrow (\exists lab. Lcos2\ lab\ l\ a\ b \wedge Lcos\ lp\ lab\ c)$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-permut3*:
assumes $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ b\ a\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-permut1*:
assumes $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ c\ b$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-permut2*:
assumes $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
shows $Lcos3\ lp\ l\ c\ b\ a$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-exists*:
assumes $QCong\ l$ **and**
 $\neg QCongNull\ l$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ b$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ c$
shows $\exists lp. Lcos3\ lp\ l\ a\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-eq-refl*:
assumes $QCong\ l$ **and**
 $\neg QCongNull\ l$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ a$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ b$ **and**
 $QCongAAcute\ c$
shows $EqLcos3\ l\ a\ b\ c\ l\ a\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-eq-sym*:
assumes $EqLcos3\ l1\ a\ b\ c\ l2\ d\ e\ f$
shows $EqLcos3\ l2\ d\ e\ f\ l1\ a\ b\ c$
<proof>

lemma *lcos3-uniqueness*:
assumes $Lcos3\ l1\ l\ a\ b\ c$ **and**

Lcos3 l2 l a b c
shows *l1 EqLTarski l2*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos3-eql-lcos3*:
assumes *Lcos3 la lla a b c* **and**
lla EqLTarski llb **and**
la EqLTarski lb
shows *Lcos3 lb llb a b c*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos3-lg-anga*:
assumes *Lcos3 lp l a b c*
shows *Lcos3 lp l a b c* \wedge *QCong lp* \wedge *QCong l* \wedge *QCongAAcute a* \wedge *QCongAAcute b* \wedge *QCongAAcute c*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos3-lg-not-null*:
assumes *Lcos3 lp l a b c*
shows \neg *QCongNull l* \wedge \neg *QCongNull lp*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos3-eq-trans*:
assumes *EqLcos3 l1 a b c l2 d e f* **and**
EqLcos3 l2 d e f l3 g h i
shows *EqLcos3 l1 a b c l3 g h i*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos-eq-lcos3-eq*:
assumes *QCongAAcute c* **and**
QCongAAcute d **and**
EqLcos la a lb b
shows *EqLcos3 la a c d lb b c d*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *lcos2-eq-lcos3-eq*:
assumes *QCongAAcute e* **and**
EqLcos2 la a b lb c d
shows *EqLcos3 la a b e lb c d e*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *projp-id*:
assumes *P P' Projp A B* **and**
P Q' Projp A B
shows $P' = Q'$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *projp-idem*:
assumes *P P' Projp A B*
shows $P' P' Projp A B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *col-projp-eq*:
assumes *Col A B P* **and**
P P' Projp A B
shows $P = P'$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *projp-col*:
assumes *P P' Projp A B*
shows *Col A B P'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *project-id*:
assumes *P P' Proj A B X Y* **and**

Col A B P
shows $P = P'$
<proof>

lemma *project-not-id*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $\neg Col A B P$
shows $P \neq P'$
<proof>

lemma *project-col*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $Col A B P$
<proof>

lemma *project-not-col*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $P \neq P'$
shows $\neg Col A B P$
<proof>

lemma *par-col-project*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\neg A B Par X Y$ **and**
 $P P' Par X Y$ **and**
 $Col A B P'$
shows $P P' Proj A B X Y$
<proof>

lemma *cong-conga3-cong3*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $Cong A B A' B'$ **and**
 $A B C CongA3 A' B' C'$
shows $A B C Cong3 A' B' C'$
<proof>

lemma *project-par-dir*:
assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P P' Par X Y$
<proof>

lemma *project-idem*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P' P' Proj A B X Y$
<proof>

lemma *perp-projp*:
assumes $P' PerpAt A B P P'$
shows $P P' Projp A B$
<proof>

lemma *proj-distinct*:
assumes $P P' Projp A B$
shows $P' \neq A \vee P' \neq B$
<proof>

lemma *l13-10-aux1*:
assumes $Col PO A B$ **and**
 $Col PO P Q$ **and**
 $PO P Perp P A$ **and**
 $PO Q Perp Q B$ **and**
 $QCong la$ **and**
 $QCong lb$ **and**
 $QCong lp$ **and**
 $QCong lq$ **and**

la PO A and
 lb PO B and
 lp PO P and
 lq PO Q
shows $\exists a. QCongAAcute a \wedge Lcos lp la a \wedge Lcos lq lb a$
 <proof>

lemma *l13-10-aux2*:
assumes Col PO A B and
 $QCong la$ and
 $QCong lla$ and
 $QCong lb$ and
 $QCong llb$ and
 la PO A and
 lla PO A and
 lb PO B and
 llb PO B and
 $A \neq PO$ and
 $B \neq PO$
shows $\exists a. QCongAAcute a \wedge Lcos lla la a \wedge Lcos llb lb a$
 <proof>

lemma *l13-6-bis*:
assumes Lcos lp l1 a and
 $Lcos lp l2 a$
shows l1 EqLTarski l2
 <proof>

lemma *lcos3-lcos2*:
assumes EqLcos3 l1 a b n l2 c d n
shows EqLcos2 l1 a b l2 c d
 <proof>

lemma *lcos2-lcos*:
assumes EqLcos2 l1 a c l2 b c
shows EqLcos l1 a l2 b
 <proof>

lemma *lcos-per-anga*:
assumes Lcos lp la a and
 la PO A and
 lp PO P and
 $Per A P PO$
shows $a A PO P$
 <proof>

lemma *lcos-lcos-cop--col*:
assumes Lcos lp la a and
 $Lcos lp lb b$ and
 la PO A and
 lb PO B and
 lp PO P and
 $a A PO P$ and
 $b B PO P$ and
 $Coplanar PO A B P$
shows Col A B P
 <proof>

lemma *l13-10-aux3*:
assumes $\neg Col PO A A'$ and
 $B \neq PO$ and
 $C \neq PO$ and
 $Col PO A B$ and
 $Col PO B C$ and
 $B' \neq PO$ and
 $C' \neq PO$ and

Col PO A' B' and
Col PO B' C' and
PO Perp2 B C' C B' and
PO Perp2 C A' A C' and
Bet A PO B
shows *Bet A' PO B'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-10-aux4*:
assumes \neg *Col PO A A' and*
B \neq PO and
C \neq PO and
Col PO A B and
Col PO B C and
B' \neq PO and
C' \neq PO and
Col PO A' B' and
Col PO B' C' and
PO Perp2 B C' C B' and
PO Perp2 C A' A C' and
Bet PO A B
shows *PO Out A' B'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-10-aux5*:
assumes \neg *Col PO A A' and*
B \neq PO and
C \neq PO and
Col PO A B and
Col PO B C and
B' \neq PO and
C' \neq PO and
Col PO A' B' and
Col PO B' C' and
PO Perp2 B C' C B' and
PO Perp2 C A' A C' and
PO Out A B
shows *PO Out A' B'*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-per2--perp-aux*:
assumes *A \neq B and*
X \neq Y and
B \neq X and
Coplanar A B X Y and
Per A B X and
Per A B Y
shows *A B Perp X Y*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-per2--perp*:
assumes *A \neq B and*
X \neq Y and
B \neq X \vee B \neq Y and
Coplanar A B X Y and
Per A B X and
Per A B Y
shows *A B Perp X Y*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-10*:
assumes \neg *Col PO A A' and*
B \neq PO and
C \neq PO and
Col PO A B and
Col PO B C and

$B' \neq PO$ and
 $C' \neq PO$ and
 $Col\ PO\ A'\ B'$ and
 $Col\ PO\ B'\ C'$ and
 $PO\ Perp2\ B\ C'\ C\ B'$ and
 $PO\ Perp2\ C\ A'\ A\ C'$
shows $PO\ Perp2\ A\ B'\ B\ A'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Pj-exists*:
fixes $A\ B\ C$
shows $\exists D. A\ B\ Pj\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *project-trivial*:
assumes $A \neq B$
and $X \neq Y$
and $Col\ A\ B\ P$
and $\neg A\ B\ Par\ X\ Y$
shows $P\ P\ Proj\ A\ B\ X\ Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *pj-col-project*:
assumes $A \neq B$
and $X \neq Y$
and $Col\ P'\ A\ B$
and $\neg A\ B\ Par\ X\ Y$
and $X\ Y\ Pj\ P\ P'$
shows $P\ P'\ Proj\ A\ B\ X\ Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *pj-trivial*:
shows $A\ B\ Pj\ C\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *O-not-positive*:
shows $\neg Ps\ PO\ E\ PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *col-pos-or-neg*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $PO \neq X$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ X$
shows $Ps\ PO\ E\ X \vee Ng\ PO\ E\ X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *length-cong*:
assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
shows $Cong\ A\ B\ PO\ AB$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangular-equality-equiv-a* :
assumes $\forall PO\ E\ A. PO \neq E \longrightarrow (\forall E'\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC. Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC)$
shows $\forall PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC. PO \neq E \wedge Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangular-equality-equiv-b* :
assumes $\forall PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC. PO \neq E \wedge Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$

$Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC$

shows $\forall\ PO\ E\ A.\ PO \neq E \longrightarrow (\forall\ E'\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC.\ Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC)$

<proof>

lemma *triangular-equality-equiv* :

shows $(\forall\ PO\ E\ A.\ PO \neq E \longrightarrow (\forall\ E'\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC.\ Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC))$

\longleftrightarrow

$(\forall\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ AB\ BC\ AC.\ PO \neq E \wedge Bet\ A\ B\ C \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB \wedge$
 $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC \wedge Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
 $\longrightarrow Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ BC\ AC)$

<proof>

lemma *sign-dec*:

assumes $Col\ PO\ E\ A$

and $PO \neq E$

shows $A = PO \vee Ps\ PO\ E\ A \vee Ng\ PO\ E\ A$

<proof>

lemma *not-neg-pos*:

assumes $E \neq PO$

and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$

and $\neg Ng\ PO\ E\ A$

shows $Ps\ PO\ E\ A \vee A = PO$

<proof>

lemma *Tarski-Pre-Non-Euclidean-aux-pre*:

assumes $\exists\ A\ B\ C\ D\ T.\ \neg((Bet\ A\ D\ T \wedge Bet\ B\ D\ C \wedge A \neq D)$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists\ X\ Y.\ Bet\ A\ B\ X \wedge Bet\ A\ C\ Y \wedge Bet\ X\ T\ Y))$

shows $\exists\ A0\ B0\ C0\ D0\ T0.\ (Bet\ A0\ D0\ T0 \wedge Bet\ B0\ D0\ C0 \wedge A0 \neq D0 \wedge$
 $(\forall\ X\ Y.\ ((Bet\ A0\ B0\ X \wedge Bet\ A0\ C0\ Y) \longrightarrow \neg Bet\ X\ T0\ Y)))$

<proof>

end

end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-Archimedes*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

begin

2 Continuity Axioms

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

2.1 Definitions

definition *greenberg-s-axiom* ::

bool

(GreenBergsAxiom)

where

greenberg-s-axiom $\equiv \forall\ P\ Q\ R\ A\ B\ C.$

$\neg Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge Acute\ A\ B\ C \wedge Q \neq R \wedge Per\ P\ Q\ R \longrightarrow (\exists\ S.\ P\ S\ Q\ LtA\ A\ B\ C \wedge Q\ Out\ S\ R)$

definition *aristotle-s-axiom* ::

bool

(*AristotleAxiom*) **where**
aristotle-s-axiom $\equiv \forall P Q A B C.$
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge \text{Acute } A B C \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists X Y. B \text{ Out } A X \wedge B \text{ Out } C Y \wedge \text{Per } B X Y \wedge P Q \text{ Lt } X Y)$

definition *Axiom1*:: *bool where Axiom1* $\equiv \forall A B C D.$
 $(\exists I. \text{Col } I A B \wedge \text{Col } I C D) \vee \neg (\exists I. \text{Col } I A B \wedge \text{Col } I C D)$

definition *PreGrad* :: '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* \Rightarrow *bool where*
PreGrad *A B C D* $\equiv (A \neq B \wedge \text{Bet } A B C \wedge \text{Bet } A C D \wedge \text{Cong } A B C D)$

fun *Sym* :: '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* \Rightarrow '*p* **where**
Sym *A B C* = (if (*A* \neq *B* \wedge *Bet* *A B C*) then
 (SOME *x*::'*p*. *PreGrad* *A B C x*)
 else
A)

fun *Gradn* :: [*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *nat* \Rightarrow '*p* **where**
Gradn *A B n* = (if (*A* = *B*) then
A
 else
 (if (*n* = 0) then
A
 else
 (if (*n* = 1) then
B
 else
 (*Sym* *A B* (*Gradn* *A B* (*n*-1))))))

definition *Grad* :: [*p*, '*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *bool where*
Grad *A B C* $\equiv \exists n. (n \neq 0) \wedge (C = \text{Gradn } A B n)$

inductive *GradI* :: [*p*, '*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *bool for* *A B*
where
gradi-init : *GradI* *A B B*
| *gradi-stab* : *GradI* *A B C'* if
GradI *A B C*
and *Bet* *A C C'*
and *Cong* *A B C C'*

definition *Reach* :: [*p*, '*p*, '*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *bool where*
Reach *A B C D* $\equiv \exists B'. \text{Grad } A B B' \wedge C D \text{ Le } A B'$

definition *archimedes-axiom* ::
bool
(*ArchimedesAxiom*) **where**
archimedes-axiom $\equiv \forall A B C D::'*p*.
A \neq *B* \longrightarrow *Reach* *A B C D*$

inductive *GradA* :: [*p*, '*p*, '*p*, '*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *bool for* *A B C*
where
grada-init : *GradA* *A B C D E F* if
A B C Cong *A D E F*
| *grada-stab* : *GradA* *A B C G H I* if
GradA *A B C D E F*
and *SAMS* *D E F A B C*
and *D E F A B C Sum* *A G H I*

inductive *GradAExp* :: [*p*, '*p*, '*p*, '*p*, '*p*] \Rightarrow *bool for* *A B C*
where
gradaexp-init : *GradAExp* *A B C D E F* if
A B C Cong *A D E F*
| *gradaexp-stab* : *GradAExp* *A B C G H I* if
GradAExp *A B C D E F*
and *SAMS* *D E F D E F*
and *D E F D E F Sum* *A G H I*

definition *Grad2* :: [*p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*] ⇒ *bool* **where**
Grad2 A B C D E F ≡ ∃ *n*. (*n* ≠ 0) ∧ (*C* = *Gradn A B n*) ∧ (*F* = *Gradn D E n*)

fun *SymR* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *'p* **where**
SymR A B = (*SOME x*::*'p*. *B Midpoint A x*)

fun *GradExpn* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *nat* ⇒ *'p* **where**
(*GradExpn A B n*) = (if (*A* = *B*) then
A
else
(if (*n* = 0) then
A
else
(if (*n* = 1) then
B
else
(*SymR A (GradExpn A B (n-1))*))))))

definition *GradExp* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *bool* **where**
GradExp A B C ≡ ∃ *n*. (*n* ≠ 0) ∧ *C* = *GradExpn A B n*

definition *GradExp2* :: [*p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*,*'p*] ⇒ *bool* **where**
GradExp2 A B C D E F ≡ ∃ *n*. (*n* ≠ 0) ∧ (*C* = *GradExpn A B n*) ∧ (*F* = *GradExpn D E n*)

fun *MidR* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *'p* **where**
MidR A B = (*SOME x*. *x Midpoint A B*)

fun *GradExpInvn* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *nat* ⇒ *'p* **where**
(*GradExpInvn A B n*) = (if (*A* = *B*) then
A
else
(if (*n* = 0) then
B
else
(if (*n* = 1) then
(*MidR A B*)
else
(*MidR A (GradExpInvn A B (n-1))*))))))

definition *GradExpInv* :: *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *'p* ⇒ *bool* **where**
GradExpInv A B C ≡ ∃ *n*. *B* = *GradExpInvn A C n*

2.2 Propositions

lemma *PreGrad-lem1*:
assumes *A* ≠ *B* **and**
Bet A B C
shows ∃ *x*. *PreGrad A B C x*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *PreGrad-uniq*:
assumes *PreGrad A B C x* **and**
PreGrad A B C y
shows *x* = *y*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Diff-Mid--PreGrad*:
assumes *A* ≠ *B* **and**
B Midpoint A C
shows *PreGrad A B B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Diff-Mid-Mid-PreGrad*:
assumes *A* ≠ *B* **and**
B Midpoint A C **and**

C Midpoint B D
shows *PreGrad A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *Sym-Diff--Diff*:
assumes *Sym A B C = D* **and**
A ≠ D
shows *A ≠ B*
<proof>

lemma *Sym-Refl*:
Sym A A A = A
<proof>

lemma *Diff-Mid--Sym*:
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
B Midpoint A C
shows *Sym A B B = C*
<proof>

lemma *Mid-Mid--Sym*:
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
B Midpoint A C **and**
C Midpoint B D
shows *Sym A B C = D*
<proof>

lemma *Sym-Bet--Bet-Bet*:
assumes *Sym A B C = D* **and**
A ≠ B **and**
Bet A B C
shows *Bet A B D ∧ Bet A C D*
<proof>

lemma *Sym-Bet--Cong*:
assumes *Sym A B C = D* **and**
A ≠ B **and**
Bet A B C
shows *Cong A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *LemSym-aux*:
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
Bet A B C **and**
Bet A C D **and**
Cong A B C D
shows *Sym A B C = D*
<proof>

lemma *Lem-Gradn-id-n*:
Gradn A A n = A
<proof>

lemma *Lem-Gradn-0*:
Gradn A B 0 = A
<proof>

lemma *Lem-Gradn-1*:
Gradn A B 1 = B
<proof>

lemma *Diff--Gradn-Sym*:
assumes *A ≠ B* **and**
n > 1
shows *Gradn A B n = Sym A B (Gradn A B (n-1))*
<proof>

lemma *Diff--Bet-Gradn-Suc*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Le-Gradn-Suc*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff--Bet-Gradn*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \neq 0$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Le-Gradn-n*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \neq 0$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Bet-Gradn-Suc-Gradn-Suc2*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff--Bet-Gradn-Gradn-SucA*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff--Bet-Gradn-Gradn-Suc*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Bet-Gradn-Gradn-Suc*:
shows $Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-Le-Gradn-Suc*:
shows $A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Bet-Gradn-Suc-Gradn-Suc2*:
shows $Bet\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-Suc-Le-Gradn-Suc2*:
shows $B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ Le\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Le--Bet-Gradn-Plus*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \leq m$
shows $Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Le-Gradn-Plus*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \leq m$
shows $A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + n))$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Diff-Le-Bet--Gradn-Gradn:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$n \leq m$

shows $Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ m)$

<proof>

lemma *Diff-Le-Gradn:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$n \leq m$

shows $A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ m)$

<proof>

lemma *Diff--Cong-Gradn-Suc-Gradn-Suc2:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $Cong\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$

<proof>

lemma *Cong-Gradn-Suc-Gradn-Suc2:*

shows $Cong\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$

<proof>

lemma *Cong-Gradn-Gradn-Suc:*

shows $Cong\ a\ b\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ n)\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ (Suc\ n))$

<proof>

lemma *Diff-Bet-Bet-Cong-Gradn-Suc:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ C$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)\ C$

shows $C = (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))$

<proof>

lemma *grad-rec-0-1:*

shows $Cong\ a\ b\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 0)\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 1)$

<proof>

lemma *grad-rec-1-2:*

shows $Cong\ a\ b\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 1)\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 2)$

<proof>

lemma *grad-rec-2-3:*

shows $Cong\ a\ b\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 2)\ (Gradn\ a\ b\ 3)$

<proof>

lemma *grad-rec-a-a:*

shows $(Gradn\ a\ a\ n) = a$

<proof>

lemma *Gradn-uniq-aux-1:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $Gradn\ A\ B\ n \neq Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)$

<proof>

lemma *Gradn-uniq-aux-1-aa:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + n) \neq Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + (Suc\ n))$

<proof>

lemma *Gradn-uniq-aux-1-bb:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + n) \neq Gradn\ A\ B\ (k + (Suc\ (Suc\ n)))$

<proof>

lemma *Gradn-aux-1-0:*

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n) \neq A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-aux-1-1:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \neq 0$
shows $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n) \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-aux-1-1-bis:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \neq 1$
shows $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-aux-1-2:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n = A$
shows $n = 0$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-aux-1-3:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n = B$
shows $n = 1$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-uniq-aux-2-a:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n \neq 0$
shows $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ 0 \neq \text{Gradn } A \ B \ n$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-uniq-aux-2:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $n < m$
shows $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n \neq \text{Gradn } A \ B \ m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-uniq:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ m$
shows $n = m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-le-suc-1:*
shows $A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n) \ \text{Le } A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n))$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-le-1:*
assumes $m \leq n$
shows $A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ m) \ \text{Le } A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n))$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn-le-suc-2:*
shows $B \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)) \ \text{Le } B \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)))$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grad-equiv-coq-1:*
shows $\text{Grad } A \ B \ B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grad-aab--ab:*
assumes $\text{Grad } A \ A \ B$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grad-stab*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ C'$
shows $Grad\ A\ B\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad--bet*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad--col*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Col\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-neq--neq13*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $A \neq C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-neq--neq12*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$
shows $A \neq B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad112--eq*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ A\ B$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad121--eq*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ A$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad--le*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$
shows $A\ B\ Le\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad2-init*:
shows $Grad2\ A\ B\ B\ C\ D\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Grad2-stab*:
assumes $Grad2\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ C'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ C'$ **and**
 $Bet\ D\ F\ F'$ **and**
 $Cong\ D\ E\ F\ F'$
shows $Grad2\ A\ B\ C'\ D\ E\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-cong2-grad--grad2-aux-1*:
assumes $C = (Gradn\ A\ B\ 0)$ **and**
 $Bet\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ E\ F$
shows $F = Gradn\ D\ E\ 2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-cong2-grad--grad2-aux-2*:
assumes $Bet\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n))\ E\ F$
shows $F = Gradn\ D\ E\ (Suc\ n)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-cong2-grad--grad2-aux*:
assumes $n \neq 0$ **and**
 $C = (Gradn\ A\ B\ n)$ **and**
 $Bet\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ E\ F$
shows $F = Gradn\ D\ E\ n$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-cong2-grad--grad2*:
assumes $Grad\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ B\ C\ E\ F$
shows $Grad2\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad2--grad123*:
assumes $Grad2\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $Grad\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad2--grad456*:
assumes $Grad2\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $Grad\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-sum-aux-R1*:
assumes
 $A\ C\ Le\ A\ D$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ D\ A\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A\ E'$ **and**
 $A\ Out\ E\ E'$
shows $Bet\ A\ E'\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-sum-aux-0*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $D = Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n))$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ D\ A\ E$ **and**
 $C = Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ C\ A\ E'$ **and**
 $A\ Out\ E\ E'$
shows $Bet\ A\ E'\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-sum-aux-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $D = Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n))$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ E$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ D\ C\ E$ **and**
 $F = Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ E'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ F\ C\ E'$ **and**
 $C \neq A$
shows $Bet\ A\ E'\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-sum-aux-1A*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$C = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } (\text{Suc } 0))$

shows $B \ \text{Midpoint } A \ C$

<proof>

lemma *grad-sum-aux-2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$D = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A \ C \ E$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A \ D \ C \ E$ **and**

$F = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A \ C \ E'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A \ F \ C \ E'$ **and**

$C \neq A$

shows $\text{Cong } A \ B \ E' \ E$

<proof>

lemma *grad-sum-aux*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$C = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)$ **and**

$D = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } m)$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A \ C \ E$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A \ D \ C \ E$

shows $E = \text{Gradn } A \ B \ ((\text{Suc } n) + (\text{Suc } m))$

<proof>

lemma *grad-sum*:

assumes $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$\text{Grad } A \ B \ D$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A \ C \ E$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A \ D \ C \ E$

shows $\text{Grad } A \ B \ E$

<proof>

lemma *SymR-ex*:

assumes $B \ \text{Midpoint } A \ C$

shows $C = \text{SymR } A \ B$

<proof>

lemma *SymR--midp*:

assumes $C = \text{SymR } A \ B$

shows $B \ \text{Midpoint } A \ C$

<proof>

lemma *SymR-uniq*:

assumes $C = \text{SymR } A \ B$ **and**

$D = \text{SymR } A \ B$

shows $C = D$

<proof>

lemma *GradExpn-1*:

shows $\text{GradExpn } A \ A \ n = A$

<proof>

lemma *GradExpn-2*:

shows $\text{Bet } A \ B \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n))$

<proof>

lemma *GradExpn-3*:

shows $\text{Bet } A \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)) \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)))$

<proof>

lemma *GradExpn-4*:

shows $\text{Cong } A \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)) \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)) \ (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)))$

<proof>

lemma *gradexp-init*:

shows $\text{GradExp } A \ B \ B$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp-stab-aux-0*:

assumes $C = \text{GradExpn } A \ B \ 0$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A \ C \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A \ C \ C \ C'$
shows $C' = \text{GradExpn } A \ B \ 0$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp-stab-aux-n*:

assumes $C = \text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A \ C \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A \ C \ C \ C'$
shows $C' = \text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp-stab*:

assumes $\text{GradExp } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } A \ C \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A \ C \ C \ C'$
shows $\text{GradExp } A \ B \ C'$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp--grad-aux-1*:

shows $\forall C. (C = (\text{GradExpn } A \ A \ (\text{Suc } n)) \longrightarrow \text{Grad } A \ A \ C)$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp--grad-aux*:

assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\forall C. (C = (\text{GradExpn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n)) \longrightarrow \text{Grad } A \ B \ C)$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp--grad*:

assumes $\text{GradExp } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *gradexp-le--reach*:

assumes $\text{GradExp } A \ B \ B'$ **and**
 $C \ D \ \text{Le } A \ B'$
shows $\text{Reach } A \ B \ C \ D$
<proof>

lemma *grad--ex-gradexp-le-aux-0*:

assumes $A = B$
shows $\exists D. \text{GradExp } A \ B \ D \wedge A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n) \ \text{Le } A \ D$
<proof>

lemma *grad--ex-gradexp-le-aux-1*:

assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists D. \text{GradExp } A \ B \ D \wedge A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n) \ \text{Le } A \ D$
<proof>

lemma *grad--ex-gradexp-le-aux*:

shows $\exists D. \text{GradExp } A \ B \ D \wedge A \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ n) \ \text{Le } A \ D$
<proof>

lemma *grad--ex-gradexp-le*:

assumes $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C$
shows $\exists D. \text{GradExp } A \ B \ D \wedge A \ C \ \text{Le } A \ D$
<proof>

lemma *reach--ex-gradexp-le*:

assumes *Reach A B C D*
shows $\exists B'. \text{GradExp } A B B' \wedge C D \text{ Le } A B'$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexp2-init*:
shows *GradExp2 A B B C D D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *GradExp2-stab*:
assumes *GradExp2 A B C D E F and*
Bet A C C' and
Cong A C C C' and
Bet D F F' and
Cong D F F F'
shows *GradExp2 A B C' D E F'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexp2--gradexp123*:
assumes *GradExp2 A B C D E F*
shows *GradExp A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexp2--gradexp456*:
assumes *GradExp2 A B C D E F*
shows *GradExp D E F*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *MidR-uniq*:
assumes *C = MidR A B and*
D = MidR A B
shows *C = D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *MidR-ex-0*:
shows *(MidR A B) Midpoint A B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *MidR-ex-1*:
assumes *C = (MidR A B)*
shows *C Midpoint A B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *MidR-ex-aux*:
assumes *C Midpoint A B*
shows *C = (SOME x. x Midpoint A B)*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *MidR-ex*:
assumes *C Midpoint A B*
shows *C = (MidR A B)*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexpinv-init-aux*:
shows *B = GradExpInvn A B 0*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexpinv-init*:
shows *GradExpInv A B B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexpinv-stab-aux-0*:
assumes *B = GradExpInvn A C 0 and*
Bet A B' B and
Cong A B' B' B
shows *B' = GradExpInvn A C (Suc 0)*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *gradexpinv-stab-aux-n*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B'\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B'\ B'\ B$ **and**

$B = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ (Suc\ n)$

shows $B' = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ (Suc\ (Suc\ n))$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexpinv-stab*:

assumes $Bet\ A\ B'\ B$ **and**

$Cong\ A\ B'\ B'\ B$ **and**

$GradExpInv\ A\ B\ C$

shows $GradExpInv\ A\ B'\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux-1-0*:

assumes $C = GradExpn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ 0)$

shows $B = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ 0$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *SymR-MidR*:

assumes $A = SymR\ B\ C$

shows $C = MidR\ A\ B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *MidR-comm*:

assumes $C = MidR\ A\ B$

shows $C = MidR\ B\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *MidR-SymR*:

assumes $C = MidR\ A\ B$

shows $A = SymR\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *MidR-AA*:

shows $A = MidR\ A\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *MidR-AB*:

assumes $A = MidR\ A\ B$

shows $A = B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux-1-n-aa*:

shows $GradExpInvn\ A'\ (MidR\ A'\ C')\ n = GradExpInvn\ A'\ C'\ (Suc\ n)$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux-1-n-a*:

assumes $\forall\ A\ B\ C. (C = GradExpn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)) \longrightarrow B = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ n$

shows $\forall\ A'\ B'\ C'. (C' = GradExpn\ A'\ B'\ (Suc(Suc\ n))) \longrightarrow B' = GradExpInvn\ A'\ C'\ (Suc\ n)$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux-1-b*:

shows $\forall\ A\ B\ C. C = GradExpn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n) \longrightarrow B = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ n$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux-1*:

assumes $C = GradExpn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)$

shows $B = GradExpInvn\ A\ C\ n$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv-aux*:

assumes $GradExp\ A\ B\ C$

shows $GradExpInv\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux-1-a-0*:

assumes $B' = \text{MidR } A' (\text{GradExpInvn } A' C' (\text{Suc } 0))$

shows $C' = \text{SymR } A' (\text{GradExpn } A' B' (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } 0)))$

<proof>

lemma *sym-mid*:

shows $\text{SymR } A (\text{MidR } A B) = B$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpn-suc-suc*:

shows $\text{GradExpn } A B (\text{Suc } n) = \text{GradExpn } A (\text{MidR } A B) (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux-1-a-n*:

assumes $\forall A B C. (B = \text{MidR } A (\text{GradExpInvn } A C (\text{Suc } n))) \longrightarrow$

$C = \text{SymR } A (\text{GradExpn } A B (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)))$

shows $B' = \text{MidR } A' (\text{GradExpInvn } A' C' (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))) \longrightarrow$

$C' = \text{SymR } A' (\text{GradExpn } A' B' (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))))$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux-1-a*:

shows $\forall A B C. B = \text{MidR } A (\text{GradExpInvn } A C (\text{Suc } n)) \longrightarrow$

$C = \text{SymR } A (\text{GradExpn } A B (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)))$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux-1-n*:

assumes $B = \text{GradExpInvn } A C n \longrightarrow C = \text{GradExpn } A B (\text{Suc } n)$

shows $B' = \text{GradExpInvn } A' C' (\text{Suc } n) \longrightarrow C' = \text{GradExpn } A' B' (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux-1*:

shows $B = \text{GradExpInvn } A C n \longrightarrow C = \text{GradExpn } A B (\text{Suc } n)$

<proof>

lemma *gradexpinv--gradexp-aux*:

assumes $\text{GradExpInv } A B C$

shows $\text{GradExp } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *gradexp--gradexpinv*:

shows $\text{GradExp } A B C \longleftrightarrow \text{GradExpInv } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *reach--ex-gradexp-lt-aux*:

shows $\forall A B C P Q R. ((A \neq B \wedge A B \text{ Le } P R \wedge R = \text{GradExpn } P Q (\text{Suc } n)) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists C. \text{GradExp } A C B \wedge A C \text{ Lt } P Q))$

<proof>

lemma *reach--grad-min-1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**

$A C \text{ Le } A (\text{Gradn } A B (\text{Suc } 0))$

shows $\exists D E. (\text{Bet } A D C \wedge \text{Grad } A B D \wedge E \neq C \wedge \text{Bet } A C E \wedge \text{Bet } A D E \wedge \text{Cong } A B D E)$

<proof>

lemma *reach--grad-min-n*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A B C$ **and**

$A C \text{ Le } A (\text{Gradn } A B (\text{Suc } n)) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists D E. (\text{Bet } A D C \wedge \text{Grad } A B D \wedge E \neq C \wedge \text{Bet } A C E \wedge \text{Bet } A D E \wedge \text{Cong } A B D E))$

shows $A C \text{ Le } A (\text{Gradn } A B (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n))) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists D E. (\text{Bet } A D C \wedge \text{Grad } A B D \wedge E \neq C \wedge \text{Bet } A C E \wedge \text{Bet } A D E \wedge \text{Cong } A B D E))$

<proof>

lemma *reach--grad-min-aux:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$

shows $(Grad\ A\ B\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)) \wedge A\ C\ Le\ A\ (Gradn\ A\ B\ (Suc\ n)))$

$\longrightarrow (\exists\ D\ E. (Bet\ A\ D\ C \wedge Grad\ A\ B\ D \wedge E \neq C \wedge Bet\ A\ C\ E \wedge Bet\ A\ D\ E \wedge Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E))$

<proof>

lemma *reach--grad-min:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Bet\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$Reach\ A\ B\ A\ C$

shows $\exists\ D\ E. (Bet\ A\ D\ C \wedge Grad\ A\ B\ D \wedge E \neq C \wedge Bet\ A\ C\ E \wedge Bet\ A\ D\ E \wedge Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E)$

<proof>

lemma *reach--ex-gradexp-lt:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Reach\ P\ Q\ A\ B$

shows $\exists\ C. GradExp\ A\ C\ B \wedge A\ C\ Lt\ P\ Q$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux-0:*

assumes $Bet\ A0\ D1\ A1$ **and**

$Cong\ E0\ E1\ A1\ D1$ **and**

$D = Gradn\ A0\ D1\ (Suc\ 0)$

shows $\exists\ A\ E. (Grad2\ A0\ A1\ A\ E0\ E1\ E \wedge Cong\ E0\ E\ A\ D \wedge Bet\ A0\ D\ A)$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux-n:*

assumes $\forall\ A0\ D1\ A1\ E0\ E1\ D.$

$(Bet\ A0\ D1\ A1 \wedge Cong\ E0\ E1\ A1\ D1 \wedge D = Gradn\ A0\ D1\ (Suc\ n)) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists\ A\ E. (Grad2\ A0\ A1\ A\ E0\ E1\ E \wedge Cong\ E0\ E\ A\ D \wedge Bet\ A0\ D\ A))$

shows $\forall\ A0\ D1\ A1\ E0\ E1\ D.$

$(Bet\ A0\ D1\ A1 \wedge Cong\ E0\ E1\ A1\ D1 \wedge D = Gradn\ A0\ D1\ (Suc(Suc\ n))) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists\ A\ E. (Grad2\ A0\ A1\ A\ E0\ E1\ E \wedge Cong\ E0\ E\ A\ D \wedge Bet\ A0\ D\ A))$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux0:*

shows $\forall\ A0\ D1\ A1\ E0\ E1\ D.$

$(Bet\ A0\ D1\ A1 \wedge Cong\ E0\ E1\ A1\ D1 \wedge D = Gradn\ A0\ D1\ (Suc\ n)) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists\ A\ E. (Grad2\ A0\ A1\ A\ E0\ E1\ E \wedge Cong\ E0\ E\ A\ D \wedge Bet\ A0\ D\ A))$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux1:*

assumes $Bet\ A0\ D1\ A1$ **and**

$Cong\ E0\ E1\ A1\ D1$ **and**

$Grad\ A0\ D1\ D$

shows $\exists\ A\ E. (Grad2\ A0\ A1\ A\ E0\ E1\ E \wedge Cong\ E0\ E\ A\ D \wedge Bet\ A0\ D\ A)$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux2-0:*

assumes $Saccheri\ A0\ B0\ B1\ A1$ **and**

$A = Gradn\ A0\ A1\ (Suc\ 0)$ **and**

$E = Gradn\ B0\ B1\ (Suc\ 0)$ **and**

$Saccheri\ A0\ B0\ B\ A$

shows $B0\ B\ Le\ B0\ E$

<proof>

lemma *t22-18-aux2-Sucn:*

assumes $\forall\ A\ A0\ A1\ B\ B0\ B1\ E.$

$Saccheri\ A0\ B0\ B1\ A1 \wedge A = Gradn\ A0\ A1\ (Suc\ n) \wedge$

$E = Gradn\ B0\ B1\ (Suc\ n) \wedge Saccheri\ A0\ B0\ B\ A \longrightarrow B0\ B\ Le\ B0\ E$

shows $\forall\ A\ A0\ A1\ B\ B0\ B1\ E.$

Saccheri $A0 B0 B1 A1 \wedge A = \text{Gradn } A0 A1 (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)) \wedge$
 $E = \text{Gradn } B0 B1 (\text{Suc}(\text{Suc } n)) \wedge \text{Saccheri } A0 B0 B A \longrightarrow B0 B \text{ Le } B0 E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-18-aux2-n*:

shows $\forall A A0 A1 B B0 B1 E.$
Saccheri $A0 B0 B1 A1 \wedge A = \text{Gradn } A0 A1 (\text{Suc } n) \wedge$
 $E = \text{Gradn } B0 B1 (\text{Suc } n) \wedge \text{Saccheri } A0 B0 B A$
 $\longrightarrow B0 B \text{ Le } B0 E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-18-aux2*:

assumes *Saccheri* $A0 B0 B1 A1$ **and**
Grad2 $A0 A1 A B0 B1 E$ **and**
Saccheri $A0 B0 B A$
shows $B0 B \text{ Le } B0 E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-18*:

assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A0 B0 B1 A1. \text{Saccheri } A0 B0 B1 A1 \longrightarrow \neg (B0 B1 \text{ Lt } A1 A0)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-19*:

assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C D. \text{Saccheri } A B C D \longrightarrow \neg \text{Obtuse } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *archi--obtuse-case-elimination*:

assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\neg \text{hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-23-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A M N$ **and**
Per $B C A$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
M Midpoint $A B$ **and**
Per $M N A$ **and**
Col $A C N$ **and**
M Midpoint $N L$
shows $\text{Bet } A N C \wedge \text{Lambert } N L B C \wedge \text{Cong } B L A N$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-23*:

assumes $\neg \text{hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals}$
shows $\forall A B C M N L.$
 $\neg \text{Col } A M N \wedge \text{Per } B C A \wedge A \neq C \wedge \text{M Midpoint } A B \wedge$
 $\text{Per } M N A \wedge \text{Col } A C N \wedge \text{M Midpoint } N L \longrightarrow$
 $(\text{Bet } A N C \wedge N C \text{ Le } A N \wedge L N \text{ Le } B C)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux-0-a*:

assumes
 $\neg \text{Col } A B0 C0$ **and**
 $A C0 \text{ Perp } B0 C0$ **and**
 $B = \text{GradExpn } A B0 (\text{Suc } 0)$ **and**
 $E = \text{GradExpn } B0 C0 (\text{Suc } 0)$ **and**
 $A C0 \text{ Perp } B C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A C0 C$
shows $B0 E \text{ Le } B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux-0*:

shows $\forall A B0 C0 B C E.$
 $\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $(B = GradExpn A B0 (Suc 0)) \wedge (E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc 0)) \wedge$
 $A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C \longrightarrow$
 $B0 E Le B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux-suc*:

assumes $\neg hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$ **and**
 $\forall A B0 C0 B C E.$
 $\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $(B = GradExpn A B0 (Suc n)) \wedge (E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc n)) \wedge$
 $A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C \longrightarrow$
 $B0 E Le B C$

shows

$\forall A B0 C0 B C E.$
 $\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $(B = GradExpn A B0 (Suc(Suc n))) \wedge (E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc(Suc n))) \wedge$
 $A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C \longrightarrow$
 $B0 E Le B C$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux-n*:

assumes $\neg hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$

shows $\forall A B0 C0 B C E.$
 $(\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $(B = GradExpn A B0 (Suc n)) \wedge (E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc n)) \wedge$
 $A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C) \longrightarrow$
 $B0 E Le B C$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux*:

assumes $\neg hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals$

shows $\forall A B0 B00 C0 B C E.$
 $\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge B0 = B00 \wedge$
 $GradExp2 A B0 B B00 C0 E \wedge A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C \longrightarrow$
 $B0 E Le B C$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux1-0*:

shows $\forall A B0 C0 E.$
 $(\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc 0)) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B C. GradExp2 A B0 B B0 C0 E \wedge A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C)$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux1-suc*:

assumes $\forall A B0 C0 E.$
 $(\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc(n))) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B C. GradExp2 A B0 B B0 C0 E \wedge A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C)$

shows $\forall A B0 C0 E.$

$(\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc(Suc(n)))) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B C. GradExp2 A B0 B B0 C0 E \wedge A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C)$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux1-n*:

shows $\forall A B0 C0 E.$
 $(\neg Col A B0 C0 \wedge A C0 Perp B0 C0 \wedge$
 $E = GradExpn B0 C0 (Suc(n))) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B C. GradExp2 A B0 B B0 C0 E \wedge A C0 Perp B C \wedge Col A C0 C)$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *t22-24-aux1*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B0 \ C0$ **and**
 $A \ C0 \ \text{Perp } B0 \ C0$ **and**
 $\text{GradExp } B0 \ C0 \ E$
shows $\exists B \ C. \ \text{GradExp2 } A \ B0 \ B \ B0 \ C0 \ E \wedge A \ C0 \ \text{Perp } B \ C \wedge \text{Col } A \ C0 \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *t22-24*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

2.3 Equivalence Grad / GradI (inductive)

lemma *Grad1--GradI*:
shows $\text{GradI } A \ B \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ 1)$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Gradn--GradI*:
shows $\text{GradI } A \ B \ (\text{Gradn } A \ B \ (\text{Suc } n))$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Grad--GradI*:
assumes $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{GradI } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *GradIAAB--not*:
assumes $\text{GradI } A \ A \ B$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *GradI--Grad*:
assumes $\text{GradI } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

theorem *Grad-GradI*:
shows $\text{Grad } A \ B \ C \longleftrightarrow \text{GradI } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

2.4 GradA

lemma *grad-distincts*:
assumes $\text{GradA } A \ B \ C \ D \ E \ F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grad-ABC*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $\text{GradA } A \ B \ C \ A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *gradaexp-distincts*:
assumes $\text{GradAExp } A \ B \ C \ D \ E \ F$
shows $A \neq B \wedge C \neq B \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *gradaexp-ABC*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$
shows $\text{GradAExp } A \ B \ C \ A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga2-grad--grad-aux1*:
assumes $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $GradA\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *conga2-grad--grad-aux2*:
assumes $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ CongA\ D'\ E'\ F'$
shows $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D'\ E'\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *conga2-grad--grad*:
assumes $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $A\ B\ C\ CongA\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ CongA\ D'\ E'\ F'$
shows $GradA\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'\ E'\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad--lea*:
assumes $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $A\ B\ C\ LeA\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad-out--out*:
assumes $E\ Out\ D\ F$ **and**
 $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $B\ Out\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad2-sams-suma--grad-aux*:
shows $\forall\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I\ K\ L\ M.$
 $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F \wedge GradA\ A\ B\ C\ G\ H\ I \wedge$
 $SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I \wedge D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I\ SumA\ K\ L\ M \longrightarrow GradA\ A\ B\ C\ K\ L\ M$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *grad2-sams-suma--grad*:
assumes $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**
 $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I$ **and**
 $D\ E\ F\ G\ H\ I\ SumA\ K\ L\ M$
shows $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ K\ L\ M$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *gradaexp--grad*:
assumes $GradAExp\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
shows $GradA\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-archi-aux*:
assumes $Per\ PO\ A\ B$ **and**
 $PO \neq A$ **and**
 $B \neq A$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $D \neq E$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ C\ D$ **and**
 $Bet\ C\ D\ E$ **and**
 $Bet\ D\ E\ B$ **and**
 $C\ PO\ D\ CongA\ D\ PO\ E$
shows $C\ D\ Lt\ D\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *acute-archi-aux1*:
assumes $Per\ PO\ A0\ B$ **and**
 $B \neq A0$ **and**
 $Bet\ A0\ A1\ B$ **and**

$GradA A0 PO A1 P Q R$ and
 $A0 \neq A1$
shows $A0 PO B LeA P Q R \vee (\exists A. Bet A0 A1 A \wedge Bet A0 A B \wedge P Q R CongA A0 PO A)$
 <proof>

lemma acute-archi-aux2-1-a:
assumes $Per PO A0 B$ and
 $PO \neq A0$ and
 $B \neq A0$ and
 $Bet A0 A1 B$ and
 $A0 \neq A1$ and $\neg Col PO A0 B$ and $\neg Col A0 PO A1$ and $PO \neq A1$ and $PO \neq B$
shows $\exists P Q R. (GradA A0 PO A1 P Q R \wedge (A0 PO B LeA P Q R \vee$
 $(\exists A'. Bet A0 A1 A' \wedge Bet A0 A' B \wedge P Q R CongA A0 PO A' \wedge A0 A1 Le A0 A' \wedge$
 $(\exists A. Bet A0 A A' \wedge A0 PO A' CongA A0 PO A1 \wedge A0 A1 Le A A'))))$
 <proof>

lemma acute-archi-aux2-1:
assumes $Per PO A B$ and
 $PO \neq A$ and
 $B \neq A$ and
 $Bet A B0 B$ and
 $A \neq B0$ and $\neg Col PO A B$ and $\neg Col A PO B0$ and $PO \neq B0$ and $PO \neq B$
shows $\exists P Q R. (GradA A PO B0 P Q R \wedge (A PO B LeA P Q R \vee$
 $(\exists A'. Bet A B0 A' \wedge Bet A A' B \wedge P Q R CongA A PO A' \wedge A B0 Le A A' \wedge$
 $(\exists A0. Bet A A0 A' \wedge A0 PO A' CongA A PO B0 \wedge A B0 Le A0 A'))))$
 <proof>

lemma acute-archi-aux2-2:
assumes $Per PO A0 B$ and
 $PO \neq A0$ and
 $B \neq A0$ and
 $Bet A0 A1 B$ and
 $A0 \neq A1$ and
 $Grad A0 A1 C$ and
 $Bet A0 C C'$ and
 $Cong A0 A1 C C'$ and
 $\neg Col PO A0 B$ and
 $\neg Col A0 PO A1$ and
 $PO \neq A1$ and
 $PO \neq B$ and
 $Per PO A0 B \wedge PO \neq A0 \wedge$
 $B \neq A0 \wedge Bet A0 A1 B \wedge$
 $A0 \neq A1 \wedge$
 $\neg Col PO A0 B \wedge$
 $\neg Col A0 PO A1 \wedge$
 $PO \neq A1 \rightarrow (\exists P Q R.$
 $(GradA A0 PO A1 P Q R \wedge$
 $(A0 PO B LeA P Q R \vee$
 $(\exists A'.$
 $Bet A0 A1 A' \wedge$
 $Bet A0 A' B \wedge$
 $P Q R CongA A0 PO A' \wedge$
 $A0 C Le A0 A' \wedge (\exists A. (Bet A0 A A' \wedge A PO A' CongA A0 PO A1 \wedge A0 A1 Le A A'))))))$
shows $\exists P Q R. (GradA A0 PO A1 P Q R \wedge$
 $(A0 PO B LeA P Q R \vee$
 $(\exists A'. Bet A0 A1 A' \wedge Bet A0 A' B \wedge P Q R CongA A0 PO A' \wedge A0 C' Le A0 A' \wedge$
 $(\exists A. Bet A0 A A' \wedge A PO A' CongA A0 PO A1 \wedge A0 A1 Le A A'))))$
 <proof>

lemma acute-archi-aux2:
assumes $Per PO A0 B$ and
 $PO \neq A0$ and
 $B \neq A0$ and
 $Bet A0 A1 B$ and
 $A0 \neq A1$ and

Grad A0 A1 C
shows $\exists P Q R. (GradA A0 PO A1 P Q R \wedge (A0 PO B LeA P Q R \vee$
 $(\exists A'. Bet A0 A1 A' \wedge Bet A0 A' B \wedge P Q R CongA A0 PO A' \wedge A0 C Le A0 A' \wedge$
 $(\exists A. Bet A0 A A' \wedge A PO A' CongA A0 PO A1 \wedge A0 A1 Le A A'))))$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *archi-in-acute-angles:*
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C D E F. \neg Col A B C \wedge Acute D E F$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists P Q R. GradA A B C P Q R \wedge D E F LeA P Q R)$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *angles-archi-aux:*
assumes *GradA A B C D E F* **and**
GradA A B C G H I **and**
 $\neg SAMS D E F G H I$
shows $\exists P Q R. GradA A B C P Q R \wedge \neg SAMS P Q R A B C$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *angles-archi-aux1:*
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C D E F.$
 $\neg Col A B C \wedge \neg Bet D E F \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists P Q R. GradA A B C P Q R \wedge (D E F LeA P Q R \vee \neg SAMS P Q R A B C))$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *archi-in-angles:*
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C. \forall D ::'p. \forall E ::'p. \forall F ::'p. (\neg Col A B C \wedge D \neq E \wedge F \neq E) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists P Q R. GradA A B C P Q R \wedge (D E F LeA P Q R \vee \neg SAMS P Q R A B C))$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *archi--grada-destruction:*
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C. \neg Col A B C \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists P Q R. GradA A B C P Q R \wedge \neg SAMS P Q R A B C)$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *gradaexp-destruction-aux:*
assumes *GradA A B C P Q R*
shows $\exists S T U. GradAExp A B C S T U \wedge (Obtuse S T U \vee P Q R LeA S T U)$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *archi--gradaexp-destruction:*
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows $\forall A B C. \neg Col A B C \longrightarrow (\exists P Q R. GradAExp A B C P Q R \wedge Obtuse P Q R)$
⟨proof⟩

2.5 Equivalence Greenberg - Aristotle

lemma *aristotle--greenberg:*
assumes *aristotle-s-axiom*
shows *greenberg-s-axiom*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *greenberg--aristotle:*
assumes *greenberg-s-axiom*
shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
⟨proof⟩

theorem *equiv-aristotle---greenberg:*

shows *aristotle-s-axiom* \longleftrightarrow *greenberg-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

end
end

theory *Tarski-Postulate-Parallels*

imports
Tarski-Neutral-Archimedes

begin

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

3 Parallel's Postulate

3.1 Definitions

definition *tarski-s-parallel-postulate* ::

bool

(*TarskiSParallelPostulate*)

where

tarski-s-parallel-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D T.$

$Bet A D T \wedge Bet B D C \wedge A \neq D$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists X Y. Bet A B X \wedge Bet A C Y \wedge Bet X T Y)$

definition *euclid-5* ::

bool (*Euclid5*)

where

euclid-5 \equiv

$\forall P Q R S T U.$

$BetS P T Q \wedge BetS R T S \wedge BetS Q U R \wedge \neg Col P Q S \wedge Cong P T Q T \wedge Cong R T S T$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists I. BetS S Q I \wedge BetS P U I)$

definition *euclid-s-parallel-postulate* ::

bool (*EuclidSParallelPostulate*)

where

euclid-s-parallel-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D P Q R.$

$B C OS A D \wedge SAMS A B C B C D \wedge A B C B C D SumA P Q R \wedge \neg Bet P Q R$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists Y. B Out A Y \wedge C Out D Y)$

definition *playfair-s-postulate* ::

bool

(*PlayfairSPostulate*)

where

playfair-s-postulate \equiv

$\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.$

$A1 A2 Par B1 B2 \wedge Col P B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 Par C1 C2 \wedge Col P C1 C2$

\longrightarrow

$Col C1 B1 B2 \wedge Col C2 B1 B2$

definition *decidability-of-intersection* ::

bool

(*DecidabilityIntersection*)

where

decidability-of-intersection \equiv

$\forall A B C D.$

$(\exists I. Col I A B \wedge Col I C D) \vee \neg (\exists I. Col I A B \wedge Col I C D)$

definition *alternate-interior-angles-postulate* ::

bool

(*AlternateInteriorAnglesPostulate*)

where

alternate-interior-angles-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D.$

$A C TS B D \wedge A B Par C D$

\longrightarrow

$B A C Cong A D C A$

definition *consecutive-interior-angles-postulate* ::

bool

(*ConsecutiveInteriorAnglesPostulate*)

where

consecutive-interior-angles-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D.$

$B C OS A D \wedge A B Par C D$

\longrightarrow

$A B C Supp A B C D$

definition *alternative-playfair-s-postulate* ::

bool

(*AlternativePlayfairSPostulate*)

where

alternative-playfair-s-postulate \equiv

$\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.$

$P Perp2 A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge \neg Col A1 A2 P \wedge Col P B1 B2 \wedge$

$Coplanar A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 Par C1 C2 \wedge Col P C1 C2$

\longrightarrow

$Col C1 B1 B2 \wedge Col C2 B1 B2$

definition *proclus-postulate* ::

bool

(*ProclusPostulate*)

where

proclus-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D P Q.$

$A B Par C D \wedge Col A B P \wedge \neg Col A B Q \wedge Coplanar C D P Q$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists Y. Col P Q Y \wedge Col C D Y)$

definition *triangle-postulate* ::

bool

(*TrianglePostulate*)

where

triangle-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D E F.$

$A B C TriSum A D E F$

\longrightarrow

$Bet D E F$

definition *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom* ::

bool

(*BachmannsLotschnittaxiom*)

where

bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom \equiv

$\forall P Q R P1 R1.$

$(P \neq Q \wedge Q \neq R \wedge Per P Q R \wedge Per Q P P1 \wedge Per Q R R1 \wedge$
 $Coplanar P Q R P1 \wedge Coplanar P Q R R1$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists S. Col P P1 S \wedge Col R R1 S))$

definition *legendre-s-parallel-postulate* ::

bool

(*LegendresParallelPostulate*)

where

legendre-s-parallel-postulate \equiv

$\exists A B C.$

$\neg Col A B C \wedge$

$Acute A B C \wedge$

$(\forall T. T InAngle A B C \longrightarrow (\exists X Y. B Out A X \wedge B Out C Y \wedge Bet X T Y))$

definition *weak-inverse-projection-postulate* ::

bool

(*WeakInverseProjectionPostulate*)

where

weak-inverse-projection-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C D E F P Q.$

$((Acute A B C \wedge Per D E F \wedge A B C A B C Sum A D E F \wedge$
 $B Out A P \wedge P \neq Q \wedge Per B P Q \wedge Coplanar A B C Q)$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists Y. B Out C Y \wedge Col P Q Y))$

definition *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle* ::

bool

(*WeakTriangleCircumscriptionPrinciple*)

where

weak-triangle-circumscription-principle \equiv

$\forall A B C A1 A2 B1 B2.$

$(\neg Col A B C \wedge Per A C B \wedge A1 A2 PerpBisect B C \wedge$

$B1 B2 PerpBisect A C \wedge Coplanar A B C A1 \wedge Coplanar A B C A2 \wedge$

$Coplanar A B C B1 \wedge Coplanar A B C B2$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists I. Col A1 A2 I \wedge Col B1 B2 I))$

definition *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate* ::

bool

(*WeakTarskiParallelPostulate*)

where

weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C T.$

$(Per A B C \wedge T InAngle A B C$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists X Y. B Out A X \wedge B Out C Y \wedge Bet X T Y))$

definition *existential-playfair-s-postulate* ::

bool

(*ExistentialPlayfairPostulate*)

where

existential-playfair-s-postulate \equiv

$\exists A1 A2 P.$

$\neg \text{Col } A1 \ A2 \ P \wedge$

$(\forall \ B1 \ B2 \ C1 \ C2.$

$A1 \ A2 \ \text{Par } B1 \ B2 \wedge \text{Col } P \ B1 \ B2 \wedge A1 \ A2 \ \text{Par } C1 \ C2 \wedge \text{Col } P \ C1 \ C2$

\longrightarrow

$(\text{Col } C1 \ B1 \ B2 \wedge \text{Col } C2 \ B1 \ B2))$

definition *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals* ::

bool

(PostulateRightSaccheriQuadrilaterals)

where

postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals \equiv

$\forall \ A \ B \ C \ D.$

Saccheri $A \ B \ C \ D$

\longrightarrow

Per $A \ B \ C$

definition *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral* ::

bool

(PostulateExistenceRightSaccheriQuadrilateral)

where

postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral \equiv

$\exists \ A \ B \ C \ D.$

Saccheri $A \ B \ C \ D \wedge \text{Per } A \ B \ C$

definition *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights* ::

bool

(PostulateExistenceTriangleAnglesSumTwoRights)

where

postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights \equiv

$\exists \ A \ B \ C \ D \ E \ F.$

$\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C \wedge A \ B \ C \ \text{TriSum} \ A \ D \ E \ F \wedge \text{Bet } D \ E \ F$

definition *inverse-projection-postulate* ::

bool

(InverseProjectionPostulate)

where

inverse-projection-postulate \equiv

$\forall \ A \ B \ C \ P \ Q.$

Acute $A \ B \ C \wedge B \ \text{Out } A \ P \wedge P \neq Q \wedge \text{Per } B \ P \ Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ Q$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists \ Y. B \ \text{Out } C \ Y \wedge \text{Col } P \ Q \ Y)$

definition *alternative-proclus-postulate* ::

bool

(AlternativeProclusPostulate)

where

alternative-proclus-postulate \equiv

$\forall \ A \ B \ C \ D \ P \ Q.$

$P \ \text{Perp2 } A \ B \ C \ D \wedge \neg \text{Col } C \ D \ P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D \wedge \text{Col } A \ B \ P \wedge$

$\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } C \ D \ P \ Q$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists \ Y. (\text{Col } P \ Q \ Y \wedge \text{Col } C \ D \ Y))$

definition *strong-parallel-postulate* ::

bool

(StrongParallelPostulate)

where

strong-parallel-postulate \equiv

$\forall P Q R S T U.$
 $BetS P T Q \wedge BetS R T S \wedge \neg Col P R U \wedge Coplanar P Q R U \wedge$
 $Cong P T Q T \wedge Cong R T S T$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\exists I. (Col S Q I \wedge Col P U I))$

definition *triangle-circumscription-principle* ::

bool
 $(TriangleCircumscriptionPrinciple)$ **where**
triangle-circumscription-principle \equiv

$\forall A B C.$
 $\neg Col A B C$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\exists D. Cong A D B D \wedge Cong A D C D \wedge Coplanar A B C D)$

definition *thales-converse-postulate*::

bool
 $(ThalesConversePostulate)$ **where**
thales-converse-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C M.$
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge Per A C B$
 \longrightarrow
 $Cong M A M C$

definition *existential-thales-postulate* ::

bool
 $(ExistentialThalesPostulate)$ **where**
existential-thales-postulate \equiv

$\exists A B C M.$
 $\neg Col A B C \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge Cong M A M C \wedge Per A C B$

definition *thales-postulate*::

bool
 $(ThalesPostulate)$ **where**
thales-postulate \equiv

$\forall A B C M.$
 $M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge Cong M A M C$
 \longrightarrow
 $Per A C B$

definition *posidonius-postulate* ::

bool
 $(PosidoniusPostulate)$ **where**
posidonius-postulate \equiv

$\exists A1 A2 B1 B2.$
 $\neg Col A1 A2 B1 \wedge B1 \neq B2 \wedge Coplanar A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge$
 $(\forall A3 A4 B3 B4.$
 $Col A1 A2 A3 \wedge Col B1 B2 B3 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A3 B3 \wedge$
 $Col A1 A2 A4 \wedge Col B1 B2 B4 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A4 B4$
 \longrightarrow
 $Cong A3 B3 A4 B4)$

definition *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals* ::

bool
 $(PostulateOfRightLambertQuadrilaterals)$ **where**
postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals \equiv

$\forall A B C D.$
Lambert A B C D
 \longrightarrow
Per B C D

definition *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral* ::
bool
(PostulateExistenceRightLambertQuadrilateral) **where**
postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral \equiv
 $\exists A B C D.$
Lambert A B C D \wedge *Per B C D*

definition *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles* ::
bool
(PostulateOfExistenceOfSimilarTriangles) **where**
postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles \equiv
 $\exists A B C D E F.$
 \neg *Col A B C* \wedge \neg *Cong A B D E* \wedge *A B C Cong A D E F* \wedge
B C A Cong A E F D \wedge *C A B Cong A F D E*

definition *midpoint-converse-postulate* ::
bool
(MidpointConversePostulate) **where**
midpoint-converse-postulate \equiv
 $\forall A B C P Q.$
 \neg *Col A B C* \wedge *P Midpoint B C* \wedge *A B Par Q P* \wedge *Col A C Q*
 \longrightarrow
Q Midpoint A C

definition *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism* ::
bool
(PostulateOfTransitivityOfParallelism) **where**
postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism \equiv
 $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2.$
A1 A2 Par B1 B2 \wedge *B1 B2 Par C1 C2*
 \longrightarrow
A1 A2 Par C1 C2

definition *perpendicular-transversal-postulate* ::
bool
(PerpendicularTransversalPostulate) **where**
perpendicular-transversal-postulate \equiv
 $\forall A B C D P Q.$
A B Par C D \wedge *A B Perp P Q* \wedge *Coplanar C D P Q*
 \longrightarrow
C D Perp P Q

definition *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals* ::
bool
(PostulateOfParallelismOfPerpendicularTransversals) **where**
postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals \equiv
 $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2.$
A1 A2 Par B1 B2 \wedge *A1 A2 Perp C1 C2* \wedge *B1 B2 Perp D1 D2* \wedge
Coplanar A1 A2 C1 D1 \wedge *Coplanar A1 A2 C1 D2* \wedge
Coplanar A1 A2 C2 D1 \wedge *Coplanar A1 A2 C2 D2*
 \longrightarrow
C1 C2 Par D1 D2

definition *universal-posidonius-postulate* ::
bool
 (*UniversalPosidoniusPostulate*) **where**
universal-posidonius-postulate \equiv

$$\forall A1 A2 A3 A4 B1 B2 B3 B4.$$

$$A1 A2 \text{ Par } B1 B2 \wedge \text{Col } A1 A2 A3 \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 B3 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A3 B3 \wedge$$

$$\text{Col } A1 A2 A4 \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 B4 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A4 B4$$

\longrightarrow
Cong *A3 B3 A4 B4*

definition *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate* ::
bool
 (*AlternativeStrongParallelPostulate*) **where**
alternative-strong-parallel-postulate \equiv

$$\forall A B C D P Q R.$$

$$B C \text{ OS } A D \wedge A B C B C D \text{ Sum} A P Q R \wedge \neg \text{Bet } P Q R$$

\longrightarrow
 ($\exists Y. \text{Col } B A Y \wedge \text{Col } C D Y$)

definition *Postulate01* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate01 \equiv *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate02* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate02 \equiv *playfair-s-postulate*

definition *Postulate03* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate03 \equiv *triangle-postulate*

definition *Postulate04* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate04 \equiv *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*

definition *Postulate05* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate05 \equiv *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism*

definition *Postulate06* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate06 \equiv *midpoint-converse-postulate*

definition *Postulate07* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate07 \equiv *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*

definition *Postulate08* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate08 \equiv *consecutive-interior-angles-postulate*

definition *Postulate09* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate09 \equiv *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*

definition *Postulate10* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate10 \equiv *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals*

definition *Postulate11* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate11 \equiv *universal-posidonius-postulate*

definition *Postulate12* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate12 \equiv *alternative-playfair-s-postulate*

definition *Postulate13* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate13 \equiv *proclus-postulate*

definition *Postulate14* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate14 \equiv *alternative-proclus-postulate*

definition *Postulate15* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate15 \equiv *triangle-circumscription-principle*

definition *Postulate16* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate16 \equiv *inverse-projection-postulate*

definition *Postulate17* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate17 \equiv *euclid-5*

definition *Postulate18* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate18 \equiv *strong-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate19* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate19 \equiv *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate20* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate20 \equiv *euclid-s-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate21* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate21 \equiv *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*

definition *Postulate22* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate22 \equiv *posidonius-postulate*

definition *Postulate23* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate23 \equiv *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles*

definition *Postulate24* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate24 \equiv *thales-postulate*

definition *Postulate25* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate25 \equiv *thales-converse-postulate*

definition *Postulate26* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate26 \equiv *existential-thales-postulate*

definition *Postulate27* :: *bool* **where**
Postulate27 \equiv *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*

definition *Postulate28* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate28 \equiv *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral*

definition *Postulate29* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate29 \equiv *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals*

definition *Postulate30* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate30 \equiv *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral*

definition *Postulate31* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate31 \equiv *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*

definition *Postulate32* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate32 \equiv *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate33* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate33 \equiv *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*

definition *Postulate34* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate34 \equiv *legendre-s-parallel-postulate*

definition *Postulate35* :: *bool* **where**

Postulate35 \equiv *existential-playfair-s-postulate*

3.2 Propositions

lemma *euclid-5--original-euclid*:

assumes *Euclid5*

shows *EuclidSParallelPostulate*

<proof>

lemma *tarski-s-euclid-implies-euclid-5*:

assumes *TarskiSParallelPostulate*

shows *Euclid5*

<proof>

lemma *tarski-s-implies-euclid-s-parallel-postulate*:

assumes *TarskiSParallelPostulate*

shows *EuclidSParallelPostulate*

<proof>

theorem *tarski-s-euclid-implies-playfair-s-postulate*:

assumes *TarskiSParallelPostulate*

shows *PlayfairSPostulate*

<proof>

lemma *tarski-s-euclid-remove-degenerated-cases*:

assumes $\forall A B C D T. A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge A \neq D \wedge$

$A \neq T \wedge B \neq C \wedge B \neq D \wedge B \neq T \wedge C \neq D \wedge$

$C \neq T \wedge D \neq T \wedge \neg Col A B C \wedge Bet A D T \wedge$

$Bet B D C \wedge \neg Col B C T \longrightarrow$

$(\exists x y. (Bet A B x \wedge Bet A C y \wedge Bet x T y))$

shows $\forall A B C D T. Bet A D T \wedge Bet B D C \wedge A \neq D \longrightarrow$

$(\exists x y. (Bet A B x \wedge Bet A C y \wedge Bet x T y))$

<proof>

lemma *alternate-interior--consecutive-interior*:
assumes *AlternateInteriorAnglesPostulate*
shows *ConsecutiveInteriorAnglesPostulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--playfair-aux-1*:
assumes *A1 A2 Par C1 C2 and*
Col P C1 C2 and
Col P P1 P2 and
P1 P2 Perp A1 A2 and
Col Q A1 A2
shows *Coplanar P Q A1 C1*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--playfair-aux-2*:
assumes *A1 A2 Par C1 C2 and*
Col P C1 C2 and
Col Q A1 A2 and
Col B1 B2 B3 and
 \neg *Col A1 A2 P and*
Col P B1 B2 and
Coplanar A1 A2 B1 B2 and
A1 A2 ParStrict B1 B2
shows *Coplanar P Q C1 B3*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--playfair-aux*:
assumes *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
shows \forall *A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.*
(P Perp2 A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge \neg Col A1 A2 P \wedge Col P B1 B2 \wedge
Coplanar A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge
A1 A2 Par C1 C2 \wedge Col P C1 C2) \longrightarrow
Col C1 B1 B2
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--playfair-bis*:
assumes *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
shows *alternative-playfair-s-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--proclus-aux*:
assumes *greenberg-s-axiom and*
alternate-interior-angles-postulate
shows \forall *A C D P Q. (P A ParStrict C D \wedge C D Perp P C \wedge*
P A OS C Q \wedge P C OS Q A \wedge P C OS Q D)
 \longrightarrow
 $(\exists$ *Y. Col P Q Y \wedge Col C D Y)
⟨*proof*⟩*

lemma *alternate-interior--proclus*:
assumes *greenberg-s-axiom and*
alternate-interior-angles-postulate
shows *proclus-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *alternate-interior--triangle*:
assumes *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
shows *triangle-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom-aux-R1*:
assumes *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*
shows \forall *A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2 IAB IAC IBD.*

$IAB \neq IAC \wedge IAB \neq IBD \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } B1 B2 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } C1 C2 \wedge$
 $B1 B2 \text{ Perp } D1 D2 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A1 A2 IAB \wedge$
 $\text{Col } B1 B2 IAB \wedge \text{Col } A1 A2 IAC \wedge$
 $\text{Col } C1 C2 IAC \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 IBD \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 IBD \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C1 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D2 \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists I. \text{Col } C1 C2 I \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 I)$
 <proof>

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom-aux-R2*:
assumes $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2 IAB IAC IBD.$
 $IAB \neq IAC \wedge IAB \neq IBD \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } B1 B2 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } C1 C2 \wedge$
 $B1 B2 \text{ Perp } D1 D2 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A1 A2 IAB \wedge$
 $\text{Col } B1 B2 IAB \wedge \text{Col } A1 A2 IAC \wedge$
 $\text{Col } C1 C2 IAC \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 IBD \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 IBD \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C1 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D2 \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists I. \text{Col } C1 C2 I \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 I)$
shows *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*
 <proof>

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom-aux*:
shows *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom* \longleftrightarrow
 $(\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2 IAB IAC IBD.$
 $IAB \neq IAC \wedge IAB \neq IBD \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } B1 B2 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Perp } C1 C2 \wedge$
 $B1 B2 \text{ Perp } D1 D2 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A1 A2 IAB \wedge$
 $\text{Col } B1 B2 IAB \wedge \text{Col } A1 A2 IAC \wedge$
 $\text{Col } C1 C2 IAC \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 IBD \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 IBD \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C1 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D2 \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists I. \text{Col } C1 C2 I \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 I))$
 <proof>

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom--legendre-s-parallel-postulate*:
assumes *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*
shows *legendre-s-parallel-postulate*
 <proof>

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom--weak-inverse-projection-postulate*:
assumes *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*
shows *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*
 <proof>

lemma *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom--weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*:
assumes *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*
shows *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*
 <proof>

lemma *consecutive-interior--alternate-interior*:
assumes *consecutive-interior-angles-postulate*
shows *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
 <proof>

lemma *existential-playfair--rah-1*:
postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals \longleftrightarrow
hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *existential-playfair--rah*:
assumes *existential-playfair-s-postulate*
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *existential-saccheri--rah*:
assumes *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral*
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *existential-triangle--rah*:
assumes *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *inverse-projection-postulate--proclus-bis*:
assumes *inverse-projection-postulate*
shows *alternative-proclus-postulate*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *strong-parallel-postulate-implies-inter-dec*:
shows *decidability-of-intersection*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-1*:
assumes *Bet A B x and*
Bet C y A and
B C ParStrict x y
shows *False*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-2*:
assumes *A ≠ D and*
B ≠ D and
 \neg *Col A B C and*
Col A B x and
Bet A D T and
Bet B D C and
Bet y A C and
Bet x T y
shows *False*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-3*:
assumes
Bet A D T and
 \neg *Col B C T and*
Bet B D C and
Bet B x A and
Bet x T y and
B C ParStrict x y
shows *False*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-4-1*:
assumes *A ≠ D and*

$C \neq D$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Col } A C y$ and
 $\text{Bet } A D T$ and

$\text{Bet } B D C$ and
 $A \text{ Out } B x$ and
 $\text{Bet } T y x$

shows *False*
(proof)

lemma *impossible-case-4-2*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and

$\text{Col } A C y$ and
 $\text{Bet } A D T$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } B C T$ and
 $\text{Bet } B D C$ and
 $\text{Bet } B A x$ and
 $\text{Bet } T y x$ and
 $B C \text{ ParStrict } x y$

shows *False*
(proof)

lemma *impossible-case-4*:

assumes $A \neq D$ and

$C \neq D$ and
 $D \neq T$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Col } A C y$ and
 $\text{Bet } A D T$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } B C T$ and
 $\text{Bet } B D C$ and
 $\text{Col } A B x$ and
 $\text{Bet } T y x$ and
 $B C \text{ ParStrict } x y$

shows *False*
(proof)

lemma *impossible-two-sides-not-col*:

assumes $A \neq D$ and

$C \neq D$ and

$\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Bet } A D T$ and

$\text{Bet } B D C$ and
 $\text{Bet } B Y T$

shows $\neg \text{Col } A C Y$
(proof)

lemma *triangle-circumscription-implies-tarski-s-euclid-aux1*:

assumes *triangle-circumscription-principle* and

$B \neq D$ and
 $C \neq D$ and
 $D \neq T$ and
 $T \neq X$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{Col } A B M1$ and
 $\text{Bet } A D T$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } B C T$ and
 $\text{Bet } B D C$ and
 $\text{Col } T Y Z$ and
 $\text{Bet } Y T X$ and

Bet Y M1 Z1 and
Cong Y T T X and
Cong Y M1 M1 Z1 and
B C Perp T Z and
A B Perp Y Z1
shows $\exists x. Col A B x \wedge B C ParStrict x T \wedge Cong X x Y x$
 <proof>

lemma *triangle-circumscription-implies-tarski-s-euclid-aur:*

assumes *triangle-circumscription-principle and*
B \neq D and
C \neq D and
D \neq T and
T \neq X and
 $\neg Col A B C$ and
Col A B M1 and
Col A C M2 and
Bet A D T and
 $\neg Col B C T$ and
Bet B D C and
Col T Y Z and
Bet Y T X and
Bet Y M1 Z1 and
Bet Y M2 Z2 and
Cong Y T T X and
Cong Y M1 M1 Z1 and
Cong Y M2 M2 Z2 and
B C Perp T Z and
A B Perp Y Z1 and
A C Perp Y Z2
shows $\exists x y. Bet A B x \wedge Bet A C y \wedge Bet x T y$
 <proof>

lemma *triangle-circumscription-implies-tarski-s-euclid:*

assumes *triangle-circumscription-principle*
shows *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*
 <proof>

lemma *thales-converse-postulate--thales-existence:*

assumes *thales-converse-postulate*
shows *existential-thales-postulate*
 <proof>

lemma *thales-converse-postulate--weak-triangle-circumscription-principle:*

assumes *thales-converse-postulate*
shows *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*
 <proof>

lemma *thales-existence--rah:*

assumes *existential-thales-postulate*
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 <proof>

lemma *thales-postulate--thales-converse-postulate:*

assumes *thales-postulate*
shows *thales-converse-postulate*

⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle--existential-triangle:*

assumes *triangle-postulate*

shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*

⟨proof⟩

lemma *legendre-aux-tr:*

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and**

triangle-postulate

shows $(\forall A B C P Q. \neg($
 $Q A \text{Perp} P Q \wedge P B \text{Perp} P Q \wedge Q A \text{ParStrict} P B \wedge$
 $Q A \text{ParStrict} P C \wedge P B \text{OS} Q C \wedge P Q \text{OS} C A \wedge P Q \text{OS} C B))$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *legendre-aux1-tr:*

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and**

triangle-postulate

shows $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.$
 $(P \text{Perp2} A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge \neg \text{Col} A1 A2 P \wedge$
 $\text{Col} P B1 B2 \wedge \text{Coplanar} A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{Par} C1 C2 \wedge \text{Col} P C1 C2 \wedge$
 $\neg B1 B2 \text{TS} A1 C1)$

→

$\text{Col} C1 B1 B2$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *legendre-aux2-tr:*

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and**

triangle-postulate

shows $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.$
 $(P \text{Perp2} A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge \neg \text{Col} A1 A2 P \wedge$
 $\text{Col} P B1 B2 \wedge \text{Coplanar} A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{Par} C1 C2 \wedge \text{Col} P C1 C2)$

→

$\text{Col} C1 B1 B2$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle--playfair-bis:*

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and**

triangle-postulate

shows *alternative-playfair-s-postulate*

⟨proof⟩

lemma *rah--existential-saccheri:*

assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*

shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral*

⟨proof⟩

lemma *rah--posidonius-aux:*

assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*

shows $\forall A1 A2 A3 B1 B2 B3.$

$(\text{Per} A2 A1 B1 \wedge \text{Per} A1 A2 B2 \wedge$
 $\text{Cong} A1 B1 A2 B2 \wedge A1 A2 \text{OS} B1 B2 \wedge$
 $\text{Col} A1 A2 A3 \wedge \text{Col} B1 B2 B3 \wedge$
 $A1 A2 \text{Perp} A3 B3)$

→

$\text{Cong} A3 B3 A1 B1$

⟨proof⟩

lemma *rah--posidonius*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *posidonius-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rah--rectangle-principle*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rah--similar*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rah--thales-postulate*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *thales-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rah--triangle*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows *triangle-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rectangle-principle--rectangle-existence*:
assumes *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals*
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *similar--rah-aux*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F$ **and**
 $B C A \text{ Cong } A E F D$ **and**
 $C A B \text{ Cong } A F D E$ **and**
 $B C A \text{ Le } A A B C$ **and**
 $D E \text{ Lt } A B$
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *similar--rah*:
assumes *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles*
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-5*:
shows $\forall P Q R S U I.$
 $\neg (\text{Bet } S Q U R \wedge \neg \text{Col } P Q S \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Col } P R U \wedge P R \text{ Par } Q S \wedge$
 $\text{Bet } S Q I \wedge \text{Bet } U I P)$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *impossible-case-6*:
shows $\forall P Q R S U I.$
 $\neg (\text{Bet } S Q U R \wedge \neg \text{Col } P Q S \wedge$

$P S \text{ Par } Q R \wedge \text{Bet } S Q I \wedge \text{Bet } I P U$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *impossible-case-7:*

shows $\forall P Q R S U I.$

$\neg (\text{Bet } S Q U R \wedge \neg \text{Col } P Q S \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Col } P R U \wedge P R \text{ Par } Q S \wedge$
 $P S \text{ Par } Q R \wedge \text{Col } P U I \wedge \text{Bet } Q I S)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *impossible-case-8:*

shows $\forall P Q R S U I.$

$\neg (\text{Bet } S Q U R \wedge \neg \text{Col } P Q S \wedge$
 $P R \text{ Par } Q S \wedge P S \text{ Par } Q R \wedge$
 $\text{Col } P U I \wedge \text{Bet } I S Q)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *strong-parallel-postulate-implies-tarski-s-euclid-aux:*

assumes *strong-parallel-postulate* **and**

$A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq D$ **and**

$A \neq T$ **and**

$B \neq D$ **and**

$B \neq T$ **and**

$D \neq T$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B T$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A D T$

shows $\exists B' B'' MB X.$

$(\text{Bet } A B X \wedge T X \text{ ParStrict } B D \wedge$
 $\text{Bet } S B MB T \wedge \text{Bet } S B' MB B'' \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } B MB T MB \wedge \text{Cong } B' MB B'' MB \wedge$
 $\text{Col } B B' D \wedge \text{Bet } B'' T X \wedge$
 $B \neq B' \wedge B'' \neq T)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *strong-parallel-postulate-implies-tarski-s-euclid :*

assumes *strong-parallel-postulate*

shows *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *midpoint-converse-postulate-implies-playfair:*

assumes *midpoint-converse-postulate*

shows *playfair-s-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *playfair-implies-par-trans:*

assumes *playfair-s-postulate*

shows *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-trans-implies-playfair:*

assumes *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism*

shows *playfair-s-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-perp-perp-implies-par-perp-2-par:*

assumes *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*

shows *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-perp-2-par-implies-par-perp-perp:*

assumes *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals*

shows *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-perp-perp-implies-playfair:*

assumes *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*

shows *playfair-s-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *playfair--universal-posidonius-postulate:*

assumes *playfair-s-postulate*

shows *universal-posidonius-postulate*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *weak-inverse-projection-postulate--bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom-aux:*

assumes *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*

shows $\forall A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 Q P R M.$

$(A1 A2 \text{Perp } B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 \text{Perp } C1 C2 \wedge$

$\text{Col } A1 A2 Q \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 Q \wedge$

$\text{Col } A1 A2 P \wedge \text{Col } C1 C2 P \wedge$

$\text{Col } B1 B2 R \wedge \text{Coplanar } Q P R C1 \wedge$

$\text{Coplanar } Q P R C2 \wedge \neg \text{Col } Q P R \wedge$

$M \text{InAngle } P Q R \wedge M Q P \text{CongA } M Q R)$

\longrightarrow

$(B1 B2 \text{ParStrict } C1 C2 \wedge$

$\exists S. Q \text{Out } M S \wedge \text{Col } C1 C2 S))$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *weak-inverse-projection-postulate--bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom:*

assumes *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*

shows *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle--bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom:*

assumes *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*

shows *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *universal-posidonius-postulate--perpendicular-transversal-postulate-aux-lem:*

fixes $A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2 IAB IAC IBD$

assumes

$IAB \neq IAC$ **and**

$IAB \neq IBD$ **and**

$A1 A2 \text{Perp } B1 B2$ **and**

$A1 A2 \text{Perp } C1 C2$ **and**

$B1 B2 \text{Perp } D1 D2$ **and**

$\text{Col } A1 A2 IAB$ **and**

$\text{Col } B1 B2 IAB$ **and**

$\text{Col } A1 A2 IAC$ **and**

$\text{Col } C1 C2 IAC$ **and**

$\text{Col } B1 B2 IBD$ **and**

$\text{Col } D1 D2 IBD$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C1$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD C2$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D1$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } IAB IAC IBD D2$ **and**

postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals

shows $\exists I. \text{Col } C1 C2 I \wedge \text{Col } D1 D2 I$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *universal-posidonius-postulate--perpendicular-transversal-postulate-aux:*

assumes *universal-posidonius-postulate*

shows $\forall E F G H R P.$

$E G \text{Perp } R P \wedge \text{Coplanar } F H P R \wedge \text{Col } E G R \wedge \text{Saccheri } E F H G \longrightarrow$

$F H \text{Perp } P R$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *universal-posidonius-postulate--perpendicular-transversal-postulate:*
 assumes *universal-posidonius-postulate*
 shows *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *playfair--alternate-interior:*
 assumes *playfair-s-postulate*
 shows *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *playfair-bis--playfair:*
 assumes *alternative-playfair-s-postulate*
 shows *playfair-s-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *playfair-s-postulate-implies-midpoint-converse-postulate:*
 assumes *playfair-s-postulate*
 shows *midpoint-converse-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *inter-dec-plus-par-perp-perp-imp-ly-triangle-circumscription:*
 assumes
 perpendicular-transversal-postulate
 shows *triangle-circumscription-principle*
(*proof*)

lemma *original-euclid--original-spp:*
 assumes *euclid-s-parallel-postulate*
 shows *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *original-spp--inverse-projection-postulate:*
 assumes *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate*
 shows *inverse-projection-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *proclus-bis--proclus:*
 assumes *alternative-proclus-postulate*
 shows *proclus-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *proclus-s-postulate-implies-strong-parallel-postulate:*
 assumes *proclus-postulate*
 shows *strong-parallel-postulate*
(*proof*)

lemma *rectangle-existence--rah:*
 assumes *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral*
 shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(*proof*)

lemma *posidonius-postulate--rah:*
 assumes *posidonius-postulate*
 shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
(*proof*)

lemma *playfair--existential-playfair:*
 assumes *playfair-s-postulate*
 shows *existential-playfair-s-postulate*
(*proof*)

3.3 Equivalences

lemma *proclus--aristotle*:
 assumes *proclus-postulate*
 shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *aristotle--obtuse-case-elimination*:
 assumes *aristotle-s-axiom*
 shows \neg *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *aristotle--acute-or-right*:
 assumes *aristotle-s-axiom*
 shows *hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
 \vee
 hypothesis-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Axiom1ProofIsabelleHOL*:
 shows *Axiom1*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

theorem *equivalent-postulates-without-decidability-of-intersection-of-lines*:
 shows (*Postulate07* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate12*) \wedge
 (*Postulate12* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate08*) \wedge
 (*Postulate08* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate06*) \wedge
 (*Postulate06* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate09*) \wedge
 (*Postulate09* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate02*) \wedge
 (*Postulate02* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate11*) \wedge
 (*Postulate11* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate10*) \wedge
 (*Postulate10* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate05*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Cycle-1*:
 shows (*Postulate01* \longrightarrow *Postulate02*) \wedge
 (*Postulate09* \longrightarrow *Postulate15*) \wedge
 (*Postulate15* \longrightarrow *Postulate01*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Cycle-2*:
 shows (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate13*) \wedge
 (*Postulate13* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate14*) \wedge
 (*Postulate14* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate16*) \wedge
 (*Postulate16* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate17*) \wedge
 (*Postulate17* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate18*) \wedge
 (*Postulate18* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate19*) \wedge
 (*Postulate19* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate20*) \wedge
 (*Postulate20* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate01*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Cycle-3*:
 shows (*Postulate03* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate21*) \wedge
 (*Postulate21* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate22*) \wedge
 (*Postulate22* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate23*) \wedge
 (*Postulate23* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate24*) \wedge
 (*Postulate24* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate25*) \wedge
 (*Postulate25* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate26*) \wedge
 (*Postulate26* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate27*) \wedge
 (*Postulate27* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate28*) \wedge
 (*Postulate28* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate29*) \wedge
 (*Postulate29* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate30*) \wedge
 (*Postulate30* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate03*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterCycle1*:
assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and** *Postulate03*
shows *Postulate12*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterCycle2*:
assumes *Postulate07*
shows *Postulate03*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterCycle3*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *Postulate02*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterCycle4*:
assumes *Postulate09*
shows *Postulate15*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterAx1-R1*:
assumes *Postulate13*
shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterAx1*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterAx3*:
assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and** *Postulate02*
shows *Postulate01*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterAx4*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *Axiom1*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterAx5*:
assumes *Postulate02*
shows *Postulate01*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *PPR-Theorem-4-bis*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *greenberg-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *PPR-Proposition-6*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows *aristotle-s-axiom*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *InterCycle1bis*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *Postulate03* \longrightarrow *Postulate12*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *weak-inverse-projection-postulate--weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*:
assumes *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*
shows *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate--weak-inverse-projection-postulate-aux* :

assumes *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

shows $\forall A B C P T.$

$Per\ A\ B\ C \wedge T\ InAngle\ A\ B\ C \wedge$

$P \neq T \wedge P\ B\ A\ CongA\ P\ B\ C \wedge Per\ B\ P\ T \wedge Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ P$

\longrightarrow

$((\exists X. (B\ Out\ A\ X \wedge Col\ T\ P\ X)) \vee (\exists Y. (B\ Out\ C\ Y \wedge Col\ T\ P\ Y)))$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate--weak-inverse-projection-postulate*:

assumes *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

shows *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P31-P32*:

shows *Postulate31* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate32*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P31-P04*:

shows *Postulate31* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate04*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P04-P33*:

shows *Postulate04* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate33*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *equivalent-postulates-without-any-continuity-bis*:

shows *Postulate04* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate33* \wedge

Postulate31 \longleftrightarrow *Postulate04* \wedge

Postulate31 \longleftrightarrow *Postulate32*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P4-P34*:

assumes *Postulate04*

shows *Postulate34*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P01--P35*:

assumes *Postulate01*

shows *Postulate35*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *P35--P01*:

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom* **and**

Postulate01

shows *Postulate35*

$\langle proof \rangle$

theorem *stronger-legendre-s-first-theorem*:

assumes *aristotle-s-axiom*

shows $\forall A B C D E F. C\ A\ B\ A\ B\ C\ SumA\ D\ E\ F \longrightarrow SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ B\ C\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

theorem *legendre-s-first-theorem*:

assumes *archimedes-axiom*

shows $\forall A B C D E F. C\ A\ B\ A\ B\ C\ SumA\ D\ E\ F \longrightarrow SAMS\ D\ E\ F\ B\ C\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

theorem *legendre-s-second-theorem*:

assumes *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*

shows *triangle-postulate*

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *legendre-s-third-theorem-aux*:

assumes *aristotle-s-axiom* and
triangle-postulate
shows *euclid-s-parallel-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

theorem *legendre-s-third-theorem*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom* and
triangle-postulate
shows *euclid-s-parallel-postulate*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *legendre-aux*:
assumes \neg *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows $\forall A B C D B_1 C_1 P Q R S T U V W X.$
 \neg *Col* $A B C \wedge A C B$ *Cong* $A C B D \wedge$
Cong $A C B D \wedge B C$ *TS* $A D \wedge A$ *Out* $B B_1 \wedge A$ *Out* $C C_1 \wedge$ *Bet* $B_1 D C_1 \wedge$
Defect $A B C P Q R \wedge$ *Defect* $A B_1 C_1 S T U \wedge$ *P* $Q R P Q R$ *Sum* $A V W X \longrightarrow$
 $(SAMS P Q R P Q R \wedge V W X LeA S T U)$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *legendre-aux1*:
shows $\forall A B C B' C'.$
 \neg *Col* $A B C \wedge A$ *Out* $B B' \wedge A$ *Out* $C C' \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists D'. D' InAngle B A C \wedge A C' B' CongA C' B' D' \wedge$
Cong $A C' B' D' \wedge B' C' TS A D')$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *legendre-aux2*:
assumes \neg *hypothesis-of-obtuse-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
shows $\forall A B C.$
 \neg *Col* $A B C \wedge$ *Acute* $B A C \wedge$
 $(\forall T. T InAngle B A C \longrightarrow (\exists X Y. A Out B X \wedge A Out C Y \wedge Bet X T Y))$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\forall P Q R S T U. Defect A B C P Q R \wedge GradAExp P Q R S T U \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B' C' P' Q' R'. (A Out B B' \wedge A Out C C' \wedge$
Defect $A B' C' P' Q' R' \wedge S T U LeA P' Q' R'))$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *legendre-s-fourth-theorem-aux*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom* and
legendre-s-parallel-postulate
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
⟨*proof*⟩

theorem *legendre-s-fourth-theorem*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom* and
legendre-s-parallel-postulate
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P34-P21*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom* and
Postulate34
shows *Postulate21*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P34-P27*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom* and
Postulate34
shows *Postulate27*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P25-33*:
assumes *Postulate25*
shows *Postulate33*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P23-33*:
assumes *Postulate23*
shows *Postulate33*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P01-35*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *Postulate35*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *P35-27*:
assumes *Postulate35*
shows *Postulate27*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Thm10-1*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate02*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate03*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate04*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate05*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate06*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate07*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate08*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate09*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate10*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Thm10-2*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate11*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate12*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate13*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate14*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate15*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate16*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate17*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate18*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate19*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate20*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Thm10-3*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate21*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate22*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate23*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate24*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate25*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate26*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate27*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate28*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate29*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate30*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Thm10-4*:
assumes *archimedes-axiom*
shows (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate31*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate32*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate33*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate34*) \wedge
 (*Postulate01* \longleftrightarrow *Postulate35*)
 ⟨*proof*⟩

theorem *Thm10:*

assumes *archimedes-axiom*

shows $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate02}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate03}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate04}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate05}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate06}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate07}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate08}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate09}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate10}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate11}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate12}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate13}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate14}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate15}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate16}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate17}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate18}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate19}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate20}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate21}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate22}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate23}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate24}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate25}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate26}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate27}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate28}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate29}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate30}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate31}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate32}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate33}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate34}) \wedge$
 $(\text{Postulate01} \longleftrightarrow \text{Postulate35})$

<proof>

theorem *equivalent-postulates-assuming-greenberg-s-axiom:*

assumes *greenberg-s-axiom*

shows $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{alternate-interior-angles-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{alternative-playfair-s-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{alternative-playfair-s-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{alternative-proclus-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{alternative-strong-parallel-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{consecutive-interior-angles-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{euclid-5}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{euclid-s-parallel-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{existential-playfair-s-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{existential-thales-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{inverse-projection-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{midpoint-converse-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{perpendicular-transversal-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{playfair-s-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{posidonius-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{universal-posidonius-postulate}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate}$
 $\quad \longleftrightarrow \text{postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate}$
 $\quad \longleftrightarrow \text{postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate}$
 $\quad \longleftrightarrow \text{postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate} \longleftrightarrow \text{postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles}) \wedge$
 $(\text{tarski-s-parallel-postulate}$

\longleftrightarrow *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals*) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow proclus-postulate) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow strong-parallel-postulate) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow tarski-s-parallel-postulate) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow thales-postulate) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow thales-converse-postulate) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow triangle-circumscription-principle) \wedge
(tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow triangle-postulate)
 ⟨proof⟩

theorem *equivalent-postulates-assuming-archimedes-axiom:*

assumes *archimedes-axiom*

shows *alternate-interior-angles-postulate \longleftrightarrow alternative-playfair-s-postulate* \wedge
alternative-playfair-s-postulate \longleftrightarrow alternative-proclus-postulate \wedge
alternative-proclus-postulate \longleftrightarrow alternative-strong-parallel-postulate \wedge
alternative-strong-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom \wedge
bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom \longleftrightarrow consecutive-interior-angles-postulate \wedge
consecutive-interior-angles-postulate \longleftrightarrow euclid-5 \wedge
euclid-5 \longleftrightarrow euclid-s-parallel-postulate \wedge
euclid-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow existential-playfair-s-postulate \wedge
existential-playfair-s-postulate \longleftrightarrow existential-thales-postulate \wedge
existential-thales-postulate \longleftrightarrow inverse-projection-postulate \wedge
inverse-projection-postulate \longleftrightarrow legendre-s-parallel-postulate \wedge
legendre-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow midpoint-converse-postulate \wedge
midpoint-converse-postulate \longleftrightarrow perpendicular-transversal-postulate \wedge
perpendicular-transversal-postulate \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism \wedge
postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism \longleftrightarrow playfair-s-postulate \wedge
playfair-s-postulate \longleftrightarrow posidonius-postulate \wedge
posidonius-postulate \longleftrightarrow universal-posidonius-postulate \wedge
universal-posidonius-postulate \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral \wedge
postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral \wedge
postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights \wedge
postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles \wedge
postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals \wedge
postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals \longleftrightarrow
postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals \wedge
postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals \wedge
postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals \longleftrightarrow postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism \wedge
postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism \longleftrightarrow proclus-postulate \wedge
proclus-postulate \longleftrightarrow strong-parallel-postulate \wedge
strong-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow tarski-s-parallel-postulate \wedge
tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow thales-postulate \wedge
thales-postulate \longleftrightarrow thales-converse-postulate \wedge
thales-converse-postulate \longleftrightarrow triangle-circumscription-principle \wedge
triangle-circumscription-principle \longleftrightarrow triangle-postulate \wedge
triangle-postulate \longleftrightarrow weak-inverse-projection-postulate \wedge
weak-inverse-projection-postulate \longleftrightarrow weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate \wedge
weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate \longleftrightarrow weak-triangle-circumscription-principle

⟨proof⟩

4 Szmielew: hyperbolic plane postulate

4.1 Definition

definition *hyperbolic-plane-postulate* ::

bool

(HyperbolicPlanePostulate) **where**

hyperbolic-plane-postulate \equiv

```

 $\forall A1 A2 P.$ 
 $\neg Col A1 A2 P$ 
 $\longrightarrow$ 
 $(\exists B1 B2 C1 C2.$ 
 $A1 A2 Par B1 B2 \wedge Col P B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 Par C1 C2 \wedge Col P C1 C2 \wedge \neg Col C1 B1 B2)$ 

```

4.2 Propositions

```

lemma hpp--nP35:
  assumes greenberg-s-axiom
  shows hyperbolic-plane-postulate  $\longleftrightarrow \neg Postulate35$ 
 $\langle proof \rangle$ 

```

```

lemma aah--hpp:
  assumes hypothesis-of-acute-saccheri-quadrilaterals
  shows hyperbolic-plane-postulate
 $\langle proof \rangle$ 

```

```

theorem szmielew-s-theorem:
  assumes aristotle-s-axiom
  shows  $\forall P:: bool.$ 
     $(playfair-s-postulate \longrightarrow P) \wedge (hyperbolic-plane-postulate \longrightarrow \neg P)$ 
     $\longrightarrow$ 
     $(P \longleftrightarrow playfair-s-postulate)$ 
 $\langle proof \rangle$ 

```

```

end
end

```

```

theory Tarski-Neutral-Continuity

```

```

imports
  Tarski-Neutral

```

```

begin

```

```

context Tarski-neutral-dimensionless

```

```

begin

```

5 Continuity

5.1 Definitions

```

definition OnCircle ::
   $[ 'p, 'p, 'p ] \Rightarrow bool$ 
   $(- OnCircle - - [99,99,99] 50)$ 
  where
     $P OnCircle A B \equiv Cong A P A B$ 

```

```

definition InCircle ::
   $[ 'p, 'p, 'p ] \Rightarrow bool$ 
   $(- InCircle - - [99,99,99] 50)$ 
  where
     $P InCircle A B \equiv A P Le A B$ 

```

```

definition OutCircle ::
   $[ 'p, 'p, 'p ] \Rightarrow bool$ 
   $(- OutCircle - - [99,99,99] 50)$ 
  where
     $P OutCircle A B \equiv A B Le A P$ 

```

definition *InCircleS* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(- *InCircleS* - - [99,99,99] 50)

where

$P \text{ InCircleS } A B \equiv A P Lt A B$

definition *OutCircleS* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(- *OutCircleS* - - [99,99,99] 50)

where

$P \text{ OutCircleS } A B \equiv A B Lt A P$

definition *Diam* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Diam* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$Diam A B PO P \equiv Bet A PO B \wedge A \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$

definition *EqC* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*EqC* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$EqC A B C D \equiv$

$\forall X. (X \text{ OnCircle } A B \longleftrightarrow X \text{ OnCircle } C D)$

definition *InterCCAt* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*InterCCAt* - - - - - [99,99,99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$InterCCAt A B C D P Q \equiv$

$\neg EqC A B C D \wedge$

$P \neq Q \wedge P \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge P \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } A B$

definition *InterCC* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*InterCC* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$InterCC A B C D \equiv \exists P Q. InterCCAt A B C D P Q$

definition *TangentCC* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*TangentCC* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$TangentCC A B C D \equiv$

$\exists X. (X \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge X \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge$

$(\forall Y. (Y \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Y \text{ OnCircle } C D) \longrightarrow X = Y))$

definition *Tangent* ::

$['p, 'p, 'p, 'p] \Rightarrow bool$
(*Tangent* - - - - [99,99,99,99] 50)

where

$Tangent\ A\ B\ PO\ P \equiv$
 $\exists X. (Col\ A\ B\ X \wedge X\ OnCircle\ PO\ P \wedge$
 $(\forall Y. (Col\ A\ B\ Y \wedge Y\ OnCircle\ PO\ P) \longrightarrow X = Y))$

definition *TangentAt* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(TangentAt\ -\ -\ -\ -\ [99,99,99,99]\ 50)$

where

$TangentAt\ A\ B\ PO\ P\ T \equiv Tangent\ A\ B\ PO\ P \wedge Col\ A\ B\ T \wedge T\ OnCircle\ PO\ P$

definition *Concyclic* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(Concyclic\ -\ -\ -\ -\ [99,99,99,99]\ 50)$

where

$Concyclic\ A\ B\ C\ D \equiv Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ D \wedge$
 $(\exists PO\ P. A\ OnCircle\ PO\ P \wedge B\ OnCircle\ PO\ P \wedge$
 $C\ OnCircle\ PO\ P \wedge D\ OnCircle\ PO\ P)$

definition *ConcyclicGen* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(ConcyclicGen\ -\ -\ -\ -\ [99,99,99,99]\ 50)$

where

$ConcyclicGen\ A\ B\ C\ D \equiv$
 $Concyclic\ A\ B\ C\ D \vee$
 $(Col\ A\ B\ C \wedge Col\ A\ B\ D \wedge Col\ A\ C\ D \wedge Col\ B\ C\ D)$

definition *Concyclic2* ::

$[p, p, p, p] \Rightarrow bool$
 $(Concyclic2\ -\ -\ -\ -\ [99,99,99,99]\ 50)$

where

$Concyclic2\ A\ B\ C\ D \equiv Coplanar\ A\ B\ C\ D \wedge$
 $(\exists P. Cong\ P\ A\ P\ B \wedge Cong\ P\ A\ P\ C \wedge Cong\ P\ A\ P\ D)$

definition *segment-circle* :: *bool*

$(SegmentCircle\ 50)$

where

$segment-circle \equiv \forall A\ B\ P\ Q. (P\ InCircle\ A\ B \wedge Q\ OutCircle\ A\ B) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists Z. Bet\ P\ Z\ Q \wedge Z\ OnCircle\ A\ B)$

definition *one-point-line-circle* :: *bool*

$(OnePointLineCircle\ 50)$

where

$one-point-line-circle \equiv \forall A\ B\ U\ V\ P.$
 $Col\ U\ V\ P \wedge U \neq V \wedge Bet\ A\ P\ B \longrightarrow (\exists Z. Col\ U\ V\ Z \wedge Z\ OnCircle\ A\ B)$

definition *two-points-line-circle* :: *bool*

$(TwoPointLineCircle\ 50)$

where

$TwoPointLineCircle \equiv \forall A\ B\ U\ V\ P.$
 $(Col\ U\ V\ P \wedge U \neq V \wedge Bet\ A\ P\ B) \longrightarrow (\exists Z1\ Z2. Col\ U\ V\ Z1 \wedge Z1\ OnCircle\ A\ B \wedge$
 $Col\ U\ V\ Z2 \wedge Z2\ OnCircle\ A\ B \wedge$
 $Bet\ Z1\ P\ Z2 \wedge (P \neq B \longrightarrow Z1 \neq Z2))$

definition *circle-circle* :: bool
 (CircleCircle 50)
where
 $circle_circle \equiv \forall A B C D P Q.$
 $(P \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge P \text{ InCircle } A B \wedge Q \text{ OutCircle } A B)$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists Z. Z \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z \text{ OnCircle } C D)$

definition *circle-circle-bis* :: bool
 (CircleCircleBis 50)
where
 $circle_circle_bis \equiv \forall A B C D P Q.$
 $(P \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge P \text{ InCircle } A B \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Q \text{ InCircle } C D)$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists Z. Z \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z \text{ OnCircle } C D)$

definition *circle-circle-axiom* :: bool
 (CircleCircleAxiom 50)
where
 $circle_circle_axiom \equiv \forall A B C D B' D'.$
 $(\text{Cong } A B' A B \wedge \text{Cong } C D' C D \wedge \text{Bet } A D' B \wedge \text{Bet } C B' D)$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists Z. \text{Cong } A Z A B \wedge \text{Cong } C Z C D)$

definition *circle-circle-two* :: bool
 (CircleCircleTwo 50)
where
 $circle_circle_two \equiv \forall A B C D P Q.$
 $(P \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge P \text{ InCircle } A B \wedge Q \text{ OutCircle } A B)$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists Z1 Z2. Z1 \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z1 \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge$
 $Z2 \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z2 \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge$
 $((P \text{ InCircleS } A B \wedge Q \text{ OutCircleS } A B) \longrightarrow Z1 \neq Z2))$

definition *euclid-s-prop-1-22* :: bool
 (EuclidsProp122 50)
where
 $euclid_s_prop_1_22 \equiv \forall A B C D E F A' B' C' D' E' F'.$
 $(A B C D \text{ SumS } E' F' \wedge A B E F \text{ SumS } C' D' \wedge C D E F \text{ SumS } A' B' \wedge$
 $E F \text{ Le } E' F' \wedge C D \text{ Le } C' D' \wedge A B \text{ Le } A' B') \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists P Q R. \text{Cong } P Q A B \wedge \text{Cong } P R C D \wedge \text{Cong } Q R E F)$

definition *Nested* ::
 $[(nat \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool), (nat \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool)] \Rightarrow bool$
 (Nested - - [99,99] 50)
where
 $Nested A B \equiv$
 $(\forall n. (\exists An Bn. A n An \wedge B n Bn)) \wedge$
 $(\forall n An Am Bm Bn.$
 $(A n An \wedge A (Suc n) Am \wedge B (Suc n) Bm \wedge B n Bn)$
 \longrightarrow
 $(Bet An Am Bm \wedge Bet Am Bm Bn \wedge Am \neq Bm))$

definition *CantorsAxiom* :: bool
 (CantorsAxiom 50)
where

$CantorsAxiom \equiv \forall A B. \text{Nested } A B \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists X. \forall n \text{ An } Bn. (A n \text{ An} \wedge B n \text{ Bn}) \longrightarrow \text{Bet An } X \text{ Bn})$

definition *DedekindsAxiom* :: bool

(*DedekindsAxiom* 50)

where

$DedekindsAxiom \equiv \forall \text{Alpha Beta}.$

$(\exists A. \forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow \text{Bet } A \text{ X } Y) \longrightarrow$

$(\exists B. \forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow \text{Bet } X \text{ B } Y)$

definition *DedekindVariant* :: bool

(*DedekindVariant* 50)

where

$DedekindVariant \equiv \forall \text{Alpha Beta} :: 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}. \forall A C.$

$(\text{Alpha } A \wedge \text{Beta } C \wedge$

$(\forall P. A \text{ Out } P C \longrightarrow (\text{Alpha } P \vee \text{Beta } P)) \wedge$

$(\forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow (\text{Bet } A \text{ X } Y \wedge X \neq Y)))$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists B. \forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow \text{Bet } X \text{ B } Y)$

definition *Alpha'Fun* :: 'p \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool)

where

$\text{Alpha}'\text{Fun } A \text{ Alpha} \equiv \lambda X :: 'p. X' = A \vee (\exists X :: 'p. \text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Bet } A \text{ X}' X)$

definition *Beta'Fun* :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool)

where

$\text{Beta}'\text{Fun } A C \text{ Alpha} \equiv \lambda Y :: 'p. A \text{ Out } Y' C \wedge \neg (\exists X :: 'p. \text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Bet } A \text{ Y}' X)$

definition *Eq* ::

$['p, 'p] \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

(*- Eq - [99,99]* 50)

where

$A \text{ Eq } B \equiv A = B$

inductive *FOF* :: bool \Rightarrow bool

where

$eq\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (A \text{ Eq } B) \text{ for } A B :: 'p$

| $bet\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (\text{Bet } A B C) \text{ for } A B C :: 'p$

| $cong\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (\text{Cong } A B C D) \text{ for } A B C D :: 'p$

| $not\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (\neg P) \text{ if } \text{FOF } P \text{ for } P :: \text{bool}$

| $and\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (P \wedge Q) \text{ if } \text{FOF } P \text{ and } \text{FOF } Q \text{ for } P Q :: \text{bool}$

| $or\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (P \vee Q) \text{ if } \text{FOF } P \text{ and } \text{FOF } Q \text{ for } P Q :: \text{bool}$

| $implies\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (P \longrightarrow Q) \text{ if } \text{FOF } P \text{ and } \text{FOF } Q \text{ for } P Q :: \text{bool}$

| $forall\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (\forall A :: 'p. P A) \text{ if } \forall A. \text{FOF } (P A) \text{ for } P :: 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

| $exists\text{-fof} : \text{FOF } (\exists A :: 'p. P A) \text{ if } \text{FOF } (P A) \text{ for } P :: 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

definition *FirstOrderDedekind* :: bool

(*FirstOrderDedekind* 50)

where

$\text{FirstOrderDedekind} \equiv$

$\forall \text{Alpha Beta} :: 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}.$

$(\forall X :: 'p. \text{FOF } (\text{Alpha } X)) \wedge$

$(\forall Y :: 'p. \text{FOF } (\text{Beta } Y)) \wedge$

$(\exists A. \forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow \text{Bet } A \text{ X } Y)$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists B. \forall X Y. (\text{Alpha } X \wedge \text{Beta } Y) \longrightarrow \text{Bet } X \text{ B } Y)$

definition *AlphaFun* :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow

'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool)

where

$\text{AlphaFun } A B C D P Q \equiv$

$\lambda X. \text{Bet } P \text{ X } Q \wedge (\exists X0. X0 \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge C \text{ Out } X X0 \wedge X0 \text{ InCircle } A B)$

definition *BetaFun* :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow

'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow ('p \Rightarrow bool)

where

$BetaFun\ A\ B\ C\ D\ P\ Q \equiv$
 $\lambda\ Y. Bet\ P\ Y\ Q \wedge (\exists\ Y0. Y0\ OnCircle\ C\ D \wedge C\ Out\ Y\ Y0 \wedge Y0\ OutCircle\ A\ B)$

definition $DedekindLemFun:: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow$
 $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$

where

$DedekindLemFun \equiv$
 $\lambda\ A\ B\ C\ D\ P\ Q. \lambda\ R. \lambda\ X\ Y. (Bet\ P\ X\ Q \wedge$
 $(\exists\ X0. X0\ OnCircle\ C\ D \wedge C\ Out\ X\ X0 \wedge X0\ InCircle\ A\ B) \wedge$
 $Bet\ P\ Y\ Q \wedge$
 $(\exists\ Y0. Y0\ OnCircle\ C\ D \wedge C\ Out\ Y\ Y0 \wedge Y0\ OutCircle\ A\ B))$
 \longrightarrow
 $Bet\ X\ R\ Y$

5.2 Propositions

lemma *inc112*:

shows $A\ InCircle\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma *onc212*:

shows $B\ OnCircle\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma *onc-sym*:

assumes $P\ OnCircle\ A\ B$
shows $B\ OnCircle\ A\ P$
<proof>

lemma *ninc--outcs*:

assumes $\neg (X\ InCircle\ PO\ P)$
shows $X\ OutCircleS\ PO\ P$
<proof>

lemma *inc--outc-1*:

assumes $P\ InCircle\ A\ B$
shows $B\ OutCircle\ A\ P$
<proof>

lemma *inc--outc-2*:

assumes $B\ OutCircle\ A\ P$
shows $P\ InCircle\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma *inc--outc*:

shows $P\ InCircle\ A\ B \longleftrightarrow B\ OutCircle\ A\ P$
<proof>

lemma *incs--outcs-1*:

assumes $P\ InCircleS\ A\ B$
shows $B\ OutCircleS\ A\ P$
<proof>

lemma *incs--outcs-2*:

assumes $B\ OutCircleS\ A\ P$
shows $P\ InCircleS\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma *incs--outcs*:

shows $P\ InCircleS\ A\ B \longleftrightarrow B\ OutCircleS\ A\ P$
<proof>

lemma *onc--inc*:

assumes $P\ OnCircle\ A\ B$
shows $P\ InCircle\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *onc--outc:*

assumes $P \text{ OnCircle } A B$

shows $P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *inc-outc--onc:*

assumes $P \text{ InCircle } A B$ **and**

$P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

shows $P \text{ OnCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *incs--inc:*

assumes $P \text{ InCircleS } A B$

shows $P \text{ InCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *outcs--outc:*

assumes $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

shows $P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *incs--noutc-1:*

assumes $P \text{ InCircleS } A B$

shows $\neg P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *incs--noutc-2:*

assumes $\neg P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

shows $P \text{ InCircleS } A B$

<proof>

lemma *incs--noutc:*

shows $P \text{ InCircleS } A B \longleftrightarrow \neg P \text{ OutCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *outcs--ninc-1:*

assumes $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

shows $\neg P \text{ InCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *outcs--ninc-2:*

assumes $\neg P \text{ InCircle } A B$

shows $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

<proof>

lemma *outcs--ninc:*

shows $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B \longleftrightarrow \neg P \text{ InCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *inc--noutcs-1:*

assumes $P \text{ InCircle } A B$

shows $\neg P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

<proof>

lemma *inc--noutcs-2:*

assumes $\neg P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

shows $P \text{ InCircle } A B$

<proof>

lemma *inc--noutcs:*

$P \text{ InCircle } A B \longleftrightarrow \neg P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$

<proof>

lemma *outc--nincs-1:*

assumes $P \text{ OutCircle } A B$
shows $\neg P \text{ InCircleS } A B$
{proof}

lemma *outc--nincs-2*:
assumes $\neg P \text{ InCircleS } A B$
shows $P \text{ OutCircle } A B$
{proof}

lemma *outc--nincs*:
shows $P \text{ OutCircle } A B \longleftrightarrow \neg P \text{ InCircleS } A B$
{proof}

lemma *inc-eq*:
assumes $P \text{ InCircle } A A$
shows $A = P$
{proof}

lemma *outc-eq*:
assumes $A \text{ OutCircle } A B$
shows $A = B$
{proof}

lemma *onc2--cong*:
assumes $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$
shows $\text{Cong } PO A PO B$
{proof}

lemma *bet-inc2--incs*:
assumes $X \neq U$ **and**
 $X \neq V$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } U X V$ **and**
 $U \text{ InCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $V \text{ InCircle } PO P$
shows $X \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
{proof}

lemma *bet-incs2--incs*:
assumes $\text{Bet } U X V$ **and**
 $U \text{ InCircleS } PO P$ **and**
 $V \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
shows $X \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
{proof}

lemma *bet-inc2--inc*:
assumes $U \text{ InCircle } A B$ **and**
 $V \text{ InCircle } A B$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } U P V$
shows $P \text{ InCircle } A B$
{proof}

lemma *col-inc-onc2--bet*:
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $\text{Col } U V P$ **and**
 $P \text{ InCircle } A B$
shows $\text{Bet } U P V$
{proof}

lemma *onc2-out--outcs:*
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $P \text{ Out } U V$
shows $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-inc2-outcs--out:*
assumes $U \text{ InCircle } A B$ **and**
 $V \text{ InCircle } A B$ **and**
 $Col U V P$ **and**
 $P \text{ OutCircleS } A B$
shows $P \text{ Out } U V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-onc2--mid:*
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $Col U V A$
shows $A \text{ Midpoint } U V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *chord-completion:*
assumes $U \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $P \text{ InCircle } A B$
shows $\exists V. V \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge \text{Bet } U P V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *outcs-exists:*
shows $\exists Q. Q \text{ OutCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *outcs-exists1:*
assumes $X \neq PO$
shows $\exists Q. PO \text{ Out } X Q \wedge Q \text{ OutCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *incs-exists:*
assumes $PO \neq P$
shows $\exists Q. Q \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *incs-exists1:*
assumes $X \neq PO$ **and**
 $P \neq PO$
shows $\exists Q. PO \text{ Out } X Q \wedge Q \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *onc-exists*:

assumes $X \neq PO$ and
 $PO \neq P$

shows $\exists Q. Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge PO \text{ Out } X Q$
(proof)

lemma *diam-points*:

shows $\exists Q1 Q2. \text{Bet } Q1 PO Q2 \wedge \text{Col } Q1 Q2 X \wedge Q1 \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge Q2 \text{ OnCircle } PO P$
(proof)

lemma *symmetric-encircle*:

assumes $PO \text{ Midpoint } X Y$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO P$

shows $Y \text{ OnCircle } PO P$
(proof)

lemma *mid-enc2--per*:

assumes $U \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and
 $V \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and

$X \text{ Midpoint } U V$
shows $\text{Per } PO X U$
(proof)

lemma *mid-enc2--perp*:

assumes $PO \neq X$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and
 $X \text{ Midpoint } A B$

shows $PO X \text{ Perp } A B$
(proof)

lemma *col-enc2--perp--mid*:

assumes $PO \neq X$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $\text{Col } A B X$ and
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ and
 $PO X \text{ Perp } A B$

shows $X \text{ Midpoint } A B$
(proof)

lemma *circle-circle-os*:

assumes $I \text{ OnCircle } A B$ and
 $I \text{ OnCircle } C D$ and

$\neg \text{Col } A C I$ and
 $\neg \text{Col } A C P$

shows $\exists Z. Z \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge A C \text{ OS } P Z$
(proof)

lemma *circle-circle-cop*:
assumes $I \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**
 $I \text{ OnCircle } C D$
shows $\exists Z. Z \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge \text{Coplanar } A C P Z$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *line-circle-two-points*:
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $\text{Col } U V W$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $W \text{ OnCircle } PO P$
shows $W = U \vee W = V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *onc2-mid--incs*:
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $M \text{ Midpoint } U V$
shows $M \text{ InCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circle-cases*:
shows $X \text{ OnCircle } PO P \vee X \text{ InCircleS } PO P \vee X \text{ OutCircleS } PO P$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inc--radius*:
assumes $X \text{ InCircle } PO P$
shows $\exists Y. Y \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge \text{Bet } PO X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inc-onc2-out--eq*:
assumes $A \text{ InCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $C \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $A \text{ Out } B C$
shows $B = C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *onc-not-center*:
assumes $PO \neq P$ **and**
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$
shows $A \neq PO$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *onc2-per--mid*:
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $M \neq U$ **and**
 $U \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $V \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**
 $\text{Col } M U V$ **and**
 $\text{Per } PO M U$
shows $M \text{ Midpoint } U V$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-chord-cong-center*:
assumes A *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 B *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 C *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 D *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 M *Midpoint* A B **and**
 N *Midpoint* C D **and**
Cong A B C D
shows *Cong* PO N PO M
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *cong-chord-cong-center1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $M \neq A$ **and**
 $N \neq C$
 A *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 B *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 C *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 D *OnCircle* PO P **and**
Col M A B **and**
Col N C D **and**
Per PO M A **and**
Per PO N C **and**
Cong A B C D
shows *Cong* PO N PO M
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *onc-sym--onc*:
assumes *Bet* PO A B **and**
 A *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 B *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 X *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 X Y *ReflectL* A B
shows Y *OnCircle* PO P
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *mid-onc--diam*:
assumes A *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 PO *Midpoint* A B
shows *Diam* A B PO P
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *chord-le-diam*:
assumes *Diam* A B PO P **and**
 U *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 V *OnCircle* PO P
shows U V *Le* A B
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *chord-lt-diam*:
assumes \neg *Col* PO U V **and**
Diam A B PO P **and**
 U *OnCircle* PO P **and**
 V *OnCircle* PO P
shows U V *Lt* A B
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *inc2-le-diam*:
assumes *Diam* A B PO P **and**

$U \text{ InCircle } PO \ P$ and
 $V \text{ InCircle } PO \ P$
shows $U \ V \text{ Le } A \ B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *onc-col-diam--eq*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$ and
 $Col \ A \ B \ X$
shows $X = A \vee X = B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-onc-le-a*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $Bet \ B \ PO \ T$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$
shows $T \ A \text{ Le } T \ X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-onc-lt-a* :
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $PO \neq P$ and
 $PO \neq T$ and
 $X \neq A$ and
 $Bet \ B \ PO \ T$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$
shows $T \ A \text{ Lt } T \ X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-onc-le-b*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $Bet \ A \ PO \ T$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$
shows $T \ X \text{ Le } T \ A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-onc-lt-b*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $T \neq PO$ and
 $X \neq A$ and
 $Bet \ A \ PO \ T$ and
 $X \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$
shows $T \ X \text{ Lt } T \ A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *incs2-lt-diam*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $U \text{ InCircleS } PO \ P$ and
 $V \text{ InCircleS } PO \ P$
shows $U \ V \text{ Lt } A \ B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *incs-onc-diam--lt*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $U \text{ InCircleS } PO \ P$ and
 $V \text{ OnCircle } PO \ P$
shows $U \ V \text{ Lt } A \ B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *diam-cong-incs--outcs*:
assumes $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \ P$ and
 $Cong \ A \ B \ U \ V$ and
 $U \text{ InCircleS } PO \ P$
shows $V \text{ OutCircleS } PO \ P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *diam-uniqueness*:

assumes *Diam A B PO P* **and**

Cong A X A B **and**

X OnCircle PO P

shows $X = B$

<proof>

lemma *onc3--ncol*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

A OnCircle PO P **and**

B OnCircle PO P **and**

C OnCircle PO P

shows $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

lemma *diam-exists*:

shows $\exists A B. \text{Diam } A B PO P \wedge \text{Col } A B T$

<proof>

lemma *chord-intersection*:

assumes *A OnCircle PO P* **and**

B OnCircle PO P **and**

X OnCircle PO P **and**

Y OnCircle PO P **and**

A B TS X Y

shows $X Y TS A B$

<proof>

lemma *ray-cut-chord*:

assumes *Diam A B PO P* **and**

X OnCircle PO P **and**

Y OnCircle PO P **and**

A B TS X Y **and**

X Y OS PO A

shows $X Y TS PO B$

<proof>

lemma *center-col--diam*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

Col PO A B **and**

A OnCircle PO P **and**

B OnCircle PO P

shows *Diam A B PO P*

<proof>

lemma *diam--midpoint*:

assumes *Diam A B PO P*

shows *PO Midpoint A B*

<proof>

lemma *diam-sym*:

assumes *Diam A B PO P*

shows *Diam B A PO P*

<proof>

lemma *diam-end-uniqueness*:

assumes *Diam A B PO P* **and**

Diam A C PO P

shows $B = C$

<proof>

lemma *center-onc2-mid--ncol*:

assumes

$\neg \text{Col } PO A B$ **and**

M Midpoint A B
shows $\neg \text{Col } A \text{ } PO \text{ } M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-chord--diam-or-ncol:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $T \neq A$ **and**
 $T \neq B$ **and**
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $Bet \ A \ T \ B$
shows $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \text{ } P \vee \neg \text{Col } PO \ A \ T \wedge \neg \text{Col } PO \ B \ T$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *mid-chord--diam-or-ncol:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $T \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$
shows $Diam \ A \ B \ PO \text{ } P \vee \neg \text{Col } PO \ A \ T \wedge \neg \text{Col } PO \ B \ T$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-mid-onc2-perp--col:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $X \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$ **and**
 $X \ Y \text{ Perp } A \ B$ **and**
 $Coplanar \ PO \ A \ B \ Y$
shows $\text{Col } X \ Y \ PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-cop2-onc3--eq:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $C \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$ **and**
 $Coplanar \ A \ B \ C \ PO$ **and**
 $Cong \ X \ A \ X \ B$ **and**
 $Cong \ X \ A \ X \ C$ **and**
 $Coplanar \ A \ B \ C \ X$
shows $X = PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tree-points-onc-cop:*

assumes $PO \neq P$
shows $\exists A \ B \ C. A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge$
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge C \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge$
 $Coplanar \ A \ B \ C \ PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tree-points-onc-cop2:*

assumes $PO \neq P$
shows $\exists A \ B \ C. A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge$
 $A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge C \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge$
 $Coplanar \ A \ B \ C \ PO \wedge Coplanar \ A \ B \ C \ Q$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tree-points-onc:*

assumes $PO \neq P$
shows $\exists A \ B \ C.$
 $A \neq B \wedge A \neq C \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge B \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P \wedge C \text{ OnCircle } PO \text{ } P$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-cop-onc2--ex-onc-os-out*:

assumes $A \neq I$ **and**

$B \neq I$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B PO$ **and**

$A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$\text{Bet } A I B$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B C PO$

shows $\exists C1. C1 \text{ Out } PO I \wedge C1 \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge A B OS C C1$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-chara-1*:

assumes $\text{EqC } A B C D$

shows $A = C \wedge \text{Cong } A B C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-chara-2*:

assumes $A = C$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B C D$

shows $\text{EqC } A B C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-chara*:

shows $\text{EqC } A B C D \longleftrightarrow (A = C \wedge \text{Cong } A B C D)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *neqc-chara-1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\neg \text{EqC } A B C D$

shows $\exists X. X \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge \neg X \text{ OnCircle } C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *neqc-chara-2*:

assumes

$X \text{ OnCircle } A B$ **and**

$\neg X \text{ OnCircle } C D$

shows $\neg \text{EqC } A B C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *neqc-chara*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $\neg \text{EqC } A B C D \longleftrightarrow (\exists X. X \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge \neg X \text{ OnCircle } C D)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-refl*:

shows $\text{EqC } A B A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-sym*:

assumes $\text{EqC } A B C D$

shows $\text{EqC } C D A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqc-trans*:

assumes $\text{EqC } A B C D$ **and**

$\text{EqC } C D E F$

shows $\text{EqC } A B E F$

<proof>

lemma *cop2-onc6--eqc*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

$A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$C \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B C PO$ **and**

$A \text{ OnCircle } O' P'$ **and**

$B \text{ OnCircle } O' P'$ **and**

$C \text{ OnCircle } O' P'$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B C O'$

shows $\text{EqC } PO P O' P'$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-aux*:

assumes $\text{Concylic } A B C D$

shows $\exists PO P. A \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge B \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge C \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge$
 $D \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C PO$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-perm-1*:

assumes $\text{Concylic } A B C D$

shows $\text{Concylic } B C D A$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-gen-perm-1*:

assumes $\text{ConcylicGen } A B C D$

shows $\text{ConcylicGen } B C D A$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-perm-2*:

assumes $\text{Concylic } A B C D$

shows $\text{Concylic } B A C D$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-gen-perm-2*:

assumes $\text{ConcylicGen } A B C D$

shows $\text{ConcylicGen } B A C D$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-trans-1*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } P Q R$ **and**

$\text{Concylic } P Q R A$ **and**

$\text{Concylic } P Q R B$

shows $\text{Concylic } Q R A B$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-gen-trans-1*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } P Q R$ **and**

$\text{ConcylicGen } P Q R A$ **and**

$\text{ConcylicGen } P Q R B$

shows $\text{ConcylicGen } Q R A B$

<proof>

lemma *concylic-pseudo-trans*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } P Q R$ **and**

$\text{Concylic } P Q R A$ **and**

$\text{Concylic } P Q R B$ **and**

$\text{Concylic } P Q R C$ **and**

$Concyclic\ P\ Q\ R\ D$
shows $Concyclic\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *conyclic-gen-pseudo-trans*:
assumes $\neg\ Col\ P\ Q\ R$ **and**
 $ConcyclicGen\ P\ Q\ R\ A$
 $ConcyclicGen\ P\ Q\ R\ B$
 $ConcyclicGen\ P\ Q\ R\ C$
 $ConcyclicGen\ P\ Q\ R\ D$
shows $ConcyclicGen\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Concyclic--Concyclic2*:
assumes $Concyclic\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Concyclic2\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Concyclic2--Concyclic*:
assumes $Concyclic2\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $Concyclic\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *TangentCC-Col*:
assumes $TangentCC\ A\ B\ C\ D$ **and**
 $X\ OnCircle\ A\ B$ **and**
 $X\ OnCircle\ C\ D$
shows $Col\ X\ A\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tangent-neq*:
assumes $PO \neq P$ **and**
 $Tangent\ A\ B\ PO\ P$
shows $A \neq B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *diam-not-tangent*:
assumes $P \neq PO$ **and**
 $Col\ PO\ A\ B$
shows $\neg\ Tangent\ A\ B\ PO\ P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tangent-out*:
assumes $X \neq T$ **and**
 $Col\ A\ B\ X$ **and**
 $TangentAt\ A\ B\ PO\ P\ T$
shows $X\ OutCircleS\ PO\ P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tangentat-perp*:
assumes $PO \neq P$ **and**
 $TangentAt\ A\ B\ PO\ P\ T$
shows $A\ B\ Perp\ PO\ T$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *tangency-chara-R1*:

assumes $P \neq PO$ **and**

$\exists X. (X \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge X \text{ PerpAt } A B PO X)$

shows $Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara-R2*:

assumes $P \neq PO$ **and**

$Tangent A B PO P$

shows $\exists X. (X \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge X \text{ PerpAt } A B PO X)$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara*:

assumes $P \neq PO$

shows $(\exists X. (X \text{ OnCircle } PO P \wedge X \text{ PerpAt } A B PO X)) \longleftrightarrow Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara2-R1*:

assumes $Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$ **and**

$(\forall X. Col A B X \longrightarrow X = Q \vee X \text{ OutCircleS } PO P)$

shows $Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara2-R2*:

assumes $Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$ **and**

$Tangent A B PO P$

shows $\forall X. Col A B X \longrightarrow X = Q \vee X \text{ OutCircleS } PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara2*:

assumes $Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$

shows $(\forall X. Col A B X \longrightarrow X = Q \vee X \text{ OutCircleS } PO P) \longleftrightarrow Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara3-R1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$ **and**

$\forall X. (Col A B X \longrightarrow X \text{ OutCircle } PO P)$

shows $Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara3-R2*:

assumes $Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$ **and**

$Tangent A B PO P$

shows $\forall X. (Col A B X \longrightarrow X \text{ OutCircle } PO P)$

<proof>

lemma *tangency-chara3*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$Q \text{ OnCircle } PO P$ **and**

$Col Q A B$

shows $(\forall X. (Col A B X \longrightarrow X \text{ OutCircle } PO P)) \longleftrightarrow Tangent A B PO P$

<proof>

lemma *intercc--neq*:

assumes $InterCC A B C D$

shows $A \neq C$

<proof>

lemma *tangentcc--neg*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
TangentCC $A B C D$
shows $A \neq C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *interccat--neg*:
assumes *InterCCAt* $A B C D P Q$
shows $A \neq C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *interccat--ncol*:
assumes *InterCCAt* $A B C D P Q$
shows $\neg \text{Col } A C P$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cop-onc2--oreq*:
assumes *InterCCAt* $A B C D P Q$ **and**
Coplanar $A C P Q$ **and**
Z OnCircle $A B$ **and**
Z OnCircle $C D$ **and**
Coplanar $A C P Z$
shows $Z = P \vee Z = Q$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *tangent-construction*:
assumes *segment-circle* **and**
X OutCircle $PO P$
shows $\exists Y. \text{Tangent } X Y PO P$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *dedekind-equiv-R1*:
assumes *DedekindsAxiom*
shows *DedekindVariant*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *dedekind-equiv-R2*:
assumes *DedekindVariant*
shows *DedekindsAxiom*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *dedekind-equiv*:
shows *DedekindsAxiom* \longleftrightarrow *DedekindVariant*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *dedekind--fod*:
assumes *DedekindsAxiom*
shows *FirstOrderDedekind*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *circle-circle-aux*:
assumes $\forall A B C D P Q. (P \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge Q \text{ OnCircle } C D \wedge$
 $P \text{ InCircleS } A B \wedge Q \text{ OutCircleS } A B \wedge$
 $(A C OS P Q \vee (\text{Col } P A C \wedge \neg \text{Col } Q A C) \vee (\neg \text{Col } P A C \wedge \text{Col } Q A C)) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists Z. Z \text{ OnCircle } A B \wedge Z \text{ OnCircle } C D))$
shows *circle-circle*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *fod--circle-circle*:
assumes *FirstOrderDedekind*
shows *CircleCircle*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--diff0*:
assumes *Nested A B*
shows $\forall n \ A n \ B n. \ A \ n \ A n \ \wedge \ B \ n \ B n \ \longrightarrow \ A n \neq B n$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--sym*:
assumes *Nested A B*
shows *Nested B A*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--ex-left*:
assumes *Nested A B*
shows $\exists \ A n. \ A \ n \ A n$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--ex-right*:
assumes *Nested A B*
shows $\exists \ B n. \ B \ n \ B n$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--aux1-1*:
fixes *n::nat*
assumes *Nested A B*
shows $\forall \ A m \ B m. \ A \ n \ A n \ \wedge \ A \ (Suc \ n) \ A m \ \wedge \ B \ (Suc \ n) \ B m \ \longrightarrow \ Bet \ A n \ A m \ B m$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--aux1-2*:
fixes *n::nat*
assumes *Nested A B*
shows $(n < m \ \wedge \ (Suc \ n) \leq m) \ \longrightarrow \ ((\forall \ A m \ B m. \ A \ n \ A n \ \wedge \ A \ m \ A m \ \wedge \ B \ m \ B m \ \longrightarrow \ Bet \ A n \ A m \ B m))$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--aux1*:
fixes *n::nat*
assumes *Nested A B and*
 n < m
shows $\forall \ A m \ B m. \ A \ n \ A n \ \wedge \ A \ m \ A m \ \wedge \ B \ m \ B m \ \longrightarrow \ Bet \ A n \ A m \ B m$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--aux2*:
assumes *Nested A B and*
 n < m and
 A n An and
 A m Am and
 B n Bn
shows *Bet An Am Bn*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--bet*:
assumes *Nested A B and*
 n < n1 and
 A n An and
 A n1 An1 and
 B m Bm
shows *Bet An An1 Bm*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *nested--diff*:
assumes *Nested A B and*
 A n An and
 B m Bm

shows $An \neq Bm$
<proof>

lemma *dedekind--cantor*:
assumes *DedekindsAxiom*
shows *CantorsAxiom*
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-Continuous*

imports
Tarski-Neutral-Continuity

begin

6 Tarski Neutral Continuous

6.1 Tarski's axiom system for Neutral Continuous

locale *Tarski-Neutral-Continuous* = *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless* +
assumes *continuity* : $\forall Alpha Beta.$
 $(\exists A. \forall X Y. (Alpha X \wedge Beta Y) \longrightarrow Bet A X Y) \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists B. \forall X Y. (Alpha X \wedge Beta Y) \longrightarrow Bet X B Y)$

context *Tarski-Neutral-Continuous*

begin

6.2 Definitions

6.3 Propositions

theorem *continuity-DedekindAxiom* :
shows *DedekindsAxiom*
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-Archimedes-Continuity*

imports
Tarski-Neutral-Archimedes
Tarski-Neutral-Continuity
begin

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

7 Archimedes continuity

7.1 Definitions

definition *AlphaTmp* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where
 $AlphaTmp A B \equiv \lambda X. X = A \vee (A Out B X \wedge Reach A B A X)$

definition *BetaTmp* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where

$BetaTmp\ A\ B \equiv \lambda\ X.\ A\ Out\ B\ X \wedge \neg\ Reach\ A\ B\ A\ X$

definition $NestedBis :: (nat \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow (nat \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow bool$
where

$NestedBis\ A\ B \equiv$
 $(\forall\ n.\ \exists\ An\ Bn.\ A\ n\ An \wedge B\ n\ Bn) \wedge$
 $(\forall\ n\ An\ An'.\ A\ n\ An \wedge A\ n\ An' \longrightarrow An = An') \wedge$
 $(\forall\ n\ Bn\ Bn'.\ B\ n\ Bn \wedge B\ n\ Bn' \longrightarrow Bn = Bn') \wedge$
 $(\forall\ n\ An\ Am\ Bm\ Bn.\ A\ n\ An \wedge A\ (Suc\ n)\ Am \wedge B\ (Suc\ n)\ Bm \wedge B\ n\ Bn \longrightarrow$
 $Bet\ An\ Am\ Bm \wedge Bet\ Am\ Bm\ Bn \wedge Am \neq Bm)$

definition $CantorVariant :: bool$

where

$CantorVariant \equiv \forall\ A\ B.\ NestedBis\ A\ B \longrightarrow$
 $(\exists\ X.\ \forall\ n\ An\ Bn.\ A\ n\ An \wedge B\ n\ Bn \longrightarrow Bet\ An\ X\ Bn)$

definition $inj :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow bool$

where

$inj\ f \equiv \forall\ A\ B :: 'p.\ f\ A = f\ B \longrightarrow A = B$

definition $pres-bet :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow bool$

where

$pres-bet\ f \equiv \forall\ A\ B\ C.\ Bet\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow Bet\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

definition $pres-cong :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow bool$

where

$pres-cong\ f \equiv \forall\ A\ B\ C\ D.\ Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D \longrightarrow Cong\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)\ (f\ D)$

definition $extension :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow bool$

where

$extension\ f \equiv inj\ f \wedge pres-bet\ f \wedge pres-cong\ f$

definition $inj-line :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$

where

$inj-line\ f\ P\ Q \equiv \forall\ A\ B.\ Col\ P\ Q\ A \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ B \wedge f\ A = f\ B \longrightarrow A = B$

definition $pres-bet-line :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$

where

$pres-bet-line\ f\ P\ Q \equiv$
 $\forall\ A\ B\ C.\ Col\ P\ Q\ A \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ B \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ C \wedge Bet\ A\ B\ C$
 \longrightarrow
 $Bet\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

definition $pres-cong-line :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$

where

$pres-cong-line\ f\ P\ Q \equiv$
 $\forall\ A\ B\ C\ D.\ Col\ P\ Q\ A \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ B \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ C \wedge Col\ P\ Q\ D \wedge Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$
 \longrightarrow
 $Cong\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)\ (f\ D)$

definition $line-extension :: ('p \Rightarrow 'p) \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$

where

$line-extension\ f\ P\ Q \equiv P \neq Q \wedge inj-line\ f\ P\ Q \wedge pres-bet-line\ f\ P\ Q \wedge pres-cong-line\ f\ P\ Q$

definition $line-completeness :: bool$

where

$line-completeness \equiv archimedes-axiom \wedge$
 $(\forall\ f.\ \forall\ P\ Q.\ line-extension\ f\ P\ Q$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\forall\ A.\ Col\ (f\ P)\ (f\ Q)\ A \longrightarrow (\exists\ B.\ Col\ P\ Q\ B \wedge f\ B = A)))$

7.2 Propositions

lemma $archimedes-aux :$

assumes $\forall A B C. A \text{ Out } B C \longrightarrow \text{Reach } A B A C$
shows *ArchimedesAxiom*
<proof>

lemma *dedekind-variant--archimedes*:
assumes *DedekindVariant*
shows *archimedes-axiom*
<proof>

lemma *dedekind--archimedes*:
assumes *DedekindsAxiom*
shows *archimedes-axiom*
<proof>

lemma *nested-bis--nested*:
assumes *NestedBis A B*
shows *Nested A B*
<proof>

lemma *cantor--cantor-variant-1*:
assumes *CantorsAxiom*
shows *CantorVariant*
<proof>

lemma *cantor--cantor-variant-2*:
assumes *CantorVariant*
shows *CantorsAxiom*
<proof>

lemma *cantor--cantor-variant*:
shows *CantorsAxiom* \longleftrightarrow *CantorVariant*
<proof>

lemma *inj-line-symmetry*:
assumes *inj-line f P Q*
shows *inj-line f Q P*
<proof>

lemma *pres-bet-line-symmetry*:
assumes *pres-bet-line f P Q*
shows *pres-bet-line f Q P*
<proof>

lemma *pres-cong-line-symmetry*:
assumes *pres-cong-line f P Q*
shows *pres-cong-line f Q P*
<proof>

lemma *line-extension-symmetry*:
assumes *line-extension f P Q*
shows *line-extension f Q P*
<proof>

lemma *inj-line-stability*:
assumes *Col P Q R and*
P \neq R and
inj-line f P Q
shows *inj-line f P R*
<proof>

lemma *pres-bet-line-stability*:
assumes *Col P Q R and*
P \neq R and
pres-bet-line f P Q
shows *pres-bet-line f P R*
<proof>

lemma *pres-cong-line-stability*:

assumes $Col\ P\ Q\ R$ **and**

$P \neq R$ **and**

pres-cong-line $f\ P\ Q$

shows *pres-cong-line* $f\ P\ R$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *line-extension-stability*:

assumes $Col\ P\ Q\ R$ **and**

$P \neq R$ **and**

line-extension $f\ P\ Q$

shows *line-extension* $f\ P\ R$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *line-extension-reverse-bet*:

assumes *line-extension* $f\ P\ Q$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ A$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ B$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ C$ **and**

Bet $(f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

shows *Bet* $A\ B\ C$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *pres-bet-line--col*:

assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**

pres-bet-line $f\ P\ Q$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ A$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ B$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ C$

shows $Col\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *col2-diff-inj-line--diff*:

assumes *inj-line* $f\ P\ Q$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ A$ **and**

$Col\ P\ Q\ B$ **and**

$A \neq B$

shows $f\ A \neq f\ B$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *extension--line-extension*:

assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**

extension f

shows *line-extension* $f\ P\ Q$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *extension-reverse-bet*:

assumes *extension* f **and**

Bet $(f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

shows *Bet* $A\ B\ C$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *extension-reverse-col*:

assumes *extension* f **and**

$Col\ (f\ A)\ (f\ B)\ (f\ C)$

shows $Col\ A\ B\ C$

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *line-completeness-aux*:

assumes *line-completeness* **and**

archimedes-axiom **and**

extension f **and**

$\neg\ Col\ P\ Q\ R$ **and**

$Coplanar (f P) (f Q) (f R) A$
shows $\exists B. Coplanar P Q R B \wedge f B = A$
 <proof>

lemma *segment-circle--one-point-line-circle-R1*:
assumes *SegmentCircle*
shows *OnePointLineCircle*
 <proof>

lemma *segment-circle--one-point-line-circle-R2*:
assumes *OnePointLineCircle*
shows *SegmentCircle*
 <proof>

lemma *segment-circle--one-point-line-circle*:
shows *SegmentCircle* \longleftrightarrow *OnePointLineCircle*
 <proof>

lemma *one-point-line-circle--two-points-line-circle-R1* :
assumes *one-point-line-circle*
shows *two-points-line-circle*
 <proof>

lemma *one-point-line-circle--two-points-line-circle-R2* :
assumes *two-points-line-circle*
shows *one-point-line-circle*
 <proof>

lemma *one-point-line-circle--two-points-line-circle* :
shows *one-point-line-circle* \longleftrightarrow *two-points-line-circle*
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle-bis--circle-circle-axiom-R1*:
assumes *circle-circle-bis*
shows *circle-circle-axiom*
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle-bis--circle-circle-axiom-R2*:
assumes *circle-circle-axiom*
shows *circle-circle-bis*
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle-bis--circle-circle-axiom*:
shows *circle-circle-bis* \longleftrightarrow *circle-circle-axiom*
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle--circle-circle-bis*:
assumes *circle-circle*
shows *circle-circle-bis*
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle-bis--one-point-line-circle-aux*:
assumes *circle-circle-bis* **and**
 $Col U V P$ **and** $U \neq V$ **and** $Bet A P B$ **and** $\neg Per A U V$
shows $\exists Z. Col U V Z \wedge Z OnCircle A B$
 <proof>

lemma *circle-circle-bis--one-point-line-circle*:
assumes *circle-circle-bis*
shows *one-point-line-circle*
 <proof>

```

lemma circle-circle--circle-circle-two-R1 :
  assumes circle-circle
  shows circle-circle-two
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma circle-circle--circle-circle-two-R2 :
  assumes circle-circle-two
  shows circle-circle
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma circle-circle--circle-circle-two :
  shows circle-circle  $\longleftrightarrow$  circle-circle-two
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma euclid-22-aux:
  assumes A B C D SumS E' F' and
    C D E F SumS A' B' and
    E F Le E' F' and
    A B Le A' B' and
    A Out B C1 and
    Cong A C1 C D and
    Bet B A C2 and
    Cong A C2 C D and
    B Out A E1 and
    Cong B E1 E F
  shows Bet C1 E1 C2
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma circle-circle-bis--euclid-22:
  assumes circle-circle-bis
  shows euclid-s-prop-1-22
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma triangle-inequality1:
  assumes A B B C SumS D E
  shows A C Le D E
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma euclid-22--circle-circle:
  assumes euclid-s-prop-1-22
  shows circle-circle
  ⟨proof⟩

theorem equivalent-variants-of-circle-circle:
  shows (circle-circle  $\longleftrightarrow$  circle-circle-two)  $\wedge$ 
    (circle-circle-two  $\longleftrightarrow$  circle-circle-bis)  $\wedge$ 
    (circle-circle-bis  $\longleftrightarrow$  circle-circle-axiom)  $\wedge$ 
    (circle-circle-axiom  $\longleftrightarrow$  euclid-s-prop-1-22)
  ⟨proof⟩

theorem equivalent-variants-of-line-circle:
  shows (segment-circle  $\longleftrightarrow$  one-point-line-circle)  $\wedge$ 
    (one-point-line-circle  $\longleftrightarrow$  two-points-line-circle)
  ⟨proof⟩

end
end

theory Hilbert-Neutral

imports
  Tarski-Neutral

begin

```

8 Hilbert - Geometry - neutral dimension less

8.1 Axioms

locale *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre* =
fixes

IncidL :: 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
IncidP :: 'p ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
EqL :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
EqP :: 'c ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
IsL :: 'b ⇒ bool **and**
IsP :: 'c ⇒ bool **and**
BetH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **and**
CongH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **and**
CongaH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

context *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre*

begin

8.2 Definitions

definition *ColH* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool
where

ColH A B C ≡ (∃ l. *IsL* l ∧ *IncidL* A l ∧ *IncidL* B l ∧ *IncidL* C l)

definition *IncidLP* :: 'b ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **where**

IncidLP l p ≡ *IsL* l ∧ *IsP* p ∧ (∀ A. *IncidL* A l → *IncidP* A p)

definition *cut* :: 'b ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **where**

cut l A B ≡ *IsL* l ∧ ¬ *IncidL* A l ∧ ¬ *IncidL* B l ∧ (∃ I. *IncidL* I l ∧ *BetH* A I B)

definition *outH* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **where**

outH P A B ≡ *BetH* P A B ∨ *BetH* P B A ∨ (P ≠ A ∧ A = B)

definition *disjoint* ::

'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **where**
disjoint A B C D ≡ ¬ (∃ P. *BetH* A P B ∧ *BetH* C P D)

definition *same-side* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **where**

same-side A B l ≡ *IsL* l ∧ (∃ P. *cut* l A P ∧ *cut* l B P)

definition *same-side'* ::

'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **where**
same-side' A B X Y ≡
X ≠ Y ∧
(∀ l: 'b. (*IsL* l ∧ *IncidL* X l ∧ *IncidL* Y l) → *same-side* A B l)

definition *Para* :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **where**

Para l m ≡ *IsL* l ∧ *IsL* m ∧
(¬(∃ X. *IncidL* X l ∧ *IncidL* X m)) ∧ (∃ p. *IncidLP* l p ∧ *IncidLP* m p)

definition *Bet* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

where

Bet A B C ≡ *BetH* A B C ∨ A = B ∨ B = C

definition *Cong* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

where

Cong A B C D ≡ (*CongH* A B C D ∧ A ≠ B ∧ C ≠ D) ∨ (A = B ∧ C = D)

definition *ParaP* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

where

ParaP A B C D ≡ ∀ l m.
IsL l ∧ *IsL* m ∧ *IncidL* A l ∧ *IncidL* B l ∧ *IncidL* C m ∧ *IncidL* D m
→
Para l m

definition *is-line* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool

where

is-line A B l ≡ (IsL l ∧ A ≠ B ∧ IncidL A l ∧ IncidL B l)

definition *cut'* ::

'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

where

cut' A B X Y ≡ X ≠ Y ∧ (∀ l. (IsL l ∧ IncidL X l ∧ IncidL Y l) → cut l A B)

definition *Midpoint* :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool

(- *Midpoint* - - [99,99,99] 50)

where *M Midpoint* A B ≡ Bet A M B ∧ Cong A M M B

end

locale *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless* = *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre* IncidL IncidP EqL EqP

IsL IsP BetH CongH CongaH

for

IncidL :: 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**

IncidP :: 'p ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**

EqL :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**

EqP :: 'c ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**

IsL :: 'b ⇒ bool **and**

IsP :: 'c ⇒ bool **and**

BetH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **and**

CongH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool **and**

CongaH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool +

fixes PP PQ PR :: 'p

assumes

EqL-refl: *IsL* l → *EqL* l l **and**

EqL-sym: *IsL* l1 ∧ *IsL* l2 ∧ *EqL* l1 l2 → *EqL* l2 l1 **and**

EqL-trans: (*EqL* l1 l2 ∧ *EqL* l2 l3) → *EqL* l1 l3 **and**

EqP-refl: *IsP* p → *EqP* p p **and**

EqP-sym: *EqP* p1 p2 → *EqP* p2 p1 **and**

EqP-trans: (*EqP* p1 p2 ∧ *EqP* p2 p3) → *EqP* p1 p3 **and**

IncidL-morphism: (*IsL* l ∧ *IsL* m ∧ *IncidL* P l ∧ *EqL* l m) → *IncidL* P m **and**

IncidP-morphism: (*IsP* p ∧ *IsP* q ∧ *IncidP* M p ∧ *EqP* p q) → *IncidP* M q **and**

Is-line: *IncidL* P l → *IsL* l **and**

Is-plane: *IncidP* P p → *IsP* p

assumes

line-existence: A ≠ B → (∃ l. *IsL* l ∧ (*IncidL* A l ∧ *IncidL* B l)) **and**

line-uniqueness: A ≠ B ∧ *IsL* l ∧ *IsL* m ∧

IncidL A l ∧ *IncidL* B l ∧ *IncidL* A m ∧ *IncidL* B m →

EqL l m **and**

two-points-on-line: ∀ l. *IsL* l → (∃ A B. *IncidL* A l ∧ *IncidL* B l ∧ A ≠ B)

assumes

lower-dim-2: PP ≠ PQ ∧ PQ ≠ PR ∧ PP ≠ PR ∧ ¬ *ColH* PP PQ PR **and**

plan-existence: ∀ A B C. ((¬ *ColH* A B C) →

(∃ p. *IsP* p ∧ *IncidP* A p ∧ *IncidP* B p ∧ *IncidP* C p)) **and**

one-point-on-plane: ∀ p. ∃ A. *IsP* p → *IncidP* A p **and**

plane-uniqueness: ¬ *ColH* A B C ∧ *IsP* p ∧ *IsP* q ∧

IncidP A p ∧ *IncidP* B p ∧ *IncidP* C p ∧ *IncidP* A q ∧ *IncidP* B q ∧ *IncidP* C q →

EqP p q **and**

line-on-plane: ∀ A B l p. A ≠ B ∧ *IsL* l ∧ *IsP* p ∧

IncidL A l ∧ *IncidL* B l ∧ *IncidP* A p ∧ *IncidP* B p → *IncidLP* l p

assumes

between-diff: *BetH* A B C → A ≠ C **and**

between-col: *BetH* A B C → *ColH* A B C **and**

between-comm: *BetH* A B C → *BetH* C B A **and**

between-out: A ≠ B → (∃ C. *BetH* A B C) **and**

between-only-one: *BetH* A B C → ¬ *BetH* B C A **and**

pasch: ¬ *ColH* A B C ∧ *IsL* l ∧ *IsP* p ∧

IncidP A p ∧ *IncidP* B p ∧ *IncidP* C p ∧ *IncidLP* l p ∧ ¬ *IncidL* C l ∧

(*cut* l A B)

→

$(cut\ l\ A\ C) \vee (cut\ l\ B\ C)$

assumes

cong-permr: $CongH\ A\ B\ C\ D \longrightarrow CongH\ A\ B\ D\ C$ **and**

cong-existence: $\bigwedge A\ B\ A'\ P::'p. A \neq B \wedge A' \neq P \wedge IsL\ l \wedge$

$IncidL\ A'\ l \wedge IncidL\ P\ l \longrightarrow$

$(\exists B'. (IncidL\ B'\ l \wedge outH\ A'\ P\ B' \wedge CongH\ A'\ B'\ A\ B))$ **and**

cong-pseudo-transitivity:

$CongH\ A\ B\ C\ D \wedge CongH\ A\ B\ E\ F \longrightarrow CongH\ C\ D\ E\ F$ **and**

addition :

$ColH\ A\ B\ C \wedge ColH\ A'\ B'\ C' \wedge$

$disjoint\ A\ B\ B\ C \wedge disjoint\ A'\ B'\ B'\ C' \wedge$

$CongH\ A\ B\ A'\ B' \wedge CongH\ B\ C\ B'\ C' \longrightarrow$

$CongH\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$ **and**

cong-a-refl: $\neg ColH\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

cong-a-comm : $\neg ColH\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ C\ B\ A$ **and**

cong-a-permlr: $CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F \longrightarrow CongaH\ C\ B\ A\ F\ E\ D$ **and**

cong-a-out-conga: $(CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ D\ E\ F \wedge$

$outH\ B\ A\ A' \wedge outH\ B\ C\ C' \wedge outH\ E\ D\ D' \wedge outH\ E\ F\ F') \longrightarrow$

$CongaH\ A'\ B'\ C'\ D'\ E'\ F'$ **and**

cong-4-existence:

$\neg ColH\ P\ PO\ X \wedge \neg ColH\ A\ B\ C \longrightarrow$

$(\exists Y. (CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ X\ PO\ Y \wedge same-side'\ P\ Y\ PO\ X))$ **and**

cong-4-uniqueness:

$\neg ColH\ P\ PO\ X \wedge \neg ColH\ A\ B\ C \wedge$

$CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ X\ PO\ Y \wedge CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ X\ PO\ Y' \wedge$

$same-side'\ P\ Y\ PO\ X \wedge same-side'\ P\ Y'\ PO\ X \longrightarrow$

$outH\ PO\ Y\ Y'$ **and**

cong-5 : $\neg ColH\ A\ B\ C \wedge \neg ColH\ A'\ B'\ C' \wedge$

$CongH\ A\ B\ A'\ B' \wedge CongH\ A\ C\ A'\ C' \wedge$

$CongaH\ B\ A\ C\ B'\ A'\ C' \longrightarrow$

$CongaH\ A\ B\ C\ A'\ B'\ C'$

context *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

8.3 Propositions

lemma *betH-distincts*:

assumes *BetH* $A\ B\ C$

shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$

<proof>

lemma *congH-perm*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $CongH\ A\ B\ B\ A$

<proof>

lemma *congH-refl*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows $CongH\ A\ B\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *congH-sym*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$CongH\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $CongH\ C\ D\ A\ B$

<proof>

lemma *colH-permut-231*:

assumes $ColH\ A\ B\ C$

shows $ColH\ B\ C\ A$

<proof>

lemma *colH-permut-312*:
assumes *ColH A B C*
shows *ColH C A B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-permut-213*:
assumes *ColH A B C*
shows *ColH B A C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-permut-132*:
assumes *ColH A B C*
shows *ColH A C B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-permut-321*:
assumes *ColH A B C*
shows *ColH C B A*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *other-point-exists*:
fixes *A::'p*
shows $\exists B. A \neq B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-trivial111*:
shows *ColH A A A*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-trivial112*:
shows *ColH A A B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-trivial122*:
shows *ColH A B B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-trivial121*:
shows *ColH A B A*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-dec*:
shows $ColH A B C \vee \neg ColH A B C$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *colH-trans*:
assumes $X \neq Y$ **and**
ColH X Y A **and**
ColH X Y B **and**
ColH X Y C
shows *ColH A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-colH*:
assumes *Bet A B C*
shows *ColH A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *ncolH-exists*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. \neg ColH A B C$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *ncolH-distincts*:
assumes $\neg ColH A B C$

shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *betH-expand*:
assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $BetH\ A\ B\ C \wedge A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C \wedge ColH\ A\ B\ C$
<proof>

lemma *inter-uniquenessH*:
assumes $A' \neq B'$ **and**
 $\neg ColH\ A\ B\ A'$ **and**
 $ColH\ A\ B\ X$ **and**
 $ColH\ A\ B\ Y$ **and**
 $ColH\ A'\ B'\ X$ **and**
 $ColH\ A'\ B'\ Y$
shows $X = Y$
<proof>

lemma *inter-incid-uniquenessH*:
assumes $\neg IncidL\ P\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ P\ m$ **and**
 $IncidL\ X\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ Y\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ X\ m$ **and**
 $IncidL\ Y\ m$
shows $X = Y$
<proof>

lemma *between-only-one'*:
assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $\neg BetH\ B\ A\ C$
<proof>

lemma *betH-colH*:
assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $ColH\ A\ B\ C \wedge A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *cut-comm*:
assumes $cut\ l\ A\ B$
shows $cut\ l\ B\ A$
<proof>

lemma *line-on-plane'*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $IncidP\ A\ p$ **and**
 $IncidP\ B\ p$ **and**
 $ColH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $IncidP\ C\ p$
<proof>

lemma *inner-pasch-aux*:
assumes $\neg ColH\ B\ C\ P$ **and**
 $Bet\ A\ P\ C$ **and**
 $Bet\ B\ Q\ C$
shows $\exists X. Bet\ P\ X\ B \wedge Bet\ Q\ X\ A$
<proof>

lemma *betH-trans1*:
assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $BetH\ B\ C\ D$
shows $BetH\ A\ C\ D$
<proof>

lemma *betH-trans2*:
assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

BetH B C D
shows *BetH A B D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *betH-trans*:
assumes *BetH A B C* **and**
BetH B C D
shows *BetH A B D* \wedge *BetH A C D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *not-cut3*:
assumes *IncidP A p* **and**
IncidP B p **and**
IncidP C p **and**
IncidLP l p **and**
 \neg *IncidL A l* **and**
 \neg *ColH A B C* **and**
 \neg *cut l A B* **and**
 \neg *cut l A C*
shows \neg *cut l B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *betH-trans0*:
assumes *BetH A B C* **and**
BetH A C D
shows *BetH B C D* \wedge *BetH A B D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *betH-outh2--betH*:
assumes *BetH A B C* **and**
outh B C C' **and**
outh B A A'
shows *BetH A' B C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *cong-existence'*:
fixes *A B*: $'p$
assumes *A* \neq *B* **and**
IncidL M l
shows $\exists A' B'. \text{IncidL } A' l \wedge \text{IncidL } B' l \wedge \text{BetH } A' M B' \wedge \text{CongH } M A' A B \wedge \text{CongH } M B' A B$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *betH-to-bet*:
assumes *BetH A B C*
shows *Bet A B C* \wedge *A* \neq *B* \wedge *B* \neq *C* \wedge *A* \neq *C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *betH-line*:
assumes *BetH A B C*
shows $\exists l. \text{IncidL } A l \wedge \text{IncidL } B l \wedge \text{IncidL } C l$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *bet-identity*:
assumes *Bet A B A*
shows *A = B*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *morph*:
assumes *IsL l* **and**
IsL m **and**
EqL l m
shows $\forall A. \text{IncidL } A l \longleftrightarrow \text{IncidL } A m$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *point3-online-exists*:

assumes *IncidL A l* **and**

IncidL B l

shows $\exists C. \text{IncidL } C l \wedge C \neq A \wedge C \neq B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-betH121*:

shows $\neg \text{BetH } A B A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-identity*:

assumes *Cong A B C C*

shows $A = B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cong-inner-transitivity*:

assumes *Cong A B C D* **and**

Cong A B E F

shows *Cong C D E F*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *other-point-on-line*:

assumes *IncidL A l*

shows $\exists B. A \neq B \wedge \text{IncidL } B l$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-disjoint*:

assumes *BetH A B C*

shows *disjoint A B B C*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *addition-betH*:

assumes *BetH A B C* **and**

BetH A' B' C' **and**

CongH A B A' B' **and**

CongH B C B' C'

shows *CongH A C A' C'*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *outH-trivial*:

assumes $A \neq B$

shows *outH A B B*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-side-refl*:

assumes *IsL l* **and**

$\neg \text{IncidL } A l$

shows *same-side A A l*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-side-prime-refl*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } A B C$

shows *same-side' C C A B*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *outH-expand*:

assumes *outH A B C*

shows $\text{outH } A B C \wedge \text{ColH } A B C \wedge A \neq C \wedge A \neq B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *construction-uniqueness*:

assumes $BetH\ A\ B\ D$ **and**

$BetH\ A\ B\ E$ **and**

$CongH\ B\ D\ B\ E$

shows $D = E$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-distinct*:

assumes $outH\ A\ B\ C$

shows $A \neq B \wedge A \neq C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out-same-side*:

assumes $IncidL\ A\ l$ **and**

$\neg\ IncidL\ B\ l$ **and**

$outH\ A\ B\ C$

shows *same-side* $B\ C\ l$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *between-one*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

$ColH\ A\ B\ C$

shows $BetH\ A\ B\ C \vee BetH\ B\ C\ A \vee BetH\ B\ A\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *betH-dec*:

shows $BetH\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg\ BetH\ A\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cut2-not-cut*:

assumes $\neg\ ColH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$cut\ l\ A\ B$ **and**

$cut\ l\ A\ C$

shows $\neg\ cut\ l\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *strong-pasch*:

assumes $\neg\ ColH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$IncidP\ A\ p$ **and**

$IncidP\ B\ p$ **and**

$IncidP\ C\ p$ **and**

$IncidLP\ l\ p$ **and**

$\neg\ IncidL\ C\ l$ **and**

$cut\ l\ A\ B$

shows $(cut\ l\ A\ C \wedge \neg\ cut\ l\ B\ C) \vee (cut\ l\ B\ C \wedge \neg\ cut\ l\ A\ C)$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out2-out*:

assumes $C \neq D$ **and**

$BetH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$BetH\ A\ B\ D$

shows $BetH\ B\ C\ D \vee BetH\ B\ D\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *out2-out1*:

assumes $C \neq D$ **and**

$BetH\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

$BetH\ A\ B\ D$

shows $BetH\ A\ C\ D \vee BetH\ A\ D\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *betH2-out*:

assumes $B \neq C$ **and**

$BetH A B D$ and
 $BetH A C D$
shows $BetH A B C \vee BetH A C B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *segment-construction*:
shows $\exists E. Bet A B E \wedge Cong B E C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *lower-dim-e*:
shows $\exists A B C. \neg (Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B)$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *outH-dec*:
shows $outH A B C \vee \neg outH A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *out-construction*:
assumes $X \neq Y$ and
 $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. CongH A C X Y \wedge outH A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *segment-constructionH*:
assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $C \neq D$
shows $\exists E. BetH A B E \wedge CongH B E C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *EqL-dec*:
shows $EqL l m \vee \neg EqL l m$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cut-exists*:
assumes $IsL l$ and
 $\neg IncidL A l$
shows $\exists B. cut l A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *outH-col*:
assumes $outH A B C$
shows $ColH A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cut-distinct*:
assumes $cut l A B$
shows $A \neq B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side-not-cut*:
assumes $same-side A B l$
shows $\neg cut l A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *IncidLP-morphism*:
assumes
 $IsL m$ and
 $IsP q$ and
 $IncidLP l p$ and
 $EqL l m$ and
 $EqP p q$
shows $IncidLP m q$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side--plane*:
assumes $same-side A B l$

shows $\exists p. \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidLP } l \ p$
<proof>

lemma *same-side-prime--plane*:

assumes *same-side'* $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $\exists p. \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } C \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } D \ p$
<proof>

lemma *cut-same-side-cut*:

assumes *cut* $l \ P \ X$ **and**
same-side $X \ Y \ l$

shows *cut* $l \ P \ Y$
<proof>

lemma *isosceles-congaH*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } A \ B \ C$ **and**
CongH $A \ B \ A \ C$

shows *CongaH* $A \ B \ C \ A \ C \ B$
<proof>

lemma *cong-distincts*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Cong $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $C \neq D$
<proof>

lemma *cong-sym*:

assumes *Cong* $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows *Cong* $C \ D \ A \ B$
<proof>

lemma *cong-trans*:

assumes *Cong* $A \ B \ C \ D$ **and**
Cong $C \ D \ E \ F$

shows *Cong* $A \ B \ E \ F$
<proof>

lemma *betH-not-congH*:

assumes *BetH* $A \ B \ C$

shows $\neg \text{CongH } A \ B \ A \ C$
<proof>

lemma *congH-permlr*:

assumes
 $C \neq D$ **and**
CongH $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows *CongH* $B \ A \ D \ C$
<proof>

lemma *congH-perms*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
CongH $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows *CongH* $B \ A \ C \ D \wedge \text{CongH } A \ B \ D \ C \wedge \text{CongH } C \ D \ A \ B \wedge$
CongH $D \ C \ A \ B \wedge \text{CongH } C \ D \ B \ A \wedge \text{CongH } D \ C \ B \ A \wedge \text{CongH } B \ A \ D \ C$
<proof>

lemma *congH-perml*:

assumes
 $C \neq D$ **and**
CongH $A \ B \ C \ D$

shows *CongH* $B \ A \ C \ D$
<proof>

lemma *bet-cong3-bet*:
assumes $A' \neq B'$ **and**
 $B' \neq C'$ **and**
 $A' \neq C'$ **and**
BetH $A B C$ **and**
ColH $A' B' C'$ **and**
CongH $A B A' B'$ **and**
CongH $B C B' C'$ **and**
CongH $A C A' C'$
shows *BetH* $A' B' C'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *betH-congH3-outH-betH*:
assumes *BetH* $A B C$ **and**
outH $A' B' C'$ **and**
CongH $A C A' C'$ **and**
CongH $A B A' B'$
shows *BetH* $A' B' C'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *outH-sym*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
outH $A B C$
shows *outH* $A C B$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *soustraction-betH*:
assumes *BetH* $A B C$ **and**
BetH $A' B' C'$ **and**
CongH $A B A' B'$ **and**
CongH $A C A' C'$
shows *CongH* $B C B' C'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *ncolH-expand*:
assumes \neg *ColH* $A B C$
shows \neg *ColH* $A B C \wedge A \neq B \wedge B \neq C \wedge A \neq C$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *betH-outH--outH*:
assumes *BetH* $A B C$ **and**
outH $B C D$
shows *outH* $A C D$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *th12*:
assumes \neg *ColH* $A B C$ **and**
 \neg *ColH* $A' B' C'$ **and**
CongH $A B A' B'$ **and**
CongH $A C A' C'$ **and**
CongaH $B A C B' A' C'$
shows *CongaH* $A B C A' B' C' \wedge$ *CongaH* $A C B A' C' B' \wedge$ *CongH* $B C B' C'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *th14*:
assumes \neg *ColH* $A B C$ **and**
 \neg *ColH* $A' B' C'$ **and**
CongaH $A B C A' B' C'$ **and**
BetH $A B D$ **and**
BetH $A' B' D'$
shows *CongaH* $C B D C' B' D'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *congH-colH-betH*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq I$ **and**
 $B \neq I$ **and**
 $CongH\ I\ A\ I\ B$ **and**
 $ColH\ I\ A\ B$
shows $BetH\ A\ I\ B$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *plane-separation*:
assumes $\neg ColH\ A\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $\neg ColH\ B\ X\ Y$ **and**
 $IncidP\ A\ p$ **and**
 $IncidP\ B\ p$ **and**
 $IncidP\ X\ p$ **and**
 $IncidP\ Y\ p$
shows $cut'\ A\ B\ X\ Y \vee same-side'\ A\ B\ X\ Y$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side-comm*:
assumes $same-side\ A\ B\ l$
shows $same-side\ B\ A\ l$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side-not-incid*:
assumes $same-side\ A\ B\ l$
shows $\neg IncidL\ A\ l \wedge \neg IncidL\ B\ l$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *out-same-side'*:
assumes $X \neq Y$ **and**
 $IncidL\ X\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ Y\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ A\ l$ **and**
 $\neg IncidL\ B\ l$ **and**
 $outH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $same-side'\ B\ C\ X\ Y$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side-trans*:
assumes $same-side\ A\ B\ l$ **and**
 $same-side\ B\ C\ l$
shows $same-side\ A\ C\ l$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *colH-IncidL--IncidL*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $IncidL\ A\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ B\ l$ **and**
 $ColH\ A\ B\ C$
shows $IncidL\ C\ l$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *IncidL-not-IncidL--not-colH*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $IncidL\ A\ l$ **and**
 $IncidL\ B\ l$ **and**
 $\neg IncidL\ C\ l$
shows $\neg ColH\ A\ B\ C$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *same-side-prime-not-colH*:
assumes $same-side'\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $\neg ColH\ A\ C\ D \wedge \neg ColH\ B\ C\ D$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *OS2--TS*:

assumes *same-side'* $Y Z P O X$ **and**
same-side' $X Y P O Z$
shows *cut'* $X Z P O Y$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *th15-aux-1*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } H P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H P O K$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' K'$ **and**
same-side' $H K P O L$ **and**
same-side' $H' K' O' L'$ **and**
cut' $K L P O H$ **and**
CongaH $H P O L H' O' L'$ **and**
CongaH $K P O L K' O' L'$
shows *CongaH* $H P O K H' O' K'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *th15-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } H P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H P O K$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' K'$ **and**
same-side' $H K P O L$ **and**
same-side' $H' K' O' L'$ **and**
CongaH $H P O L H' O' L'$ **and**
CongaH $K P O L K' O' L'$
shows *CongaH* $H P O K H' O' K'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *th15*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } H P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K P O L$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } K' O' L'$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H P O K$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } H' O' K'$ **and**
 $(\text{cut}' H K P O L \wedge \text{cut}' H' K' O' L') \vee (\text{same-side}' H K P O L \wedge \text{same-side}' H' K' O' L')$ **and**
CongaH $H P O L H' O' L'$ **and**
CongaH $K P O L K' O' L'$
shows *CongaH* $H P O K H' O' K'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *th17*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } X Y Z1$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } X Y Z2$ **and**
ColH $X I Y$ **and**
BetH $Z1 I Z2$ **and**
CongH $X Z1 X Z2$ **and**
CongH $Y Z1 Y Z2$
shows *CongaH* $X Y Z1 X Y Z2$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *congaH-existence-congH*:

assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } P P O X$ **and**
 $\neg \text{ColH } A B C$
shows $\exists Y. (\text{CongaH } A B C X P O Y \wedge \text{same-side}' P Y P O X \wedge \text{CongH } P O Y U V)$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *th18-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } A B C$ **and**

$\neg \text{ColH } A' B' C'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A B A' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A C A' C'$ and
 $\text{CongH } B C B' C'$
shows $\text{CongaH } B A C B' A' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *th19*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } PO A B$ and
 $\neg \text{ColH } O1 A1 B1$ and
 $\neg \text{ColH } O2 A2 B2$ and
 $\text{CongaH } A PO B A1 O1 B1$ and
 $\text{CongaH } A PO B A2 O2 B2$
shows $\text{CongaH } A1 O1 B1 A2 O2 B2$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *congaH-sym*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } A B C$ and
 $\neg \text{ColH } D E F$ and
 $\text{CongaH } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{CongaH } D E F A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *congaH-commr*:

assumes $\neg \text{ColH } A B C$ and
 $\neg \text{ColH } D E F$ and
 $\text{CongaH } A B C D E F$
shows $\text{CongaH } A B C F E D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-preserves-col*:

assumes $\text{BetH } A B C$ and
 $\text{CongH } A B A' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } B C B' C'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A C A' C'$
shows $\text{ColH } A' B' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-preserves-col-stronger*:

assumes $A \neq B$ and
 $A \neq C$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $\text{ColH } A B C$ and
 $\text{CongH } A B A' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } B C B' C'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A C A' C'$
shows $\text{ColH } A' B' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *betH-congH2--False*:

assumes $\text{BetH } A B C$ and
 $\text{BetH } A' C' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A B A' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A C A' C'$
shows *False*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-preserves-bet*:

assumes $A' \neq B'$ and
 $B' \neq C'$ and
 $A' \neq C'$ and
 $\text{BetH } A B C$ and
 $\text{CongH } A B A' B'$ and
 $\text{CongH } B C B' C'$ and
 $\text{CongH } A C A' C'$

shows $BetH A' B' C'$
(proof)

lemma *axiom-five-segmentsH*:

assumes $A \neq D$ **and**
 $A' \neq D'$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $B' \neq D'$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
 $C' \neq D'$ **and**
 $CongH A B A' B'$ **and**
 $CongH B C B' C'$ **and**
 $CongH A D A' D'$ **and**
 $CongH B D B' D'$ **and**
 $BetH A B C$ **and**
 $BetH A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A' \neq D'$
shows $CongH C D C' D'$
(proof)

lemma *five-segment*:

assumes $Cong A B A' B'$ **and**
 $Cong B C B' C'$ **and**
 $Cong A D A' D'$ **and**
 $Cong B D B' D'$ **and**
 $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $Bet A' B' C'$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $Cong C D C' D'$
(proof)

lemma *bet-comm*:

assumes $Bet A B C$
shows $Bet C B A$
(proof)

lemma *bet-trans*:

assumes $Bet A B D$ **and**
 $Bet B C D$
shows $Bet A B C$
(proof)

lemma *cong-transitivity*:

assumes $Cong A B E F$ **and**
 $Cong C D E F$
shows $Cong A B C D$
(proof)

lemma *cong-permT*:

shows $Cong A B B A$
(proof)

lemma *pasch-general-case*:

assumes $Bet A P C$ **and**
 $Bet B Q C$ **and**
 $A \neq P$ **and**
 $P \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq Q$ **and**
 $Q \neq C$ **and**
 $\neg (Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B)$
shows $\exists x. Bet P x B \wedge Bet Q x A$
(proof)

lemma *lower-dim-l*:

shows $\neg (Bet PP PQ PR \vee Bet PQ PR PP \vee Bet PR PP PQ)$
(proof)

```

lemma ColH-bets:
  assumes ColH A B C
  shows Bet A B C  $\vee$  Bet B C A  $\vee$  Bet C A B
  <proof>

end
end

```

```
theory Tarski-Neutral-Hilbert
```

```

imports
  Tarski-Neutral
  Hilbert-Neutral

```

```
begin
```

9 Tarski neutral dimensionless - Hilbert

```
context Tarski-neutral-dimensionless
```

```
begin
```

9.1 Definition

```

definition isLine:: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  isLine l  $\equiv$  (fst l  $\neq$  snd l)

```

```

definition Line :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p where
  Line A B = (if A  $\neq$  B then (Pair A B) else undefined)

```

```

definition IncidentL :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  IncidentL A l  $\equiv$  isLine l  $\wedge$  Col A (fst l) (snd l)

```

```

definition EqTL:: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool
  (- =l= - [99,99] 50) where
  l1 =l= l2  $\equiv$  isLine l1  $\wedge$  isLine l2  $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  X. (IncidentL X l1  $\longleftrightarrow$  IncidentL X l2))

```

```

definition Col-H:: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  Col-H A B C  $\equiv$   $\exists$  l. (isLine l  $\wedge$  IncidentL A l  $\wedge$  IncidentL B l  $\wedge$  IncidentL C l)

```

```

definition isPlane :: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  isPlane pl  $\equiv$  ( $\forall$  P Q R::'p. pl = (P,Q,R)  $\longrightarrow$   $\neg$  Col P Q R)

```

```

definition Plane :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p where
  Plane A B C = (A,B,C)

```

```

definition IncidentP :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool
  where
  IncidentP A pl  $\equiv$  (isPlane pl)  $\wedge$  ( $\exists$  P Q R. pl = Plane P Q R  $\wedge$  Coplanar A P Q R)

```

```

definition EqTP:: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool (- =p= - [99,99] 50) where
  p1 =p= p2  $\equiv$  isPlane p1  $\wedge$  isPlane p2  $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  X. (IncidentP X p1  $\longleftrightarrow$  IncidentP X p2))

```

```

definition IncidentLP :: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  IncidentLP l p  $\equiv$  isLine l  $\wedge$  isPlane p  $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  A. IncidentL A l  $\longrightarrow$  IncidentP A p)

```

```

definition Between-H :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  Between-H A B C  $\equiv$  Bet A B C  $\wedge$  A  $\neq$  B  $\wedge$  B  $\neq$  C  $\wedge$  A  $\neq$  C

```

```

definition cut-H :: 'p  $\times$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where
  cut-H l A B  $\equiv$  isLine l  $\wedge$   $\neg$  IncidentL A l  $\wedge$   $\neg$  IncidentL B l  $\wedge$ 
    ( $\exists$  I. IncidentL I l  $\wedge$  Between-H A I B)

```

```

definition outH :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool where

```

$outH P A B \equiv Between-H P A B \vee Between-H P B A \vee (P \neq A \wedge A = B)$

definition *same-side-scott* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where *same-side-scott* $E A B \equiv E \neq A \wedge E \neq B \wedge Col-H E A B \wedge \neg Between-H A E B$

definition *disjoint-H* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where *disjoint-H* $A B C D \equiv (\exists P. Between-H A P B \wedge Between-H C P D)$

definition *same-side-H* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \times 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where *same-side-H* $A B l \equiv isLine l \wedge (\exists P. cut-H l A P \wedge cut-H l B P)$

definition *same-side'-H* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$
where
same-side'-H $A B X Y \equiv X \neq Y \wedge (\forall l. isLine l \wedge (IncidentL X l \wedge IncidentL Y l) \rightarrow same-side-H A B l)$

definition *CongA-H* :: $'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
CongA-H $A B C D E F \equiv A B C CongA D E F$

definition *Para-H* :: $'p \times 'p \Rightarrow 'p \times 'p \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
Para-H $l m \equiv isLine l \wedge isLine m \wedge (\neg(\exists X. IncidentL X l \wedge IncidentL X m)) \wedge (\exists p. IncidentLP l p \wedge IncidentLP m p)$

9.2 Propositions

lemma *EqL--diff-left*:
assumes $l1 =l= l1$
shows $fst l1 \neq snd l1$
<proof>

lemma *EqL--diff-right*:
assumes $l1 =l= l2$
shows $(fst l2) \neq (snd l2)$
<proof>

lemma *axiom-line-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists l. isLine l \wedge IncidentL A l \wedge IncidentL B l$
<proof>

lemma *incident-eq*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $IncidentL A l$ **and**
 $IncidentL B l$
shows $Line A B =l= l$
<proof>

lemma *eq-transitivity*:
assumes $l =l= m$ **and**
 $m =l= n$
shows $l =l= n$
<proof>

lemma *eq-reflexivity*:
assumes $isLine l$
shows $l =l= l$
<proof>

lemma *eq-symmetry*:
assumes $l =l= m$
shows $m =l= l$
<proof>

lemma *eq-incident*:

assumes $l = l = m$
shows $\text{IncidentL } A \ l \longleftrightarrow \text{IncidentL } A \ m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *axiom-Incidl-morphism:*

assumes $\text{IncidentL } P \ l$ **and**
 $l = l = m$
shows $\text{IncidentL } P \ m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *axiom-line-uniqueness:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentL } A \ l$ **and** $\text{IncidentL } B \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentL } A \ m$ **and** $\text{IncidentL } B \ m$
shows $l = l = m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *axiom-two-points-on-line:*

assumes $\text{isLine } l$
shows $\exists A \ B. \text{IncidentL } B \ l \wedge \text{IncidentL } A \ l \wedge A \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cols-coincide-1:*

assumes $\text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cols-coincide-2:*

assumes $\text{Col } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cols-coincide:*

shows $\text{Col } A \ B \ C \longleftrightarrow \text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ncols-coincide:*

shows $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C \longleftrightarrow \neg \text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lower-dim'*:

shows $\exists PA \ PB \ PC. PA \neq PB \wedge PB \neq PC \wedge$
 $PA \neq PC \wedge \neg \text{Col-H } PA \ PB \ PC$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *axiom-plane-existence:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
shows $\exists p. \text{IncidentP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidentP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidentP } C \ p$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *incidentp-eqp:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } A \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } B \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } C \ p$
shows $(\text{Plane } A \ B \ C) = p = p$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eqp-transitivity:*

assumes $p =p= q$ **and**
 $q =p= r$
shows $p =p= r$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *eqp-reflexivity*:
assumes *isPlane* p
shows $p =p= p$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *eqp-symmetry*:
assumes $p =p= q$
shows $q =p= p$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *eqp-incidentp*:
assumes $p =p= q$
shows $\text{IncidentP } A \ p \longleftrightarrow \text{IncidentP } A \ q$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-Incidp-morphism* :
assumes $\text{IncidentP } M \ p$ **and**
 $\text{EqTP } p \ q$
shows $\text{IncidentP } M \ q$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-plane-uniqueness*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } A \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } B \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } C \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } A \ q$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } B \ q$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } C \ q$
shows $p =p= q$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-one-point-on-plane*:
assumes *isPlane* p
shows $\exists A. \text{IncidentP } A \ p$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-line-on-plane*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentL } A \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentL } B \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } A \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidentP } B \ p$
shows $\text{IncidentLP } l \ p$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-between-col*:
assumes $\text{Between-H } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col-H } A \ B \ C$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-between-diff*:
assumes *Between-H A B C*
shows $A \neq C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *axiom-between-comm*:
assumes *Between-H A B C*
shows *Between-H C B A*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *axiom-between-out*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. \textit{Between-H A B C}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *axiom-between-only-one*:
assumes *Between-H A B C*
shows $\neg \textit{Between-H B C A}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *between-one*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $\textit{Col A B C}$
shows $\textit{Between-H A B C} \vee \textit{Between-H B C A} \vee \textit{Between-H B A C}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *axiom-between-one*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $\textit{Col-H A B C}$
shows $\textit{Between-H A B C} \vee \textit{Between-H B C A} \vee \textit{Between-H B A C}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cut-two-sides*:
shows $\textit{cut-H l A B} \longleftrightarrow (\textit{fst l}) (\textit{snd l}) \textit{TS A B}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cop-plane-aux*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D* **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $\exists p. \textit{IncidentP A p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP B p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP C p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP D p}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *cop-plane*:
assumes *Coplanar A B C D*
shows $\exists p. \textit{IncidentP A p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP B p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP C p} \wedge \textit{IncidentP D p}$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plane-cop*:
assumes *IncidentP A p* **and**
IncidentP B p **and**
IncidentP C p **and**
IncidentP D p

shows *Coplanar A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *axiom-pasch*:
assumes \neg *Col-H A B C* **and**
 IncidentP A p **and**
 IncidentP B p **and**
 IncidentP C p **and**
 IncidentLP l p **and**
 \neg *IncidentL C l* **and**
 cut-H l A B
shows *cut-H l A C* \vee *cut-H l B C*
<proof>

lemma *Incid-line*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 IncidentL A l **and**
 IncidentL B l **and**
 Col P A B
shows *IncidentL P l*
<proof>

lemma *out-outH*:
assumes *P Out A B*
shows *outH P A B*
<proof>

lemma *axiom-hcong-1-existence*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A' \neq P$ **and**
 IncidentL A' l **and**
 IncidentL P l
shows $\exists B'. \text{IncidentL } B' l \wedge \text{outH } A' P B' \wedge \text{Cong } A' B' A B$
<proof>

lemma *axiom-hcong-1-uniqueness*:
assumes
 IncidentL M l **and**
 IncidentL A' l **and**

 IncidentL A'' l **and**

 Between-H A' M B' **and**
 Cong M A' A B **and**
 Cong M B' A B **and**
 Between-H A'' M B'' **and**
 Cong M A'' A B **and**
 Cong M B'' A B
shows $(A' = A'' \wedge B' = B'') \vee (A' = B'' \wedge B' = A'')$
<proof>

lemma *axiom-hcong-scott*:
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $P \neq Q$
shows $\exists B. \text{same-side-scott } A B C \wedge \text{Cong } P Q A B$
<proof>

lemma *col-disjoint-bet*:
assumes *Col-H A B C* **and**
disjoint-H A B B C
shows *Bet A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-hcong-3*:
assumes *Col-H A B C* **and**
Col-H A' B' C' **and**
disjoint-H A B B C **and**
disjoint-H A' B' B' C' **and**
Cong A B A' B' **and**
Cong B C B' C'
shows *Cong A C A' C'*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *exists-not-incident*:
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C. \neg \text{IncidentL } C \text{ (Line } A \text{ B)}$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *same-side-one-side*:
assumes *same-side-H A B l*
shows $(fst\ l) (snd\ l) OS\ A\ B$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *one-side-same-side*:
assumes $(fst\ l)(snd\ l) OS\ A\ B$
shows *same-side-H A B l*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *OS-distinct*:
assumes $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
shows $P \neq Q$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *OS-same-side'*:
assumes $P\ Q\ OS\ A\ B$
shows *same-side'-H A B P Q*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *same-side-OS*:
assumes *same-side'-H P Q A B*
shows $A\ B\ OS\ P\ Q$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *outH-out*:
assumes *outH P A B*
shows $P\ Out\ A\ B$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *incident-col*:
assumes *IncidentL M l*
shows $Col\ M\ (fst\ l)(snd\ l)$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *col-incident*:
assumes $(fst\ l) \neq (snd\ l)$ **and**

Col M (fst l)(snd l)
shows *IncidentL M l*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Bet-Between-H*:
assumes *Bet A B C and*
A ≠ B and
B ≠ C
shows *Between-H A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-cong-5'*:
assumes
 \neg *Col-H A' B' C' and*
Cong A B A' B' and
Cong A C A' C' and
B A C CongA B' A' C'
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-cong-5'-bis*:
assumes \neg *Col-H A B C and*

Cong A B A' B' and
Cong A C A' C' and
B A C CongA B' A' C'
shows *A B C CongA A' B' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-hcong-4-existence*:
assumes \neg *Col-H P PO X and*
 \neg *Col-H A B C*
shows $\exists Y. (A B C CongA X PO Y \wedge \text{same-side}'\text{-H } P Y PO X)$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *same-side-trans*:
assumes *same-side-H A B l and*
same-side-H B C l
shows *same-side-H A C l*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *same-side-sym*:
assumes *same-side-H A B l*
shows *same-side-H B A l*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-hcong-4-uniqueness*:
assumes \neg *Col-H P PO X and*
 \neg *Col-H A B C and*
A B C CongA X PO Y and
A B C CongA X PO Y' and
same-side}'\text{-H } P Y PO X and
same-side}'\text{-H } P Y' PO X
shows *outH PO Y Y'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-conga-comm*:
assumes \neg *Col-H A B C*
shows *A B C CongA C B A*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-congaH-outH-congaH*:
assumes *A B C CongA D E F and*
Between-H B A A' \vee Between-H B A' A \vee B ≠ A \wedge A = A' and
Between-H B C C' \vee Between-H B C' C \vee B ≠ C \wedge C = C' and
Between-H E D D' \vee Between-H E D' D \vee E ≠ D \wedge D = D' and

Between-H E F F' \vee Between-H E F' F \vee E \neq F \wedge F = F'
shows *A' B C' CongA D' E F'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-conga-permlr:*
assumes *A B C CongA D E F*
shows *C B A CongA F E D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *axiom-conga-refl:*
assumes \neg *Col-H A B C*
shows *A B C CongA A B C*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-2D*

imports
Tarski-Neutral

begin

10 Tarski's axiom system for neutral geometry: 2D

10.1 Definitions

locale *Tarski-neutral-2D = Tarski-neutral-dimensionless +*
assumes *upper-dim: \forall a b c p q.*

$$p \neq q \wedge$$

$$\text{Cong } a \ p \ a \ q \wedge$$

$$\text{Cong } b \ p \ b \ q \wedge$$

$$\text{Cong } c \ p \ c \ q$$

$$\longrightarrow$$

$$(\text{Bet } a \ b \ c \vee \text{Bet } b \ c \ a \vee \text{Bet } c \ a \ b)$$

10.2 Propositions

context *Tarski-neutral-2D*

begin

lemma *all-coplanar:*
Coplanar A B C D
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *per2--col:*
assumes *Per A X C and*
 $X \neq C$ **and**
Per B X C
shows *Col A B X*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *perp2--col:*
assumes *X Y Perp A B and*
 $X Z \text{ Perp } A B$
shows *Col X Y Z*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *l12-9-2D:*
assumes *A1 A2 Perp C1 C2 and*
 $B1 \ B2 \ \text{Perp } C1 \ C2$
shows *A1 A2 Par B1 B2*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

```

lemma perp-in2--col:
  assumes  $P \text{ PerpAt } A B X Y$  and
     $P \text{ PerpAt } A' B' X Y$ 
  shows  $Col A B A'$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

lemma perp2-trans:
  assumes  $P \text{ Perp2 } A B C D$  and
     $P \text{ Perp2 } C D E F$ 
  shows  $P \text{ Perp2 } A B E F$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

lemma perp2-par:
  assumes  $PO \text{ Perp2 } A B C D$ 
  shows  $A B \text{ Par } C D$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

lemma not-par-strict-inter-exists:
  assumes  $\neg A1 B1 \text{ ParStrict } A2 B2$ 
  shows  $\exists X. Col X A1 B1 \wedge Col X A2 B2$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

lemma not-par-inter-exists:
  assumes  $\neg A1 B1 \text{ Par } A2 B2$ 
  shows  $\exists X. Col X A1 B1 \wedge Col X A2 B2$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

end
end

```

theory *Tarski-Neutral-Continuity-2D*

```

imports
  Tarski-Neutral-2D
  Tarski-Neutral-Continuity
begin

```

```

context Tarski-neutral-2D

```

```

begin

```

11 Tarski Neutral Continuity 2D

11.1 Definitions

11.2 Propositions

```

lemma mid-onc2-perp--col:
  assumes  $A \neq B$  and
     $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$  and
     $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$  and
     $X \text{ Midpoint } A B$  and
     $X Y \text{ Perp } A B$ 
  shows  $Col X Y PO$ 
   $\langle proof \rangle$ 

```

```

lemma mid2-onc4--eq:
  assumes  $B \neq C$  and
     $A \neq B$  and
     $A \text{ OnCircle } PO P$  and
     $B \text{ OnCircle } PO P$  and
     $C \text{ OnCircle } PO P$  and

```

D OnCircle PO P and
X Midpoint A C and
X Midpoint B D
shows $X = PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong2-onc3--eq:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
A OnCircle PO P and
B OnCircle PO P and
C OnCircle PO P and
Cong X A X B and
Cong X A X C
shows $X = PO$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *onc2-mid-cong-col:*
assumes $U \neq V$ **and**
U OnCircle PO P and
V OnCircle PO P and
M Midpoint U V and
Cong U X V X
shows $Col PO X M$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cong-onc3-cases:*
assumes $Cong A X A Y$ **and**
A OnCircle PO P and
X OnCircle PO P and
Y OnCircle PO P
shows $X = Y \vee X Y ReflectL PO A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *bet-cong-onc3-cases:*
assumes $T \neq PO$ **and**
Bet A PO T and
Cong T X T Y and
A OnCircle PO P and
X OnCircle PO P and
Y OnCircle PO P
shows $X = Y \vee X Y ReflectL PO A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *prop-7-8:*
assumes $Diam A B PO P$ **and**
Bet A PO T and
X OnCircle PO P and
Y OnCircle PO P and
A PO X LeA A PO Y
shows $T Y Le T X$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *Prop-7-8-uniqueness:*
assumes $T \neq PO$ **and**
 $X \neq Y$ **and**

Cong T X T Y and
Cong T X T Z and

X OnCircle PO P and
Y OnCircle PO P and
Z OnCircle PO P

shows $Z = X \vee Z = Y$
<proof>

lemma *chords-midpoints-col-par:*

assumes

A OnCircle PO P and
B OnCircle PO P and
C OnCircle PO P and
D OnCircle PO P and
M Midpoint A B and
N Midpoint C D and
Col PO M N and
 \neg *Col PO A B and*
 \neg *Col PO C D*

shows *A B Par C D*

<proof>

lemma *onc3-mid2--ncol:*

assumes

A OnCircle PO P and
B OnCircle PO P and
C OnCircle PO P and
A' Midpoint A C and
B' Midpoint B C and
 \neg *Col A B C*

shows \neg *Col PO A' B' \vee A' = PO \vee B' = PO*

<proof>

lemma *onc4-cong2--eq:*

assumes *A \neq B and*

C \neq D and

\neg *A B Par C D and*

A OnCircle PO P and

B OnCircle PO P and

C OnCircle PO P and

D OnCircle PO P and

Cong A X B X and

Cong C X D X

shows *PO = X*

<proof>

lemma *onc2--oreq:*

assumes *InterCCAAt A B C D P Q and*

Z OnCircle A B and

Z OnCircle C D

shows *Z = P \vee Z = Q*

<proof>

end

end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-3D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

begin

12 Tarski's axiom system for neutral geometry: 3D

12.1 Definitions

locale *Tarski-neutral-3D = Tarski-neutral-dimensionless +*

fixes *TS1 and TS2 and TS3 and TS4*
assumes *lower-dim-3*: $\neg (\exists X.$
 $((Bet\ TS1\ TS2\ X \vee Bet\ TS2\ X\ TS1 \vee Bet\ X\ TS1\ TS2) \wedge$
 $(Bet\ TS3\ TS4\ X \vee Bet\ TS4\ X\ TS3 \vee Bet\ X\ TS3\ TS4) \vee$
 $(Bet\ TS1\ TS3\ X \vee Bet\ TS3\ X\ TS1 \vee Bet\ X\ TS1\ TS3) \wedge$
 $(Bet\ TS2\ TS4\ X \vee Bet\ TS4\ X\ TS2 \vee Bet\ X\ TS2\ TS4) \vee$
 $(Bet\ TS1\ TS4\ X \vee Bet\ TS4\ X\ TS1 \vee Bet\ X\ TS1\ TS4) \wedge$
 $(Bet\ TS2\ TS3\ X \vee Bet\ TS3\ X\ TS2 \vee Bet\ X\ TS2\ TS3)))$
assumes *upper-dim-3*: $\forall A\ B\ C\ P\ Q\ R.$
 $P \neq Q \wedge Q \neq R \wedge P \neq R \wedge$
 $Cong\ A\ P\ A\ Q \wedge Cong\ B\ P\ B\ Q \wedge Cong\ C\ P\ C\ Q \wedge$
 $Cong\ A\ P\ A\ R \wedge Cong\ B\ P\ B\ R \wedge Cong\ C\ P\ C\ R \longrightarrow$
 $(Bet\ A\ B\ C \vee Bet\ B\ C\ A \vee Bet\ C\ A\ B)$

context *Tarski-neutral-3D*

begin

12.2 Propositions

lemma *not-coplanar-S1-S2-S3-S4*:
shows $\neg Coplanar\ TS1\ TS2\ TS3\ TS4$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-3D-Hilbert*

imports
Tarski-Neutral-Hilbert
Tarski-Neutral-3D

begin

13 Tarski neutral dimensionless - Hilbert

context *Tarski-neutral-3D*

begin

13.1 Definition

13.2 Propositions

lemma *lower-dim-3'*:
shows $\neg (\exists p. isPlane\ p \wedge IncidentP\ TS1\ p \wedge IncidentP\ TS2\ p \wedge$
 $IncidentP\ TS3\ p \wedge IncidentP\ TS4\ p)$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

end
end

theory *Tarski-Euclidean*

imports
Tarski-Neutral
Tarski-Postulate-Parallels

begin

14 Tarski Euclidean

14.1 Tarski's axiom system for Euclidean

locale *Tarski-Euclidean* = *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless* +

assumes *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*:

$$\forall A B C D T. (\text{Bet } A D T \wedge \text{Bet } B D C \wedge A \neq D) \\ \longrightarrow \\ (\exists X Y. \text{Bet } A B X \wedge \text{Bet } A C Y \wedge \text{Bet } X T Y)$$

context *Tarski-Euclidean*

begin

14.2 Definitions

14.3 Propositions

theorem *tarski-s-parallel-postulate-thm*:

shows *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *Post02*:

shows *Postulate02*

<proof>

theorem *playfair-s-postulate-thm*:

shows *playfair-s-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *Post03*:

shows *Postulate03*

<proof>

theorem *triangle-postulate-thm*:

shows *triangle-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *Post04*:

shows *Postulate04*

<proof>

theorem *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom-thm*:

shows *bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*

<proof>

lemma *Post05*:

shows *Postulate05*

<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism-thm*:

shows *postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism*

<proof>

lemma *Post06*:

shows *Postulate06*

<proof>

theorem *midpoint-converse-postulate-thm*:

shows *midpoint-converse-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *Post07*:

shows *Postulate07*

<proof>

theorem *alternate-interior-angles-postulate-thm*:

shows *alternate-interior-angles-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post08*:
shows *Postulate08*
<proof>

theorem *consecutive-interior-angles-postulate-thm*:
shows *consecutive-interior-angles-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post09*:
shows *Postulate09*
<proof>

theorem *perpendicular-transversal-postulate-thm*:
shows *perpendicular-transversal-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post10*:
shows *Postulate10*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals*
<proof>

lemma *Post11*:
shows *Postulate11*
<proof>

theorem *universal-posidonius-postulate-thm*:
shows *universal-posidonius-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post12*:
shows *Postulate12*
<proof>

theorem *alternative-playfair-s-postulate-thm*:
shows *alternative-playfair-s-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post13*:
shows *Postulate13*
<proof>

theorem *proclus-postulate-thm*:
shows *proclus-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post14*:
shows *Postulate14*
<proof>

theorem *alternative-proclus-postulate-thm*:
shows *alternative-proclus-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post15*:
shows *Postulate15*
<proof>

theorem *triangle-circumscription-principle-thm*:
shows *triangle-circumscription-principle*
<proof>

lemma *Post16*:
shows *Postulate16*
<proof>

theorem *inverse-projection-postulate-thm*:
shows *inverse-projection-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post17*:
shows *Postulate17*
<proof>

theorem *euclid-5-thm*:
shows *euclid-5*
<proof>

lemma *Post18*:
shows *Postulate18*
<proof>

theorem *strong-parallel-postulate-thm*:
shows *strong-parallel-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post19*:
shows *Postulate19*
<proof>

theorem *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate-thm*:
shows *alternative-strong-parallel-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post20*:
shows *Postulate20*
<proof>

theorem *euclid-s-parallel-postulate-thm*:
shows *euclid-s-parallel-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post21*:
shows *Postulate21*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights*
<proof>

lemma *Post22*:
shows *Postulate22*
<proof>

theorem *posidonius-postulate-thm*:
shows *posidonius-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post23*:
assumes *Postulate01*
shows *Postulate23*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles*
<proof>

lemma *Post24*:
shows *Postulate24*
<proof>

theorem *thales-postulate-thm*:
shows *thales-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post25*:
shows *Postulate25*
<proof>

theorem *thales-converse-postulate-thm*:
shows *thales-converse-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post26*:
shows *Postulate26*
<proof>

theorem *existential-thales-postulate-thm*:
shows *existential-thales-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post27*:
shows *Postulate27*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals*
<proof>

lemma *Post28*:
shows *Postulate28*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral*
<proof>

lemma *Post29*:
shows *Postulate29*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals*
<proof>

lemma *Post30*:
shows *Postulate30*
<proof>

theorem *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral-thm*:
shows *postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral*
<proof>

lemma *Post31*:
shows *Postulate31*
<proof>

theorem *weak-inverse-projection-postulate-thm*:
shows *weak-inverse-projection-postulate*
<proof>

lemma *Post32*:
shows *Postulate32*

<proof>

theorem *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate-thm:*

shows *weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *Post33:*

shows *Postulate33*

<proof>

theorem *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle-thm:*

shows *weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*

<proof>

lemma *Post34:*

shows *Postulate34*

<proof>

theorem *legendre-s-parallel-postulate-thm:*

shows *legendre-s-parallel-postulate*

<proof>

theorem *TarskiPP:*

shows *tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *parallel-uniqueness:*

assumes *A1 A2 Par B1 B2 and*

Col P B1 B2 and

A1 A2 Par C1 C2 and

Col P C1 C2

shows *Col C1 B1 B2 \wedge Col C2 B1 B2*

<proof>

lemma *par-trans:*

assumes *A1 A2 Par B1 B2 and*

B1 B2 Par C1 C2

shows *A1 A2 Par C1 C2*

<proof>

lemma *l12-16:*

assumes *A1 A2 Par B1 B2 and*

Coplanar B1 B2 C1 C2 and

X Inter A1 A2 C1 C2

shows $\exists Y. Y \text{ Inter } B1 B2 C1 C2$

<proof>

lemma *par-dec:*

shows $A B \text{ Par } C D \vee \neg A B \text{ Par } C D$

<proof>

lemma *par-not-par:*

assumes *A B Par C D and*

$\neg A B \text{ Par } P Q$

shows $\neg C D \text{ Par } P Q$

<proof>

lemma *cop-par--inter:*

assumes *A B Par C D and*

$\neg A B \text{ Par } P Q$ **and**

Coplanar C D P Q

shows $\exists Y. Col P Q Y \wedge Col C D Y$

<proof>

lemma *l12-19:*

assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**

$A B \text{ Par } C D$ and
 $B C \text{ Par } D A$
shows $Cong A B C D \wedge Cong B C D A \wedge B D \text{ TS } A C \wedge A C \text{ TS } B D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-20-bis:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ and
 $Cong A B C D$ and
 $B D \text{ TS } A C$
shows $B C \text{ Par } D A \wedge Cong B C D A \wedge A C \text{ TS } B D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-20:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ and
 $Cong A B C D$ and
 $A C \text{ TS } B D$
shows $B C \text{ Par } D A \wedge Cong B C D A \wedge A C \text{ TS } B D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-21-a:
assumes $A C \text{ TS } B D$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $B A C \text{ Cong } A D C A$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-21:
assumes $A C \text{ TS } B D$
shows $B A C \text{ Cong } A D C A \longleftrightarrow A B \text{ Par } C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-22-a:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A C$ and
 $P A \text{ OS } B D$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $B A P \text{ Cong } A D C P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-22:
assumes $P \text{ Out } A C$ and
 $P A \text{ OS } B D$
shows $B A P \text{ Cong } A D C P \longleftrightarrow A B \text{ Par } C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma l12-23:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$
shows $\exists B' C'. A C \text{ TS } B B' \wedge A B \text{ TS } C C' \wedge Bet B' A C' \wedge$
 $A B C \text{ Cong } A B A C' \wedge A C B \text{ Cong } A C A B'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma cop2-npar--inter:
assumes $Coplanar A B X Y$ and
 $Coplanar A' B' X Y$ and
 $\neg A B \text{ Par } A' B'$
shows $\exists P. Col P X Y \wedge (Col P A B \vee Col P A' B')$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma not-par-one-not-par:
assumes $\neg A B \text{ Par } A' B'$
shows $\neg A B \text{ Par } X Y \vee \neg A' B' \text{ Par } X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma col-par-par-col:
assumes $Col A B C$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } A' B'$ and
 $B C \text{ Par } B' C'$
shows $Col A' B' C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop-par-perp--perp*:

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } P Q$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } C D P Q$

shows $C D \text{ Perp } P Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *cop4-par-perp2--par*:

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$A B \text{ Perp } E F$ **and**

$C D \text{ Perp } G H$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B E G$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B E H$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B F G$ **and**

$\text{Coplanar } A B F H$

shows $E F \text{ Par } G H$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-mid-ts*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$ **and**

$A A' \text{ TS } B B'$

shows $\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A A' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B B'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-mid-os*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$ **and**

$A A' \text{ OS } B B'$

shows $\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A B' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B A'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-cong-mid*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$

shows $\exists M. (M \text{ Midpoint } A A' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B B') \vee (M \text{ Midpoint } A B' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B A')$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-strict-cong-mid1*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$

shows $(A A' \text{ TS } B B' \wedge (\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A A' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B B')) \vee$

$(A A' \text{ OS } B B' \wedge (\exists M. M \text{ Midpoint } A B' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B A'))$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-mid*:

assumes $A B \text{ Par } A' B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$

shows $\exists M. (M \text{ Midpoint } A A' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B B') \vee$

$(M \text{ Midpoint } A B' \wedge M \text{ Midpoint } B A')$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ts-cong-par-cong-par*:

assumes $A A' \text{ TS } B B'$ **and**

$\text{Cong } A B A' B'$ **and**

$A B \text{ Par } A' B'$

shows $\text{Cong } A B' A' B \wedge A B' \text{ Par } A' B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgs-cong*:

assumes $\text{ParallelogramStrict } A B C D$

shows $\text{Cong } A B C D \wedge \text{Cong } A D B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-cong*:
assumes *Parallelogram A B C D*
shows $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D \wedge Cong\ A\ D\ B\ C$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rmb-cong*:
assumes *Rhombus A B C D*
shows $Cong\ A\ B\ B\ C \wedge Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D \wedge Cong\ A\ B\ D\ A$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rmb-per*:
assumes *M Midpoint A C* **and**
Rhombus A B C D
shows *Per A M D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *per-rmb*:
assumes *Plg A B C D* **and**
M Midpoint A C **and**
Per A M B
shows *Rhombus A B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *perp-rmb*:
assumes *Plg A B C D* **and**
A C Perp B D
shows *Rhombus A B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg-conga1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
Plg A B C D
shows $B\ A\ C\ Cong\ A\ D\ C\ A$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *os-cong-par-cong-par*:
assumes $A\ A'\ OS\ B\ B'$ **and**
 $Cong\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $A\ B\ Par\ A'\ B'$
shows $Cong\ A\ A'\ B\ B' \wedge A\ A'\ Par\ B\ B'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgs-permut*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
shows *ParallelogramStrict B C D A*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg-permut*:
assumes *Parallelogram A B C D*
shows *Parallelogram B C D A*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgs-mid*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
shows $\exists\ M. M\ Midpoint\ A\ C \wedge M\ Midpoint\ B\ D$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg-mid*:
assumes *Parallelogram A B C D*
shows $\exists\ M. M\ Midpoint\ A\ C \wedge M\ Midpoint\ B\ D$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg-mid-2*:
assumes *Parallelogram A B C D* **and**
I Midpoint A C

shows I Midpoint $B D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-not-comm-1*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramStrict* $A B D C$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-not-comm-2*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramStrict* $B A C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-not-comm*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows \neg *ParallelogramStrict* $A B D C \wedge \neg$ *ParallelogramStrict* $B A C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plg-not-comm-R1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows \neg *Parallelogram* $A B D C$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plg-not-comm-R2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows \neg *Parallelogram* $B A C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plg-not-comm*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows \neg *Parallelogram* $A B D C \wedge \neg$ *Parallelogram* $B A C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *parallelogram-to-plg*:
assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
shows *Plg* $A B C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *parallelogram-equiv-plg*:
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D \longleftrightarrow$ *Plg* $A B C D$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *plg-conga*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

 $B \neq C$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows $A B C$ *Cong* $A C D A \wedge B C D$ *Cong* $A D A B$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *half-plgs-R1*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$ **and**
 P Midpoint $A B$ **and**
 Q Midpoint $C D$ **and**
 M Midpoint $A C$
shows $P Q$ *Par* $A D \wedge$ *Cong* $A D P Q$
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *half-plgs-R2*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$ **and**
 P Midpoint $A B$ **and**
 Q Midpoint $C D$ **and**
 M Midpoint $A C$

shows M Midpoint P Q
 \langle proof \rangle

lemma *half-plgs*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D **and**

P Midpoint A B **and**

Q Midpoint C D **and**

M Midpoint A C

shows P Q Par A D \wedge M Midpoint P Q \wedge *Cong* A D P Q

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-two-sides*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D

shows A C *TS* B D \wedge B D *TS* A C

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-par-strict*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D

shows A B ParStrict C D \wedge A D ParStrict B C

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-half-plgs-aux*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D **and**

P Midpoint A B **and**

Q Midpoint C D

shows *ParallelogramStrict* A P Q D

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-comm2*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* A B C D

shows *ParallelogramStrict* B A D C

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgf-comm2*:

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* A B C D

shows *ParallelogramFlat* B A D C

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plg-comm2*:

assumes *Parallelogram* A B C D

shows *Parallelogram* B A D C

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *par-preserves-conga-os*:

assumes A B Par C D **and**

Bet A D P **and**

$D \neq P$ **and**

A D *OS* B C

shows B A P *CongA* C D P

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *cong3-par2-par*:

assumes $A \neq C$ **and**

B A C *Cong3* B' A' C' **and**

B A Par B' A' **and**

B C Par B' C'

shows A C Par A' $C' \vee \neg B$ B' ParStrict A $A' \vee \neg B$ B' ParStrict C C'

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *square-perp-rectangle*:

assumes *Rectangle* A B C D **and**

A C *Perp* B D

shows *Square* A B C D

\langle proof \rangle

lemma *plgs-half-plgs*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $A B$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $C D$
shows *ParallelogramStrict* $A P Q D \wedge$ *ParallelogramStrict* $B P Q C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *parallel-2-plg*:
assumes \neg *Col* $A B C$ **and**
 $A B$ *Par* $C D$ **and**
 $A D$ *Par* $B C$
shows *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *par-2-plg*:
assumes \neg *Col* $A B C$ **and**
 $A B$ *Par* $C D$ **and**
 $A D$ *Par* $B C$
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plg-cong-1*:
assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
shows *Cong* $A B C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plg-cong-2*:
assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
shows *Cong* $A D B C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgs-cong-1*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows *Cong* $A B C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plgs-cong-2*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows *Cong* $A D B C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *Plg-perm*:
assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$
shows *Parallelogram* $A B C D \wedge$ *Parallelogram* $B C D A \wedge$
Parallelogram $C D A B \wedge$ *Parallelogram* $D A B C \wedge$
Parallelogram $A D C B \wedge$ *Parallelogram* $D C B A \wedge$
Parallelogram $C B A D \wedge$ *Parallelogram* $B A D C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plg-not-comm-1*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows \neg *Parallelogram* $A B D C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *plg-not-comm-2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows \neg *Parallelogram* $B A C D$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *parallelogram-strict-midpoint*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$ **and**
Col $I A C$ **and**
Col $I B D$
shows *I* *Midpoint* $A C \wedge$ *I* *Midpoint* $B D$

<proof>

lemma *rmb-perp*:
 assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 Rhombus $A B C D$
 shows $A C \text{ Perp } B D$
<proof>

lemma *rect-permut*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows *Rectangle* $B C D A$
<proof>

lemma *rect-comm2*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows *Rectangle* $B A D C$
<proof>

lemma *rect-per1*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows $\text{Per } B A D$
<proof>

lemma *rect-per2*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows $\text{Per } A B C$
<proof>

lemma *rect-per3*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows $\text{Per } B C D$
<proof>

lemma *rect-per4*:
 assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
 shows $\text{Per } A D C$
<proof>

lemma *plg-per-rect1*:
 assumes *Plg* $A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Per } D A B$
 shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-per-rect2*:
 assumes *Plg* $A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Per } C B A$
 shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-per-rect3*:
 assumes *Plg* $A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A D C$
 shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-per-rect4*:
 assumes *Plg* $A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Per } B C D$
 shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-per-rect*:
 assumes *Plg* $A B C D$ **and**
 $\text{Per } D A B \vee \text{Per } C B A \vee \text{Per } A D C \vee \text{Per } B C D$

shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *rect-per:*

assumes *Rectangle* $A B C D$
shows $Per B A D \wedge Per A B C \wedge Per B C D \wedge Per A D C$
<proof>

lemma *plgf-rect-id:*

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$ **and**
Rectangle $A B C D$
shows $(A = D \wedge B = C) \vee (A = B \wedge D = C)$
<proof>

lemma *cop-perp3--perp:*

assumes *Coplanar* $A B C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Perp } B C$ **and**
 $B C \text{ Perp } C D$ **and**
 $C D \text{ Perp } D A$
shows $D A \text{ Perp } A B$
<proof>

lemma *cop-perp3--rect:*

assumes *Coplanar* $A B C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Perp } B C$ **and**
 $B C \text{ Perp } C D$ **and**
 $C D \text{ Perp } D A$
shows *Rectangle* $A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *conga-to-par-os:*

assumes *Bet* $A D P$ **and**
 $A D \text{ OS } B C$ **and**
 $B A P \text{ Cong } A C D P$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-par:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge A D \text{ Par } B C$
<proof>

lemma *plg-par-1:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
<proof>

lemma *plg-par-2:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Parallelogram $A B C D$
shows $A D \text{ Par } B C$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-pars-1:*

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-pars-2:*

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$
shows $A D \text{ ParStrict } B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-cong*:

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$Cong A B C D$

shows $Cong A C B D \vee Cong A D B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-cong-cong*:

assumes $Col A B C$ **and**

$Col A B D$ **and**

$Cong A B C D$

shows $Cong A C B D \vee Cong A D B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-cop*:

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$

shows $Coplanar A B C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-plg* :

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$Cong A B C D$

shows $Plg A B C D \vee Plg A B D C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong-plg-2* :

assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$Cong A B C D$

shows $Parallelogram A B C D \vee Parallelogram A B D C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par-cong3-rect*:

assumes $A \neq C \vee B \neq D$ **and**

$A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**

$Cong A B C D$ **and**

$Cong A D B C$ **and**

$Cong A C B D$

shows $Rectangle A B C D \vee Rectangle A B D C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pars-par-pars*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**

$A D \text{ Par } B C$

shows $A D \text{ ParStrict } B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pars-par-plg*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**

$A D \text{ Par } B C$

shows $Plg A B C D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-par-pars-not-cong*:

assumes $P \text{ Out } A B$ **and**

$P \text{ Out } A' B'$ **and**

$A A' \text{ ParStrict } B B'$

shows $\neg Cong A A' B B'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-uniqueness*:

assumes $Parallelogram A B C D$ **and**

$Parallelogram A B C D'$

shows $D = D'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgs-trans-trivial*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D* **and**
ParallelogramStrict C D A B'
shows *Parallelogram A B B' A*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *par-strict-trans*:
assumes *A B ParStrict C D* **and**
C D ParStrict E F
shows *A B Par E F*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgs-pseudo-trans*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D* **and**
ParallelogramStrict C D E F
shows *Parallelogram A B F E*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgf-plgs-trans*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat A B C D **and**
ParallelogramStrict C D E F
shows *ParallelogramStrict A B F E*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgf-plgf-plgf*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
ParallelogramFlat A B C D **and**
ParallelogramFlat C D E F
shows *ParallelogramFlat A B F E*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plg-pseudo-trans*:
assumes *Parallelogram A B C D* **and**
Parallelogram C D E F
shows *Parallelogram A B F E* \vee ($A = B \wedge C = D \wedge E = F \wedge A = E$)
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Square-Rhombus*:
assumes *Square A B C D*
shows *Rhombus A B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *plgs-in-angle*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
shows *D InAngle A B C*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *par-par-cong-cong-parallelogram*:
assumes $B \neq D$ **and**
Cong A B C D **and**
Cong B C D A **and**
B C Par A D **and**
A B Par C D
shows *Parallelogram A B C D*
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *degenerated-rect-eq*:
assumes *Rectangle A B B C*
shows $A = C$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *rect-2-rect*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Rectangle A B C1 D1 **and**

Rectangle A B C2 D2
shows *Rectangle C1 D1 D2 C2*
<proof>

lemma *ncol123-plg--plgs:*
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol124-plg--plgs:*
assumes \neg *Col A B D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol134-plg--plgs:*
assumes \neg *Col A C D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol234-plg--plgs:*
assumes \neg *Col B C D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *ParallelogramStrict A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol123-plg--pars1234:*
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A B ParStrict C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol124-plg--pars1234:*
assumes \neg *Col A B D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A B ParStrict C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol134-plg--pars1234:*
assumes \neg *Col A C D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A B ParStrict C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol234-plg--pars1234:*
assumes \neg *Col B C D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A B ParStrict C D*
<proof>

lemma *ncol123-plg--pars1423:*
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A D ParStrict B C*
<proof>

lemma *ncol124-plg--pars1423:*
assumes \neg *Col A B D* **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows *A D ParStrict B C*
<proof>

lemma *ncol134-plg--pars1423:*
assumes \neg *Col A C D* **and**

Parallelogram A B C D
shows $A D \text{ ParStrict } B C$
<proof>

lemma *ncol234-plg--pars1423:*
assumes $\neg \text{Col } B C D$ **and**
Parallelogram A B C D
shows $A D \text{ ParStrict } B C$
<proof>

lemma *sac-plg:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *Parallelogram A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *sac-rectangle:*
assumes *Saccheri A B C D*
shows *Rectangle A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *exists-square:*
assumes $A \neq B$
shows $\exists C D. \text{Square } A B C D$
<proof>

lemma *euclidT:*
assumes *Bet A D T and*
Bet B D C and
 $A \neq D$
shows $\exists X Y. \text{Bet } A B X \wedge \text{Bet } A C Y \wedge \text{Bet } X T Y$
<proof>

lemma *eqv-refl:*
shows $A B \text{ EqV } A B$
<proof>

lemma *eqv-sym:*
assumes $A B \text{ EqV } C D$
shows $C D \text{ EqV } A B$
<proof>

lemma *eqv-trans:*
assumes $A B \text{ EqV } C D$ **and**
 $C D \text{ EqV } E F$
shows $A B \text{ EqV } E F$
<proof>

lemma *eqv-comm:*
assumes $A B \text{ EqV } C D$
shows $B A \text{ EqV } D C$
<proof>

lemma *vector-construction:*
shows $\exists D. A B \text{ EqV } C D$
<proof>

lemma *vector-construction-uniqueness:*
assumes $A B \text{ EqV } C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ EqV } C D'$
shows $D = D'$
<proof>

lemma null-vector:
assumes $A A EqV B C$
shows $B = C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma vector-uniqueness:
assumes $A B EqV A C$
shows $B = C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-trivial:
shows $A A EqV B B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-permut:
assumes $A B EqV C D$
shows $A C EqV B D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-par:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A B EqV C D$
shows $A B Par C D$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-opp-null:
assumes $A B EqV B A$
shows $A = B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-sum:
assumes $A B EqV A' B'$ **and**
 $B C EqV B' C'$
shows $A C EqV A' C'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma null-sum:
shows $A B B A SumV C C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma chasles:
shows $A B B C SumV A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma eqv-mid :
assumes $A B EqV B C$
shows $B Midpoint A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma mid-eqv:
assumes $A Midpoint B C$
shows $B A EqV A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma sum-sym:
assumes $A B C D SumV E F$
shows $C D A B SumV E F$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma opposite-sum:
assumes $A B C D SumV E F$
shows $B A D C SumV F E$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma null-sum-eq:
assumes $A B B C SumV D D$

shows $A = C$
<proof>

lemma *is-to-ise*:

assumes $A B C D \text{ SumV } E F$
shows $A B C D \text{ SumVExists } E F$
<proof>

lemma *ise-to-is*:

assumes $A B C D \text{ SumVExists } E F$
shows $A B C D \text{ SumV } E F$
<proof>

lemma *sum-exists*:

shows $\exists E F. A B C D \text{ SumV } E F$
<proof>

lemma *sum-uniqueness-pappus*:

assumes $A B C D \text{ SumV } E F$ **and**
 $A B C D \text{ SumV } E' F'$
shows $E F \text{ EqV } E' F'$
<proof>

lemma *same-dir-reft*:

shows $A B \text{ SameDir } A B$
<proof>

lemma *same-dir-ts*:

assumes $A B \text{ SameDir } C D$
shows $\exists M. \text{Bet } A M D \wedge \text{Bet } B M C$
<proof>

lemma *one-side-col-out*:

assumes $\text{Col } A X Y$ **and**
 $A B \text{ OS } X Y$
shows $A \text{ Out } X Y$
<proof>

lemma *par-ts-same-dir*:

assumes $A B \text{ ParStrict } C D$ **and**
 $\exists M. \text{Bet } A M D \wedge \text{Bet } B M C$
shows $A B \text{ SameDir } C D$
<proof>

lemma *same-dir-out*:

assumes $A B \text{ SameDir } A C$
shows $A \text{ Out } B C \vee (A = B \wedge A = C)$
<proof>

lemma *same-dir-out1*:

assumes $A B \text{ SameDir } B C$
shows $A \text{ Out } B C \vee (A = B \wedge A = C)$
<proof>

lemma *same-dir-null*:

assumes $A A \text{ SameDir } B C$
shows $B = C$
<proof>

lemma *plgs-out-plgs*:

assumes $\text{ParallelogramStrict } A B C D$ **and**
 $A \text{ Out } B B'$ **and**
 $D \text{ Out } C C'$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A B' D C'$
shows $\text{ParallelogramStrict } A B' C' D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgs-plgs-bet*:

assumes *ParallelogramStrict* $A B C D$ **and**

Bet $A B B'$ **and**

ParallelogramStrict $A B' C' D$

shows *Bet* $D C C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgf-plgf-bet*:

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$ **and**

Bet $A B B'$ **and**

ParallelogramFlat $A B' C' D$

shows *Bet* $D C C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-plg-bet*:

assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$ **and**

Bet $A B B'$ **and**

Parallelogram $A B' C' D$

shows *Bet* $D C C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plgf-out-plgf*:

assumes *ParallelogramFlat* $A B C D$ **and**

A Out $B B'$ **and**

D Out $C C'$ **and**

Cong $A B' D C'$

shows *ParallelogramFlat* $A B' C' D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-out-plg*:

assumes *Parallelogram* $A B C D$ **and**

A Out $B B'$ **and**

D Out $C C'$ **and**

Cong $A B' D C'$

shows *Parallelogram* $A B' C' D$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-sym*:

assumes $A B$ *SameDir* $C D$

shows $C D$ *SameDir* $A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-trans*:

assumes $A B$ *SameDir* $C D$ **and**

$C D$ *SameDir* $E F$

shows $A B$ *SameDir* $E F$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-comm*:

assumes $A B$ *SameDir* $C D$

shows $B A$ *SameDir* $D C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-same-dir1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

Bet $A B C$

shows $A B$ *SameDir* $A C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bet-same-dir2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

Bet $A B C$

shows $A B \text{ SameDir } B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plg-opp-dir*:
assumes $\text{Parallelogram } A B C D$
shows $A B \text{ SameDir } D C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-dec*:
shows $A B \text{ SameDir } C D \vee \neg A B \text{ SameDir } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-or-opp-dir*:
assumes $A B \text{ Par } C D$
shows $A B \text{ SameDir } C D \vee A B \text{ OppDir } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-id*:
assumes $A B \text{ SameDir } B A$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-dir-id*:
assumes $A B \text{ OppDir } A B$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-dir-to-null*:
assumes $A B \text{ SameDir } C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ SameDir } D C$
shows $A = B \wedge C = D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-dir-to-null*:
assumes $A B \text{ OppDir } C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ OppDir } D C$
shows $A = B \wedge C = D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *same-not-opp-dir*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A B \text{ SameDir } C D$
shows $\neg A B \text{ OppDir } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-not-same-dir*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A B \text{ OppDir } C D$
shows $\neg A B \text{ SameDir } C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *vector-same-dir-cong*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$
shows $\exists X Y. A B \text{ SameDir } X Y \wedge \text{Cong } X Y C D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *project-par*:
assumes $P P' \text{ Proj } A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' \text{ Proj } A B X Y$ **and**
 $P Q \text{ Par } X Y$
shows $P' = Q'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *ker-col*:

assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $Col P Q P'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ker-par*:
assumes $P \neq Q$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P Q Par X Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-uniqueness*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $P Q' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P' = Q'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-col-eq*:
assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $Col P Q P'$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P' = Q'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-preserves-bet*:
assumes $Bet P Q R$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $R R' Proj A B X Y$
shows $Bet P' Q' R'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *triangle-par*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $A B Par A' B'$ **and**
 $B C Par B' C'$ **and**
 $A C Par A' C'$
shows $A B C CongA A' B' C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *par3-conga3* :
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $A B Par A' B'$ **and**
 $B C Par B' C'$ **and**
 $A C Par A' C'$
shows $A B C CongA3 A' B' C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-par-eq*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $P Q Par A B$
shows $P Q EqV P' Q'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *eqv-project-eq-eq*:
assumes $P Q EqV R S$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $R P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $S S' Proj A B X Y$
shows $Q' = S'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *eqv-eq-project*:
assumes $P Q EqV R S$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $R P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $S Q' Proj A B X Y$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *eqv-cong*:
assumes $A B EqV C D$
shows $Cong A B C D$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *project-preserves-eqv*:
assumes $P Q EqV R S$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $Q Q' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $R R' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $S S' Proj A B X Y$
shows $P' Q' EqV R' S'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *cop-par--perp2*:
assumes $Coplanar A B C P$ **and**
 $A B Par C D$
shows $P Perp2 A B C D$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-11*:
assumes $\neg Col PO A A'$ **and**
 $B \neq PO$ **and**
 $C \neq PO$ **and**
 $Col PO A B$ **and**
 $Col PO B C$ **and**
 $B' \neq PO$ **and**
 $C' \neq PO$ **and**
 $Col PO A' B'$ **and**
 $Col PO B' C'$ **and**
 $B C' Par C B'$ **and**
 $C A' Par A C'$
shows $A B' Par B A'$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-14*:
assumes $PO A ParStrict O' A'$ **and**
 $Col PO A B$ **and**
 $Col PO B C$ **and**
 $Col PO A C$ **and**
 $Col O' A' B'$ **and**
 $Col O' B' C'$ **and**
 $Col O' A' C'$ **and**
 $A C' Par A' C$ **and**
 $B C' Par B' C$
shows $A B' Par A' B$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-15-1*:
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 $\neg PO B Par A C$ **and**
 $Coplanar PO B A C$ **and**
 $A B ParStrict A' B'$ **and**
 $A C ParStrict A' C'$ **and**
 $Col PO A A'$ **and**
 $Col PO B B'$ **and**
 $Col PO C C'$
shows $B C Par B' C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-15-2-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\neg \text{PO } A \ \text{Par } B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{PO } B \ \text{Par } A \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } A \ A'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } B \ B'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } C \ C'$

shows $B \ C \ \text{Par } B' \ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-15-2*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{PO } B \ \text{Par } A \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } A \ A'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } B \ B'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } C \ C'$

shows $B \ C \ \text{Par } B' \ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-15*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
Coplanar $\text{PO } B \ A \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } A \ A'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } B \ B'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } C \ C'$

shows $B \ C \ \text{Par } B' \ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-15-par*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $A \ A' \ \text{Par } B \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ A' \ \text{Par } C \ C'$

shows $B \ C \ \text{Par } B' \ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-18-2*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{ParStrict } B' \ C'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } A \ A'$ **and**
 $\text{Col } \text{PO } B \ B'$

shows $\text{Col } \text{PO } C \ C'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-18-3-R1*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ B'$ **and**
 $A \ C \ \text{ParStrict } A' \ C'$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{ParStrict } B' \ C'$ **and**
 $A \ A' \ \text{Par } B \ B'$

shows $C \ C' \ \text{Par } A \ A'$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l13-18-3-R2*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A C \text{ ParStrict } A' C' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ ParStrict } B' C' \text{ and}$
 $A A' \text{ Par } B B'$
shows $C C' \text{ Par } B B'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-18-3*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C \text{ and}$
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A C \text{ ParStrict } A' C' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ ParStrict } B' C' \text{ and}$
 $A A' \text{ Par } B B'$
shows $C C' \text{ Par } A A' \wedge C C' \text{ Par } B B'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-18*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C \text{ and}$
 $A B \text{ ParStrict } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A C \text{ ParStrict } A' C'$
shows $(B C \text{ ParStrict } B' C' \wedge \text{Col } PO A A' \wedge \text{Col } PO B B' \longrightarrow \text{Col } PO C C')$
 $\wedge ((B C \text{ ParStrict } B' C' \wedge A A' \text{ Par } B B') \longrightarrow (C C' \text{ Par } A A' \wedge C C' \text{ Par } B B'))$
 $\wedge (A A' \text{ Par } B B' \wedge A A' \text{ Par } C C' \longrightarrow B C \text{ Par } B' C')$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-19-aux*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO A B \text{ and}$
 $A \neq A' \text{ and}$
 $A \neq C \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq A \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq A' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq C \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq C' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq B \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq B' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq D \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq D' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A C \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A A' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A C' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B D \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B B' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B D' \text{ and}$
 $\neg A B \text{ Par } C D \text{ and}$
 $A B \text{ Par } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A D \text{ Par } A' D' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ Par } B' C'$
shows $C D \text{ Par } C' D'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-19*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO A B \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq A \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq A' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq C \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq C' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq B \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq B' \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq D \text{ and}$
 $PO \neq D' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A C \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A A' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO A C' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B D \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B B' \text{ and}$
 $\text{Col } PO B D' \text{ and}$

$A B \text{ Par } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A D \text{ Par } A' D' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ Par } B' C'$
shows $C D \text{ Par } C' D'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-19-par-aux*:
assumes $X \neq A$ **and**

$Y \neq B$ **and**

$Col X A C$ **and**
 $Col X A A'$ **and**
 $Col X A C'$ **and**
 $Col Y B D$ **and**
 $Col Y B B'$ **and**
 $Col Y B D'$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 $A \neq A'$ **and**
 $X A \text{ ParStrict } Y B$ **and**
 $\neg A B \text{ Par } C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Par } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A D \text{ Par } A' D' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ Par } B' C'$
shows $C D \text{ Par } C' D'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *l13-19-par*:
assumes $X \neq A$ **and**
 $X \neq A'$ **and**

$Y \neq B$ **and**
 $Y \neq B'$ **and**

$Col X A C$ **and**
 $Col X A A'$ **and**
 $Col X A C'$ **and**
 $Col Y B D$ **and**
 $Col Y B B'$ **and**
 $Col Y B D'$ **and**
 $X A \text{ ParStrict } Y B$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Par } A' B' \text{ and}$
 $A D \text{ Par } A' D' \text{ and}$
 $B C \text{ Par } B' C'$
shows $C D \text{ Par } C' D'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *sum-to-sump*:
assumes $Sum PO E E' A B C$
shows $Sump PO E E' A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *sump-to-sum*:
assumes $Sump PO E E' A B C$
shows $Sum PO E E' A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *project-col-project*:
assumes $A \neq C$
and $Col A B C$
and $P P' \text{ Proj } A B X Y$
shows $P P' \text{ Proj } A C X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *pj-uniqueness*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E' \ A'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E' \ A''$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A''$
shows $A' = A''$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pj-right-comm*:
assumes $A \ B \ Pj \ C \ D$
shows $A \ B \ Pj \ D \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pj-left-comm*:
assumes $A \ B \ Pj \ C \ D$
shows $B \ A \ Pj \ C \ D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pj-comm*:
assumes $A \ B \ Pj \ C \ D$
shows $B \ A \ Pj \ D \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-1*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\neg PO \ E \ Par \ E \ E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-2*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\neg PO \ E \ Par \ PO \ E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-3*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\neg PO \ E' \ Par \ E \ E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-4*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $PO \neq E$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-5*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $PO \neq E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par-6*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $E \neq E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *grid-not-par*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\neg PO \ E \ Par \ E \ E' \wedge \neg PO \ E \ Par \ PO \ E' \wedge$
 $\neg PO \ E' \ Par \ E \ E' \wedge PO \neq E \wedge PO \neq E' \wedge E \neq E'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *proj-id*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $A \ A' \ Proj \ PO \ E' \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A'$
shows $A = PO$

<proof>

lemma *sum-uniqueness*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

and *Sum* $PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C1$

and *Sum* $PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C2$

shows $C1 = C2$

<proof>

lemma *opp0*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

shows *Opp* $PO \ E \ E' \ PO \ PO$

<proof>

lemma *sum-O-O*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

shows *Sum* $PO \ E \ E' \ PO \ PO \ PO$

<proof>

lemma *sum-par-strict-a*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

and *Ar2* $PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$

and $A \neq PO$

and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$

shows $A' \neq PO$

<proof>

lemma *sum-par-strict-b*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

and *Ar2* $PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$

and $A \neq PO$

and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$

and *Col* $PO \ E' \ A'$

and *PO E Pj A' C'*

and *PO E' Pj B C'*

and $E' \ E \ Pj \ C' \ C$

shows $(PO \ E \ ParStrict \ A' \ C' \vee B = PO)$

<proof>

lemma *sum-par-strict*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$

and *Ar2* $PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$

and $A \neq PO$

and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$

and *Col* $PO \ E' \ A'$

and *PO E Pj A' C'*

and *PO E' Pj B C'*

and $E' \ E \ Pj \ C' \ C$

shows $A' \neq PO \wedge (PO \ E \ ParStrict \ A' \ C' \vee B = PO)$

<proof>

end

end

theory *Tarski-Euclidean-2D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

Tarski-Postulate-Parallels

Tarski-Euclidean

Tarski-Neutral-2D

begin

15 Tarski Euclidean 2D

15.1 Tarski's axiom system for Euclidean 2D

locale *Tarski-Euclidean-2D* = *Tarski-Euclidean* +
assumes *upper-dim*: $\forall a b c p q.$
 $p \neq q \wedge$
 $Cong\ a\ p\ a\ q \wedge$
 $Cong\ b\ p\ b\ q \wedge$
 $Cong\ c\ p\ c\ q$
 \longrightarrow
 $(Bet\ a\ b\ c \vee Bet\ b\ c\ a \vee Bet\ c\ a\ b)$

sublocale *Tarski-Euclidean-2D* \subseteq *Tarski-neutral-2D*
<proof>

context *Tarski-Euclidean-2D*

begin

15.2 Definitions

15.3 Propositions

lemma *l12-16-2D*:
assumes *A1 A2 Par B1 B2 and*
 $X\ Inter\ A1\ A2\ C1\ C2$
shows $\exists Y. Y\ Inter\ B1\ B2\ C1\ C2$
<proof>

lemma *par-inter*:
assumes *A B Par C D and*
 $\neg A\ B\ Par\ P\ Q$
shows $\exists Y. Col\ P\ Q\ Y \wedge Col\ C\ D\ Y$
<proof>

lemma *not-par-inter*:
assumes $\neg A\ B\ Par\ A'\ B'$
shows $\exists P. Col\ P\ X\ Y \wedge (Col\ P\ A\ B \vee Col\ P\ A'\ B')$
<proof>

lemma *par-perp--perp*:
assumes *A B Par C D and*
 $A\ B\ Perp\ P\ Q$
shows $C\ D\ Perp\ P\ Q$
<proof>

lemma *par-perp2--par*:
assumes *A B Par C D and*
 $A\ B\ Perp\ E\ F$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Perp\ G\ H$
shows $E\ F\ Par\ G\ H$
<proof>

lemma *perp3--perp*:
assumes *A B Perp B C and*
 $B\ C\ Perp\ C\ D$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Perp\ D\ A$
shows $D\ A\ Perp\ A\ B$
<proof>

lemma *perp3--rect*:
assumes *A B Perp B C and*
 $B\ C\ Perp\ C\ D$ **and**
 $C\ D\ Perp\ D\ A$
shows *Rectangle A B C D*
<proof>

lemma *projp-is-project*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B$
shows $\exists X Y. P P' Proj A B X Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-is-project-perp*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B$
shows $\exists X Y. P P' Proj A B X Y \wedge A B Perp X Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-to-project*:
assumes $A B Perp X Y$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B$
shows $P P' Proj A B X Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-to-projp*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $A B Perp X Y$
shows $P P' Proj A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-project-to-perp*:
assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$
shows $A B Perp X Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-par-project*:
assumes $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $X Y Par X' Y'$
shows $P P' Proj A B X' Y'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *project-project-par* :
assumes $P \neq P'$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X Y$ **and**
 $P P' Proj A B X' Y'$
shows $X Y Par X' Y'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-preserves-bet*:
assumes $Bet A B C$ **and**
 $A A' Projp X Y$ **and**
 $B B' Projp X Y$ **and**
 $C C' Projp X Y$
shows $Bet A' B' C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-preserves-quiv*:
assumes $A B EqV C D$ **and**
 $A A' Projp X Y$ **and**
 $B B' Projp X Y$ **and**
 $C C' Projp X Y$ **and**
 $D D' Projp X Y$
shows $A' B' EqV C' D'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp2-col*:
assumes $P A Projp B C$ **and**
 $Q A Projp B C$
shows $Col A P Q$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *projp-projp-perp*:
assumes $P1 \neq P2$ **and**
 $P1 P \text{ Projp } Q1 Q2$ **and**
 $P2 P \text{ Projp } Q1 Q2$
shows $P1 P2 \text{ Perp } Q1 Q2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-projp2-eq*:
assumes $A A' \text{ Projp } C D$ **and**
 $B B' \text{ Projp } C D$ **and**
 $A B \text{ Perp } C D$
shows $A' = B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-par-projp2-eq*:
assumes $Col L11 L12 P$ **and**
 $L11 L12 \text{ Par } L21 L22$ **and**
 $P P' \text{ Projp } L21 L22$ **and**
 $P' P'' \text{ Projp } L11 L12$
shows $P = P''$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-2-par-projp2-cong*:
assumes $Col L11 L12 A'$ **and**
 $Col L11 L12 B'$ **and**
 $L11 L12 \text{ Par } L21 L22$ **and**
 $A' A \text{ Projp } L21 L22$ **and**
 $B' B \text{ Projp } L21 L22$
shows $Cong A B A' B'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *project-existence*:
assumes $X \neq Y$
and $A \neq B$
and $\neg X Y \text{ Par } A B$
shows $\exists P'. P P' \text{ Proj } A B X Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sum-exists*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Col PO E A$
and $Col PO E B$
shows $\exists C. Sum PO E E' A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-exists*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Col PO E A$
shows $\exists MA. Opp PO E E' A MA$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sum-A-O*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Col PO E A$
shows $Sum PO E E' A PO A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *sum-O-B*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Col PO E B$
shows $Sum PO E E' PO B B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp0-uniqueness*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col PO E E'$

and $Opp\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ M$
shows $M = PO$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *proj-pars*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $A \neq PO$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$
and $PO\ E\ Par\ A'\ C'$
and $A\ A'\ Proj\ PO\ E'\ E\ E'$
shows $PO\ E\ ParStrict\ A'\ C'$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-O-B-eq*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ B\ C$
shows $B = C$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-A-O-eq*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ PO\ C$
shows $A = C$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-A-B-A*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ A$
shows $B = PO$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-A-B-B*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ B$
shows $A = PO$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-uniquenessB*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ X\ C$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ Y\ C$
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-uniquenessA*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ B\ C$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ Y\ B\ C$
shows $X = Y$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-B-null*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ A$
shows $B = PO$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-A-null*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ B$
shows $A = PO$
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sum-plg*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$

and $(A \neq PO) \vee (B \neq PO)$
shows $\exists A' C'. \text{Plg } PO B C' A' \wedge \text{Plg } C' A' A C$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-cong*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
and $(A \neq PO \vee B \neq PO)$
shows *ParallelogramFlat* $PO A C B$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-cong2*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
and $(A \neq PO \vee B \neq PO)$
shows *Cong* $PO A B C \wedge \text{Cong } PO B A C$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-comm*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
shows *Sum* $PO E E' B A C$
 <proof>

lemma *cong-sum*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and $PO \neq C \vee B \neq A$
and *Ar2* $PO E E' A B C$
and *Cong* $PO A B C$
and *Cong* $PO B A C$
shows *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-iff-cong-a*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Ar2* $PO E E' A B C$
and $PO \neq C \vee B \neq A$
and *Cong* $PO A B C$
and *Cong* $PO B A C$
shows *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-iff-cong-b*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and $PO \neq C \vee B \neq A$
and *Sum* $PO E E' A B C$
shows *Cong* $PO A B C \wedge \text{Cong } PO B A C$
 <proof>

lemma *sum-iff-cong*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Ar2* $PO E E' A B C$
and $PO \neq C \vee B \neq A$
shows $(\text{Cong } PO A B C \wedge \text{Cong } PO B A C) \longleftrightarrow \text{Sum } PO E E' A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *opp-comm*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Opp* $PO E E' X Y$
shows *Opp* $PO E E' Y X$
 <proof>

lemma *opp-uniqueness*:

assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO E E'$
and *Opp* $PO E E' A MA1$
and *Opp* $PO E E' A MA2$

shows $MA1 = MA2$
(proof)

lemma *proj-preserves-sum*:
assumes *grid-ok*: $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $\text{Ar1 } PO \ E' \ A' \ B' \ C'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ B \ B'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ C \ C'$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E' \ E \ A' \ B' \ C'$
(proof)

lemma *sum-assoc-1*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ C \ BC$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ BC \ ABC$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ C \ ABC$
(proof)

lemma *sum-assoc-2*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ C \ BC$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ C \ ABC$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ BC \ ABC$
(proof)

lemma *sum-assoc*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ C \ BC$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ BC \ ABC \equiv \text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ C \ ABC$
(proof)

lemma *sum-y-axis-change*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E''$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E'' \ A \ B \ C$
(proof)

lemma *sum-x-axis-unit-change*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ U$
and $U \neq PO$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ U \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
(proof)

lemma *change-grid-sum-0*:
assumes $PO \ E \ \text{ParStrict } O' \ E'$
and $\text{Ar1 } PO \ E \ A \ B \ C$
and $\text{Ar1 } O' \ E' \ A' \ B' \ C'$
and $PO \ O' \ Pj \ E \ E'$
and $PO \ O' \ Pj \ A \ A'$
and $PO \ O' \ Pj \ B \ B'$
and $PO \ O' \ Pj \ C \ C'$
and $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $A = PO$
shows $\text{Sum } O' \ E' \ E \ A' \ B' \ C'$
(proof)

lemma *change-grid-sum*:
assumes $PO\ E\ ParStrict\ O'\ E'$
and $Ar1\ PO\ E\ A\ B\ C$
and $Ar1\ O'\ E'\ A'\ B'\ C'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ E\ E'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ A\ A'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ B\ B'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ C\ C'$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Sum\ O'\ E'\ E\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *double-null-null*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ PO$
shows $A = PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-null-double-not-null*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ C$
and $A \neq PO$
shows $C \neq PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *double-not-null-not-nul*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ C$
and $C \neq PO$
shows $A \neq PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-ar2*:
assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AMB$
shows $Ar2\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AMB$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-null*:
assumes $grid-ok: \neg\ Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$
shows $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-exists*:
assumes $grid-ok: \neg\ Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ B$
shows $\exists\ D. Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-uniqueness*:
assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ D1$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ D2$
shows $D1 = D2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-ar2*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Ar2\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-A-O*:
assumes $grid-ok: \neg\ Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$
shows $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ PO\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *diff-O-A*:
assumes $Opp\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ mA$

shows $\text{Diff } PO E E' PO A mA$
(proof)

lemma *diff-O-A-opp*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' PO A mA$
shows $\text{Opp } PO E E' A mA$
(proof)

lemma *diff-uniquenessA*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B C$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A' B C$
shows $A = A'$
(proof)

lemma *diff-uniquenessB*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B C$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B' C$
shows $B = B'$
(proof)

lemma *diff-null-eq*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B PO$
shows $A = B$
(proof)

lemma *midpoint-opp*:
assumes $\text{Ar2 } PO E E' PO A B$
and $\text{PO Midpoint } A B$
shows $\text{Opp } PO E E' A B$
(proof)

lemma *sum-diff*:
assumes $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B S$
shows $\text{Diff } PO E E' S A B$
(proof)

lemma *diff-sum*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' S A B$
shows $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B S$
(proof)

lemma *diff-opp*:
assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B AmB$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' B A BmA$
shows $\text{Opp } PO E E' AmB BmA$
(proof)

lemma *sum-stable*:
assumes $A = B$
and $\text{Sum } PO E E' A C S1$
and $\text{Sum } PO E E' B C S2$
shows $S1 = S2$
(proof)

lemma *diff-stable*:
assumes $A = B$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A C D1$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' B C D2$
shows $D1 = D2$
(proof)

lemma *plg-to-sum*:
assumes $\text{Ar2 } PO E E' A B C$
and $\text{ParallelogramFlat } PO A C B$
shows $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B C$
(proof)

lemma *opp-midpoint*:

assumes *Opp* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ MA$

shows *PO Midpoint* $A\ MA$

<proof>

lemma *diff-to-plg*:

assumes $A \neq PO \vee B \neq PO$

and *Diff* $PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ dBA$

shows *ParallelogramFlat* $PO\ A\ B\ dBA$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-col*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S$

shows $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E' \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ A \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ B \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ C \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-permut*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S$

shows *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ C\ A\ B\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-comm-1-2*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S$

shows *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ C\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-comm-2-3*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S$

shows *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ B\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-exists*:

assumes *Ar2* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$

shows $\exists S. sum3\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-uniqueness*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S1$

and *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ S2$

shows $S1 = S2$

<proof>

lemma *sum4-col*:

assumes *Sum4* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$

shows $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E' \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ A \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ B \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ C \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ D \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum22-col*:

assumes *sum22* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$

shows $\neg Col\ PO\ E\ E' \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ A \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ B \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ C \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ D \wedge Col\ PO\ E\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum-to-sum3*:

assumes *Sum* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$

and *Sum* $PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ X\ S$

shows *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ X\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum3-to-sum4*:

assumes *sum3* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ ABC$

and *Sum* $PO\ E\ E'\ ABC\ X\ S$

shows *Sum4* $PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ X\ S$

<proof>

lemma *sum-A-exists*:

assumes $Ar2\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ AB\ PO$
shows $\exists B. Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-B-exists*:

assumes $Ar2\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ AB\ PO$
shows $\exists A. Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum4-equiv-a*:

assumes $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum4-equiv-b*:

assumes $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum4-equiv*:

shows $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S \longleftrightarrow sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum4-permut*:

assumes $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ D\ A\ B\ C\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum22-permut*:

assumes $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ D\ A\ B\ C\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum4-comm*:

assumes $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $Sum4\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ C\ D\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum22-comm*:

assumes $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D\ S$
shows $sum22\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ C\ D\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-abcd*:

assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ D\ CD$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ D\ AD$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ CD\ S$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ BC\ AD\ S$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-diff-diff-a*:

assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ dBA$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ B\ dCB$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ A\ dCA$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ dCB\ dBA\ dCA$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-diff-diff-b*:

assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ dBA$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ B\ dCB$

and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ dCB\ dBA\ dCA$
shows $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ A\ dCA$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $sum-diff2-diff-sum2-a$:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ Y\ Z$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ A\ dXA$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ Y\ B\ dYB$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ dXA\ dYB\ dZC$
shows $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ Z\ C\ dZC$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $sum-diff2-diff-sum2-b$:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ Y\ Z$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ A\ dXA$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ Y\ B\ dYB$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ Z\ C\ dZC$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ dXA\ dYB\ dZC$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $sum-opp$:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ MX\ PO$
shows $Opp\ PO\ E\ E'\ X\ MX$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $sum-diff-diff$:
assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ AX\ BX\ AXMBX$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ AX\ CX\ AXMCX$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ BX\ CX\ BXMCX$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AXMBX\ BXMCX\ AXMCX$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $prod-to-prodp$:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Prodp\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $project-pj$:
assumes $P\ P'\ Proj\ A\ B\ X\ Y$
shows $X\ Y\ Pj\ P\ P'$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $prodp-to-prod$:
assumes $Prodp\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $prod-exists$:
assumes $grid-ok: \neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ A$
and $Col\ PO\ E\ B$
shows $\exists C. Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $prod-uniqueness$:
assumes $grid-ok: \neg Col\ PO\ E\ E'$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C1$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C2$
shows $C1 = C2$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma $prod-0-l$:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ PO \ A \ PO$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-0-r*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ PO \ PO$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-1-l*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ E \ A \ A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-1-r*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ E \ A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inv-exists*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
and $\text{Col } PO \ E \ A$
and $A \neq PO$
shows $\exists IA. \text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ IA \ A \ E$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-null*:
assumes $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ PO$
shows $A = PO \vee B = PO$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-y-axis-change*:
assumes $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E''$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E'' \ A \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *proj-preserves-prod*:
assumes $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
and $\text{Ar1 } PO \ E' \ A' \ B' \ C'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ A \ A'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ B \ B'$
and $E \ E' \ Pj \ C \ C'$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E' \ E \ A' \ B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-assoc1*:
assumes $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ C \ BC$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ BC \ ABC$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ C \ ABC$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-assoc2*:

assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$ **and**
 $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ C\ ABC$
shows $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ BC\ ABC$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-assoc*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
shows $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ BC\ ABC \longleftrightarrow Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ C\ ABC$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-comm*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-O-l-eq*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ B\ C$
shows $C = PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-O-r-eq*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ PO\ C$
shows $C = PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-uniquenessA*:
assumes $B \neq PO$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A'\ B\ C$
shows $A = A'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-uniquenessB*:
assumes $A \neq PO$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B'\ C$
shows $B = B'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *distr-l*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ D$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ D\ AD$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ AC\ AD$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *distr-r*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ D$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ D\ C\ DC$
shows $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC\ DC$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-1-l-eg*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ B$
shows $A = E \vee B = PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-1-r-eg*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ A$
shows $B = E \vee A = PO$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *change-grid-prod-l-O*:
assumes $PO\ E\ ParStrict\ O'\ E'$
and $Ar1\ PO\ E\ PO\ B\ C$
and $Ar1\ O'\ E'\ A'\ B'\ C'$

and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ PO\ A'$

and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ C\ C'$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ O'\ E'\ E\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *change-grid-prod1*:
assumes $PO\ E\ ParStrict\ O'\ E'$
and $Ar1\ PO\ E\ E\ B\ C$
and $Ar1\ O'\ E'\ A'\ B'\ C'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ E\ E'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ E\ A'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ B\ B'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ C\ C'$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ E\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ O'\ E'\ E\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *change-grid-prod*:
assumes $PO\ E\ ParStrict\ O'\ E'$
and $Ar1\ PO\ E\ A\ B\ C$
and $Ar1\ O'\ E'\ A'\ B'\ C'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ E\ E'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ A\ A'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ B\ B'$
and $PO\ O'\ Pj\ C\ C'$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ O'\ E'\ E\ A'\ B'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-sym*:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
shows $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *l14-31-1*:
assumes $Ar^{2p4}\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C\ D$
and $C \neq PO$

and $\exists X. \text{Prod } PO E E' A B X \wedge \text{Prod } PO E E' C D X$
shows $\text{Prod } PO C E' A B D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l14-31-2*:

assumes $\text{Ar2p4 } PO E E' A B C D$
and $C \neq PO$
and $\text{Prod } PO C E' A B D$
shows $\exists X. \text{Prod } PO E E' A B X \wedge \text{Prod } PO E E' C D X$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *prod-x-axis-unit-change*:

assumes $\text{Ar2p4 } PO E E' A B C D$
and $\text{Col } PO E U$
and $U \neq PO$
and $\exists X. \text{Prod } PO E E' A B X \wedge \text{Prod } PO E E' C D X$
shows $\exists Y. \text{Prod } PO U E' A B Y \wedge \text{Prod } PO U E' C D Y$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-prod*:

assumes $\text{Opp } PO E E' E ME$
and $\text{Opp } PO E E' X MX$
shows $\text{Prod } PO E E' X ME MX$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *distr-l-diff*:

assumes $\text{Diff } PO E E' B C BMC$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' A B AB$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' A C AC$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' A BMC ABMC$
shows $\text{Diff } PO E E' AB AC ABMC$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *diff-of-squares*:

assumes $\text{Prod } PO E E' A A A2$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' B B B2$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A2 B2 A2MB2$
and $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B APB$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B AMB$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' APB AMB F$
shows $A2MB2 = F$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *eq-squares-eq-or-opp*:

assumes $\text{Prod } PO E E' A A A2$
and $\text{Prod } PO E E' B B A2$
shows $A = B \vee \text{Opp } PO E E' A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *diff-2-prod*:

assumes $\text{Opp } PO E E' E ME$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' A B AMB$
and $\text{Diff } PO E E' B A BMA$
shows $\text{Prod } PO E E' AMB ME BMA$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l14-36-a*:

assumes $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B C$ **and**
 $\text{PO Out } A B$
shows $\text{Bet } PO A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l14-36-b*:

assumes $\text{Sum } PO E E' A B C$
and $\text{PO Out } A B$
shows $PO \neq A \wedge PO \neq C \wedge A \neq C$

<proof>

lemma *pos-null-neg*:

assumes *Opp PO E E' A MA*

shows *Ps PO E A \vee PO = A \vee Ps PO E MA*

<proof>

lemma *sum-pos-pos*:

assumes *Ps PO E A*

and *Ps PO E B*

and *Sum PO E E' A B AB*

shows *Ps PO E AB*

<proof>

lemma *prod-pos-pos*:

assumes *Ps PO E A*

and *Ps PO E B*

and *Prod PO E E' A B AB*

shows *Ps PO E AB*

<proof>

lemma *pos-not-neg*:

assumes *Ps PO E A*

shows \neg *Ng PO E A*

<proof>

lemma *neg-not-pos*:

assumes *Ng PO E A*

shows \neg *Ps PO E A*

<proof>

lemma *opp-pos-neg*:

assumes *Ps PO E A*

and *Opp PO E E' A MA*

shows *Ng PO E MA*

<proof>

lemma *opp-neg-pos*:

assumes *Ng PO E A*

and *Opp PO E E' A MA*

shows *Ps PO E MA*

<proof>

lemma *ltP-ar2*:

assumes *LtP PO E E' A B*

shows *Ar2 PO E E' A B A*

<proof>

lemma *ltP-neg*:

assumes *LtP PO E E' A B*

shows $A \neq B$

<proof>

lemma *leP-refl*:

shows *LeP PO E E' A A*

<proof>

lemma *ltP-sum-pos*:

assumes *Ps PO E B*

and *Sum PO E E' A B C*

shows *LtP PO E E' A C*

<proof>

lemma *pos-opp-neg*:

assumes *Ps PO E A*

and *Opp PO E E' A mA*

shows $Ng PO E mA$
<proof>

lemma *diff-pos-diff-neg*:
assumes $Diff PO E E' A B AmB$
and $Diff PO E E' B A BmA$
and $Ps PO E AmB$
shows $Ng PO E BmA$
<proof>

lemma *not-pos-and-neg*:
shows $\neg(Ps PO E A \wedge Ng PO E A)$
<proof>

lemma *leP-asym*:
assumes $LeP PO E E' A B$
and $LeP PO E E' B A$
shows $A = B$
<proof>

lemma *leP-trans*:
assumes $LeP PO E E' A B$
and $LeP PO E E' B C$
shows $LeP PO E E' A C$
<proof>

lemma *leP-sum-leP*:
assumes $LeP PO E E' A X$
and $LeP PO E E' B Y$
and $Sum PO E E' A B C$
and $Sum PO E E' X Y Z$
shows $LeP PO E E' C Z$
<proof>

lemma *square-pos*:
assumes $PO \neq A$
and $Prod PO E E' A A A2$
shows $Ps PO E A2$
<proof>

lemma *ltP-neg*:
assumes $LtP PO E E' A PO$
shows $Ng PO E A$
<proof>

lemma *ps-le*:
assumes $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Bet PO X E \vee Bet PO E X$
shows $LeP PO E E' PO X$
<proof>

lemma *lt-diff-ps*:
assumes $LtP PO E E' Y X$
and $Diff PO E E' X Y XMY$
shows $Ps PO E XMY$
<proof>

lemma *col-2-le-or-ge*:
assumes $\neg Col PO E E'$
and $Col PO E A$
and $Col PO E B$
shows $LeP PO E E' A B \vee LeP PO E E' B A$
<proof>

lemma *compatibility-of-sum-with-order:*

assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ APC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BPC$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ APC\ BPC$
(*proof*)

lemma *compatibility-of-prod-with-order:*

assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ A$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ B$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ AB$
(*proof*)

lemma *pos-inv-pos:*

assumes $PO \neq A$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ A$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ IA\ A\ E$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ IA$
(*proof*)

lemma *le-pos-prod-le:*

assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ C$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC$
(*proof*)

lemma *bet-lt12-le23:*

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C$
(*proof*)

lemma *bet-lt12-le13:*

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C$
(*proof*)

lemma *bet-lt21-le32:*

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ B$
(*proof*)

lemma *bet-lt21-le31:*

assumes $Bet\ A\ B\ C$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ A$
(*proof*)

lemma *opp-2-le-le:*

assumes $Opp\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ MA$
and $Opp\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ MB$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ MB\ MA$
(*proof*)

lemma *diff-2-le-le:*

assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AMC$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BMC$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AMC\ BMC$
(*proof*)

lemma *length-pos*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ L$

shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ L$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-id-1*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ PO$

shows $A = B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-id-2*:

assumes $PO \neq E$

shows $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ PO$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-id*:

shows $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ PO \longleftrightarrow (A = B \wedge PO \neq E)$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-eq-cong-1*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$

and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ D\ AB$

shows $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-eq-cong-2*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$

and $Cong\ A\ B\ C\ D$

shows $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ D\ AB$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ltP-pos*:

assumes $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ A$

shows $Ps\ PO\ E\ A$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet-leP*:

assumes $Bet\ PO\ AB\ CD$

and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ AB$

and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ CD$

shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ CD$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *leP-bet*:

assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ CD$

and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ AB$

and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ PO\ CD$

shows $Bet\ PO\ AB\ CD$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-Ar2*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$

shows $(Col\ PO\ E\ AB \wedge \neg Col\ PO\ E\ E') \vee AB = PO$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-leP-le-1*:

assumes $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$

and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ C\ D\ CD$

and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ CD$

shows $A\ B\ Le\ C\ D$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *length-leP-le-2:*

assumes *Length PO E E' A B AB*
and *Length PO E E' C D CD*
and *A B Le C D*

shows *LeP PO E E' AB CD*

<proof>

lemma *l15-3:*

assumes *Sum PO E E' A B C*

shows *Cong PO B A C*

<proof>

lemma *length-uniqueness:*

assumes *Length PO E E' A B AB*
and *Length PO E E' A B AB'*

shows *AB = AB'*

<proof>

lemma *length-Ps:*

assumes *AB ≠ PO*

and *Length PO E E' A B AB*

shows *Ps PO E AB*

<proof>

lemma *length-not-col-null:*

assumes *Col PO E E'*

and *Length PO E E' A B AB*

shows *AB = PO*

<proof>

lemma *not-triangular-equality1:*

assumes *PO ≠ E*

shows $\neg (\forall E' B C AB BC AC. \text{Bet } A B C \wedge \text{Length } PO E E' A B AB \wedge \text{Length } PO E E' B C BC \wedge \text{Length } PO E E' A C AC \longrightarrow \text{Sum } PO E E' AB BC AC)$

<proof>

lemma *triangular-equality:*

assumes *PO ≠ E*

and *Bet A B C*

and *IsLength PO E E' A B AB*

and *IsLength PO E E' B C BC*

and *IsLength PO E E' A C AC*

shows *Sumg PO E E' AB BC AC*

<proof>

lemma *length-O:*

assumes *PO ≠ E*

shows *Length PO E E' PO PO PO*

<proof>

lemma *triangular-equality-bis:*

assumes *A ≠ B ∨ A ≠ C ∨ B ≠ C*

and *PO ≠ E*

and *Bet A B C*

and *Length PO E E' A B AB*

and *Length PO E E' B C BC*

and *Length PO E E' A C AC*

shows *Sum PO E E' AB BC AC*

<proof>

lemma *length-out:*

assumes $A \neq B$
and $C \neq D$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ C \ D \ CD$
shows $PO \text{ Out } AB \ CD$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *image-preserves-bet1*:
assumes $Bet \ A \ B \ C$
and $A \ A' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $B \ B' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $C \ C' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
shows $Bet \ A' \ B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *image-preserves-col*:
assumes $Col \ A \ B \ C$
and $A \ A' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $B \ B' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $C \ C' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
shows $Col \ A' \ B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *image-preserves-out*:
assumes $A \ \text{Out } B \ C$
and $A \ A' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $B \ B' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
and $C \ C' \ \text{Reflect } X \ Y$
shows $A' \ \text{Out } B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *project-preserves-out*:
assumes $A \ \text{Out } B \ C$
and $\neg \ A \ B \ \text{Par } X \ Y$
and $A \ A' \ \text{Proj } P \ Q \ X \ Y$
and $B \ B' \ \text{Proj } P \ Q \ X \ Y$
and $C \ C' \ \text{Proj } P \ Q \ X \ Y$
shows $A' \ \text{Out } B' \ C'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conga-bet-conga*:
assumes $A \ B \ C \ \text{Cong} \ A \ D \ E \ F$
and $A' \neq B$
and $C' \neq B$
and $D' \neq E$
and $F' \neq E$
and $Bet \ A \ B \ A'$
and $Bet \ C \ B \ C'$
and $Bet \ D \ E \ D'$
and $Bet \ F \ E \ F'$
shows $A' \ B \ C' \ \text{Cong} \ A \ D' \ E \ F'$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *thales*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $Col \ P \ A \ B$
and $Col \ P \ C \ D$
and $\neg \ Col \ P \ A \ C$
and $A \ C \ \text{Pj } B \ D$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ P \ A \ A1$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ P \ B \ B1$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ P \ C \ C1$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ P \ D \ D1$
and $\text{Prodg } PO \ E \ E' \ A1 \ D1 \ AD$
shows $\text{Prodg } PO \ E \ E' \ C1 \ B1 \ AD$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *length-existence*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\exists \ AB. \text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l15-7*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $\text{Per } A \ C \ B$
and $H \ \text{PerpAt } C \ H \ A \ B$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ C \ AC$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ H \ AH$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AC \ AC \ AC2 \longleftrightarrow \text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ AH \ AC2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l15-7-1*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $\text{Per } A \ C \ B$
and $H \ \text{PerpAt } C \ H \ A \ B$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ C \ AC$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ H \ AH$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AC \ AC \ AC2$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ AH \ AC2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *l15-7-2*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $\text{Per } A \ C \ B$
and $H \ \text{PerpAt } C \ H \ A \ B$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ C \ AC$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ H \ AH$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ AH \ AC2$
shows $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AC \ AC \ AC2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *length-sym*:
assumes $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
shows $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ A \ AB$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *pythagoras*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $\text{Per } A \ C \ B$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ AB$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ C \ AC$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ B \ C \ BC$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AC \ AC \ AC2$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ BC \ BC \ BC2$
and $\text{Prod } PO \ E \ E' \ AB \ AB \ AB2$
shows $\text{Sum } PO \ E \ E' \ AC2 \ BC2 \ AB2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-length-exists*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } PO \ E \ E'$
shows $\exists \ XY. \text{IsLength } PO \ E \ E' \ X \ Y \ XY$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *lt-to-ltp*:
assumes $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ L$
and $\text{Length } PO \ E \ E' \ C \ D \ M$

and $A B Lt C D$
shows $LtP PO E E' L M$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ltp-to-lep*:
assumes $LtP PO E E' L M$
shows $LeP PO E E' L M$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *ltp-to-lt*:
assumes $Length PO E E' A B L$
and $Length PO E E' C D M$
and $LtP PO E E' L M$
shows $A B Lt C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-col*:
assumes $Ar2 PO E E' A B A$
and $Prod PO E E' A B AB$
shows $Col PO E AB$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *square-increase-strict*:
assumes $Ar2 PO E E' A B A$
and $Ps PO E A$
and $Ps PO E B$
and $LtP PO E E' A B$
and $Prod PO E E' A A A2$
and $Prod PO E E' B B B2$
shows $LtP PO E E' A2 B2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *square-increase*:
assumes $Ar2 PO E E' A B A$
and $Ps PO E A$
and $Ps PO E B$
and $LeP PO E E' A B$
and $Prod PO E E' A A A2$
and $Prod PO E E' B B B2$
shows $LeP PO E E' A2 B2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *signeq--prod-pos*:
assumes $SignEq PO E A B$
and $Prod PO E E' A B C$
shows $Ps PO E C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *pos-neg--prod-neg*:
assumes $Ps PO E A$
and $Ng PO E B$
and $Prod PO E E' A B C$
shows $Ng PO E C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-signEq-prod-neg*:
assumes $A \neq PO$
and $B \neq PO$
and $\neg SignEq PO E A B$
and $Prod PO E E' A B C$
shows $Ng PO E C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *prod-pos--signeq*:
assumes $A \neq PO$
and $B \neq PO$

and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $P_s\ PO\ E\ C$
shows $SignEq\ PO\ E\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $prod-ng---not-signeq$:
assumes $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ C$
and $Ng\ PO\ E\ C$
shows $\neg\ SignEq\ PO\ E\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $ltp--diff-pos$:
assumes $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ D$
shows $P_s\ PO\ E\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $diff-pos--ltp$:
assumes $Diff\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ A\ D$
and $P_s\ PO\ E\ D$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $square-increase-rev$:
assumes $P_s\ PO\ E\ A$
and $P_s\ PO\ E\ B$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A_2\ B_2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ A\ A_2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ B\ B_2$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $ltp--ltps$:
assumes $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LtP_s\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $ltps--ltp$:
assumes $LtP_s\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $ltp--lep-neq$:
assumes $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B \wedge A \neq B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $lep-neq--ltp$:
assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $A \neq B$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $sum-preserves-ltp$:
assumes $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $sum-preserves-lep$:
assumes $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-preserves-ltp-rev*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *sum-preserves-lep-rev*:
assumes $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ BC$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong2-lea--le*:
assumes $Cong\ A\ B\ D\ E$
and $Cong\ A\ C\ D\ F$
and $F\ D\ E\ LeA\ C\ A\ B$
shows $E\ F\ Le\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lea-out-lea*:
assumes $B\ Out\ A\ A'$
and $B\ Out\ C\ C'$
and $E\ Out\ D\ D'$
and $E\ Out\ F\ F'$
and $A\ B\ C\ LeA\ D\ E\ F$
shows $A'\ B\ C'\ LeA\ D'\ E\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *lta-out-lta*:
assumes $B\ Out\ A\ A'$
and $B\ Out\ C\ C'$
and $E\ Out\ D\ D'$
and $E\ Out\ F\ F'$
and $A\ B\ C\ LtA\ D\ E\ F$
shows $A'\ B\ C'\ LtA\ D'\ E\ F'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *pythagoras-obtuse*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $Obtuse\ A\ C\ B$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ AC\ AC^2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ BC\ BC\ BC^2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ AB\ AB^2$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC^2\ BC^2\ S^2$
shows $LtP\ PO\ E\ E'\ S^2\ AB^2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *pythagoras-obtuse-or-per*:
assumes $PO \neq E$
and $Obtuse\ A\ C\ B \vee Per\ A\ C\ B$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ B\ AB$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ A\ C\ AC$
and $Length\ PO\ E\ E'\ B\ C\ BC$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC\ AC\ AC^2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ BC\ BC\ BC^2$
and $Prod\ PO\ E\ E'\ AB\ AB\ AB^2$
and $Sum\ PO\ E\ E'\ AC^2\ BC^2\ S^2$
shows $LeP\ PO\ E\ E'\ S^2\ AB^2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *pythagoras-acute*:

assumes $PO \neq E$
and *Acute* $A C B$
and *Length* $PO E E' A B AB$
and *Length* $PO E E' A C AC$
and *Length* $PO E E' B C BC$
and *Prod* $PO E E' AC AC AC^2$
and *Prod* $PO E E' BC BC BC^2$
and *Prod* $PO E E' AB AB AB^2$
and *Sum* $PO E E' AC^2 BC^2 S^2$
shows *LtP* $PO E E' AB^2 S^2$

<proof>

lemma *pyth-context*:

assumes $\neg Col PO E E'$
shows $\exists AB BC AC AB^2 BC^2 AC^2 SS. Col PO E AB \wedge Col PO E BC \wedge Col PO E AC \wedge$
 $Col PO E AB^2 \wedge Col PO E BC^2 \wedge Col PO E AC^2 \wedge$
 $Length PO E E' A B AB \wedge Length PO E E' B C BC \wedge$
 $Length PO E E' A C AC \wedge Prod PO E E' AB AB AB^2 \wedge$
 $Prod PO E E' BC BC BC^2 \wedge Prod PO E E' AC AC AC^2 \wedge$
 $Sum PO E E' AB^2 BC^2 SS$

<proof>

lemma *length-pos-or-null*:

assumes *Length* $PO E E' A B AB$
shows *Ps* $PO E AB \vee A = B$
<proof>

lemma *sum-pos-null*:

assumes $\neg Ng PO E A$
and $\neg Ng PO E B$
and *Sum* $PO E E' A B PO$
shows $A = PO \wedge B = PO$
<proof>

lemma *length-not-neg*:

assumes *Length* $PO E E' A B AB$
shows $\neg Ng PO E AB$
<proof>

lemma *signEq-refl*:

assumes $PO \neq E$
and *Col* $PO E A$
shows $A = PO \vee SignEq PO E A A$
<proof>

lemma *square-not-neg*:

assumes *Prod* $PO E E' A A A^2$
shows $\neg Ng PO E A^2$
<proof>

lemma *root-uniqueness*:

assumes $\neg Ng PO E A$
and $\neg Ng PO E B$
and *Prod* $PO E E' A A C$
and *Prod* $PO E E' B B C$
shows $A = B$
<proof>

lemma *inter-tangent-circle*:

assumes $P \neq Q$
and *Cong* $P PO Q PO$
and *Col* $P PO Q$
and *P M Le* $P PO$
and *Q M Le* $Q PO$
shows $M = PO$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-circle-per*:
 assumes $\text{Cong } P \ A \ Q \ A$
 and $P \ M \ \text{Le } P \ A$
 and $Q \ M \ \text{Le } Q \ A$
 and $A \ T \ \text{Projp } P \ Q$
 and $\text{Per } P \ T \ M$
 shows $T \ M \ \text{Le } T \ A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-circle-obtuse*:
 assumes $\text{Cong } P \ A \ Q \ A$
 and $P \ M \ \text{Le } P \ A$
 and $Q \ M \ \text{Le } Q \ A$
 and $A \ T \ \text{Projp } P \ Q$
 and $\text{Obtuse } P \ T \ M \ \vee \ \text{Per } P \ T \ M$
 shows $T \ M \ \text{Le } T \ A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circle-projpbetween*:
 assumes $\text{Cong } P \ A \ Q \ A$
 and $A \ T \ \text{Projp } P \ Q$
 shows $\text{Bet } P \ T \ Q$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *inter-circle*:
 assumes $\text{Cong } P \ A \ Q \ A$
 and $P \ M \ \text{Le } P \ A$
 and $Q \ M \ \text{Le } Q \ A$
 and $A \ T \ \text{Projp } P \ Q$
 shows $T \ M \ \text{Le } T \ A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *projpb-lt*:
 assumes $\text{Cong } P \ A \ Q \ A$
 and $A \ T \ \text{Projp } P \ Q$
 shows $T \ A \ \text{Lt } P \ A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Ps-Col*:
 assumes $\text{Ps } P \ O \ E \ A$
 shows $\text{Col } P \ O \ E \ A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *PythRel-exists*:
 assumes $\neg \text{Col } P \ O \ E \ E'$
 shows $\forall A \ B. \ \text{Col } P \ O \ E \ A \ \wedge \ \text{Col } P \ O \ E \ B \ \longrightarrow \ (\exists C. \ \text{PythRel } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C)$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *opp-same-square*:
 assumes $\text{Opp } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A \ B$
 and $\text{Prod } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A \ A \ A^2$
 shows $\text{Prod } P \ O \ E \ E' \ B \ B \ A^2$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *PythOK*:
 assumes $\text{PythRel } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A \ B \ C$
 and $\text{Prod } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A \ A \ A^2$
 and $\text{Prod } P \ O \ E \ E' \ B \ B \ B^2$
 and $\text{Prod } P \ O \ E \ E' \ C \ C \ C^2$
 shows $\text{Sum } P \ O \ E \ E' \ A^2 \ B^2 \ C^2$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *PythRel-uniqueness*:
assumes *PythRel PO E E' A B C1*
and *PythRel PO E E' A B C2*
and $(Ps\ PO\ E\ C1 \wedge Ps\ PO\ E\ C2) \vee C1 = PO$
shows $C1 = C2$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

end
end

16 Tarski Euclidean 2D Continuous

theory *Tarski-Euclidean-2D-Continuous*

imports

Tarski-Euclidean-2D

Tarski-Neutral-Continuous

begin

locale *Tarski-Euclidean-2D-Continuous = Tarski-Euclidean-2D + Tarski-Neutral-Continuous*

end

theory *Highschool-Neutral*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

begin

17 Highschool Neutral

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

17.1 Definitions

17.2 Propositions

lemma *bisector-existence*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and** $B \neq C$

shows $\exists E. E\ InAngle\ A\ B\ C \wedge A\ B\ E\ CongA\ E\ B\ C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *not-col-bfoot-not-equality*:

assumes $\neg Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

Coplanar A B C I **and**

Col A B H1 **and**

$A\ B\ I\ CongA\ I\ B\ C$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ I\ H1$ **and**

$B\ C\ Perp\ I\ H2$

shows $H1 \neq B \wedge H2 \neq B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bisector-foot-out-out*:

assumes $\neg Col\ A\ B\ C$ **and**

Coplanar A B C I **and**

Col B C H2 **and**

$A\ B\ I\ CongA\ I\ B\ C$ **and**

$A\ B\ Perp\ I\ H1$ **and**

$B\ C\ Perp\ I\ H2$ **and**

B Out H1 A

shows $B \text{ Out } H2 \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *not-col-efoot-not-equality:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ I$ **and**
 $\text{Col } A \ B \ H1$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ C \ H2$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } I \ H1 \ I \ H2$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{Perp } I \ H1$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{Perp } I \ H2$
shows $H1 \neq B \wedge H2 \neq B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *equality-foot-out-out:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $I \ \text{InAngle } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ C \ H2$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } I \ H1 \ I \ H2$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{Perp } I \ H1$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{Perp } I \ H2$ **and**
 $B \ \text{Out } H1 \ A$
shows $B \ \text{Out } H2 \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *bisector-perp-equality:*

assumes $\text{Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ I$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ H1 \ A$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ C \ H2$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{Perp } I \ H1$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{Perp } I \ H2$ **and**
 $A \ B \ I \ \text{Cong} \ A \ I \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Cong } I \ H1 \ I \ H2$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *perp-equality-bisector:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $I \ \text{InAngle } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ H1 \ A$ **and**
 $\text{Col } B \ H2 \ C$ **and**
 $A \ B \ \text{Perp } I \ H1$ **and**
 $B \ C \ \text{Perp } I \ H2$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } I \ H1 \ I \ H2$
shows $A \ B \ I \ \text{Cong} \ A \ I \ B \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-permut132:*

assumes $\text{Col } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col } A \ C \ B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-permut213:*

assumes $\text{Col } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col } B \ A \ C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *col-permut231:*

assumes $\text{Col } A \ B \ C$
shows $\text{Col } B \ C \ A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

```

lemma col-permut312:
  assumes Col A B C
  shows Col C A B
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma col-permut321:
  assumes Col A B C
  shows Col C B A
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma col123-124--col134:
  assumes P ≠ Q and
    Col P Q A and
    Col P Q B
  shows Col P A B
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma col123-124--col234:
  assumes P ≠ Q and
    Col P Q A and
    Col P Q B
  shows Col Q A B
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma triangle-mid-par-strict:
  assumes ¬ Col A B C and
    P Midpoint B C and
    Q Midpoint A C
  shows A B ParStrict Q P
  ⟨proof⟩

end
end

theory Highschool-Euclidean

imports
  Tarski-Neutral-Continuity
  Highschool-Neutral
  Tarski-Euclidean

begin

18 Highschool Euclidean dimensionless

context Tarski-Euclidean

begin

lemma triangle-mid-par-strict-cong-aux:
  assumes ¬ Col A B C and
    P Midpoint B C and
    Q Midpoint A C and
    R Midpoint A B
  shows A B ParStrict Q P ∧ Cong A R P Q ∧ Cong B R P Q
  ⟨proof⟩

lemma triangle-par-mid:
  assumes ¬ Col A B C and
    P Midpoint B C and
    A B Par Q P and
    Col Q A C
  shows Q Midpoint A C
  ⟨proof⟩

```

lemma *triangle-mid-par-strict-cong-1*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ ParStrict } Q \ P \wedge \text{Cong } A \ R \ P \ Q$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-strict-cong-2*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ ParStrict } Q \ P \wedge \text{Cong } B \ R \ P \ Q$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-strict-cong-simp*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$

shows $A \ B \text{ ParStrict } Q \ P$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-strict-cong*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ ParStrict } Q \ P \wedge A \ C \text{ ParStrict } P \ R \wedge$

$B \ C \text{ ParStrict } Q \ R \wedge \text{Cong } A \ R \ P \ Q \wedge$

$\text{Cong } B \ R \ P \ Q \wedge \text{Cong } A \ Q \ P \ R \wedge$

$\text{Cong } C \ Q \ P \ R \wedge \text{Cong } B \ P \ Q \ R \wedge \text{Cong } C \ P \ Q \ R$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-flat-cong-aux*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ Par } Q \ P \wedge \text{Cong } A \ R \ P \ Q \wedge \text{Cong } B \ R \ P \ Q$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-flat-cong-1*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ Par } Q \ P \wedge \text{Cong } A \ R \ P \ Q$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-flat-cong-2*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$\text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**

$P \text{ Midpoint } B \ C$ **and**

$Q \text{ Midpoint } A \ C$ **and**

$R \text{ Midpoint } A \ B$

shows $A \ B \text{ Par } Q \ P \wedge \text{Cong } B \ R \ P \ Q$

<proof>

lemma *triangle-mid-par-flat-cong*:

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$A \neq C$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

Col $A B C$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $A C$ **and**
R *Midpoint* $A B$
shows $A B \text{ Par } Q P \wedge A C \text{ Par } P R \wedge B C \text{ Par } Q R \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A R P Q \wedge \text{Cong } B R P Q \wedge \text{Cong } A Q P R \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } C Q P R \wedge \text{Cong } B P Q R \wedge \text{Cong } C P Q R$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle-mid-par-flat:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
Col $A B C$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $A C$
shows $A B \text{ Par } Q P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle-mid-par:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $A C$
shows $A B \text{ Par } Q P$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle-mid-par-cong:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $A C$ **and**
R *Midpoint* $A B$
shows $A B \text{ Par } Q P \wedge A C \text{ Par } P R \wedge B C \text{ Par } Q R \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } A R P Q \wedge \text{Cong } B R P Q \wedge \text{Cong } A Q P R \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } C Q P R \wedge \text{Cong } B P Q R \wedge \text{Cong } C P Q R$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *triangle-mid-par-cong-1:*

assumes $B \neq C$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
Q *Midpoint* $A C$ **and**
R *Midpoint* $A B$
shows $B C \text{ Par } Q R \wedge \text{Cong } B P Q R$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-thales:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $A B$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } P A P C$
shows $\text{Per } A C B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-thales-reci:*

assumes $\text{Per } A C B$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $A B$
shows $\text{Cong } P A P B \wedge \text{Cong } P B P C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-thales-reci-1:*

assumes $\text{Per } A C B$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $A B$
shows $\text{Cong } P A P B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-thales-reci-2:*

assumes $\text{Per } A C B$ **and**
P *Midpoint* $A B$

shows *Cong P B P C*
(proof)

lemma *Per-mid-rectangle:*
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
Per B A C **and**
I Midpoint B C **and**
J Midpoint A C **and**
K Midpoint A B
shows *Rectangle A J I K*
(proof)

lemma *varignon:*
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $B \neq D$ **and**
 \neg *Col I J K* **and**
I Midpoint A B **and**
J Midpoint B C **and**
K Midpoint C D **and**
L Midpoint A D
shows *Parallelogram I J K L*
(proof)

lemma *varignon-aux-aux:*
assumes $A \neq C$ **and**
 $J \neq L$ **and**
I Midpoint A B **and**
J Midpoint B C **and**
K Midpoint C D **and**
L Midpoint A D
shows *Parallelogram I J K L*
(proof)

lemma *varignon-aux:*
assumes
 $J \neq L$ **and**
I Midpoint A B **and**
J Midpoint B C **and**
K Midpoint C D **and**
L Midpoint A D
shows *Parallelogram I J K L*
(proof)

lemma *varignon-bis:*
assumes $A \neq C \vee B \neq D$ **and**
I Midpoint A B **and**
J Midpoint B C **and**
K Midpoint C D **and**
L Midpoint A D
shows *Parallelogram I J K L*
(proof)

lemma *quadrilateral-midpoints:*
assumes \neg *Col I J K* **and**
I Midpoint A B **and**
J Midpoint B C **and**
K Midpoint C D **and**
L Midpoint A D **and**
X Midpoint I K **and**
Y Midpoint J L
shows $X = Y$
(proof)

lemma *is-circumcenter-coplanar:*

assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Coplanar } G A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circumcenter-cong-1*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Cong } A G B G$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circumcenter-cong-2*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Cong } B G C G$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circumcenter-cong-3*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Cong } C G A G$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circumcenter-cong*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Cong } A G B G \wedge \text{Cong } B G C G \wedge \text{Cong } C G A G$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm-1*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A C B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm-2*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B A C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm-3*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B C A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm-4*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C A B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm-5*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-perm*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C \wedge G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A C B \wedge$
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B A C \wedge G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B C A \wedge$
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C A B \wedge G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C B A$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-circumcenter-cases*:
assumes $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C \vee G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A C B \vee$
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B A C \vee G \text{ IsCircumcenter } B C A \vee$
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C A B \vee G \text{ IsCircumcenter } C B A$
shows $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *circumcenter-perp*:
assumes
 $B \neq C$ **and**

$G \neq A'$ **and**
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$ **and**
 $A' \text{ Midpoint } B C$
shows $G A' \text{ PerpBisect } B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *exists-circumcenter*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$
shows $\exists G. G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *circumcenter-perp-all*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $G \neq A'$ **and**
 $G \neq B'$ **and**
 $G \neq C'$ **and**
 $G \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$ **and**
 $A' \text{ Midpoint } B C$ **and**
 $B' \text{ Midpoint } A C$ **and**
 $C' \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $G A' \text{ PerpBisect } B C \wedge G B' \text{ PerpBisect } A C \wedge G C' \text{ PerpBisect } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *circumcenter-intersect*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $G \neq C'$ **and**
 $C' \text{ Midpoint } A B$ **and**
 $G A' \text{ PerpBisect } B C$ **and**
 $G B' \text{ PerpBisect } A C$
shows $G C' \text{ Perp } A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *is-circumcenter-uniqueness*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $A \neq C$ **and**
 $G1 \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$ **and**
 $G2 \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $G1 = G2$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *midpoint-thales-eci-circum*:
assumes $\text{Per } A C B$ **and**
 $P \text{ Midpoint } A B$
shows $P \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *circumcenter-per*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $B \neq C$ **and**
 $\text{Per } A B C$ **and**
 $P \text{ IsCircumcenter } A B C$
shows $P \text{ Midpoint } A C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *is-orthocenter-coplanar*:
assumes $H \text{ IsOrthocenter } A B C$
shows $\text{Coplanar } H A B C$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *construct-intersection*:
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**
 $A C \text{ Par } B X1$ **and**

$A B \text{ Par } C X2$ and
 $B C \text{ Par } A X3$
shows $\exists E. \text{ Col } E A X3 \wedge \text{ Col } E B X1$
 <proof>

lemma *not-col-par-col-diff*:
assumes $\neg \text{ Col } A B C$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$ and
 $\text{ Col } C D E$
shows $A \neq E$
 <proof>

lemma *construct-triangle*:
assumes $\neg \text{ Col } A B C$
shows $\exists D E F.$
 $\text{ Col } B D F \wedge \text{ Col } A E F \wedge \text{ Col } C D E \wedge$
 $A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge A C \text{ Par } B D \wedge B C \text{ Par } A E \wedge$
 $A B \text{ Par } C E \wedge A C \text{ Par } B F \wedge B C \text{ Par } A F \wedge$
 $D \neq E \wedge D \neq F \wedge E \neq F$
 <proof>

lemma *diff-not-col-col-par4-mid*:
assumes $D \neq E$ and
 $\neg \text{ Col } A B C$ and
 $\text{ Col } C D E$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } C D$ and
 $A B \text{ Par } C E$ and
 $A E \text{ Par } B C$ and
 $A C \text{ Par } B D$
shows $C \text{ Midpoint } D E$
 <proof>

lemma *altitude-is-perp-bisect*:
assumes $A \neq P$ and
 $E \neq F$ and
 $A A1 \text{ Perp } B C$ and
 $\text{ Col } P A1 A$ and
 $\text{ Col } A E F$ and
 $B C \text{ Par } A E$ and
 $A \text{ Midpoint } E F$
shows $A P \text{ PerpBisect } E F$
 <proof>

lemma *altitude-intersect*:
assumes $\neg \text{ Col } A B C$ and
 $A A1 \text{ Perp } B C$ and
 $B B1 \text{ Perp } A C$ and
 $C C1 \text{ Perp } A B$ and
 $\text{ Col } P A A1$ and
 $\text{ Col } P B B1$
shows $\text{ Col } P C C1$
 <proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-cases*:
assumes $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A B C \vee G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A C B \vee$
 $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } B A C \vee G \text{ IsOrthocenter } B C A \vee$
 $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } C A B \vee G \text{ IsOrthocenter } C B A$
shows $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A B C$
 <proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm*:
assumes $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A B C$
shows $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A B C \wedge G \text{ IsOrthocenter } A C B \wedge$
 $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } B A C \wedge G \text{ IsOrthocenter } B C A \wedge$
 $G \text{ IsOrthocenter } C A B \wedge G \text{ IsOrthocenter } C B A$

<proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm-1:*
assumes G *IsOrthocenter* $A B C$
shows G *IsOrthocenter* $A C B$
<proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm-2:*
assumes G *IsOrthocenter* $B A C$
shows G *IsOrthocenter* $A C B$
<proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm-3:*
assumes G *IsOrthocenter* $B C A$
shows G *IsOrthocenter* $A C B$
<proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm-4:*
assumes G *IsOrthocenter* $C A B$
shows G *IsOrthocenter* $A C B$
<proof>

lemma *IsOrthocenter-perm-5:*
assumes G *IsOrthocenter* $C B A$
shows G *IsOrthocenter* $A C B$
<proof>

lemma *orthocenter-per:*
assumes $Per A B C$ **and**
 H *IsOrthocenter* $A B C$
shows $H = B$
<proof>

lemma *orthocenter-col:*
assumes $Col H B C$ **and**
 H *IsOrthocenter* $A B C$
shows $H = B \vee H = C$
<proof>

lemma *intersection-two-medians-exist:*
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
 J *Midpoint* $A C$
shows $\exists G. Col G A I \wedge Col G B J$
<proof>

lemma *intersection-two-medians-exist-unique:*
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
 J *Midpoint* $A C$
shows $\exists! G. Col G A I \wedge Col G B J$
<proof>

lemma *intersection-two-medians-unique-R1:*
assumes $\neg Col A B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
 J *Midpoint* $A C$ **and**
 $Col G1 A I$ **and**
 $Col G1 B J$ **and**
 $Col G2 A I$ **and**
 $Col G2 B J$
shows $G1 = G2$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-coplanar:*
assumes G *IsGravityCenter* $A B C$

shows *Coplanar G A B C*
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-exist-unique:*
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$
shows $\exists! G. G \text{ IsGravityCenter } A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *three-medians-intersect:*
assumes $\neg \text{Col } A \ B \ C$ **and**
 I Midpoint B C and
 J Midpoint A C and
 K Midpoint A B
shows $\exists G. \text{Col } G \ A \ I \wedge \text{Col } G \ B \ J \wedge \text{Col } G \ C \ K$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-col:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C and*
 I Midpoint A B
shows *Col G I C*
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-diff-1:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $G \neq A$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-diff-2:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $G \neq B$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-diff-3:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $G \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-third-aux-lem:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C and*
 I Midpoint B C and J Midpoint A C and
 Col G A I and Col G B J
shows $G \neq I \wedge G \neq J$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-third-aux-1:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $\neg \text{Col } B \ G \ C$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-third-aux-2:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $\neg \text{Col } C \ G \ A$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-third-aux-3:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C*
shows $\neg \text{Col } A \ G \ B$
<proof>

lemma *is-gravity-center-third:*
assumes *G IsGravityCenter A B C and*
 G' Midpoint A G and
 A' Midpoint B C
shows *G Midpoint A' G'*

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-third-reci*:

assumes A' Midpoint $B C$ **and**

A'' Midpoint $A G$ **and**

G Midpoint $A' A''$ **and**

$\neg \text{Col } A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $A B C \wedge G$ IsGravityCenter $A C B \wedge$

G IsGravityCenter $B A C \wedge G$ IsGravityCenter $B C A \wedge$

G IsGravityCenter $C A B \wedge G$ IsGravityCenter $C B A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm-1*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $A C B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm-2*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $B A C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm-3*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $B C A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm-4*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $C A B$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-perm-5*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

shows G IsGravityCenter $C B A$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *is-gravity-center-cases*:

assumes G IsGravityCenter $A B C \vee G$ IsGravityCenter $A C B \vee$

G IsGravityCenter $B A C \vee G$ IsGravityCenter $B C A \vee$

G IsGravityCenter $C A B \vee G$ IsGravityCenter $C B A$

shows G IsGravityCenter $A B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *concylic-aux*:

assumes Concylic2 $A B C D$

shows $\exists P. \text{Cong } P A P B \wedge \text{Cong } P A P C \wedge \text{Cong } P A P D \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C P$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *concylic-trans*:

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$ **and**

Concylic2 $A B C D$ **and**

Concylic2 $A B C E$

shows Concylic2 $A B D E$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *concylic-perm-1*:

assumes Concylic2 $A B C D$

shows Concylic2 $A B D C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *conyclic-perm-2*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 A C B D*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-3*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 A C D B*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-4*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 A D B C*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-5*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 A D C B*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-6*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B A C D*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-7*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B A D C*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-8*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B C A D*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-9*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B C D A*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-10*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B D A C*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-11*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 B D C A*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-12*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 C A B D*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-13*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 C A D B*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-14*:
assumes *Concyclic2 A B C D*
shows *Concyclic2 C B A D*
<proof>

lemma *conyclic-perm-15*:

assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* C B D A
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-16*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* C D A B
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-17*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* C D B A
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-18*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D A B C
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-19*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D A C B
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-20*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D B A C
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-21*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D B C A
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-22*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D C A B
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-perm-23*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows *Concyclic2* D C B A
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-1123*:
assumes \neg Col A B C
shows *Concyclic2* A A B C
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-not-col-or-eq-aux*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C D
shows $A = B \vee A = C \vee B = C \vee \neg$ Col A B C
{proof}

lemma *conconcyclic-not-col-or-eq*:
assumes *Concyclic2* A B C A'
shows $A' = C \vee A' = B \vee A = B \vee A = C \vee A = A' \vee (\neg$ Col A B A' $\wedge \neg$ Col A C A')
{proof}

lemma *Euler-line-special-case*:
assumes Per A B C **and**
G IsGravityCenter A B C **and**
H IsOrthocenter A B C **and**
P IsCircumcenter A B C
shows Col G H P
{proof}

lemma *gravity-center-change-triangle*:
assumes G *IsGravityCenter* $A B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $B' C'$ **and**
 \neg *Col* $A B' C'$
shows G *IsGravityCenter* $A B' C'$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *Euler-line*:
assumes \neg *Col* $A B C$ **and**
 G *IsGravityCenter* $A B C$ **and**
 H *IsOrthocenter* $A B C$ **and**
 P *IsCircumcenter* $A B C$
shows *Col* $G H P$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex35*:
assumes \neg *Col* $G A Z$ **and**
 Per $G A Z$ **and**
 F *Midpoint* $A Z$ **and**
 E *Midpoint* $G Z$ **and**
 R *Midpoint* $G A$
shows *Rectangle* $F E R A$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex36-aux*:
assumes \neg *Col* $A B C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $A B$ **and**
 J *Midpoint* $A C$ **and**
 K *Midpoint* $B C$
shows *Plg* $I J K B$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex36*:
assumes $B A C$ *isosceles* **and**
 $A H$ *Perp* $B C$ **and**
 Col $B H C$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $A B$ **and**
 J *Midpoint* $A C$
shows *Rhombus* $A I H J$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex37*:
assumes \neg *Col* $S E L$ **and**
 I *Midpoint* $L S$ **and**
 M *Midpoint* $S E$ **and**
 A *Midpoint* $E L$ **and**
 $A P$ *PerpBisect* $L E$ **and**
 $Coplanar$ $S E L P$
shows $A P$ *Perp* $I M$
⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex38* :
assumes \neg *Col E A U* **and**
N Midpoint E A **and**
M Midpoint E U **and**
L Midpoint U A
shows $\exists P. \text{Col } P \ E \ L \wedge P \ \text{Midpoint } M \ N$
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex39*:
assumes \neg *Col A C T* **and**
S IsCircumcenter C T A **and**
S Midpoint C T **and**
Col C H A **and**
S H Perp A C
shows *H Midpoint A C*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex40*:
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
Bet C R B **and**
M Midpoint A B **and**
N Midpoint A C **and**
S Midpoint B R **and**
T Midpoint R C
shows *M S Par N T* \wedge *Parallelogram M S T N*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex41* :
assumes \neg *Col T L H* **and**
E Midpoint T L **and**
P Midpoint T H **and**
A \neq T **and**
A \neq P **and**
A \neq E **and**
A \neq S **and**
Bet T A S **and**
Bet P A E **and**
Bet H S L **and**
S \neq H **and**
S \neq L
shows *S A E CongA T S H* \wedge *A Midpoint T S*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex42*:
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
G IsGravityCenter A B C **and**
I Midpoint A C **and**
J Midpoint A B **and**
K Midpoint B G **and**
L Midpoint C G
shows *Parallelogram I J K L*
⟨proof⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex44-1*:
assumes *ParallelogramStrict A B C D* **and**
I Midpoint A D **and**
J Midpoint B C
shows *Parallelogram B J D I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex45*:
assumes \neg *Col A B C* **and**
I Midpoint B C **and**
Col I A M **and**
A Midpoint I M **and**
J Midpoint A I **and**
J K Par A C **and**
Col K I C **and**
Col G C A **and**
Col G M K
shows *K Midpoint I C* \wedge *A K Par M C* \wedge *G IsGravityCenter C M I*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

lemma *sesamath-4ieme-G2-ex47* :
assumes \neg *Col A C C'* **and**
 \neg *Col A A' C'* **and**
Col B' A' C' **and**
B Midpoint A C **and**
A A' Par B B' **and**
A A' Par C C'
shows *B' Midpoint A' C'*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

end
end

theory *Highschool-Euclidean-2D*

imports
Highschool-Euclidean
Tarski-Euclidean-2D

begin

19 Highschool Euclidean 2D

context *Tarski-Euclidean-2D*

begin

19.1 Definitions

19.2 Propositions

lemma *NewEX1*:
assumes *Square A B C D* **and**
Cong K A K C **and**
Cong K A A C
shows *Col B K D*
 ⟨*proof*⟩

end
end

theory *Tarski-Non-Euclidean*

imports

Tarski-Postulate-Parallels

begin

20 Tarski Non Euclidean

20.1 Definitions

locale *Tarski-Non-Euclidean* = *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless* +

fixes *A0 B0 C0 D0 T0*

assumes *NERule1*: *Bet A0 D0 T0*

and *NERule2*: *Bet B0 D0 C0*

and *NERule3*: $A0 \neq D0$

and *not-tarski-s-parallel-postulate-aux*:

$\forall X Y. ((Bet A0 B0 X \wedge Bet A0 C0 Y) \longrightarrow \neg Bet X T0 Y)$

context *Tarski-Non-Euclidean*

begin

20.2 Propositions

lemma *Tarski-Pre-Non-Euclidean-aux*:

shows $\exists A B C D T. \neg ((Bet A D T \wedge Bet B D C \wedge A \neq D)$

\longrightarrow

$(\exists X Y. Bet A B X \wedge Bet A C Y \wedge Bet X T Y))$

<proof>

lemma *NPost01*:

shows $\neg Postulate01$

<proof>

lemma *NPost02*:

shows $\neg Postulate02$

<proof>

lemma *NPost05*:

shows $\neg Postulate05$

<proof>

lemma *NPost06*:

shows $\neg Postulate06$

<proof>

lemma *NPost07*:

shows $\neg Postulate07$

<proof>

lemma *NPost08*:

shows $\neg Postulate08$

<proof>

lemma *NPost09*:

shows $\neg Postulate09$

<proof>

lemma *NPost10*:

shows $\neg Postulate10$

<proof>

lemma *NPost11*:
shows \neg *Postulate11*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost12*:
shows \neg *Postulate12*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost13*:
shows \neg *Postulate13*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost14*:
shows \neg *Postulate14*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost15*:
shows \neg *Postulate15*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost16*:
shows \neg *Postulate16*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost17*:
shows \neg *Postulate17*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost18*:
shows \neg *Postulate18*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost19*:
shows \neg *Postulate19*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

lemma *NPost20*:
shows \neg *Postulate20*
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-tarski-s-parallel-postulate-thm*:
shows \exists $A B C D T$. ($Bet A D T \wedge Bet B D C \wedge A \neq D \wedge$
 $(\forall X Y. (Bet A B X \wedge Bet A C Y) \longrightarrow \neg Bet X T Y)$)
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-playfair-s-postulate-thm*:
shows \exists $A_1 A_2 B_1 B_2 C_1 C_2 P$. $A_1 A_2 Par B_1 B_2 \wedge$
 $Col P B_1 B_2 \wedge A_1 A_2 Par C_1 C_2 \wedge Col P C_1 C_2 \wedge$
 $(\neg Col C_1 B_1 B_2 \vee \neg Col C_2 B_1 B_2)$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-postulate-of-transitivity-of-parallelism-thm*:
shows \exists $A_1 A_2 B_1 B_2 C_1 C_2$. $A_1 A_2 Par B_1 B_2 \wedge B_1 B_2 Par C_1 C_2 \wedge \neg (A_1 A_2 Par C_1 C_2)$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-midpoint-converse-postulate-thm*:
shows \exists $A B C P Q$. $\neg Col A B C \wedge P Midpoint B C \wedge A B Par Q P \wedge Col A C Q \wedge \neg Q Midpoint A C$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-alternate-interior-angles-postulate-thm*:
shows \exists $A B C D$. $A C TS B D \wedge A B Par C D \wedge \neg B A C Cong A D C A$
 \langle *proof* \rangle

theorem *not-consecutive-interior-angles-postulate-thm*:
shows \exists $A B C D$. $B C OS A D \wedge A B Par C D \wedge \neg A B C Supp A B C D$

<proof>

theorem *not-perpendicular-transversal-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C D P Q. A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge A B \text{ Perp } P Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } C D P Q \wedge \neg C D \text{ Perp } P Q$
<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-parallelism-of-perpendicular-transversals-thm:*

shows $\exists A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 D1 D2.$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Par } B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } C1 C2 \wedge B1 B2 \text{ Perp } D1 D2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } A1 A2 C1 D1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } A1 A2 C1 D2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } A1 A2 C2 D1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } A1 A2 C2 D2 \wedge \neg C1 C2 \text{ Par } D1 D2$
<proof>

theorem *not-universal-posidonius-postulate:*

shows $\exists A1 A2 A3 A4 B1 B2 B3 B4.$
 $A1 A2 \text{ Par } B1 B2 \wedge \text{Col } A1 A2 A3 \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 B3 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A3 B3 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A1 A2 A4 \wedge \text{Col } B1 B2 B4 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Perp } A4 B4 \wedge \neg \text{Cong } A3 B3 A4 B4$
<proof>

theorem *not-alternative-playfair-s-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2 P.$
 $P \text{ Perp2 } A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge \neg \text{Col } A1 A2 P \wedge \text{Col } P B1 B2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } A1 A2 B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Par } C1 C2 \wedge \text{Col } P C1 C2 \wedge$
 $(\neg \text{Col } C1 B1 B2 \vee \neg \text{Col } C2 B1 B2)$
<proof>

theorem *not-proclus-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C D P Q. (\forall Y. A B \text{ Par } C D \wedge \text{Col } A B P \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Col } A B Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } C D P Q \wedge (\neg \text{Col } P Q Y \vee \neg \text{Col } C D Y))$
<proof>

theorem *not-alternative-proclus-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C D P Q. (\forall Y. P \text{ Perp2 } A B C D \wedge \neg \text{Col } C D P \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C D \wedge \text{Col } A B P \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Col } A B Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } C D P Q \wedge (\neg \text{Col } P Q Y \vee \neg \text{Col } C D Y))$
<proof>

theorem *not-triangle-circumscription-principle-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C. \forall D. (\neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge (\neg \text{Cong } A D B D \vee \neg \text{Cong } A D C D \vee \neg \text{Coplanar } A B C D))$
<proof>

theorem *not-inverse-projection-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C P Q. \forall Y.$
 $\text{Acute } A B C \wedge B \text{ Out } A P \wedge P \neq Q \wedge \text{Per } B P Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C Q \wedge$
 $(\neg B \text{ Out } C Y \vee \neg \text{Col } P Q Y)$
<proof>

theorem *not-euclid-5-thm:*

shows $\exists P Q R S T U. \forall I.$
 $\text{BetS } P T Q \wedge \text{BetS } R T S \wedge \text{BetS } Q U R \wedge \neg \text{Col } P Q S \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } P T Q T \wedge \text{Cong } R T S T \wedge (\neg \text{BetS } S Q I \vee \neg \text{BetS } P U I)$
<proof>

theorem *not-strong-parallel-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists P Q R S T U. \forall I.$
 $\text{BetS } P T Q \wedge \text{BetS } R T S \wedge \neg \text{Col } P R U \wedge \text{Coplanar } P Q R U \wedge$
 $\text{Cong } P T Q T \wedge \text{Cong } R T S T \wedge (\neg \text{Col } S Q I \vee \neg \text{Col } P U I)$
<proof>

theorem *not-alternative-strong-parallel-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C D P Q R. \forall Y.$
 $B C \text{ OS } A D \wedge A B C B C D \text{ Sum } A P Q R \wedge \neg \text{Bet } P Q R \wedge (\neg \text{Col } B A Y \vee \neg \text{Col } C D Y)$
<proof>

theorem *not-euclid-s-parallel-postulate-thm:*

shows $\exists A B C D P Q R. \forall Y.$
 $B C \text{ OS } A D \wedge \text{SAMS } A B C B C D \wedge A B C B C D \text{ Sum } A P Q R \wedge$

$\neg \text{Bet } P \ Q \ R \wedge (\neg \text{B Out } A \ Y \vee \neg \text{C Out } D \ Y)$
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Aristotle*

imports
Tarski-Non-Euclidean

begin

21 Tarski Non Euclidean Aristotle

21.1 Definitions

locale *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Aristotle* = *Tarski-Non-Euclidean* +
assumes *aristotle: aristotle-s-axiom*

context *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Aristotle*

begin

21.2 Propositions

lemma *NPost03*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate03}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost21*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate21}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost22*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate22}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost23*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate23}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost24*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate24}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost25*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate25}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost26*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate26}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost27*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate27}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost28*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate28}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost29*:
shows $\neg \text{Postulate29}$
<proof>

lemma *NPost30*:

shows \neg *Postulate30*

<proof>

theorem *not-triangle-postulate-thm*:

shows $\exists A B C D E F. A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F \wedge \neg \text{Bet } D E F$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-existence-of-a-triangle-whose-angles-sum-to-two-rights-thm*:

shows $\forall A B C D E F. A B C \text{ TriSum} A D E F \wedge \text{Bet } D E F \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

theorem *not-posidonius-postulate-thm*:

shows $\forall A_1 A_2 B_1 B_2. \text{Col } A_1 A_2 B_1 \vee B_1 = B_2 \vee \neg \text{Coplanar } A_1 A_2 B_1 B_2 \vee$
 $(\exists A_3 A_4 B_3 B_4. \text{Col } A_1 A_2 A_3 \wedge \text{Col } B_1 B_2 B_3 \wedge A_1 A_2 \text{ Perp } A_3 B_3 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A_1 A_2 A_4 \wedge \text{Col } B_1 B_2 B_4 \wedge A_1 A_2 \text{ Perp } A_4 B_4 \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Cong } A_3 B_3 A_4 B_4)$

<proof>

theorem *not-posidonius-postulate-thm-1*:

shows $\forall A_1 A_2 B. \text{Col } A_1 A_2 B \vee (\exists A_3 A_4 B_3 B_4. \text{Col } A_1 A_2 A_3 \wedge \text{Col } B B B_3 \wedge A_1 A_2 \text{ Perp } A_3 B_3 \wedge$
 $\text{Col } A_1 A_2 A_4 \wedge \text{Col } B B B_4 \wedge A_1 A_2 \text{ Perp } A_4 B_4 \wedge$
 $\neg \text{Cong } A_3 B_3 A_4 B_4)$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-existence-of-similar-triangles-thm*:

shows $\forall A B C D E F. (\text{Col } A B C \vee \text{Cong } A B D E \vee \neg A B C \text{ Cong } A D E F \vee$
 $\neg B C A \text{ Cong } A E F D \vee \neg C A B \text{ Cong } A F D E)$

<proof>

theorem *not-thales-postulate-thm*:

shows $\exists A B C M. M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge \text{Cong } M A M C \wedge \neg \text{Per } A C B$

<proof>

theorem *not-thales-converse-postulate-thm*:

shows $\exists A B C M. M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge \text{Per } A C B \wedge \neg \text{Cong } M A M C$

<proof>

theorem *not-existential-thales-postulate-thm*:

shows $\forall A B C M. (M \text{ Midpoint } A B \wedge \text{Cong } M A M C \wedge \text{Per } A C B) \longrightarrow \text{Col } A B C$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-right-saccheri-quadrilaterals-thm*:

shows $\exists A B C D. \text{Saccheri } A B C D \wedge \neg \text{Per } A B C$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-saccheri-quadrilateral-thm*:

shows $\forall A B C D. \neg (\text{Saccheri } A B C D \wedge \text{Per } A B C)$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-right-lambert-quadrilaterals-thm*:

shows $\exists A B C D. \text{Lambert } A B C D \wedge \neg \text{Per } B C D$

<proof>

theorem *not-postulate-of-existence-of-a-right-lambert-quadrilateral-thm*:

shows $\forall A B C D. \neg (\text{Lambert } A B C D \wedge \text{Per } B C D)$

<proof>

end

end

theory *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Archimedean*

imports

Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Aristotle

begin

22 Tarski Non Euclidean

22.1 Definitions

locale *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Archimedean* = *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Aristotle* +
assumes *archimedes: archimedes-axiom*

context *Tarski-Non-Euclidean-Archimedean*

begin

22.2 Propositions

lemma *NPost04*:

shows \neg *Postulate04*
{*proof*}

lemma *NPost31*:

shows \neg *Postulate31*
{*proof*}

lemma *NPost32*:

shows \neg *Postulate32*
{*proof*}

lemma *NPost33*:

shows \neg *Postulate33*
{*proof*}

lemma *NPost34*:

shows \neg *Postulate34*
{*proof*}

lemma *NPost35*:

shows \neg *Postulate35*
{*proof*}

theorem *not-bachmann-s-lotschnittaxiom*:

shows $\exists P Q R P1 R1. P \neq Q \wedge Q \neq R \wedge \text{Per } P Q R \wedge \text{Per } Q P P1 \wedge \text{Per } Q R R1 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } P Q R P1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } P Q R R1 \wedge$
 $(\forall S. \neg \text{Col } P P1 S \vee \neg \text{Col } R R1 S)$

{*proof*}

theorem *not-weak-inverse-projection-postulate*:

shows $\exists A B C D E F P Q Y. \text{Acute } A B C \wedge \text{Per } D E F \wedge A B C A B C \text{Sum} A D E F \wedge$
 $B \text{ Out } A P \wedge P \neq Q \wedge \text{Per } B P Q \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C Q \wedge$
 $(\neg B \text{ Out } C Y \vee \neg \text{Col } P Q Y)$

{*proof*}

theorem *not-weak-tarski-s-parallel-postulate*:

shows $\exists A B C T. \text{Per } A B C \wedge T \text{ InAngle } A B C \wedge$
 $(\forall X Y. \neg B \text{ Out } A X \vee \neg B \text{ Out } C Y \vee \neg \text{Bet } X T Y)$

{*proof*}

theorem *not-weak-triangle-circumscription-principle*:

shows $\exists A B C A1 A2 B1 B2. \neg \text{Col } A B C \wedge \text{Per } A C B \wedge A1 A2 \text{PerpBisect } B C \wedge$
 $B1 B2 \text{PerpBisect } A C \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C A1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C A2 \wedge$
 $\text{Coplanar } A B C B1 \wedge \text{Coplanar } A B C B2 \wedge$
 $(\forall I. \neg \text{Col } A1 A2 I \vee \neg \text{Col } B1 B2 I)$

{*proof*}

theorem *not-legendre-s-parallel-postulate:*

fixes $A B C$

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A B C$

and $\text{Acute } A B C$

shows $\exists T. T \text{ InAngle } A B C \wedge (\forall X Y. \neg B \text{ Out } A X \vee \neg B \text{ Out } C Y \vee \neg \text{Bet } X T Y)$

<proof>

theorem *not-existential-playfair-s-postulate:*

assumes $\neg \text{Col } A1 A2 P$

shows $\exists B1 B2 C1 C2. A1 A2 \text{ Par } B1 B2 \wedge \text{Col } P B1 B2 \wedge A1 A2 \text{ Par } C1 C2 \wedge \text{Col } P C1 C2 \wedge$
 $(\neg \text{Col } C1 B1 B2 \vee \neg \text{Col } C2 B1 B2)$

<proof>

end

end

theory *Gupta-Neutral*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

begin

23 Gupta inspired variant of Tarski - Geometry

23.1 Axioms - neutral dimension less

locale *Gupta-neutral-dimensionless* =

fixes $GPA GPB GPC :: 'p$

and $\text{Bet}G :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

and $\text{Cong}G :: 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow 'p \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

assumes $\text{cong-pseudo-reflexivity}G: \forall a b.$

$\text{Cong}G a b b a$

and $\text{cong-inner-transitivity}G: \forall a b p q r s.$

$\text{Cong}G a b p q \wedge$

$\text{Cong}G a b r s$

\longrightarrow

$\text{Cong}G p q r s$

and $\text{cong-identity}G: \forall a b c.$

$\text{Cong}G a b c c$

\longrightarrow

$a = b$

and $\text{segment-construction}G: \forall a b c q.$

$\exists x. (\text{Bet}G q a x \wedge \text{Cong}G a x b c)$

and $\text{five-segment}G: \forall a b c d a' b' c' d'.$

$a \neq b \wedge$

$\text{Bet}G a b c \wedge$

$\text{Bet}G a' b' c' \wedge$

$\text{Cong}G a b a' b' \wedge$

$\text{Cong}G b c b' c' \wedge$

$\text{Cong}G a d a' d' \wedge$

$\text{Cong}G b d b' d'$

\longrightarrow

$\text{Cong}G c d c' d'$

and *between-symmetry* G : $\forall a b c.$

$BetG a b c$
 \longrightarrow
 $BetG c b a$

and *between-inner-transitivity* G : $\forall a b c d.$

$BetG a b d \wedge$
 $BetG b c d$
 \longrightarrow
 $BetG a b c$

and *inner-pasch* G : $\forall a b c p q.$

$BetG a p c \wedge$
 $BetG b q c \wedge$
 $a \neq p \wedge$
 $c \neq p \wedge$
 $b \neq q \wedge$
 $c \neq q \wedge$
 $\neg (BetG a b c \vee BetG b c a \vee BetG c a b)$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\exists x. BetG p x b \wedge BetG q x a)$

and *lower-dim* G : $\neg (BetG GPA GPB GPC \vee BetG GPB GPC GPA \vee BetG GPC GPA GPB)$

context *Gupta-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

23.2 Definitions

definition *Col* G :: ' $p \Rightarrow p \Rightarrow p \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
 $ColG A B C \equiv BetG A B C \vee BetG B C A \vee BetG C A B$

23.3 Propositions

lemma *g2-1*:
shows $CongG A B A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-2*:
assumes $CongG A B C D$
shows $CongG C D A B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *cong-inner-transitivity* T :
assumes $CongG A B C D$ **and**
 $CongG A B E F$
shows $CongG C D E F$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-3*:
assumes $CongG A B C D$
shows $CongG B A C D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-4*:
assumes $CongG A B C D$
shows $CongG A B D C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-5-a*:

assumes $CongG\ A\ B\ C\ D$ and
 $A = B$
shows $C = D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-5-b*:
assumes $CongG\ A\ B\ C\ D$ and
 $C = D$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-5*:
assumes $CongG\ A\ B\ C\ D$
shows $A = B \longleftrightarrow C = D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-6*:
shows $BetG\ A\ B\ B \wedge CongG\ B\ B\ A\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-7*:
assumes $CongG\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ and
 $CongG\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$ and
 $BetG\ A\ B\ C$ and
 $BetG\ A'\ B'\ C'$
shows $CongG\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-8*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ C$ and
 $BetG\ A\ B\ D$ and
 $CongG\ B\ C\ B\ D$ and
 $A \neq B$
shows $C = D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-9*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$
shows $BetG\ C\ A\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-10*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$
shows $BetG\ C\ B\ A$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-11*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ and
 $A \neq B$
shows $\exists D. BetG\ C\ D\ C \wedge BetG\ D\ C\ D \wedge C \neq D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-12*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$
shows $BetG\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-13*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ and
 $A \neq B$
shows $BetG\ C\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *g2-14-1*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ and
 $A \neq B$

shows $BetG\ C\ D\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $g2-14-2$:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $BetG\ D\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $g2-14$:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $BetG\ C\ D\ C \wedge BetG\ D\ C\ D$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $g2-15$:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$ **and**
 $A \neq B$
shows $BetG\ C\ D\ E$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $g2-16$:
assumes $\neg BetG\ C\ D\ E$ **and**
 $BetG\ A\ B\ A$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $between-identityT$:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ A$
shows $A = B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $cong-trivial-identityT$:
shows $CongG\ A\ A\ B\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $l2-11T$:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ C$ **and**
 $BetG\ A'\ B'\ C'$ **and**
 $CongG\ A\ B\ A'\ B'$ **and**
 $CongG\ B\ C\ B'\ C'$
shows $CongG\ A\ C\ A'\ C'$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $construction-uniquenessT$:
assumes $Q \neq A$ **and**
 $BetG\ Q\ A\ X$ **and**
 $CongG\ A\ X\ B\ C$ **and**
 $BetG\ Q\ A\ Y$ **and**
 $CongG\ A\ Y\ B\ C$
shows $X = Y$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $between-trivialT$:
shows $BetG\ A\ B\ B$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $bet-decG$:
shows $BetG\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg BetG\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $col-decG$:
shows $ColG\ A\ B\ C \vee \neg ColG\ A\ B\ C$
 $\langle proof \rangle$

lemma $inner-paschT$:

```

assumes BetG A P C and
  BetG B Q C
shows  $\exists x. \text{BetG } P \ x \ B \wedge \text{BetG } Q \ x \ A$ 
⟨proof⟩

end
end

```

```

theory Gupta-Neutral-2D

```

```

imports
  Gupta-Neutral

```

```

begin

```

24 Gupta 2D

24.1 Axioms Gupta 2D

```

locale Gupta-neutral-2D = Gupta-neutral-dimensionless GPA GPB GPC BetG CongG
for GPA GPB GPC :: 'p
and BetG :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and CongG :: 'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  'p  $\Rightarrow$  bool +
assumes upper-dimG:  $\forall a \ b \ c \ p \ q.$ 
   $p \neq q \wedge$ 
   $a \neq b \wedge$ 
   $a \neq c \wedge$ 
   $c \neq b \wedge$ 
   $CongG \ a \ p \ a \ q \wedge$ 
   $CongG \ b \ p \ b \ q \wedge$ 
   $CongG \ c \ p \ c \ q$ 
   $\longrightarrow$ 
   $(BetG \ a \ b \ c \vee BetG \ b \ c \ a \vee BetG \ c \ a \ b)$ 

```

```

context Gupta-neutral-2D

```

```

begin

```

24.2 Definitions

24.3 Propositions

```

lemma upper-dimT :
assumes  $P \neq Q$  and
  CongG A P A Q and
  CongG B P B Q and
  CongG C P C Q
shows  $BetG \ A \ B \ C \vee BetG \ B \ C \ A \vee BetG \ C \ A \ B$ 
⟨proof⟩

```

```

end

```

```

end

```

```

theory Gupta-Euclidean

```

```

imports
  Gupta-Neutral

```

```

begin

```

25 Gupta Euclidean

25.1 Axioms Gupta Euclidean

```
locale Gupta-Euclidean = Gupta-neutral-dimensionless GPA GPB GPC BetG CongG
  for GPA GPB GPC :: 'p
  and BetG :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool
  and CongG :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool +
  assumes euclidG: ∀ A B C D T.
    BetG A D T ∧ BetG B D C ∧ B ≠ D ∧ D ≠ C ∧
    ¬ (BetG A B C ∨ BetG B C A ∨ BetG C A B) ⟶
    (∃ x y. BetG A B x ∧ BetG A C y ∧ BetG x T y)
```

25.2 Definitions

25.3 Propositions

end

theory Hilbert-Neutral-2D

imports Hilbert-Neutral

begin

26 Hilbert - Geometry - Neutral 2D

26.1 Axioms: Hilbert neutral 2D

```
locale Hilbert-neutral-2D = Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless IncidL IncidP EqL EqP IsL IsP BetH CongH CongaH
  for
    IncidL :: 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool and
    IncidP :: 'p ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool and
    EqL :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool and
    EqP :: 'c ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool and
    IsL :: 'b ⇒ bool and
    IsP :: 'c ⇒ bool and
    BetH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool and
    CongH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool and
    CongaH :: 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ 'p ⇒ bool +
  assumes pasch-2D :
    IsL l ∧ ¬ ColH A B C ∧ ¬ IncidL C l ∧ cut l A B ⟶ (cut l A C ∨ cut l B C)
```

context Hilbert-neutral-2D

begin

26.2 Definitions

26.3 Propositions

```
lemma plane-separation-2D:
  assumes ¬ ColH A X Y and
    ¬ ColH B X Y
  shows cut' A B X Y ∨ same-side' A B X Y
⟨proof⟩
```

```
lemma col-upper-dim:
  assumes ColH A P Q and
    P ≠ Q and
    A ≠ B and
    A ≠ C and
    B ≠ C and
    A ≠ P and
    A ≠ Q and
    B ≠ P and
```

$B \neq Q$ and
 $C \neq P$ and
 $C \neq Q$ and
CongH $A P A Q$ and
CongH $B P B Q$ and
CongH $C P C Q$
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *TS-upper-dim*:
assumes *cut'* $A B P Q$ and
 $P \neq Q$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $A \neq C$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $A \neq P$ and
 $A \neq Q$ and
 $B \neq P$ and
 $B \neq Q$ and
 $C \neq P$ and
 $C \neq Q$ and
CongH $A P A Q$ and
CongH $B P B Q$ and
CongH $C P C Q$
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cut'-comm*:
assumes *cut'* $A B X Y$
shows *cut'* $B A X Y$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *TS-upper-dim-bis*:
assumes *BetH* $P I Q$ and
BetH $I B A$ and
 $P \neq Q$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $A \neq C$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
 $A \neq P$ and
 $A \neq Q$ and
 $B \neq P$ and
 $B \neq Q$ and
 $C \neq P$ and
 $C \neq Q$ and
CongH $A P A Q$ and
CongH $B P B Q$ and
CongH $C P C Q$
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim*:
assumes $P \neq Q$ and
 $A \neq B$ and
 $A \neq C$ and
 $B \neq C$ and
Cong $A P A Q$ and
Cong $B P B Q$ and
Cong $C P C Q$
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

end
end

theory *Hilbert-Neutral-3D*

imports *Hilbert-Neutral*

begin

27 Hilbert - Geometry - Neutral 3D

27.1 Axioms: neutral 3D

locale *Hilbert-neutral-3D* = *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless IncidL IncidP EqL EqP IsL IsP BetH CongH CongaH*
for
 IncidL :: 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 IncidP :: 'p ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 EqL :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 EqP :: 'c ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 IsL :: 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 IsP :: 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 BetH :: 'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool **and**
 CongH::'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool **and**
 CongaH::'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool +
fixes *HS1 HS2 HS3 HS4* :: 'p
assumes *plane-intersection*:
 IsP p ∧ *IsP* q ∧ *IncidP* A p ∧ *IncidP* A q
 ⟶
 (∃ B. *IncidP* B p ∧ *IncidP* B q ∧ A ≠ B)
and *lower-dim-3*:
 ¬ (∃ p. *IsP* p ∧ *IncidP* *HS1* p ∧ *IncidP* *HS2* p ∧ *IncidP* *HS3* p ∧ *IncidP* *HS4* p)

end

theory *Hilbert-Euclidean*

imports

Hilbert-Neutral
 Tarski-Euclidean
 Tarski-Neutral-Hilbert

begin

28 Hilbert - Geometry - Euclidean

28.1 Axioms: Euclidean

locale *Hilbert-Euclidean* = *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless IncidL IncidP EqL EqP IsL IsP BetH CongH CongaH*
for
 IncidL :: 'p ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 IncidP :: 'p ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 EqL :: 'b ⇒ 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 EqP :: 'c ⇒ 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 IsL :: 'b ⇒ bool **and**
 IsP :: 'c ⇒ bool **and**
 BetH :: 'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool **and**
 CongH::'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool **and**
 CongaH::'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒'p⇒bool +
assumes *euclid-uniqueness*: ∀ l P m1 m2. *IsL* l ∧ *IsL* m1 ∧ *IsL* m2 ∧
 ¬ *IncidL* P l ∧ *Para* l m1 ∧ *IncidL* P m1 ∧ *Para* l m2 ∧ *IncidL* P m2
 ⟶
 EqL m1 m2

context *Tarski-Euclidean*

begin

28.2 Definitions

28.3 Propositions

lemma *Para-Par*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $C \neq D$ **and**
Para-H (*Line A B*) (*Line C D*)
shows $A B \text{ Par } C D$
<proof>

lemma *axiom-euclid-uniqueness*:
assumes $\neg \text{IncidentL } P \ l$ **and**
Para-H $l \ m1$ **and**
IncidentL $P \ m1$ **and**
Para-H $l \ m2$ **and**
IncidentL $P \ m2$
shows $m1 =l= m2$
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-Model-Gupta-Neutral*

imports *Gupta-Neutral*

begin

context *Gupta-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*: *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*
where $TPA = GPA$ **and** $TPB = GPB$ **and** $TPC = GPC$ **and** $Bet = BetG$ **and** $Cong = CongG$
<proof>

28.4 Transport theorem from Tarski Neutral for Gupta Euclidean Model

lemma *g-l5-2*:
assumes $A \neq B$ **and**
 $BetG \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $BetG \ A \ B \ D$
shows $BetG \ B \ C \ D \vee BetG \ B \ D \ C$
<proof>

lemma *g-l5-3*:
assumes $BetG \ A \ B \ D$ **and**
 $BetG \ A \ C \ D$
shows $BetG \ A \ B \ C \vee BetG \ A \ C \ B$
<proof>

lemma *g-between-exchange4*:
assumes $BetG \ A \ B \ C$ **and**
 $BetG \ A \ C \ D$
shows $BetG \ A \ B \ D$
<proof>

lemma *g-between-inner-transitivity*:
assumes $BetG \ A \ B \ D$ **and**
 $BetG \ B \ C \ D$
shows $BetG \ A \ B \ C$
<proof>

lemma *g-not-bet-distincts*:
assumes $\neg BetG \ A \ B \ C$

shows $A \neq B \wedge B \neq C$
<proof>

lemma *g-between-symmetry*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ B\ C$
shows $BetG\ C\ B\ A$
<proof>

lemma *g-between-trivial*:
shows $BetG\ A\ B\ B$
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-2D-Model-Gupta-Neutral-2D*

imports
Gupta-Neutral-2D
Tarski-Neutral-2D

begin

context *Gupta-neutral-2D*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Tarski-neutral-2D : Tarski-neutral-2D*
where $TPA = GPA$ **and** $TPB = GPB$ **and** $TPC = GPC$ **and** $Bet = BetG$ **and** $Cong = CongG$
<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Euclidean-Model-Gupta-Euclidean*

imports
Tarski-Neutral-Model-Gupta-Neutral
Gupta-Euclidean
Tarski-Euclidean

begin

context *Gupta-Euclidean*

begin

28.5 Interpretation Tarski Gupta

lemma *euclidT*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ D\ T$ **and**
 $BetG\ B\ D\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq D$ **and**
 $\forall\ A\ B\ C\ D\ T.$
 $BetG\ A\ D\ T \wedge BetG\ B\ D\ C \wedge A \neq D$
 \longrightarrow
 $(\exists\ X\ Y. BetG\ A\ B\ X \wedge BetG\ A\ C\ Y \wedge BetG\ X\ T\ Y)$
shows $\exists\ X\ Y. BetG\ A\ B\ X \wedge BetG\ A\ C\ Y \wedge BetG\ X\ T\ Y$
<proof>

lemma *lem-euclidG*:
assumes $BetG\ A\ D\ T$ **and**
 $BetG\ B\ D\ C$ **and**
 $A \neq D$

shows $\exists X Y. \text{BetG } A B X \wedge \text{BetG } A C Y \wedge \text{BetG } X T Y$
<proof>

interpretation *Interpretation-Tarski-euclidean : Tarski-Euclidean*

where $\text{TPA} = \text{GPA}$ and $\text{TPB} = \text{GPB}$ and $\text{TPC} = \text{GPC}$ and $\text{Bet} = \text{BetG}$ and $\text{Cong} = \text{CongG}$
<proof>

end

end

theory *Gupta-Neutral-Model-Tarski-Neutral*

imports

Tarski-Neutral

Gupta-Neutral

begin

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Gupta-neutral-dimensionless : Gupta-neutral-dimensionless*

where $\text{GPA} = \text{TPA}$ and $\text{GPB} = \text{TPB}$ and $\text{GPC} = \text{TPC}$ and $\text{BetG} = \text{Bet}$ and $\text{CongG} = \text{Cong}$
<proof>

end

end

theory *Gupta-Neutral-2D-Model-Tarski-Neutral-2D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral-2D

Gupta-Neutral-2D

begin

context *Tarski-neutral-2D*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Gupta-neutral-2D : Gupta-neutral-2D*

where $\text{GPA} = \text{TPA}$ and $\text{GPB} = \text{TPB}$ and $\text{GPC} = \text{TPC}$ and $\text{BetG} = \text{Bet}$ and $\text{CongG} = \text{Cong}$
<proof>

end

end

theory *Gupta-Euclidean-Model-Tarski-Euclidean*

imports

Tarski-Euclidean

Gupta-Euclidean

begin

context *Tarski-Euclidean*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Gupta-euclidean : Gupta-Euclidean*

where $\text{GPA} = \text{TPA}$ and $\text{GPB} = \text{TPB}$ and $\text{GPC} = \text{TPC}$ and $\text{BetG} = \text{Bet}$ and $\text{CongG} = \text{Cong}$
<proof>

end
end

theory *Hilbert-Neutral-Model-Tarski-Neutral*

imports *Tarski-Neutral-Hilbert*

begin

29 Hilbert Neutral - Tarski Neutral Model

29.1 Interpretation

context *Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and*

IncidP = IncidentP and

EqL = EqTL and

EqP = EqTP and

IsL = isLine and

IsP = isPlane and

BetH = Between-H and

CongH = Cong and

CongaH = CongA-H

<proof>

interpretation *Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and*

IncidP = IncidentP and

EqL = EqTL and

EqP = EqTP and

IsL = isLine and

IsP = isPlane and

BetH = Between-H and

CongH = Cong and

CongaH = CongA-H and

PP = TPA and

PQ = TPB and

PR = TPC

<proof>

end

end

theory *Hilbert-Neutral-2D-Model-Tarski-Neutral-2D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral-Hilbert

Tarski-Neutral-2D

Hilbert-Neutral-2D

begin

30 Hilbert Neutral 2D - Tarski Neutral 2D Model

30.1 Interpretation

context *Tarski-neutral-2D*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and*

IncidP = IncidentP and

EqL = EqTL and

EqP = EqTP and

IsL = isLine and

IsP = isPlane and

BetH = Between-H and

CongH = Cong and

CongaH = CongA-H

<proof>

interpretation *Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and*

IncidP = IncidentP and

EqL = EqTL and

EqP = EqTP and

IsL = isLine and

IsP = isPlane and

BetH = Between-H and

CongH = Cong and

CongaH = CongA-H and

PP = TPA and

PQ = TPB and

PR = TPC

<proof>

interpretation *Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-2D: Hilbert-neutral-2D*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and*

IncidP = IncidentP and

EqL = EqTL and

EqP = EqTP and

IsL = isLine and

IsP = isPlane and

BetH = Between-H and

CongH = Cong and

CongaH = CongA-H and

PP = TPA and

PQ = TPB and

PR = TPC

<proof>

end

end

theory *Hilbert-Neutral-3D-Model-Tarski-Neutral-3D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral-3D-Hilbert

Hilbert-Neutral-3D

begin

31 Hilbert Neutral 3D - Tarski Neutral 3D Model

31.1 Interpretation

context *Tarski-neutral-3D*

begin

interpretation *Interpretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre*

where *IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL*

```

    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
⟨proof⟩

```

```

interpretation Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless
  where IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL
    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
    and PP = TPA        and PQ = TPB       and PR = TPC
⟨proof⟩

```

```

interpretation Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-3D: Hilbert-neutral-3D
  where IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL
    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
    and PP = TPA        and PQ = TPB       and PR = TPC
    and HS1 = TS1       and HS2 = TS2      and HS3 = TS3
    and HS4 = TS4
⟨proof⟩

```

```

end
end

```

```

theory Hilbert-Euclidean-Model-Tarski-Euclidean

```

```

imports Hilbert-Euclidean

```

```

begin

```

32 Hilbert Euclidean - Tarski Euclidean Model

32.1 Interpretation

```

context Tarski-Euclidean

```

```

begin

```

```

interpretation Interpretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless-pre
  where IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL
    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
⟨proof⟩

```

```

interpretation Intrepretation-Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless: Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless
  where IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL
    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
    and PP = TPA        and PQ = TPB       and PR = TPC
⟨proof⟩

```

```

interpretation Intrepretation-Hilbert-euclidean: Hilbert-Euclidean
  where IncidL = IncidentL and IncidP = IncidentP and EqL = EqTL
    and EqP = EqTP      and IsL = isLine   and IsP = isPlane
    and BetH = Between-H and CongH = Cong   and CongaH = CongA-H
    and PP = TPA        and PQ = TPB       and PR = TPC
⟨proof⟩

```

```

end
end

```

```

theory Tarski-Neutral-Model-Hilbert-Neutral

```

```

imports
  Tarski-Postulate-Parallels

```

Hilbert-Neutral
Gupta-Neutral

begin

33 Tarski Neutral Model Hilbert Neutral

context *Hilbert-neutral-dimensionless*

begin

interpretation *Interp-Gupta-of-Tarski-neutral-dimensionless:*

Gupta-neutral-dimensionless

where $BetG = Bet$ **and**

$CongG = Cong$ **and**

$GPA = PP$ **and**

$GPB = PQ$ **and**

$GPC = PR$

$\langle proof \rangle$

interpretation *H-to-T : Tarski-neutral-dimensionless*

where $Bet = Bet$ **and**

$Cong = Cong$ **and**

$TPA = PP$ **and**

$TPB = PQ$ **and**

$TPC = PR$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *MidH--Mid:*

assumes M *Midpoint* $A B$

shows H -to- T .*Midpoint* $M A B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *Mid--MidH:*

assumes H -to- T .*Midpoint* $M A B$

shows M *Midpoint* $A B$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-colh-1:*

assumes H -to- T .*Col* $A B C$

shows $ColH A B C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-colh-2:*

assumes $ColH A B C$

shows H -to- T .*Col* $A B C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *col-colh:*

shows H -to- T .*Col* $A B C \longleftrightarrow ColH A B C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *line-col:*

assumes $IsL l$ **and**

$IncidL A l$ **and**

$IncidL B l$ **and**

$IncidL C l$

shows H -to- T .*Col* $A B C$

$\langle proof \rangle$

lemma *bet--beth:*

assumes $A \neq B$ **and**

$B \neq C$ **and**

$Bet A B C$

shows $BetH A B C$

$\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *coplanar-plane0*:

assumes $\text{ColH } A \ B \ X$ **and**
 $\text{ColH } C \ D \ X$

shows $\exists p. \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } C \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } D \ p$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *coplanar-plane1*:

assumes $\text{Bet } A \ B \ X \vee \text{Bet } B \ X \ A \vee \text{Bet } X \ A \ B$ **and**
 $\text{Bet } C \ D \ X \vee \text{Bet } D \ X \ C \vee \text{Bet } X \ C \ D$

shows $\exists p. \text{IsP } p \wedge \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } C \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } D \ p$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *coplanar-plane*:

assumes $\text{H-to-T.Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $\exists p. \text{IsP } p \wedge \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } C \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } D \ p$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *plane-coplanar*:

assumes $\text{IncidP } A \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidP } B \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidP } C \ p$ **and**
 $\text{IncidP } D \ p$

shows $\text{H-to-T.Coplanar } A \ B \ C \ D$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *para--para*:

assumes $\text{IncidL } A \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } B \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } C \ m$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } D \ m$ **and**
 $\text{H-to-T.ParStrict } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $\text{Para } l \ m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *par--or-eq-para*:

assumes $\text{IncidL } A \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } B \ l$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } C \ m$ **and**
 $\text{IncidL } D \ m$ **and**
 $\text{H-to-T.Par } A \ B \ C \ D$

shows $\text{Para } l \ m \vee \text{EqL } l \ m$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *tarski-upper-dim*:

assumes

plane-intersection-assms: $\forall A \ p \ q. \text{IsP } p \wedge \text{IsP } q \wedge \text{IncidP } A \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } A \ q$
 $\longrightarrow (\exists B. \text{IncidP } B \ p \wedge \text{IncidP } B \ q \wedge A \neq B)$ **and**
lower-dim-3-assms: $\neg (\exists p. \text{IsP } p \wedge \text{IncidP } \text{HS1 } p \wedge \text{IncidP } \text{HS2 } p \wedge$
 $\text{IncidP } \text{HS3 } p \wedge \text{IncidP } \text{HS4 } p)$ **and**

$P \neq Q$ **and**
 $Q \neq R$ **and**
 $P \neq R$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A \ P \ A \ Q$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B \ P \ B \ Q$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } C \ P \ C \ Q$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } A \ P \ A \ R$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } B \ P \ B \ R$ **and**
 $\text{Cong } C \ P \ C \ R$

shows $\text{Bet } A \ B \ C \vee \text{Bet } B \ C \ A \vee \text{Bet } C \ A \ B$
 $\langle \text{proof} \rangle$

lemma *Col--ColH*:

assumes $\text{H-to-T.Col } A \ B \ C$

shows $\text{ColH } A \ B \ C$

<proof>

lemma *ColH--Col*:

assumes *ColH A B C*

shows *H-to-T.Col A B C*

<proof>

lemma *playfair-s-postulateH*:

assumes *euclid-uniqueness: $\forall l P m1 m2. IsL l \wedge IsL m1 \wedge IsL m2 \wedge$*

$\neg IncidL P l \wedge Para l m1 \wedge IncidL P m1 \wedge Para l m2 \wedge IncidL P m2 \longrightarrow$
 $EqL m1 m2$

shows *H-to-T.playfair-s-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *tarski-s-euclid-aux*:

assumes *euclid-uniqueness: $\forall l P m1 m2. IsL l \wedge IsL m1 \wedge IsL m2 \wedge$*

$\neg IncidL P l \wedge Para l m1 \wedge IncidL P m1 \wedge Para l m2 \wedge IncidL P m2 \longrightarrow$
 $EqL m1 m2$

shows *H-to-T.tarski-s-parallel-postulate*

<proof>

lemma *tarski-s-euclid*:

assumes *euclid-uniqueness: $\forall l P m1 m2. IsL l \wedge IsL m1 \wedge IsL m2 \wedge$*

$\neg IncidL P l \wedge Para l m1 \wedge IncidL P m1 \wedge Para l m2 \wedge IncidL P m2 \longrightarrow$
 $EqL m1 m2$

shows

$\forall A B C D T. Bet A D T \wedge Bet B D C \wedge A \neq D \longrightarrow (\exists X Y. Bet A B X \wedge Bet A C Y \wedge Bet X T Y)$

<proof>

end

end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-2D-Model-Hilbert-Neutral-2D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral-2D

Hilbert-Neutral-2D

begin

34 Tarski Neutral 2D - Hilbert Neutral 2D Model

context *Hilbert-neutral-2D*

begin

lemma *plane-separation-2D*:

assumes *$\neg ColH A X Y$ and*

$\neg ColH B X Y$

shows *$cut' A B X Y \vee same-side' A B X Y$*

<proof>

lemma *col-upper-dim*:

assumes *ColH A P Q and*

$P \neq Q$ and

$A \neq B$ and

$A \neq C$ and

$B \neq C$ and

$A \neq P$ and

$A \neq Q$ and

$B \neq P$ and

$B \neq Q$ and

$C \neq P$ and

$C \neq Q$ and

CongH A P A Q and
CongH B P B Q and
CongH C P C Q
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *TS-upper-dim:*

assumes *cut' A B P Q and*
P ≠ Q and
A ≠ B and
A ≠ C and
B ≠ C and
A ≠ P and
A ≠ Q and
B ≠ P and
B ≠ Q and
C ≠ P and
C ≠ Q and
CongH A P A Q and
CongH B P B Q and
CongH C P C Q
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *cut'-comm:*

assumes *cut' A B X Y*
shows *cut' B A X Y*
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *TS-upper-dim-bis:*

assumes *BetH P I Q and*
BetH I B A and
P ≠ Q and
A ≠ B and
A ≠ C and
B ≠ C and
A ≠ P and
A ≠ Q and
B ≠ P and
B ≠ Q and
C ≠ P and
C ≠ Q and
CongH A P A Q and
CongH B P B Q and
CongH C P C Q
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

lemma *upper-dim:*

assumes *P ≠ Q and*
A ≠ B and
A ≠ C and
B ≠ C and
Cong A P A Q and
Cong B P B Q and
Cong C P C Q
shows $Bet A B C \vee Bet B C A \vee Bet C A B$
 ⟨proof⟩

interpretation *H2D-to-T2D : Tarski-neutral-2D*

where *Bet = Bet and*

Cong = Cong and

TPA = PP and

TPB = PQ and

TPC = PR

⟨proof⟩

end
end

theory *Tarski-Neutral-3D-Model-Hilbert-Neutral-3D*

imports

Tarski-Neutral-3D
Hilbert-Neutral-3D
Tarski-Neutral-Model-Hilbert-Neutral

begin

35 Tarski Neutral 3D - Hilbert Neutral 3D Model

context *Hilbert-neutral-3D*

begin

interpretation *H3D-to-T3D : Tarski-neutral-3D*

where $Bet = Bet$ **and**

$Cong = Cong$ **and**

$TPA = PP$ **and**

$TPB = PQ$ **and**

$TPC = PR$ **and**

$TS1 = HS1$ **and** $TS2 = HS2$ **and** $TS3 = HS3$ **and** $TS4 = HS4$

<proof>

end
end

theory *Tarski-Euclidean-Model-Hilbert-Euclidean*

imports

Hilbert-Euclidean
Tarski-Neutral-3D-Model-Hilbert-Neutral-3D

begin

36 Tarski Euclidean Model Hilbert Euclidean

context *Hilbert-Euclidean*

begin

interpretation *Heucl-to-Teucl : Tarski-Euclidean*

where $Bet = Bet$ **and**

$Cong = Cong$ **and**

$TPA = PP$ **and**

$TPB = PQ$ **and**

$TPC = PR$

<proof>

end
end

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